

A2C – Deliverable D7.17

Agro2Circular

D7.17 – Lombardy Action Plan

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List of abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
ABS	Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene
AFIL	Smart Factory Association Lombardy
ANGEM	National Association of Collective Catering and Various Services
ANICAV	National Association of Vegetable Food Preserve Industrialists
AMSA	Milanese Environmental Services Company
ARERA	National Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment
ARPA	Regional Agency for Environmental Protection
ARIA	Regional company for innovation and purchasing
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
BPP	Basic Price Production
BS	Brescia
Cat.AI	Cluster High Technology Agrofood Lombardy
CBM	Circular Business Models
CE	Circular Economy
CEAP	Circular Economy Action Plan
CIB	Biogas Italian Consortium
CLM	Lombard Mobility Cluster
CNR	Italian National Research Council
CNR - IREA	Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment
CNTC	Centro Tecnológico Nacional de la Conserva
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CONAI	National Packaging Consortium
CREA	Council for Agricultural Research and Analysis of Agricultural Economics
D	Deliverable
DG	General Directorate
DMC	DMC Research Center
DUSAF	Destination of Use of Agricultural Land and Forestry
DW	Dry Weight
ECOLE	Lombardy Industrial Associations for Education
EFSA	European Food Safety Agency
EPS	Expanded PolyStyrene
ERSAF	Regional body for agriculture and forestry services
EU	European
EVA	Ethylene Vinyl Acetate
FERS	European Regional Development Fund
FIPE	Italian Federation of Public Businesses
GAE	Garlic Acid Equivalent
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GPP	Green Public Procurement
H ₂ O ₂	Hydrogen peroxide
HDPE	High Density PolyEthylene
HPH	High-pressure Homogenization

ICEI	Industrial Circular Economy Investment
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IRIS	Iris Technology, SL-
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISTAT	Italian Institute of Statistics
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVC	Kveloce Senior Europa Sociedad Limitada
LC	Lecco
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LDPE	Low Density Polyethylene
LE2C	Lombardy Energy Cleantech Cluster
LGCA	Lombardy Green Chemistry Association
LLDPE	Linear Low-Density Polyethylene
MB	Monza and Brianza
MI	Milan
MV	Mantova
MW	Microwaves
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
OERSA	National Observatory on Food Surplus, Recovery, and Waste
ORICON	Collective Catering and Nutrition Observatory
PA	Polyamide
PAYT	Pay-As-You-Throw
PCP	Pre-commercial procurement
PEF	Pulsed Electric Fields
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PGI	Protected Geographical Indication
PLA	Polylactic acid
PMMA	Polymethyl Methacrylate
PO	Producers Organization
PP	Polypropylene
PPB	Production Possibility Boundary
PRFV	Glassfiber Reinforced Plastic
PRGR	Regional Waste Management Programme
PS	Polystyrene
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
RAEE	Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RECs	Renewable Energy Communities
RENTRI	National Register of Environmental Product Traceability
R&I	Research and Innovation
SAT	Agro2Circular Self-Assessment Tool
SCC	Cluster Technologies for Smart Cities & Communities Lombardy
SCF	Supercritical fluid
SCITEC	Institute of Chemical Sciences and Technologies
SEPARATEC	Saperatec GmbH
SFE-CO ₂	Supercritical fluid extraction
SILVIA	Lombardy Information System Environmental Impact Assessment

SMEs	Small Medium Enterprises
SSICA	Experimental Station for the Food Preservation Industry
STEP	Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform
TARI	Italian waste tax
TAV	Cluster Technology Caring People
TCA	Tecnoalimenti S.C.P.A.
TIF	Total Impermeable Films
UAE	Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction
UB	Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi
UNI	Italian Standardization Body
US	Ultrasounds
VIF	Virtual Impermeable Films
VTT	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus Vtt OY
WEEE	Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment
WHP	Working group on Plastics
WP	Work Package

1.Executive summary

The present deliverable is the result of the replicability activities aimed at identifying the potential applications of the systemic solutions developed within the Agro2Circular project; it summarizes the findings and outlines an action plan designed to support the circular transition in the Lombardy Region.

Deliverable 7.17 adheres to the holistic and multidimensional approach that underpins the entire Agro2Circular project and is structured around two main lines of replicability: (i) **systemic approach to Agro2Circular value chains replicability** and (ii) **multidimensional replicability analysis according to the Agro2Circular model**.

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Figure 1 – Replicability approach

1. Replicability line 1: **Systemic approach to Agro2Circular value chains replicability**

On one hand, the territorial/contextual study of the Lombardy agri-food sector enabled the quantification and localization of biological waste from horticulture (with specific reference to the productions of interest to A2C, namely apples, lemons, cauliflower, artichokes, grapes) (**Section 3.2**) and plastic waste from agro-industry such as agricultural films and Bag-in-Bags (**Section 3.4**) in order to analyse the replicability of technological solutions demonstrated in Murcia and to implement circular value chains also in Lombardy.

The Lombardy region does not produce enough waste from agricultural films and Bag-in-Bags to justify the territorial valorisation technologies applied in Murcia, whereas the biological waste from horticulture (in particular, apples and grapes, as well as lettuce and tomatoes) could effectively support the development of territorial circular value chains. With this goal in mind, the following aspects were analysed: (i) drivers and barriers linked for example to seasonality, territoriality and the existence of competitive technologies (**Sections 3.3** and **3.5**), (ii) legislative constraints (**Section 3.6**), (iii) technology providers and potential application sectors in particular related to cosmetics and nutraceuticals (**Paragraph 3.3.6**). With the collaboration of VTT and UBocconi, replicability of A2C solutions was evaluated from an environmental (**Section 3.7**) and economic (**Section 3.10**) perspective and two potential circular business models were defined.

2. **Replicability line 2: *Multidimensional replicability analysis according to the Agro2Circular model***

On the other hand, the multidimensional model implemented and tested in Spain was applied in Lombardy as a tool to evaluate territorial readiness to circular transition (**Section 3.9**). An in-depth analysis of 8 dimensions and 33 elements able to impact on CE in Lombardy as well as feedback obtained during a co-creation session with key regional public stakeholders led to identify strengths, weaknesses and potential improvement actions in the Lombardy Region.

A cross-cutting element of both lines of replicability is the **involvement of regional stakeholders (Section 3.8)**.

Key actors operating in the value chains analysed in the Agro2Circular project were involved in discussing the A2C systemic circular solutions and evaluating their potential replicability in the Lombardy Region.

Key public stakeholders were selected and involved in a working group devoted to the application of the multidimensional model to the Lombardy Region.

Besides the event aimed to validate the multidimensional model, two additional workshops were organized at regional level for further involvement of public and private stakeholders: these were opportunities to stimulate reflections and exchanges of information on the potential of circular transition in Lombardy.

The convergence point between the two lines of replicability study is the development of a **strategic document CEAP** aimed at supporting the effective transformation of linear economy models into Circular Economy systems in the Lombardy Region with relevant indications such as (i) regional key actors and drivers of the transition to circularity, (ii) policy recommendation, (iii) examples of circular systemic solutions and related business models (**Section 3.11**).

It is important to stress that, although the replicability study was based on the adoption of the project approach (whether systemic or multidimensional), it was strongly adapted to the territorial peculiarities of the Lombardy Region, taking into account the specific productive, industrial, economic social and governance characteristics.

For this reason, the replicability study according to the systemic approach was focused on Agro2Circular technologies adoption but it also considered additional case studies highly relevant for the Lombardy Region and related to the A2C demos. In parallel, the replicability study according to the multidimensional approach was based on the involvement of key stakeholders (as in Murcia Region) but at the same time it included an in-depth analysis of each single element of the Agro2Circular model with the aim of identifying the key factors for the definition of the regional Circular Economy Action Plan.

Below **main finding and key points** from replicability activities in Lombardy Region are reported:

- Starting from annual agricultural production data and from scientific and literature evidence, a *contextual study* was conducted on the *amounts and type of residues within Lombardy agrifood industry*.

This work of data systematization was highly relevant not only for the A2C replication but also at a strategic level for the Lombardy Region because to date there is no real awareness of waste generation from the primary sector and only an in-depth study on the sector's potential can enable the waste valorisation and the implementation of circular value chains (even beyond those hypothesized in the Agro2Circular).

For example, it is possible to estimate that the production district of Northern Italy (roughly corresponding to the Po Valley area) generates approximately 420.000 tons/year of waste from tomato primary production (96.800 tons within the political borders of the Lombardy region) and 196.000 tons of processing waste every year. The wine-growing sector with its 4 production hubs in Lombardy (Franciacorta, Valtellina, Lake Garda and Oltrepò Pavese) generates approximately 98.600 tons of waste annually.

- Based on the potential economic and market value of horticultural wastes (in terms of amount, seasonality, territoriality and presence of producer's aggregations) and in compliance with the "green" principles underlying the Agro2Circular project, the most relevant case studies for the Lombardy Region were identified, along with potential valorisation routes for the replicability of the Agro2Circular model.

The waste value chains of grapes and apples were selected for the application of the Agro2Circular technological model and replicability assessment. These represent the second and fourth most abundant types of waste in Lombardy and allow for the application of the same extraction, purification and stabilization technologies tested in the Agro2Circular demonstrators. Moreover, tomato and lettuce waste constitute the first and third most significant waste streams in Lombardy and present strong potential for circularization. The application of the Agro2Circular model and

- technologies to these waste streams is feasible with slight modifications, ultimately converging on the same biomolecule applications.
- The Lombardy region shows great technological maturity for the replication of CE model studied in Murcia about horticultural waste valorisation both for polyphenols and fibre extraction step; nutraceutical and cosmetic sectors were identified for industrial synergies and for the definition of the new value chain implementing A2C technological solution Circular value chains so implemented were analysed through environmental and economic assessments. Main challenges to be addressed relate to logistic aspects and extracts' specifications but key facilitators and strengths to be leveraged include the territorial advantage of short value chains and the low environmental impact of the extraction technologies.
 - Starting from the replicability of Murcia value chains, two potential circular business model were defined and developed in Lombardy: the first CBM focuses on companies implementing diversification strategies of production, while the second one refers to companies directly implementing their activities with a circular approach, without the need to modify an existing internal product or process.
 - Stakeholder engagement activities allowed to involve both *relevant entities for the new value chain for the implementation of the technologic solutions* (for example primary producers' organization, scientific and technological representatives of "green technology" providers, cosmetic industry) and *key public regional stakeholders*. In particular, regional public authority and regional technology clusters brought their contribution to a working group using the multidimensional model in order to evaluate the current situation in Lombardy in terms of CE and identify potential improvement actions.
 - *Multidimensional regional analysis, according to the Agro2Circular model*, was mainly based on feedback from the working group involving key public stakeholders and targeted interviews with private stakeholders but additional relevant information and evaluations were obtained from: (i) contextual study with specific reference to the circular value chains of horticultural waste and agro-plastic, (ii) targeted desk research on specific dimensions or elements of the CE, (iii) previous experiences and knowledge within the TCA research team and its related industrial network.
The multidimensional analysis shows that Lombardy is ready for the circular transition thanks to the great technological maturity and the great sensitivity of the citizens (for example with very high rates of separate waste collection). An evaluation of the 8 dimensions and 33 elements impacting the Circular Economy in Lombardy reveals that the strongest aspects are the socio-economic and governance dimensions, while the weakest is standardization.

- *Two specific workshops* were organized in collaboration with a regional technological cluster to involve additional stakeholders and, starting from the multidimensional model and regional analysis, stimulate discussion and *exchange of knowledge on A2C solution*.
- In line with the multidimensional and holistic approach to the circular transition, the key actors for the implementation of an effective and efficient Circular Economy Action Plan were identified according to the quintuple helix model. Likewise specific policy recommendations transversal to the individual dimensions and elements analysed were pointed out: they are mainly related to active engagement of all stakeholders and key actors and to the public financial support.
- As a conclusion of A2C replicability activities we put forth a roadmap towards circular systems in line with regional, national and European strategies identifying 5 key objectives and stressing interdisciplinary cooperation and cooperation between science and practice.

Figure 2 – Lombardy roadmap towards circular systems

2. Introduction

Agro2Circular project aims to foster European transition to a Circular Economy supporting changes throughout value chains with a multidimensional and collaborative approach from technical design to new business models. As a final result, the consortium was able to implement circular solutions for waste valorisation in agro-food sector and to set up a multidimensional model as a self-assessment to generate effective strategies of CE.

Within this context, **D7.17 is closely related to the project Objective 2 “Providing to the A2C technological solution the circular systemic approach by building a multidimensional model enabling the solution territorial deployment and its replication and scalability”** as it is based on a systemic approach favouring the territorial implementation of circular solutions; to a greater extent D7.17 contributes to the project Objective 3 maximizing A2C impacts and facilitating A2C systemic solution replication the Lombardy region.

Both the Agro2Circular technology demonstrators, the circular value chains and the multidimensional model have been implemented and tested in the Region of Murcia, but they have been designed as replicable and scalable solutions in conceptually different European contexts.

With this goal, the activities led by TCA and LPK under Task 7.6 aimed to verify the replicability of the A2C solutions in Lombardy Region and in Lithuania’s NUTS 2 regions, respectively. Lombardy and Lithuania are two territories very different from each other and from the Region de Murcia in terms of geographical position, climatic conditions, productive vocation, socio-economic organization and this has allowed to test the applicability of the Agro2Circular solutions (both the systemic solutions and the multidimensional self-assessment model) on a spectrum of different contexts identifying.

Starting from a contextual study of the territory, D7.17 provides a framework for the replicability of the systemic solutions analysed in Murcia, identifying strengths, weaknesses and any changes needed for the implementation of circular value chains based on the valorisation of waste from the agri-food sector and for their application in Lombardy. To define the replicability of these systemic solutions, key actors and technology providers were identified and environmental and economic evaluations were conducted up to the definition of potential business models consistent with the characteristics and needs of the territory.

In parallel, a broader and more general analysis of the Lombardy context was possible thanks to the application of the multidimensional model developed by Kveloce for a self-assessment of the territory and its readiness towards the circular transition. The same collaborative co-creation approach used for the model's setting was employed at a regional level for the application of the model itself: the involvement of regional public and private stakeholders and the in-depth analysis of the 8 CE dimensions in Lombardy allowed it to define a Circular Economy Action Plan.

D7.17 is based on strong collaboration and cooperation both internally and external to the consortium: it led to the implementation of a CAEP based on a broad spectrum of skills and approaches and was able to promote a systemic and shared circular transition in Lombardy. D7.17 was drafted thanks to the close collaboration within the consortium between TCA, task leader, and the partners Kveloce, Bocconi and VTT who dealt with the aspects relating to the multidimensional model, the economic assessments dealing with the elaboration of the circular business models and the environmental assessments, respectively.

In addition, a constant comparison with the partner LPK, responsible for the replicability study in the NUTS2 regions in Lithuania, allowed us to share approaches and analysis methodologies and then to compare the results of the territorial replicability in a cross-fertilization perspective.

More in general, a constant comparison with consortium partners such as CTNC, SSICA and DMC allowed an alignment on the technological aspects for the horticultural waste valorisation.

Below the project deliverables related to D7.17:

- *D1.2 - A2C Residues Management Plan*
- *D2.2 - Agrifood waste conditioning and Extraction of substances from agrifood wastes*
- *D2.4 - Evaluation of extracts*
- *D4.1 - New formulations based on the extracts*
- *D6.5 - A2C business cases*
- *D7.7 - Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring*
- *D7.10 - A2C systemic solution model and self-assessment tool*
- *D7.18 Lithuania NUTS-2 Action Plan*

On the other hand, involving regional stakeholders outside the consortium was crucial for drafting D7.17 and defining the CEAP effectively.

Both private actors (operating in relevant value chains) and public stakeholders were involved in the replicability activities of circular solutions. A dedicated working group with selected public stakeholders contributed to applying the multidimensional model and defining priorities, recommendations and objectives for the circular transition in Lombardy. Additional workshops were organized at regional level to stimulate discussion and exchange of knowledge on Agro2Circular solutions.

3. Deliverable body

3.1. Characterization of Lombardy Region

Situated in a favourable position in the heart of Northern Italy, at the foot of the Alps and in the centre of the Po Valley, Lombardy enjoys a strategically privileged position as it is situated on the main routes connecting the Mediterranean area and central Europe. Its surface extends for 23.860 Km² and is divided almost equally between the plain (which represents about 47% of the territory) and the mountain area (which represents 41%). The remaining 12% of the region is hilly.

With 9.991.554 inhabitants and a population density of 417 inhabitants/Km² (as of 1 January 2022 according to ISTAT data), **Lombardy is the most populous region in Italy** [1].

Figure 3 - Physical map of the Lombardy region

Lombardy is the richest Italian region from an economic point of view.

The very fertile soils of the Po Valley have favoured the development of highly profitable agriculture, which uses advanced cultivation systems. The territory is completely flat, given that it is in the upper Po valley, bordered by two of the major tributaries of the Po, the Ticino to the west and the Adda to the east. The industry has developed in all the main sectors, especially in the engineering, iron and steel, textile, chemical, petrochemical, food, publishing, footwear, and furniture sectors. The tertiary sector developed in parallel with the

industrial sector. Tourism is concentrated in the lake and mountain areas and some cities of art (Milan, Bergamo, Pavia, and Mantova).

Lombardy is also in first place in Italy for Research and Innovation, with 13 university institutions and spin-offs and start-ups derived from them (about a fifth of the total number of Italian spin-offs and start-ups). The more relevant scientific sectors are Health, Energy and the Environment, Advanced Manufacturing, Food, and ICT [2].

The capital is Milan, the main economic and financial centre of Italy; considering the urban agglomeration, it is the city with the most inhabitants (1.419.085 inhabitants in 2023 according to Milan municipality data [3]) and it is also the most industrialized; other important cities are Brescia, Bergamo, Monza, Como, and Varese. Milan is the second largest Italian city in terms of inhabitants and the capital of Lombardy; almost a third of the regional population lives here, in an area that constitutes less than 7% of Lombardy. The metropolitan city of Milan is the main economic pole of Italy, with companies operating in countless sectors and fields. In recent decades there has been a progressive decline of heavy industry, in favour of the tertiary sector and services, with the birth and growth of numerous companies of international importance.

3.1.1. Population

As shown in Figure 4, 56.1% of the Lombardy population lives in the provinces of Milano, Brescia and Bergamo, which cover 38.2% of the territory. One third of the population is concentrated in the province of Milano, which covers only 6.6% of the region.

Figure 4 - Population in Lombardy provinces
(ISTAT data, 2023)

However, the province of Monza and Brianza has the highest population density, with 2,146.3 inhabitants per km² compared to the regional average of 418.3. On the other hand,

the province of Sondrio, which is mainly mountainous, has the lowest population density, with 55.9 inhabitants per km² (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Demographic map of Lombardy

The average age in Lombardy is 45.1 years compared to the national average of 45.4.

The old-age index (the percentage ratio between the population aged 65 and over and the population aged 0-14) was 172.3% in 2020, while the elderly dependency index (the percentage ratio between the population aged 65 and over and the population aged 15-64) is 35.9%.

The index of the active population structure (the ratio between the older and younger components of the working-age population) was also essentially stable: in 2020, there were 143.3 residents in the 40-64 age group for every 100 individuals aged 15-39. Figure 6 reports Lombardy population by age groups.

Figure 6 - Population in Lombardy by age groups
(ISTAT data, 2023)

3.1.2. Economy

Lombardy is considered one of the most industrialized and developed areas of Europe, it is the first region of Italy for economic importance, contributing about a fifth to the national gross domestic product. It is also home to many of the country's largest industrial, commercial, and financial businesses, and its per capita income is 35% higher than the European average. Since 1988, Lombardy has been a partner of the international network of Four Motors for Europe, including Baden-Wurttemberg, Rhone Alpes, and Catalonia. Moreover, Milano is considered one of the six European capitals together with London, Hamburg, Frankfurt, Munich, and Paris [4].

The economy of Lombardy is characterized by the great variety of sectors in which it has developed. They range from traditional sectors, such as agriculture and livestock, to heavy and light industry, to the tertiary sector, which had a strong development in recent decades. The industry remains a fundamental sector, also concerning the possibility it offers to create and implement innovations and carry out R&D activities.

In the tertiary sector, the weight of trade and finance is significant.

The Lombard production system comprises the mechanical, electronic, metallurgical, textile, chemical and petrochemical, pharmaceutical, food, publishing, footwear, and furniture sectors is still one of the most developed in Italy and Europe and has over 800.000 companies.

From the statistics on the size of enterprises, it emerges that micro and small enterprises continue to be the backbone of the production of the region, constituting over 99% of

Lombard enterprises [5]. The companies based in Lombardy largely belong to 16 industrial production systems characterized by a high concentration of companies specialized in the traditional “*Made in Italy*” sector, but also in production areas of excellence with strong ties to research and innovation, where new technologies are dominant [6].

There is considerable sub-regional diversity in the economic activities of Lombard businesses.

- The province of Milan, which alone concentrates over 40% of Lombardy's industrial enterprises, is home to various multinational and financial companies, healthcare and university institutions and research centres. It is therefore evident that Milano is a crucial economic and industrial centre not only in Italy but also in Europe.
- The provinces of Varese, Como, Lecco, Monza and Brianza, Bergamo all have a strong manufacturing sector, but also a high share of employment services.
- Lodi and Brescia are characterized by both manufacturing and agriculture, while the agricultural sector prevails in the provinces of Sondrio, Cremona, Pavia, and Mantova.

3.1.3. Land resources

The Lombardy area has a notable variety of roofing types with great complexity of shapes and structures. The land cover is characterized by a plain from the coexistence of areas intended for arable land and anthropized surfaces among which the great metropolitan area of Milan stands out.

Thanks to the DUSAF cartography (Destination of Use of Agricultural Land and Forestry), it is possible to describe the current land use of the Lombardy Region. The current classification is structured in 5 hierarchical levels, where the first level includes 5 general classes including the main types of land coverage (anthropized areas, agricultural areas, wooded areas, semi-natural environments, wetlands, and bodies of water [7]).

According to the latest data, Figure 7 shows that currently, the land used in Lombardy is organized as follows:

1. Agricultural areas (44.2% of the regional territory)
2. Wooded areas and semi-natural environments (38.6%)
3. Anthropized areas (13.8%)
4. Aquatic areas (3.3%)
5. Wetlands (0.1%)

This representation shows how the region is divided into two halves, with the agricultural areas concentrated in the southern one and the Wooded areas and semi-natural environments only in the northern one. This clear distinction is due to the presence of the so-called Po Valley, which because of the perfect landscape and soil conditions, is the most important agricultural zone of the country, with a production of around 40% of most Italian food products, including wheat, tomatoes, and grapes. In the northern part of the region, the

incidence of mountains (Prealps and Alps), don't allow agricultural activity, this is why the territory is almost all covered by wooded areas and seminatural environments, including deciduous and coniferous forests, natural grasslands, evolving areas and open areas with sparse or no vegetation.

Figure 7 - Lombardy land use

Figure 7 also shows the high incidence of urbanized areas in the middle-west part of the region, where the urban and suburban areas of Milan concentrate almost half of the people living in Lombardy. The comparison with previous analysis of the regional land use shows also how urbanization is continuously growing around Milan at the expense of agricultural lands.

Table 1 shows the different weight of the provinces in the contribution to the regional Basic Price Production (BPP) by sectors; in particular, 83% of the vegetable BPP is obtained in the provinces of Mantova, Pavia, Brescia, Cremona and Bergamo, while 82% of the animal BPP is concentrated in Brescia, Mantova, Cremona and Bergamo. From this it follows that the provinces of Brescia, Mantua, Cremona, Bergamo and Pavia represent 80% of the total agricultural production of the entire region [8].

Table 1 - Estimate of the BPP at basic prices in the Lombardy provinces in 2021 (millions of euros).

Source: ESP processing on ISTAT data

	BG	BS	CO	CR	LC	LO	MN	MI	MB	PV	SO	VA	TOT
Crops	185	445	29	380	20	137	625	163	27	483	33	19	2.546
Herbaceous	125	184	20	160	12	70	383	114	20	241	1	14	1343
Forage	47	144	3	184	2	63	128	42	2	69	6	3	693
Legumes	13	117	7	35	7	4	114	8	5	172	26	1	509
Farm	409	1.492	29	898	20	338	931	201	11	143	41	49	4.563
Milk	229	863	15	406	11	159	528	85	7	93	20	24	2.440
Meat	145	525	13	473	9	171	348	110	4	47	19	16	1.880
Other	35	104	1	19	1	8	56	6	0	3	1	10	243

In the last three years there has been a decline in the cultivation of forage crops (-2.6% for alternate crops and -1.6% for permanent crops). In the same period, the horticultural surfaces remained unchanged, with a significant decline in melon (-8.5%) and increases in the surfaces cultivated for industrial tomatoes (+1.7%) and watermelons (+8%).

3.2. Analysis of biological wastes from the horticultural sector in Lombardy

3.2.1. Biological waste from agriculture

In recent years, the Italian agri-food sector has made significant strides in reducing its environmental impact and promoting Circular Economy principles by cutting down on waste production.

Nevertheless, there is still ample room for improvement to transform circularity from a concept into a well-used practical tool for achieving enhanced sustainability. The subsequent sections will endeavour to examine the state of the art in Lombardy, highlighting both the challenges to be faced and the solutions implemented. Additionally, there will be an analysis on the feasibility of replicating the A2C model developed in Spain within the agricultural and industrial landscape of Lombardy.

3.2.1.1 Primary production in Lombardy region

As previously reported, the primary sector has great importance for the Lombardy economy. Figure 8 shows a clearer idea of the regional sectoral share: according to Polis-Lombardia report [9] 36.6% of agricultural farms in Lombardy included the cultivation of non-permanent crops in their production, while only 10.9% permanent crops. The farms, including activities related to livestock and dairy productions, were around 43.4% of the total (including livestock farming and cultivation of crops for animal feed).

Figure 8 - Agricultural farms and companies in Lombardy by type of production
Sources: Polis Lombardia 2020 from ISTAT data elaboration

More in depth, Lombardy contributes significantly to the national production of **cereals** (17% of the national production); in particular, 40% of Italian rice fields are in Lombardy.

Table 2 reports the destination of arable land in 2022. Compared to the previous year, there was an increase in cereal cultivation areas, namely wheat (+36.2%), barley (+16.8%) and corn (+1.3%); on the other hand, the production of rice (-6.3%) and sorghum (-11.2%) decreased, probably due to the exceptional drought of 2022. Legumes increased globally by 12.2%.

Table 2 - Destination of arable land in Lombardy in 2021
Source: *Il Sistema Agroalimentare della Lombardia Rapporto 2021* [10]

Crop	Used surface (hectares)
Cereals	346.546
Wheat	55.728
Hard wheat	14.549
Barley	22.855
Grain corn	157.649
Sorghum	2.301
Rice	91.528
Other cereals	1.937
Legumes	57.284
Soy	52.682
Other legumes	4.601
Forage	392.572
Fodder corn	161.575
Darnel	25.682
Legume grasses	25.845
Alfalfa	66.789
Alternating meadows	17.664
Other forage crops	95.017

The following Table 3 shows the corresponding quantities of cereals and legumes produced in 2021 and 2023.

Table 3 - Cereals and legumes production
Source: Istat 2023

Crop	2022 production (quintals)	2023 production (quintals)
Corn	11.759.210	12.950.845
Rice	4.482.240	
Wheat	3.339.121	4.241.966
Barley	1.515.894	2.053.542
Soy	1.878.395	1.993.383
Hard wheat	814.470	961.849
Sorghum	155.551	256.120
Pea	106.477	94.807

In a region with a strong zootechnical vocation such as Lombardy, the cultivation of corn is a fundamental resource in the value chains of many certified origin products. The total surfaces cover approximately 50% of the arable land and the provinces with the highest numbers are Cremona (78.000 hectares), Brescia (72.000 hectares) and Mantova (over 56.000 hectares).

On the other hand, in the province of Pavia, rice is the main crop, thanks to the abundance of water from the Ticino River and the flatness of the land making possible the creation of rice paddy fields: Pavia province alone accounts for 83% of the area devoted to rice cultivation.

According to ISTAT data (2023), Lombardy's **horticultural production** is close to 20.000 hectares; the horticultural products cultivated in the open field represent 7.5% of the national production, while the greenhouse production constitutes 4%.

Most important horticultural crops in 2023 were summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 - Most important horticultural production in Lombardy
Source: Istat 2023

Crop	2022		2023	
	Production (quintals)	Used surface (hectares)	Production (quintals)	Used surface (hectares)
Industrial tomato	5.614.475	7.053	6.577.520	8.245
Wine grapes	1.790.306	23.381	1.790.510	23.381
Melon (open filed)	882.945	2.525	935.280	2.669
Melon (greenhouse)	71.250	20.250		
Watermelon	782.280	1.281		
Apples	523.855	1.543	535.455	1.543
Lettuce (open filed)	246.085	932	225.650	893
Lettuce (greenhouse)	167.275	56.670		
Zucchini	312.847	1.475	362.654	1.575
Pear	147.875	663	149.075	663
Potatoes	128.040	529	99.300	397
Kiwi	110.395	768	112.790	764
Onion	103.895	333	101.735	303

Industrial tomato is the most important horticultural production in Lombardy, specifically in the Po Valley area. In the province of Mantova, 3.566 hectares of industrial tomatoes were cultivated in 2022 with total production of over three million quintals; the second province for the overall production of industrial tomatoes is Cremona. More generally, the Lombardy territory of Mantova and Cremona falls within the so-called "*Tomato district of Northern Italy*" including approximately 2.000 agricultural producers (grouped in 13 producer organizations) in the regions of Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Piedmont and Veneto. The following Figure 9 shows the agricultural surface area dedicated to industrial tomatoes in the 4 regions of the Tomato District of Northern Italy. Although Lombardy is only in second producers, after Emilia Romagna (with the provinces of Piacenza and Ferrara) there is a strong territorial contiguity with the other areas involved.

It is also worth noting that the Tomato district of Northern Italy also includes 25 processing plants (belonging to 20 different companies) for the processing of approximately 2.5 million tons of tomatoes to produce concentrates, pulps and pass.

Figure 9 - Agricultural surface area devoted to industrial tomatoes in the 4 regions of the Tomato District of Northern Italy
(Data from *OI Pomodoro da Industria Nord Italia*)

This strong territorial clustering also led to the legal and formal organization of industrial tomato producers: the most important is the "*OI Pomodoro da Industria Nord Italia*". It is an inter-regional and inter-professional organization recognized by the Ministry of Agricultural Policies in 2017; it associates all the economic subjects of the tomato supply chain in Northern Italy (in Emilia-Romagna, Lombardy, Piedmont, Veneto regions). Its aim is to strengthen the competitive position of the tomato production system in Northern Italy by encouraging discussion, coordination and cooperation between the subjects of the supply chain. To date *OI Pomodoro da Industria Nord Italia* gather 100% of the organized world of producers (all the POs present in Northern Italy are members of the OI) and almost all (over 99.7%) of the tomato processing industries in the Po Valley (see following Table 5).

Table 5 - POs partner of “*OI Pomodoro da Industria Nord Italia*” [11]

Name	Region	Legal form
AFE	Emilia Romagna	Cooperative society
AINPO	Emilia Romagna	Cooperative society
APO CONERPO	Emilia Romagna	Cooperative society
APOL INDUSTRIALE	Lombardy	Cooperative society
ASIPO	Emilia Romagna	Cooperative society
CASALASCO	Lombardy	Joint-stock company
C.I.C.O. SOC. COOP AGR	Emilia Romagna	Cooperative society
C.I.O.	Emilia Romagna	Cooperative society
MINGUZZI	Emilia Romagna	Consortium company
OP FERRATA	Emilia Romagna	Consortium company
OP VERDE INTESA	Lombardy	Consortium company
P.O.A	Lombardy	Consortium company
TERREMERSE	Emilia Romagna	Cooperative society
VALLI ESTENSI	Emilia Romagna	Cooperative society

Lombardy is the second largest producer of **melons** in Italy (after Sicily); as well as for the industrial tomato roughly, the production is concentrated in the same area on the border between Lombardy and Emilia Romagna. This is the production area of the “*PGI melon from Mantova*” characterized by a sweet flavour and intense aroma; the straw yellow peel can be netted or smooth and the pulp is yellow-orange to salmon. The producers of “*PGI melon from Mantova*” are gathered in the “*Consortium for the Valorisation and Protection of the Mantova Melon*”. This is the body representing producers and processors of PGI Mantova Melon; it aims to protect, promote and enhance the PGI Mantova Melon and supervise its production [12].

According to ISTAT data (2023), in 2022, 898.450 quintals of melons were produced in Lombardy (856.450 quintals from open field and 42.000 quintals from greenhouse). In the same year 21.215 quintals of melon were produced in the province of Mantova (17.640 quintals open field and 3.575 quintals from greenhouse). A fair production of melon in greenhouses is also recorded in the province of Brescia (25.500 quintals in 2022).

In addition, most of the **watermelon** production is concentrated in the provinces of Mantova and Cremona: according to ISTAT data (2023), in 2022, 702.340 quintals were produced in the province of Mantova (corresponding to 1143 hectares) and 69.600 in the province of Cremona (corresponding to 116 hectares). The remaining part of watermelon production is in the province of Pavia.

Also, for melons and watermelons, as well as for industrial tomatoes, the strong territoriality of production drives the aggregation of producers in structured organizations.

Below are the most important melon POs in the province of Mantova:

Verdeintesa

Located in Medole (province of Mantova) but also including producers from other regions (<https://verdeintesa.it/o-p/>)

Lorenzini Naturamica Soc.Cons.

Located in Sermide (province of Mantova) but also including producers from Sicily (<https://lorenzininaturamica.com/home-lorenzini/>)

OPO Bellaguarda

Located in Viadana (province of Mantova) gathers producers of melons, watermelons, pears and pumpkins

The second most important horticultural production in Lombardy is **grapes** for wines production (specifically with origin denomination); unlike tomato and melons cultivation, the vineyards present in Lombardy are more dispersed over the regional surface (see Table 6) and it is possible to identify 4 areas with the greatest wine-growing vocation as follow reported:

Franciacorta

Nestled near the city of Brescia, with an area of approximately 3.000 hectares, Franciacorta is celebrated for its exceptional sparkling wines. The region specializes in the production of high-quality Metodo Classico sparkling wines, often referred to as "Italy's answer to Champagne." The vineyards, predominantly planted with Chardonnay, Pinot Noir, and Pinot Blanc, benefit from the region's hilly terrain and limestone-rich soils.

Lake Garda (including provinces of Brescia and Mantova)

Vineyards here benefit from the moderating influence of the lake, creating a microclimate conducive to grape cultivation. White wines, particularly those crafted from the native Turbiana grape, thrive in this region.

Oltrepò Pavese

Situated south of Milan, Oltrepò Pavese is a significant wine-producing area, particularly recognized for its production of Pinot Noir. The hilly landscape and favorable climate contribute to the cultivation of a variety of grape varieties, including Barbera, Croatina, and Moscato.

Valtellina region (province of Sondrio)

Nestled in the alpine terrains of Lombardia, Valtellina is acclaimed for its mountain viticulture. The Nebbiolo grape, locally known as Chiavennasca, thrives in the steep, terraced vineyards along the Adda River. The region produces red wines, notably the Sforzato, made from dried grapes.

Table 6 - Wine grapes production in 2022 in each province of Lombardy

Source: Istat 2023

Province	Production (quintals)	Used surface (hectares)
Pavia	791.525	11.647
Brescia	658.879	6.513
Mantova	238.049	1.698
Sondrio	46.517	802
Bergamo	33.642	660
Milano	13.200	176
Lecco	3.150	62
Como	1.392	25
Lodi	1.338	19
Varese	1.295	22
Cremona	1.209	26
Monza e Brianza	110	2

The fourth largest fruit production in Lombardy is the **apple**, located in Valtellina. According to ISTAT data (2023), in 2022 in the province of Sondrio, 382.000 quintals of apples were produced on an area of 955 hectares. In Valtellina are grown mainly "Golden Delicious" and "Stark Delicious" apples, varieties with excellent organoleptic and conservation characteristics enhanced by the mountain environment. Valtellina apples are completely intended for fresh consumption and are awarded with the PGI mark.

Like the PGI Mantova melon, the Valtellina apple has a consortium dedicated to protecting, promoting, and enhancing its local varieties. The Consortium directly controls all steps of the supply chain, from field to shipping, guaranteeing traceability, quality and healthiness of the product [13]. The most important PO afferent to the "Consortium for the Valorisation and Protection of the Valtellina apple" is Melavi (<https://www.melavi.it/it/>) including more than 300 farms.

For apple production, the province of Sondrio is followed by the provinces of Pavia and Brescia with 23.660 and 19.200 quintals respectively. In this case also, production is completely intended for fresh consumption.

To conclude the overview of fruit production in Lombardy we can also mention significant cultivations of **pears** and **kiwi**, both concentrated in the province of Mantova.

Lombardy is the third largest producer of pears in Italy and the Mantova pear is awarded with the PGI mark. According to ISTAT data (2023), in 2022, 123.500 quintals of pears were produced in the province of Mantova, almost entirely destined for fresh consumption (119.250 quintals). As for tomatoes and melons, however, it is interesting to note that the characteristic production area is not limited to the "political" border of the Lombardy Region, but it concerns the entire geographical area of the Po Valley including also the provinces of Modena, Reggio Emilia, Bologna; Emilia Romagna is the most important producer in Italy.

On the other hand, about the production of vegetables, it is possible to identify a different production centre in Lombardy between the provinces of Bergamo and Brescia. 31% of the

national production of **fresh-cut lettuce** and salad is concentrated here (another 30% is in the Sele Plain in Campania Region).

Production typically takes place in a greenhouse.

According to ISTAT data (2023), in 2022, 193.200 quintals of lettuce in greenhouse were harvested in Bergamo province (42.000 hectares) and 21.300 quintals in Brescia province (7.100 hectares).

Also in this case, the territorial proximity led the producers to join in POs.

In addition, fresh-cut salads POs often associate producers from Lombardy (Bergamo and Brescia) with producers from Campania (Sele Plain) because these two territories are complementary from a seasonality of view. Following some examples:

- *OP Oasi* located in San Paolo D'Argon (province of Bergamo) - <https://opoasi.it/>
- *OP Sole e Rugiada* located in Bagnolo Mella (province of Brescia) <https://op-soleerugiada.it/>
- *OP Isola Verde* located in Telegate (province of Bergamo) <https://opisolaverde.it/>
- *OP Raggio di Sole* located in Gorlago (province of Bergamo) - <http://www.aopunolombardia.it/raggiodisole.html>

An interesting innovation in the Lombardy fresh-cut salad sector is vertical farming. Cultivation takes place without soil, within a special nutrient solution on multiple levels. This technique limits the cultivation space, shortens plant growth times, limits exposure to pathogens and achieves significant water savings (up to 90%). In October 2023, the largest European vertical farm dedicated to lettuce production was inaugurated in the province of Brescia (Verolanuova) but there are also other similar plants throughout Lombardy. Here are some examples:

- *Agricola Moderna* (<https://agricolamoderna.com/>) in the province of Milan (Melzo) produces lettuce and basil.
- *Local green* (www.localgreen.it) in the province of Pavia (Cervesina) produces lettuce, red and green kale and mizuna
- *Planet Farms* (<https://www.planetfarms.ag/it>) in the province of Monza and Brianza (Cavenago) produces lettuce and rocket.

On the other hand, open-field lettuce production is in the Po Valley: 524 hectares in Mantova and 35 hectares in Cremona were devoted to lettuce cultivation in 2022 with a production of 115.804 and 7.525 quintals, respectively (ISTAT data, 2023).

To complete the overview of the most important horticultural production in Lombardy, we need to mention **zucchini**. Production is concentrated in the province of Mantova with 109.350 quintals in 2023, followed by the provinces of Brescia and Pavia with 65.642 and 57.000 respectively (ISTAT data, 2023).

In order to devote a specific focus to the horticultural products selected for the implementation of A2C circular supply chain in Murcia, the production of lemon, cabbage, cauliflower and artichoke in Lombardy was analysed and reported in Table 7.

Soil and climate conditions in Lombardy are very different from the central-southern part of Spain, playing a significant role in production capacity of vegetable products. For these reasons, the **Lombardy production and the related waste generation of lemons, cauliflowers, cabbages and artichokes are very limited and do not represent a big issue in terms of valorisation / circularization.**

Table 7 - A2C horticultural production in Lombardy

Source: Istat 2023

	Production 2022 (quintals)	Production 2023 (quintals)
Lemon	80	80
Cabbage		
Cauliflower	4.041	4.360
Artichoke	56	76

For further information and updates on plant production in Lombardy, please consult **Annex 1 - Agricultural products in Lombardy in 2024**: it reports cultivated surface area and production ISTAT data by province.

On the other hand, from an economic point of view, **zootechnic production** represents the main part of the agricultural sector of Lombardy. According to the Regional Department of Agriculture, Food and Green Systems, there are over 12.600 farms in Lombardy.

Lombardy is in first place in Italy for cattle and pigs farming, related to huge production of milk (the highest in Italy), and processed and cured meat: Lombardy contributes to the sector of pork to 39.1% of national production, produces over 40% of milk Italian beef, and 23% of the national beef production; approximately 1.500.000 cattle are raised in Lombardy, this is equal to 25% of the national level. This data is also confirmed by ISTAT (Table 8): there are around 500.000 lactating cows and 200.000 calves for slaughter (under the age of 1), the latter equal to 40% nationwide.

Table 8 - Animals bred in Lombardy from 2018 to 2022

Source: ISTAT data

Type of farm animals	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total cattle	1.474.810	1.543.639	1.546.550	1.541.541	1.533.090
Total buffaloes	3.349	3.391	3.439	3.476	5.379
Total horses	-	-	-	-	58.750
Horses	-	-	-	-	48.440
Other types of horses (donkeys, mules, hinnies)	-	-	-	-	10.310
Total cattle and buffaloes	1.478.159	1.547.030	1.549.989	1.545.017	1.538.469
Total sheep	118.843	125.093	173.375	150.324	137.123
Total goats	112.405	111.654	106.639	102.921	94.482
Total pigs	3.988.228	3.984.633	3.983.451	3.955.536	4.427.406
Pigs weighing less than 20 kg	668.669	656.765	664.583	671.741	861.613
Pigs from 20 kg to less than 50 kg	771.710	773.620	765.565	760.398	782.220
Pigs for fattening from 50 kg to less than 80 kg	576.765	577.510	577.572	599.954	602.625
Pigs for fattening from 80 kg to less than 110 kg	681.138	685.970	680.658	675.780	739.078
Pigs for fattening of 110 kg and more	1.059.466	1.061.021	1.063.151	1.029.458	1.108.535

3.2.1.2 Waste from the primary sector

To give a first overview of waste from the primary sector, we can consider national data. According to Waste Watcher International Observatory, over 4 million tons of food were wasted in the Italian supply chain, worth over 9 billion euros [14]. According to an elaboration by the Bologna University, food waste in the supply chain accounts for 26% in agriculture, 28% in industry and 8% in distribution.

According to a separate study from Polis Lombardia, total food wastes were 5.590.000 tons with a strong impact of waste from agriculture. Table 9 reports food surplus and waste flows. The percentage of food surplus is obtained by the difference between how much food is potentially available and what is actually consumed: a significant portion of this figure is definitively classifiable as waste.

Table 9 - Food surplus and waste production throughout the food supply chain
 Source (PolisLombardia [15])

Value chain sector	Managed flow (tons)	Surplus flow (tons)	Surplus on the flow	Waste (tons)	Waste on the flow	Waste on the surplus
Primary	71.975.000	2.045.000	36,58%	1.755.000	34.3%	85,8%
Transformation	46.085.000	175.000	3,13%	75.000	1,5%	42,9%
Distribution	29.810.000	755.000	13,51%	690.000	13,5%	91,4%
Ho.Re.Ca.	3.280.000	210.000	3,76%	185.000	3,6%	88,1%
Domestic consumption	29.935.000	2.405.000	43,02%	2.405.000	47,1%	100%
Total	181.082.000	5.590.000		5.110.000		

Most waste occurs at home: the foods that Italians throw away the most are fruit, vegetables, bread and pasta, followed by meat and fish.

Taking into account only the value chain before domestic consumption, the most relevant sector in terms of surplus and waste is the primary sector with 36.58% of surplus and 34.3% of waste. Although it is not easy to precisely quantify each specific component of agricultural food waste with recent data, we have an idea of the extent of this problem at the Italian level, thanks to the CREA estimations on 2016 ISTAT data. Figure 10 shows the contribution of different agricultural production to field-related food losses. Most of the food left on the field refers to the cultivation of vegetables in the open air (4.200.000 tons in 2016); to this value we must also add 250.000 tons of waste from vegetables destined for industrial transformation [16].

Figure 10 - Agricultural production left on the field by sector
 (Source CREA elaboration from ISTAT data, 2016)

Focusing on the fruits and vegetable sectors, 30% of fruits and vegetables are rejected because they do not match consumers market tastes and aesthetic canons, despite them being perfectly edible. Based on data collected by ISTAT, it was possible to quantify the

percentage of agricultural production that remained in the fields, amounting to 3.25% of the total (17.700.586 tons) [17].

But food loss may happen at different steps of the supply chain, and this is particularly true for horticultural products, subjected to constant waste at each quality check in the large distribution chain: damaged products, products that do not conform to market standards, rotten products and/or rotten parts are rejected.

In addition, in the fruit and vegetable sector, waste is also related to the Common Market Organization applied by primary cooperatives. These rules may include the withdrawal of part of production to avoid the collapse of prices. The recalled product is, in fact, intended only in part for free distribution (for vulnerable populations, schools, and prisons), while most of it is used for distilling alcohol (36%), composting (55%), and animal feed (4%). These uses are considered waste because the product is used differently than the human consumption for which it was originally cultivated.

Summarizing, matching the feedback from direct comparison with a representative from primary producers' organization (see **Annex 3 Minute of private stakeholders' involvement activities**) and the results of available literature analysis [18] the most important reasons for waste in fruits and vegetable Lombardy sectors were identified:

With a specific focus on the Lombardy region, we considered in the following pages the most significant horticultural production as previously identified, and we estimated the waste amount starting from similar case studies and specific scientific publications.

No official data are issued because of the commercial sensitivity of this information for the producers and, in addition, published data are often largely variable, due to methodological variations and to the intrinsic compositional variability of fruit and vegetables [19].

Industrial tomato

Tomato production creates significant volumes of waste from unripe, imperfect, damaged and overripe fruits; specifically in the industrial tomato sector there are very close commercial agreements between producers and industries, so part of the production is discarded to ensure compliance with quality specifications.

It is estimated that 15% of the industrial tomatoes produced are already discarded in the field [20]

Starting from a production of 6.577.520 quintals in 2023, we can estimate waste in the primary sector of 98.600 tons/year in Lombardy. But, as previous anticipated, an estimation based only on the Lombardy region can be limited and misleading for the replicability assessments of the A2C model: considering the territorial proximity and the structural organization of the production reality, it is much more useful to evaluate tomato production and the related waste production in the whole district of Northern Italy. According to data from OI Pomodoro da Industria Nord Italia, almost 2.800.000 tons of tomatoes were produced in 2023 so

We can estimate industrial tomato agricultural waste for 420.000 tons/year in the district of Northern Italy

Lettuce

Lettuce cultivation (especially in greenhouses) takes place in a very protected environment so waste generation in the primary production step is negligible compared to the waste obtained from fresh-cut processing. In addition, tufts not suitable for harvesting are typically left in the field and used as soil enrichment so **we cannot really consider waste flows from lettuce primary production.**

Wine grape

Grape cultivation and wine production are one of the most critical agro-industrial sectors worldwide, generating large amounts of waste with negative environmental impacts, but also with high economic value and several potential applications. Waste products are generated at each stage of the winemaking process. There are two different categories showing the origin of winery waste: collection of grapes (solid waste) and winemaking process (liquid waste). The first category broadly involves grape stalks (7.5% of total solid wastes generated by winery), grape pomace (45%), grape seeds (6%), stems, as well as wine yeasts. Pomace represents 20–25% of the initial weight of the grapes, being a solid residue resulting from the processes of fermentation and pressing of the grapes [21].

In total, about 30% of the initial mass of grapes collected for winemaking is disposed [22].

Starting from a regional production of 1.790.510 quintals in 2023 **we can estimate 98.600 tons/ year of grape waste in Lombardy**

Melon and watermelon

Melons and watermelons are more resistant fruits, and their waste generation is moderate.

Some data were calculated in Tehran: approximately 10% of the production of melons and 9% of watermelons is discarded [23].

Based on these data it is possible to **estimate the waste in Lombardy at 9.500 tons and 7.000 tons for melons and watermelons, respectively**

Apples

Apples production in Lombardy is strongly related to the PGI mark and for this reason the quality standards (including aesthetics) are very rigorous

To estimate the waste from primary production due to non-compliant apples we can take into consideration an English report [24] at least 25% of apples were discarded because they were "ugly".

By transferring this data to Lombardy production, **we can estimate waste from apple primary production as 13.000 tons/year**

Zucchini

Waste material during the primary production is related to faulty zucchini fruits, out of gauge, damaged by bad weather, badly grown, without the aesthetic marketing features.

Johnson et al. (2018) evaluated on-farm food loss at the field level with an applied case study on a North Carolina farm: they estimated 4725 kg/hectare of zucchini waste (3.475 kg edible but unmarkable, 1.250 inedible) [25].

Applying this estimation to Lombard surface **we have about 7.400 tons of zucchini waste in 2023**

3.2.2. Biological waste from industry

3.2.2.1 Food industry in Lombardy region

To frame the production structure of the food industry it is possible to start with Movimprese database of Unioncamere-InfoCamere, with data updated to 2021 [26].

In 2021, Lombardy companies in the food and beverage industry registered in the Register of the Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Crafts and Agriculture constitute 6.133 units, corresponding to 10% of the national data: 5.811 companies work in the food sector and 322 in the drink sector. The following Table 10 shows the number of companies by specific branch of activity.

Table 10 - Number of companies by specific branch active in Lombardy in 2020
 Source: Movimprese database of Unioncamere-InfoCamere

	Number	%
<i>Food industries</i>	5.811	
Processing and preservation of meat and meat products	623	10,7
Processing and conservation of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	24	0,4
Processing and preservation of fruit and vegetables	122	2,1
Production of animal and vegetable oils and fats	48	0,8
Diary industry	349	6
Grain processing, starch production	134	2,3
Bakery industry	3.798	65,4
Other food products	608	10,5
Animal feed products	105	1,8
<i>Drink industries</i>	322	
Distillation, rectification and blending of spirits	62	19,3
Wine production	94	29,2
Production of other fermented, non-distilled beverages	7	2,2
Beer production	111	34,5
Malt production	-	-
Soft drinks and mineral waters	47	14,6
Total	6.133	

Most food industries are into the category of bakery and flour products, with 3.798 units (65.4% of the total): these are generally micro and small businesses producing artisanal bakery and pastry products and are present throughout the whole Lombardy territory but are concentrated above all in city areas. Then there are the industries dedicated to meat processing (10.7%) and dairy companies (6%).

Within the beverage industry, on the other hand, the largest number of companies deals with the production of beer (34.5% of the total) and the production of wines from grapes (29.2% of the total). Only 47 companies work in the sector “Soft drinks and mineral waters”.

About the territorial distribution, the greatest number of food and beverage industries (2.398 representing 29.3% of the total) are in the province of Milan; secondly, there is a high number of food and beverage companies also in the provinces of Brescia (1.171, equal to 14.3% of the total) and Bergamo (841, equal to 10.3% of the total). Summarizing, food activities in Lombardy are concentrated within the “Milan-Brescia-Bergamo triangle” where 53.9% of total businesses are observed.

Analysing more in detail each sector of food and beverage industries (Table 11) the following territorial polarizations can be observed:

- For bakery products there is a prevalence of the Milan-Brescia-Bergamo triangle, but these activities are spread throughout the whole regional territory, especially in the more urbanized areas
- The processing of meat and dairy products is closely correlated with the farms' location, so it is concentrated in the provinces of Milan, Brescia, Mantova, Cremona and Bergamo

- Similarly for wine, the distribution is strictly connected to the viticultural vocation of the regional territory, so are more relevant the provinces of Brescia, (25.8% of the total), Pavia (17.6%) and Sondrio (11.5%)

Table 11 - Number of companies (local operational units) in each province by specific branch of activity in Lombardy in 2021

Source: Movimprese database of Unioncamere-InfoCamere

	Va	Co	So	Mi	Bg	Bs	Pv	Cr	Mn	Lc	Lo	Mb	TOT
Food industries	494	388	290	2.398	841	1.171	527	483	621	296	185	492	8.186
Processing and preservation of meat and meat products	30	38	68	171	111	141	83	122	123	53	30	47	1.017
Processing and conservation of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	7	6	1	14	0	12	0	0	0	4	1	1	46
Processing and preservation of fruit and vegetables	7	2	12	62	26	41	18	10	21	9	5	9	222
Production of animal and vegetable oils and fats	4	5	1	28	1	18	2	7	2	1	0	3	72
Diary industry	28	29	43	138	72	99	19	46	88	26	24	23	635
Grain processing, starch production	7	5	5	32	15	33	46	23	36	7	5	8	222
Bakery industry	326	253	127	1.531	525	685	296	189	274	159	90	304	4.759
Other food products	78	46	31	398	69	91	52	60	51	30	25	94	1.025
Animal feed products	7	4	2	24	22	51	11	26	26	7	5	3	188
Drink industries	32	24	42	141	72	107	60	13	17	23	8	33	572
Distillation, rectification and blending of spirits	34	25	43	138	72	112	60	15	14	23	7	32	575
Wine production	15	2	7	33	7	19	11	1	0	3	0	5	103
Production of other fermented, non-distilled beverages	2	2	21	30	18	47	32	7	9	9	2	3	182
Beer production	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Malt production	0	1	1	4	1	4	1	2	0	0	1	0	15
Soft drinks and mineral waters	13	13	6	39	26	27	14	3	4	9	4	17	175
TOT	528	413	333	2.536	913	1.283	587	498	365	319	192	254	8.761

Taking more specifically into account the fruit and vegetable processing companies, we can identify, in parallel with the production of fruit and vegetables, two geographic poles (in addition to the already mentioned wine one): the tomato canning industry and the fresh cut salad production.

Tomato processing companies are in the same tomato production area so, as already mentioned, it is more interesting in this case to think about the entire area of the Po Valley and not about the political borders of the Lombardy Region.

According to data from the tomato production association [27], in Northern Italy, 2.8 million tons of tomatoes was processed in 2022: northern processing companies mainly produce concentrates, pulp and puree, while peeled tomatoes are a specific product of the southern Italian production district (see Figure 11).

Figure 11 – Raw material processed by processing companies in Northern Italy, distinguished by destination product category.

Red: concentrated; Orange: pulp; Green: puree; Blue: ready sauces

Source: OI Pomodoro da Industria Nord Italia

As shown in Figure 12, to date, there are 27 operational factories in Northern Italy, aggregated under the ownership of 20 companies:

In Lombardia:

- oCasalasco Società Agricola <https://www.casalasco.com/it/>
- oSolana Spa <https://solanaspa.it/it/>
- oZipperle <https://zipperle.it/it/> (not located in the Po Valley but in Valtellina)

In Emilia Romagna

- oEmiliana Conserve <https://www.emilianaconserve.it/>
- oCarlo Manzella <https://www.carlomanzella.it/>
- oTerre di San Giorgio <https://www.terredisangiorgio.it/>
- oSteriltom <https://www.steriltom.com/>
- oRodolfi <https://www.rodolfi.com/it>
- oGreci <http://www.greci.it/>
- oMutti <https://mutti-parma.com/it/>
- oMenù <https://www.menu.it/it/home>
- oGruppo Fini <https://gruppofini.it/>
- oConserve Italia <https://www.conserveitalia.it/it/>
- oValli Estensi <https://www.valliestensi.it/>
- oLe due valli <http://leduevalli.it/>
- oItaltom <https://www.italtom.com/it/index.html>
- oFruttage <https://www.fruttage.it/>
- oLa cesenate <https://www.lacesenate.it/>

In Veneto

- oItaliafrutta <http://www.italfruttasrl.com/>

In Piemonte

- oTomatofarm <https://www.tomatofarmspa.it/>

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Figure 12 - Processing companies associated with the Northern Italy industrial tomato OI [28]

Similarly, the structure of a production district for *fresh cut salads* in the provinces of Bergamo and Brescia is mainly due to the presence of two large processing companies, specifically Bonduelle, leader of the Italian market (<https://www.bonduelle.it/>) located San Paolo d'Argon in and Mioorto (<https://mioorto.it/>) located in Corrobio.

However, in this area there are many other smaller companies producing and transforming salad; below is a non-exhaustive list:

- Società Agricola Bergamasca <https://www.sabortofrutta.it/prodotti/>
- ErrebiOrtaggi <https://www.errebiortaggi.it/contatti>
- Terra e Vita <https://www.terravita.it/quarta-gamma-insalate-busta-confezionate>
- San Lidano Orto pronto <https://www.sanlidano.it/>
- Facchini <https://www.facchininatura.it/index.html>
- La Linea Verde <https://www.lalineaverde.it/>
- Azienda Agricola Isola Verde <https://aziendaagricolaisolaverde.it/>

3.2.2.2 Wastes from food industry

As for the analysis of waste from the primary sector, also for waste from industry, a first overview at national level is also useful. According to the Intesa Sanpaolo Bioeconomy Report, waste from food industry in Italy is less than half the EU average but still reaches a value of 15 kg per capita [29].

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838

Main reasons of waste from food industry are processing waste and scraps and/or inefficiency in the processing chain but in addition to the normal outflows from each specific unit operation we can consider the following causes of waste in food industry [17]:

With the aim to evaluate the replicability of the Agro2Circular model to the waste generated by the Lombardy agro-food industry, we will only consider the following 3 sectors most coherent with the objectives of the project and most relevant in quantitative terms (amount of processing and waste produced) and in territorial terms (clustering of production sites):

1. Tomato industry

During tomato processing, around 3–7% of material is lost: this waste is commonly called tomato pomace, being mostly made of peels, seeds, and some residual tomato tissue [30]. As previously reported, in Northern Italy 2.8 million tons of tomatoes was processed in 2022; based on Laranjeira's estimation **an annual waste from the tomato industry of between 84.000 tons and 196.000 tons can be estimated**. This estimation considers the whole territory of the Po Valley and not just the food industries in the Lombardy region.

2. Wine production

As already discussed, (paragraph 3.2.1.2 ***Waste from primary sector***), production of Lombardy grapes (1.790.510 quintals in 2023) is totally intended for transformation into wine: with a rough calculation of winemaking waste equal to 30% of the initial mass of grapes **a waste of 98.600 tons/ year can be estimated in Lombardy**.

3. Fresh cut salads

A survey conducted in a large Italian fresh-cut company revealed that at least 35% of lettuce head weight is wasted, mainly due to initial operations of external leaves and core removal [31]. To approximately calculate the waste from the Lombardy industry of fresh cut salads, we can hypothesize that lettuce production (413.360 quintals in 2022 including open field and greenhouse production) is entirely destined for transformation: starting from the Plazzotta's data **a generation of waste equal to 14.500 tons/year can be estimated.**

3.2.3 Biological wastes from the catering sector

3.2.3.1 Catering system in Lombardy

The public and private catering system, including canteens in schools and companies, restaurants, and businesses involved in the production and shipment of prepared meals, is considered one of the most important sectors in Italy. To understand its scale, in 2021, in Italy the total number of businesses registered as restaurants was 196.031, while the canteens and catering companies were 3.528 [32]; according to ORICON (Osservatorio Ristorazione Collettiva e Nutrizione), the canteen system alone, in 2016, produced around 1.5 billion meals, with the canteens in the health system in first place, followed by the education and corporate one [33].

According to ORICON, Lombardy is the Italian region with the highest number of restaurants (21.056 in 2021), representing 13.8% of the national data. The region is followed by Lazio and Campania, with fewer thousand. Also, in the sector of canteens and companies involved in the catering system, Lombardy has the national primate, with 648 companies in 2021 (19.4% of the total Italian data). The concentration of catering companies in northern Italy was already reported by ORICON in 2014, with around 111.366 million meals produced in Lombardy over a total of 414 million from all Italian companies adhering to their study (which represented 54% of the national turnover); this was confirmed again in 2016, with a clear unbalance in the geographic location of catering companies towards the north of Italy, where 57% of the national turnover is concentrated (see Figure 13).

Figure 13 - National distribution of the collective catering system based on turnover
 Source: ORICON data (2016)

From the discussion with a representative of the association of collective catering (see **Annex 3 Minutes of private stakeholders' involvement activities**) the incidence of this sector in Lombardy is also related to the presence of three airport hubs in the region, where the airline catering service takes place. As a confirmation of this, Milano Ristorazione S.p.A. (the association that manages the catering system of the city), reported that the catering companies and canteens of Milan produced 83.000 meals per day in 2022, which is related to around 9.464 tons of food produced during the year [34].

The predominance of the city of Milan in the collective catering sector over the other Lombardian provinces is due to the number of citizens and therefore to the needs of the area. This is understandable looking at the data shown by Table 12, which describes the geographical distribution of meals served by the canteens operating in Lombardy: the companies operating in the catering sector in the province of Milan produced around 72.089 meals, which is 34% of the total meals produced in the whole region (214.628.289) [35].

The data also show the differences in meals produced among canteens in different types of institutions: the prevalence of meals prepared for the education sector over other types of structures is clear for all the Lombardian provinces, especially for Milan.

After Milan, the most active provinces in terms of catering system are Brescia and Bergamo and, in this case, the greatest number of meals served is linked to schools.

Table 12 - Distribution of meals in mass catering in Lombardy according to the province and the type of structure where the canteens are located

Province	School (n. of meals per year)	Hospital (n. of meals per year)	Centers for Minors (n. of meals per year)	Centers for Elderly (n. of meals per year)	Centers for People with Disability (n. of meals per year)	Total Mass Catering (n. of meals per year)
Bergamo	6.519.819	4.863.649	5.308.664	4.940.411	658.344	22.290.887
Brescia	6.831.889	6.663.654	3.956.426	6.730.050	701.928	24.883.947
Como	3.858.990	2.486.295	1.215.078	4.026.318	388.901	11.975.582
Cremona	2.766.201	1.909.428	888.822	3.939.889	718.041	10.222.381
Lecco	2.595.052	1.634.554	596.166	1.852.514	258.044	6.936.329
Lodi	2.052.994	1.006.314	864.112	1.128.309	105.826	5.157.552
Monza and Brianza	7.830.588	5.410.807	1.666.037	2.827.190	342.751	18.077.374
Milan	28.850.685	16.302.682	10.082.118	15.404.335	1.459.359	72.089.179
Mantova	2150.601	1.977.854	1.048.315	2.917.232	227.720	8.321.722
Pavia	4.008.025	4.152.545	1.354.721	4.893.544	367.632	14.776.467
Sondrio	1.378.011	1.185.732	212.436	1.156.218	108.728	4.041.125
Varese	6.416.812	2.346.052	1.620.095	4.986.535	486.248	15.855.742
Total	75.259.669	49.939.566	28.802.990	54.802.542	5.823.521	214.628.289

3.1.1.2 Wastes from the catering sector

The production of food waste from the catering system is an issue that raised attention in Italy throughout the last decades. The problem is mainly related to the canteens and public catering businesses, while the private catering sector (restaurants) is less affected by the problem, since, in this case, the amount of food produced is closely linked to the portions ordered by the clients.

In this context could be useful to remind the definition of food waste as proposed by the Food Use for Social Innovation by Optimizing project Waste Prevention Strategies established by the European Commission: it distinguishes wasted food as (i) avoidable, (ii) possibly avoidable, and (iii) not avoidable. Avoidable waste concerns food thrown away while still edible, possibly avoidable waste instead, refers to the food and drinks that some people consume and others don't (e.g. chicken skin) or the food that can be edible if cooked differently (e.g. potato peel), while the unavoidable waste includes the inedible components of foods and products derived from the preparation [36].

MVK researchers identified the following **possible causes of waste in the private and public catering sector**:

More precisely, in the Italian canteens' food loss may happen in three steps of the supply chain:

1. Daily preparation of meals has to respect defined quantities, in compliance with standardized reference values for nutrition and diets but often it exceeds the requested quantity and is not accepted by consumers, so food surpluses are generated; it consists of food prepared but not touched by consumers. This type of surplus can become a waste but, in most cases, it already has an alternative fate.
2. The second type of residue deriving from the catering system is indeed constituted by the consumers' leftovers: it is the real waste of the canteens, requiring greater insights and innovations aimed at its reduction or exploitation.
3. A third type of waste generated by Italian canteens is represented by processing waste (the inedible parts of the raw materials used to prepare meals discarded in the kitchen or left on plates by consumers). Unlike what happens with surpluses not touched by consumers and for edible leftovers left on plates, in this case, rejection in the organic bin is inevitable because it consists of eggshells, fruit cores, bones, and so on. Although inevitable, this type of food waste constitutes a low percentage of the total production (around 3% of the total food produced).

According to the Polytechnic of Milan, the Italian catering sector generates around 210.000 tons of food excess every year, this is equal to 3.76% of the food flows managed by the entire system. Interestingly, the percentage of real waste from the flow of exceedance is 88.1% (185.000 tons), confirming that only a small part of the food surplus produced by the canteens is recovered properly [9].

These data were confirmed by the Italian Ministry of Health, Banco Alimentare, and Caritas (Italian charity organizations) which reported the same volume of food excess and, again, the same inefficiency of the food surplus management system, with only 12% of this volume getting recovered (around 25.000 tons in 2018) while the rest is just wasted [37].

On a regional scale, the inefficiency of the catering system when dealing with the difference between the amount of food produced and consumed was already underlined by Falasconi et al. in 2015 when his study reported that 15.31% of the overall processed food from six

canteens in the municipality of Verona (Veneto region – northeast of Italy) wasn't served and remained on the food containers [38].

In a more recent Sprecozero study, the amount of non-consumed food from 78 school canteens located between the region of Emilia Romagna, Lazio, and Friuli-Venezia Giulia accounted for almost 30% of the total prepared food, including 16.7% of food left on the plates and 12.7% of untouched food (prepared but not served or portions given back by the students) [39].

Looking at the data of the same study, considering the values measured in all the canteens under examination, scattered among the three regions, we know that the average production value of food waste, net of excess and successfully recovered food (7.8% of total food), is equal to 21.7%.

Different types of dishes are related to different percentages of food wasted. In particular, the same Sprecozero study analysed together the leftovers in the dishes and the total waste, it emerged that the side dish was the part of the meal less appreciated by the consumers, with 24.3% of the total amount left on the plates, while the portions of intact food were significantly higher for bread and fruit (respectively 24.6% and 27.6% of the amount given to the consumers) compared to the recovered food from the first and second courses, and side dish, where almost all of the non-consumed food turned into food waste (Table 13).

From this data, we can see that the three main parts of a meal (first, second course, and side dish) are related to around a quarter of food left on the plate, which automatically turns into waste. The percentage is high, considering the amount of food-related to it.

Table 13 - Percentage of the avoidable food waste fraction of monitored food

Course	Plate Waste (%)	Untouched Food (%)	Non-Consumed Food (%)	Recovered Food (%)	Food Waste (%)
1 st Course	22.2	4.2	26.4	0.3	26.1
2 nd Course	18.0	2.9	21.0	0.2	20.7
Side Dish	24.3	5.4	29.7	0.4	29.3
Bread	11.2	31.8	43.0	24.6	18.5
Fruit	5.4	35.8	41.2	27.6	13.6
Total	16.7	12.7	29.5	7.8	21.7

Interestingly, looking at Table 14, there's a clear difference in the leftovers on the plates as well as in the real wasted food when comparing different food classes. In particular, the food categories with the greatest amounts of not consumed food were "*Fruit and processed fruit*" (43.9% of the prepared food), "*Bakery*" (41.8% of the prepared food), and "*Vegetables and legumes*" (31.8%). "*Meat and meat products*" and "*Cake, desserts, ice creams*" were found to have food waste fractions of less than 20% of the prepared food, whereas food waste in the other food categories varied from 20% to 30% of the prepared food. The category "*Vegetables and legumes*" had the greatest percentage of food waste (31.5% of the cooked food), whereas the categories "*Starch staple foods*", "*Fish and fish products*", "*Eggs and*

egg products" and "*Dairy products*" had results ranging from 20% to 30% of the prepared food.

These results suggest that the percentage of uneaten food (therefore preservable and reusable for human consumption) is mainly related to those classes of food in which consumers have the possibility of refusing the course in advance (just as in the case of bread, fruit, and additional portions of legumes), while in the case of main portions such as meat and fish, which are generally more accepted by the consumers, the percentage of surplus food is very similar to that of actual food waste (i.e. leftovers on the plate).

Table 14 - Percentage of edible food, untouched food, and food waste per category

Food Category	Plate Waste (%)	Untouched Food (%)	Not Consumed Food (%)	Recovered Food (%)	Food Waste (%)
Vegetables and legumes	26.3	5.5	31.8	0.4	31.5
Fruit and processed fruit	5.7	38.2	43.9	29.4	14.5
Meat and meat products	14.0	2.5	16.5	0.2	16.3
Fish and fish products	21.8	3.5	25.3	0.3	25.0
Eggs and egg products	22.0	3.4	25.4	0.4	25.0
Dairy products	18.6	3.1	21.7	0.2	21.5
Starch staple foods	21.7	4.2	25.9	0.3	25.7
Bakery	11.2	30.6	41.8	23.7	18.1
Cakes, desserts, ice-cream	2.0	8.7	10.7	7.1	3.7
Condiments, sauces, herbs, spices	21.4	4.6	25.9	0.3	25.6
Total	16.7	12.7	29.5	7.8	21.7

These findings are confirmation of what was already found by Falasconi et al. in 2015: in that case, the analysis of the canteens in six schools located in the municipality of Verona, showed that the side dishes were again related to the highest percentage of food waste (24.67% of total preparations), with a particular prevalence for cooked vegetables compared to raw ones.

In Table 15 we can see how "*Pasta with fish ragout*" was the most inefficient, with a percentage of unserved food, followed by "*Risotto*" (23.63%), "*Pasta with tomato ragout*" (22.35%), and "*Soups or pasta in broth*" (18.62%). Differently from the previous study, bread also had a high percentage of waste, accounting for 900.58 kg, or 17.7% of the total, confirming that most of the time, bread is taken by the consumers but only partially consumed. We also have an overview of the acceptance of the main courses (including Beef, Pork, Chicken, Eggs, etc.), for which the unconsumed portions accounted on average for only 12.59%, suggesting a generally higher acceptance of the consumers compared to side dishes and vegetables.

Table 15 - Volumes (kg) and percentages of processed and unserved food

Category	Processed Food			Unserved Food			Inefficiency index
	Total kg	Average kg per day	Average Portion per Day	Total kg	Average kg per day	Average Portion per Day	%
Entrée	12720	101.76	509	2533.60	20.27	101	19.92
Pasta meat ragout	1774.88	104.40	522	307.47	18.09	90	17.32
Pasta fish ragout	295.81	98.60	493	135.27	45.09	225	45.73
Pasta vegetables ragout	2070.70	90.03	450	462.71	20.12	101	22.35
Soup	1479.07	92.44	462	289.27	18.08	90	19.56
Risotto	2366.51	102.89	514	440.73	19.16	96	18.62
Pasta with oil	2070.70	108.98	545	268.99	14.16	71	12.99
Main Course	7632.00	61.06	509	960.84	7.69	64	12.59
Beef	1347.8	58.60	488	241.62	10.51	88	17.94
Turkey	748.24	62.35	520	116.12	9.68	81	15.52
Chicken	1346.82	64.13	534	160.14	7.63	64	11.89
Pork	299.29	59.86	499	39.77	7.95	66	13.29
Pizza	748.24	62.35	520	47.47	3.96	33	6.34
Cold cut	598.59	66.51	554	39.58	4.40	37	6.61
Fish	897.88	56.12	468	91.72	5.73	48	10.21
Eggs	748.24	62.35	520	138.53	11.54	96	18.51
Cheese	897.88	59.86	499	85.89	5.73	48	9.57
Side dish	7632.00	61.06	509	1883.06	15.06	126	24.67
Raw vegetables	2598.13	55.28	461	680.96	14.49	121	26.21
Cooked vegetables	5033.87	64.54	538	1202.10	15.41	128	23.88
Fruit/yogurt	9540.00	76.32	509	144.26	1.15	8	1.51
Bread	5088.00	40.70	509	900.58	7.20	90	17.70
Other (sauces, garnishes)				101.01			
Total	42612.00	340.90	509	6523.35	51.37	389	15.31

Thanks to data from these two different studies, we can get an idea of the percentages of food prepared and not served, or only partially consumed, in four Italian regions, and therefore arrive at a percentage of food wasted. In addition, the data provided also gives us insight into the differences between food categories when it comes to food waste.

Although both studies are based on data obtained from other Italian regions, noting the similarity between what is reported by the canteens in the same regions, and taking into account the regulations governing collective catering at the Italian level and the guidelines for proper nutrition, we can consider the percentages of food waste found for the regions of Emilia Romagna, Lazio, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, and Veneto, i.e. about 22% of the total food produced, including leftovers on the plate, and food not served and not kept for later use.

In addition, the results of the Reduce project from Zerospreco provide us with per capita data, which are fundamental for estimating the amount of food produced and wasted in canteens in the Lombardy region.

According to the study, the average quantity of food prepared for each consumer is more than 500 g/day, of which 89.9 g/day is thrown into the bin of leftovers on plates and 69.6 g/day is made up of intact food, for a total of 159.5 g of uneaten food every day for each person in the canteen.

Given these data, considering that in 2022 the canteens located in Milan and its province produced around 83.000 meals every day and that every meal is related to a consumer 4, we can estimate that the total non-consumed food produced every day from the canteens in this part of Lombardy is equal to around 13.239 kg, of which around 5.777 kg is composed by food surplus (produced and not served), and around 7.462 kg is the amount of inevitable food waste (leftovers on the dishes).

Considering that the working days in a normal year are 255, **we can say that the province of Milan only generates around 1.473 tons/year of food surplus (given to charitable organizations if safely stored), and 1.903 tons/year of real food waste.**

3.2.4 Final picture of biological waste in Lombardy

As a conclusion of the first step of analysis of the biological waste from Lombardy horticulture, the following Table 16 summarizes the most important horticultural waste in terms of amount, source and factors facilitating (or hindering) the valorisation and circularization of waste.

Starting from this definitive picture it will be possible to identify **the priorities of applicability and replicability of the Agro2Circular circular value chains.**

For this purpose, we will match territorial specifications of Lombardy waste streams with value characteristics of the waste potential extraction methods in line with the Agro2Circular case studies.

Table 16 - Synoptic table with the territorial characterization of organic waste from Lombardy horticulture

Crop	Wastes from primary sector (tons/y)	Wastes from industry (tons/y)	Territoriality	Producers' aggregation	Seasonality
Tomato	98.600 in Lombardy 420.000 in the district of Northern Italy	Up to 196.000 in the district of Northern Italy	Po' valley	" <i>Oi Pomodoro da Industria Nord Italia</i> "	July - September
Grapes	98.600 (cumulative value)		4 different clusters	PGI and POs	September - October
Lettuce		14.500	Bergamo and Brescia district	POs	No seasonality
Apples	13.000		Valtellina	PGI and Consortium for the " <i>Valorisation and Protection of the Valtellina apple</i> "	September - October
Melons	9.500		Mantova	PSI and POs	June-August
Zucchini	7.400		Mantova		May - October
Watermelons	7.000		Mantova		May - September

As previously reported, tomato is the most abundant horticultural product in Lombardy and is also associated with an important transformation industry. This economic system, however, is not located only in the political borders of Lombardy but it concerns the whole territory of the Pò Valley (Lombardy and Emilia Romagna), so it is more useful to extend replicability considerations to the whole production area and not just to the Lombardy region. In this Northern Italy District the production of tomato waste is estimated at 616.000 tons per year (420.000 from primary sector and 196.000 from industry).

An important strength for tomato waste valorisation is the presence of a very important association bringing together economic and politic interests of both primary producers and the processing industry ("*Oi Pomodoro da Industria Nord Italia*"); on the other hand, a weakness is the seasonality of the production with presence of waste only in the months July, August and September.

The second most important horticultural product in Lombardy is the grapes with the related transformation into wine: a cumulative generation of waste from the whole supply chain is estimated at 98.600 tons per year.

Also, in this case a strength for waste valorisation is the political and organizational structure of value chain with presence of POs involving both grapes cultivation and wine production;

in addition, organizational structures related to the origin mark are present and can help waste circularization.

Furthermore, a weakness in grapes value chain from a circularization point of view is the territoriality because the regional production is not located in a single delimited area but in 4 different clusters; in addition, a strong seasonality characterizes the grapes and wine value chain with the production in the months of September and October.

The third most important horticultural production in Lombardy is lettuce, mainly located in the Bergamo and Brescia District.

Lettuce is mainly grown in greenhouses, or more in general in protected environments, and the generation of waste from the primary sector is not more relevant. Then the lettuce production is almost exclusively devoted to the fresh cut salad industry: we can estimate 14.500 tons/year of waste from this transformation industry.

As for tomato and grapes, also for the lettuce value chain the presence of POs grouping primary producers and transformers can help the valorisation of waste; another important strength is the absence of seasonality: greenhouse production all over the year allows a continuous stream of waste to be processed.

Then in the ranking of waste amount from Lombardy horticultural waste, we can find an estimation of 13.000 tons/year from apples value chain.

Apples are typically grown in Valtellina and mainly freshly consumed so for this reason we have no significant wastes from the transformation. Valtellina apple owns an origin mark and a related “*Consortium for the Valorisation and Protection*” potentially helping in collecting and valorising the waste stream. On the other hand, the potential of waste utilization is affected by the strong seasonality of the apple with the production only in the months of September and October.

Other significant waste streams from Lombardy horticultural system are melons, zucchini and watermelons: all these productions are mainly located in Mantova province in the South of the Lombardy region and are affected by seasonality.

3.3 Replicability case studies and routes for the valorisation for horticultural wastes in Lombardy

Starting from the framework described in paragraph **3.2.4 Final picture of biological waste in Lombardy**, the second step toward the selection of regional priorities was the analysis of the state of art in terms of waste value (type and content of molecules of nutritional interest): following Table 17 summarizes the results of this study for the 7 selected types of horticultural waste in Lombardy.

Table 17 - Potential value of biological wastes from Lombardy horticulture

Waste	Molecules	Content	Reference
Tomato	Lycopene	56 g/100g DW pulp and peels and 44 g/100g DW seeds	[40]
	Polyphenols	From 37 to 155 mg/100 g DW (peels)	[41]
	Fiber	39.11–59.03% DW	[42]
Grapes	Polyphenols	947 – 990 mg /kg	[43]
	Fiber	16 – 17 mg /kg	[43]
Lettuce	Polyphenols	From 5.51 to 11.00 mg GAE/g DW	[44]
	Fiber	260 g / Kg DW	[31]
Apple	Polyphenols	732 – 740 mg /kg	[43]
	Fiber	2 – 2.5 mg /kg	[43]
Melon	Polyphenols	Up to 357 GAE / 100g DW in peel	[45]
	Fiber	From 25% to 30% in seeds	[46]
Zucchini	Polyphenols	Up to 118 mg GAE /g DW	[47]
Water melon	Polyphenols	From 0.5 to 3.30 mg GAE /g DW	[48]
	Fiber	31% pectin + 14% cellulose in rind	[49]

3.3.1 Selection of replicability case studies

Based on the potential economic and market value of horticultural wastes and in compliance with the "green" principles underlying the Agro2Circular project, were identified the case studies of greatest interest for the Lombardy region and potential valorisation routes for the application of the Agro2Circular model.

As reported in Figure 14, **grapes and apples wastes value chains were selected for application of Agro2Circular technological model and replicability assessment**: they are respectively the second and fourth types of waste in Lombardy in terms of abundance and they allow the application of the extraction/purification/stabilization technologies tested in the Agro2Circular demonstrators.

On the other hand, tomato and lettuce wastes are the first and the third most important flows in Lombardy and present strengths for circularization: application of the Agro2Circular model and technologies is possible with slight modification.

In addition, it is worth to notice that the Lombardy region is not only important for agricultural and horticultural production but is also a very populous region with a strong vocation for collective catering. For this reason, additional and collateral assessments related to collective catering waste will be performed in the application of Agro2Circular model.

Figure 14 – Selection of replicability case studies in Lombardy region

3.3.2 Apples and grape wastes valorisation

Grape and apple waste valorisation can be realized following the same technological strategies analysed and applied for the Murcia case studies and described in the following deliverables (see Figure 15):

- *D2.1 - Agrifood waste conditioning and extraction of substances from agrifood wastes*
- *D2.3 - Purification and stabilisation of the extracts*
- *D2.4 - Evaluation of extracts*

Figure 15 – Route for apple and grape waste valorisation as applied in Murcia

Summarizing no waste classification process is needed because as waste is generated separately in the supplying companies which, as they work by production campaigns, generate waste from a single product; wastes are stored refrigerated/frozen depending on the time of processing for recycling.

The first step is to carry out a conditioning treatment, depending on the residue. This usually corresponds to a first washing (if necessary), followed by a cutting/chopping process to reduce the particle size to facilitate the extraction process (in 20 mm x 20 mm cubes). Subsequently, the first technological step for grape and waste valorisation is the **ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE)** with the following conditions:

- water as solvent
- residue:solvent ratio 1:3
- 1 h of treatment
- amplitude 100% (max. Power 280 W)
-

Following Table 18 reports the extraction yield.

Table 18 – Total Polyphenols and Dietary Fiber UAE extraction yield from apple and grapes waste
 Source: D2.1 - Agrifood waste conditioning and extraction of substances from agrifood wastes

	Total Polyphenols (mg/kg dry matter)	Dietary Fibre (g/100 g dry matter)
Apple waste	5,5,296 – 5,456	49 - 50
Grapes waste	14,189 – 16,245	-18 - 19

The following **purification** step of the solid extract, in which the dietary fibre is recovered, includes an oxidising treatment using 2-4% oxidising agent to degrade organic matter and stabilize the extract. Then two washing are performed to remove oxidising agent, and the extract is dehydrated at 70°C to obtain a fibre powder. This treatment increases the fibre concentration of the extract by 5%.

On the other hand, the aqueous extract, which contains phenolic compounds of interest, is purified by adsorption/desorption processes using polymeric resins with high affinity for polyphenol-type compounds so the total polyphenol content increases by more than 9%.

The last step of valorisation route for apple and grapes waste is **stabilization** performed by freeze-drying and by dehydration for phenolic compound and fibre, respectively.

Following Table 19 reports main constituent of freeze-dried apple and grape waste liquid extracts.

Table 19 Characterisation of freeze-dried apple and grape waste liquid extracts
 Source: D2.4 – Evaluation of extracts

	Freeze-dried apple waste liquid extract	Freeze-dried grape waste liquid extract
CAFFEIC ACID (mg/kg)	35 – 37.5	<10
CHLOROGENIC ACID (mg/kg)	665 - 686	<10
VITAMIN C (mg/kg)	<55	<55
TOTAL POLYPHENOLS (mg/Kg)	5,296 – 5,456	14,189 – 16,245
DIETARY FIBRE (g/100g)	-2 – 2.42	<0.1 – 0,6
MOISTURE (g/100g)	2.8 – 3.3	5 - 6
FAT (g/100g)	0.3 - 0.5	0.1
PROTEINS (g/100g)	2.1	2.0 – 2.6
CARBOHYDRATES (g/100g)	90 - 91	85.1 – 86.1
ENERGY VALUE (Kcal/100g)	379	348 - 361
ENERGY VALUE (kJ/100g)	1609 - 1610	1,487 – 1,508
SODIUM CHLORIDE (g/100g)	0.18 – 0.21	0.37 – 0.39
TOTAL ASH (g/100g)	2.1 – 2.2	6.3 – 6.4
SATURATED FATTY ACID (g/100g)	< 0.10	60.1 – 60.5
TOTAL SUGARS(g/100g)	73 - 74	0.2
FLUOPIRAM (mg/kg)	-	0.018
FLUPYRADIFURONE (mg/kg)	-	0.38

It is worth noting that more specific information on the operating conditions and technical specifications are confidential data, available in the above-mentioned Deliverables and they cannot be included in this public D7.17. Now CNTC does not own any intellectual property rights for the horticultural waste valorisation route through polyphenol and fibre extraction and purification, but this is an exploitation strategy envisaged beyond the life of the project. In this case the application of the technology for the valorisation of apples and grapes (as well as any modifications for the application for the valorisation of tomatoes and lettuce) will have to be done through a license.

3.3.3 Tomato wastes valorisation

The most characteristic and significant molecules in tomato waste is the **lycopene** but also interesting amounts of fibre and polyphenols are reported with variable concentrations depending on waste type.

Tomato pomace generally consists of 56% pulp and peels and 44% seeds on a dry basis [50] but also the composition of tomato pomace is simultaneously dependent on the type of final product and the peeling methods applied in the production line. The tomato pomace generated during the peeling phase of peeled tomato production only consists of peels without seeds. However, in the case of tomato juice and paste production, tomato pomace is a mixture of peels, seeds, and a small amount of pulp [51].

Fibers are the main component of tomato pomace (39.11–59.03% on a dry basis), and other compounds, such as oil and proteins, range between 2–16.24% and 15.08–24.67%, respectively, depending on the variety, geographical location of the cultivation areas, growing stages, ripening, type of processing, extraction conditions, as well as analytical techniques utilized. However, due to differences in the chemical composition of tomato peels and seeds, the main valuable compounds that can be recovered are largely different, as summarized in Table 20.

Table 20 - Fiber and Lycopene content in tomato waste
Source: *Elsami et al., 2023 [52]*

	Fiber (g/100g DW)	Lycopene x 10 ³ (g/100g DW)	References
Pomace	39.11 – 59.03	9.82 – 611.105	[53] [54] [55] [56]
Peels	62.79 – 78.56	50 - 1930	[57] [58] [59]
Seeds	16.00	22.01 – 37.43	[60] [41] [61]

Even if the high-value molecule characterizing tomato waste is lycopene, the presence and possibility of recovering **polyphenols** is also interesting. Also, in this case the content depends on many factors such as type of waste, cultivar, the pedoclimatic conditions. Szabo et al. (2019) [41] analysed tomato wastes (peels) from 10 different cultivars: total phenolic content ranged from 37 to 155 mg/100 g DW. Main phenolic compounds found in tomato

wastes are phenolic acids (caffeic, chlorogenic, p-coumaric, ferulic and rosmarinic acid) and flavonols (quercetin and rutin).

The first necessary step to effectively valorise tomato by-products, particularly peels and seeds, is the separation of these two fractions. Two possible routes can be used to separate tomato peels and seeds, constituting the pomace:

- Wet separation is based on the difference in density between peels and seeds. The pomace is mixed with water in a mixer-settler where seeds sink to the bottom, while peels, having a lower density, float at the top [62]. It is a water-consuming process and is suitable for fresh pomace to obtain seeds with high purity. In addition, from an environmental perspective, wet separation generates wastewater and consequently water pollution
- The dry separation method consists of a drying step for tomato pomace, which is then fed onto a cyclone by an air flow where the separation of the two fractions takes place. The peels move upward, exiting the cyclone from the upper outlet section with air, while the seeds, which are heavier, move downward in the opposite direction of air flow and leave the cyclone from the bottom outlet section. It is an energy-consuming process and allows acquiring peels with high purity; it is superior in preserving valuable water-soluble compounds present in peels and seeds with respect to the wet counterpart, which causes significant losses of micronutrients.

Figure 16 - Schematization of wet (A) and dry (B) methods for tomato peel and seed separation
Source: *Elsami et al., 2023 [52]*

For the tomato waste valorization, it is possible to follow a dual route for the extraction of lycopene or for the recovery of the phenolic fraction.

After the first step of physical separation of peels and seeds, conventional solvent extraction is among the most widely used commercial methods to recover high-added-value

compounds, lycopene from tomato wastes. However, some disadvantages are associated with this traditional unit operation, particularly the high extraction time and temperature requirements and the use of organic hazardous solvents, which negatively affect the environmental sustainability of the process and the safety of the extracted compounds [63].

Currently, conventional solvent extraction is the most widely used method for the recovery of lycopene from tomato pomace. Therefore, the application of novel technologies enabling to weaken or disrupt the cell membrane of the plant tissue to unlock the bioactive compounds can represent an effective strategy to mitigate the limitations associated with conventional solvent extraction and increase the recovery of high value-added compounds from tomato residues. Following are the main advantages deriving from the implementation of different emerging techniques, such as high-pressure homogenization (HPH), pulsed electric fields (PEF), ultrasounds (US), supercritical fluid extraction (SFE-CO₂), and microwaves (MW), in the extraction process and the comparison of their effectiveness to boost the recovery of bioactives from tomato processing by-products [52].

High-Pressure Homogenization

- Using high pressure intensifiers to expose biomass to high-levels of mechanical stress and shear results in complete deformation and disruption of the plant cell structure and improves the release of intracellular bioactive compounds from agri-food by-products
- **ADVANTAGES:** Short extraction time - No solvent or a small amount of solvent is required - Environmentally friendly method - Improved extraction yield
- **LIMITATIONS:** Non-selective method - High costs and capital investments - Operators training is required

Supercritical Fluid Extraction

- Supercritical fluids allow for increased solvating power of gases beyond their critical point to extract compounds from the biomass
- **ADVANTAGES:** Low temperature operation - Recovery of thermosensitive compounds - Selectivity increases with changing pressure and temperature - Easy scalability of the process - Reuse supercritical carbon dioxide - Use of environmentally friendly solvents
- **LIMITATIONS:** Non-selective method - Damages to heat labile compounds - Decreased intensity of equipment due to aging, lessening the reproducibility

Pulsed Electric Fields

- Exposing plant matrices to a moderate electric field and relatively low energy input induce the electroporation of cell membranes by pore formation
- **ADVANTAGES:** Selective extraction of compounds - Energy efficient and low-cost operation - Short processing time - Non-thermal and non-destructive technology - Continuous operability - Easy scalability at industrial level
- **LIMITATIONS:** High costs and capital investments - Operator training is required - Uneven distribution of the electric field in the treatment chamber - Arching phenomenon and undesirable electrochemical reactions due to high electric field intensity

Ultrasounds

- Acoustic cavitation followed by the release of a huge amount of energy creating shear stresses, allowing greater penetration of the solvent into the plant tissue
- **ADVANTAGES:** Low energy requirement - Short extraction time - Less solvent requirement - Improved extraction efficiency
- **LIMITATIONS:** Non selective method - Damages to heat labile compounds - Decreased intensity of equipment due to aging, lessening the reproducibility

Microwaves

- MW heating causes physical and biological modifications of the biomass, improving the penetration of the extracting solvent into the vegetable tissue
- **ADVANTAGES:** Short extraction time - High extraction yield - Energy efficient process - Low capital investments - Low environmental pollution
- **LIMITATIONS:** Non selective method - Non uniform heating, reducing extraction efficiency - Thermal degradation of phenolic compounds - Limited penetration of microwaves for scaling up - Changes induced on the chemical structure of the target compounds, hindering their bioactivity - Limitation for the recovery of nonpolar compounds

HPH technology is one of the most effective mechanical methods for large-scale cell disruption: a fluid containing suspended solids is pumped through a tight gap valve utilizing a high-pressure intensifier, followed by depressurization with the subsequent generation of high shear and elongational stresses, and cavitation. Consequently, cells, particles, or macromolecules suspended in the fluid are exposed to a high level of mechanical stress, getting deformed and twisted [64].

Since HPH is considered a physical treatment and needs no or a little amount of organic solvent, it is considered a very environmentally friendly method to recover target compounds from agro-industrial biomass but it is an intrinsically non-selective operation with high energy costs associated and requiring high capital investments [65]: for these reasons it is not to be considered an interesting technology for lycopene extraction from tomato wastes within replicability of the Agro2Circular model in Lombardy.

PEF is a non-thermal electrotechnology involving the exposure of plant tissue suspensions, placed between two metal electrodes, to repetitive short duration pulses ($1\mu^{-1}\text{ms}$) of moderate electric field (0.5–10 kV/cm) and relatively low energy input (1–20 kJ/kg), leading to the permeabilization of cell membranes by pores formation [66].

Organic solvents (such as ethyl lactate and/or acetone) are needed, so it is not a green technology suitable with Agro2Circular approach.

Ultrasound-assisted extraction can induce cell wall disruption, principally attributed to acoustic cavitation; the penetration of the solvent into the plant cells is favoured, as well as the release of intracellular compounds [67]. Low-frequency ultrasound (16–100 kHz) can be applied for the extraction of valuable compounds such as hydrophobic carotenoids (lycopene, beta-carotene, capsaicin, and lutein) but also hydrophilic flavonoids (anthocyanins, tannins) from agricultural by-products [68]. However, US is a non-selective extraction method, and its application could damage thermolabile compounds due to the local increase in temperature. Silva et al. [69] investigated the application of UAE for the extraction of lycopene from lycopene tomato wastes using a mixture of eco-friendly solvents, namely ethyl lactate and ethyl acetate, to increase the sustainability of the process and the highest amount of lycopene (1.33 mg/g DW) was obtained in the optimized UAE processing conditions. So, US is a greener approach for lycopene recovery in comparison to organic solvent, but it is linked to the use of organic solvents and the yield is not optimal.

Microwave technology consists of an indirect way of heating materials by means of electromagnetic radiation at wavelengths between ordinary radio waves, and infrared radiation in the frequency range between 300 MHz and 300 GHz, although in most common applications the frequency range is between 1–40 GHz. This process leads to the evaporation of moisture inside the plant cells, which in turn causes an increase in the pressure exerted on the cell wall. Subsequently, modifications of the physical and biological characteristics of the vegetable tissue occur, leading to improved penetration of the extracting solvent into the biomass and increased extraction yields of the target intracellular compounds [70]. The MAE process has been shown to be an environmentally friendly technology that enables greater extraction yields in shorter time and energy usage than traditional processes, and that can even be carried out without the use of solvents. However,

this technology also has some drawbacks that need to be monitored, such as poor selectivity, non-uniform heating, and limited penetration of the microwaves, which could lead to reduced extraction efficiencies.

From the analysis of the literature and from the comparison with the technical project partners (CTNC, SSICA, DMC) emerged that **supercritical fluid extraction of lycopene is the environmentally friendly method perfectly in line with the Agro2Circular approach.**

Currently, one of the most frequently used supercritical fluids is carbon dioxide due to its beneficial characteristics, including low critical temperature and pressure, high purity, and low cost. More importantly, carbon dioxide can be applied for the extraction of compounds that are thermally unstable and cannot be purified by steam distillation. Since lycopene is a high-added-value bioactive compound and degrades easily when subjected to thermal processing, supercritical carbon dioxide-assisted extraction (SFE-CO₂) can be applied as a green extraction process to recover tomato oleoresin rich in lycopene.

The most relevant operating conditions in SFE processes are pressure, temperature and the solvent flow rate per mass of biomass. A wide range of pressures have been explored from 77 bar, a point close to the critical pressure of CO₂ to 550 bar, a common maximum threshold for SFE equipment. In terms of temperature, conditions ranged from 32°C, once again, close to the critical temperature of CO₂, to 110 °C (the usual temperature limit of SFE units is around 100°C). Available data indicate that flow rates from 0.01 to 400 kg_{SCF} kg⁻¹ have been utilized or, for those reported in volumetric terms, from 0.05 to 400 L_{SCF} kg⁻¹. For reference, extraction times ranged from 10 min to 8 h. [71].

Annex 2 Research involving supercritical fluid extraction from tomato biomass lists all published research involving the SFE of tomato biomass and summarizes the main operating conditions (pressure, temperature, SCF flow rate, cosolvent uses (if any) and extraction time), as well as other relevant information such as the tomato source, pre-treatment applied prior to extraction and target extracts.

On the other hand, according to the Agro2Circular demonstrators, in opposition to the lycopene extraction from tomato wastes, a different valorisation of waste is possible through the recovery of polyphenols and fibre.

Ultrasound-assisted extraction has been reported in literature as an effective method for the extraction of phenolic compounds from tomato wastes due to low extraction time and solvent consumption. Sengkhampan & Phonkerd [72] performed US assisted extraction of phenolic compounds from industrial tomato wastes and analysed different operating conditions (using 95 % ethyl alcohol at a solid/solvent ratio of 1/20 w/v): they concluded that the extraction condition of 50°C for 50 min assist with ultrasonication was the best condition. As demonstrated within WP4 for other types of horticultural waste, ultrasonic assisted extraction on tomato waste also leads to two streams of high-value products: polyphenols and fibre. As in the Agro2Circular demonstrators these two products can be stabilized by freeze-drying and dehydration, respectively.

Following Figure 17 describes the two potential routes for the valorisation of tomato wastes according Agro2Circular principles.

Figure 17 – Potential route for tomato waste valorisation

Route A seems to be able to provide a greater economic return because it led to a product (lycopene) of greater commercial value; however, specific technologies are needed, and it is not easily available in the Lombardy (see paragraph **3.3.6 Mapping of technological providers**). Starting from these considerations, in the study of replicability of Agro2Circular value chains in the Lombardy region, Route B seems to be the most feasible because it allows the use of the same plants and the same technological suppliers of the apple and grape waste valorisation chains. In addition, the implementation of a single extraction plant able to valorise (with appropriate modifications to the process parameters) waste from different horticultural sources would allow to overcome, or at least reduce, the seasonality constraints of waste generation by using different feeds in different seasons.

3.3.4 Lettuce waste valorisation

Lettuce by-product might be an interesting and cheap source of health-promoting antioxidant polyphenols: discarded external leaves of lettuce have been reported to show higher phenol content than the edible portions, due to the intense secondary metabolism activated by external stresses and fresh-cut processing further promotes polyphenol production in lettuce tissue, as a response to cell injury such as eaf cutting or shredding [73].

Viacava et al. [44] reported up to 11.00 mg GAE/g DW in the most photosynthetic lettuce leaves (outermost ones) while in the middle leaves the total phenolic content ranges from

5.51 to 8.59 mg GAE/g DW. The major phenolic compounds identified were the phenolic acids chicoric, chlorogenic and isochlorogenic while the flavonoid profile of lettuce byproducts is mainly composed by flavones (luteolin derivatives) and flavonols (quercetin derivatives) [74].

The dietary fibre content in lettuce byproducts is also interesting: Plazzota et al. (2018) reported an average value of 260 g/Kg DW.

Literature attention has been mainly focused on the extraction of lettuce polyphenols by traditional solid-liquid extraction with organic solvents ([75], [76]) but “green” alternatives are possible. Plazzotta & Manzocco [77] studied Ultrasound Assisted Extraction of phenolic fraction from lettuce waste. The 20s US treatment resulted in a total polyphenol amount not significantly different from that of the control extract obtained by traditional extraction carried out for 15 min. However, the application of US treatments for 70 and 120 s resulted in a 28 and 47% increase in phenolic extraction.

Based on this scientific evidence, **it is possible to apply for the valorisation of lettuce waste the same technological route described in the Agro2Circular demonstrator** (see Figure 18). Starting from an ultrasound-assisted extraction, two fractions are obtained to be separated through sieve filtering. The liquid phase is subjected to purification (concentration via nanofiltration + adsorption/desorption with resins) and then to freeze-drying stabilization: the final product is freeze-dried phenolic extract. The solid phase is subjected to purification (washes with oxidizing agents + sieve filtering) and then to dehydration purification: the final product is dehydrated fibre extract.

Figure 18 – Potential route for lettuce waste valorisation

3.3.5 Other wastes

Valorisation potential of other significant horticultural wastes are following reported but we did not selected them for the application of Agro2Circular model because of several factors such as (i) lower presence/availability of waste in the region, (ii) lower concentration of compounds of interest, (iii) greater logistical and/or organizational difficulties in the creation of the new circular value chain, (iv) greater technological difficulties in the application of the solutions identified in Murcia.

- As previously reported, **melons** cultivation in Lombardy generates around 9.500 tons/years of wastes. Gómez-García et al. [78] illustrated the great potential of these by-products to develop natural and functional compounds rich in phytochemicals and dietary fibre.

Following Table 21 reports total phenolic and total flavonoids from different by-products of melon fruit.

Table 21 - Total phenolic and total flavonoids from different by-products of melon fruit

Type of waste	Phenolics (mg/ GAE100g DW)	Flavonoids (mg/ QE100g DW)	References
Leaf	111.77	59.48	[79]
Pulp	313.45	72.62	[80]
Peel	357.80	204.28	[80]
Seeds	99.69	3.61	[81]

The main content in dietary fibre (from 25% to 30%) is reported in seeds [82]; in addition, the value of melon by-products is also related to the greater presence of carotenoids but today very scarce reports involving the extraction of melon carotenoids are known and developing eco-friendly methodologies for major recovery is needed.

- **Zucchini** cultivation generates the sixth most abundant waste flow from Lombardy horticulture and this waste is rescued as an effective, inexpensive and bio-sustainable source for nutraceutical and cosmeceutical purposes. Piccolella et al. [47] through ultrasound assisted maceration, recovered up to 118 mg GAE/g from Zucchini 'Lungo Fiorentino' waste material (faulty zucchini fruits, out of gauge, damaged by bad weather, badly grown, without the aesthetic marketing features). The phenolic compounds of greatest interest are p-coumaric acid, quercetin and kaempferol and derivatives.
- Waste from **watermelon** is the seventh most abundant flow from horticulture in Lombardy; the main non-edible parts are the seeds and the rind. Watermelon rind constitutes approximately 30% of the whole fruit and is most often dumped arbitrarily into the environment, raising environmental concerns. Mendez et al. [49] obtained fibre from watermelon rind with a solid–liquid ratio extraction in acidic aqueous solutions: yield was 31.61% in pectin and 14.28% in

cellulose. According to Agro2Circular main routes of waste valorisation, it is also possible to extract phenolic compounds from watermelon rind using ultrasound-assisted extraction [48].

Watermelon wastes are also reported as source of additional biocomponents of nutritional and economic value such as lycopene [83] and cutin [84].

3.3.6 Mapping of technological providers

The Lombardy region shows **great technological maturity** for the replication of the CE model studied in Murcia on horticultural waste both for polyphenols and fibre extraction step of and for the biomolecules application step in the nutraceutical / cosmetic / functional food sectors. Often the same company can operate at both points of the supply chain.

A first example of technological providers for the valorisation of biological wastes from horticulture is **Intercos S.p.A.** (<https://www.intercos.com/>) based in Agrate Brianza (MB): it is a prominent company in the cosmetic industry, serving global beauty brands since its establishment in 1972. Operating on a global scale, Intercos Spa is known for its production facilities and internal research centres. The company actively engages in research projects centred around harnessing the potential of agrifood waste as a sustainable source for cosmetic ingredients. Instead of allowing these waste materials to contribute to environmental issues, Intercos Spa focuses on extracting valuable active molecules from them for cosmetic applications. Using innovative technologies and research expertise, the company aims to unlock the potential of renewable resources, transforming them into high-quality cosmetic ingredients with beneficial properties. This approach aligns with Circular Economy principles and sustainable development, contributing to waste reduction and minimizing reliance on non-renewable resources.

Intercos Spa boasts previous R&D experience in the field of circular economy with the creation of functional cosmetics starting from agri-food waste: in collaboration with and Amarey (<https://amarey.it/>, innovative startup specializing in functional products obtained from coffee), Intercos Spa developed the "*coffee butter*" with toning and emollient properties. This product comes from the 'silverskin', a thin film covering the coffee beans and released during the roasting process. To date silverskin is a waste but its specific fat composition gives it very interesting chemical-physical characteristics [85].

Several other companies also operate in the Lombardy area in the sector of biomolecule extraction and their application to cosmetics/nutraceuticals; several companies also have previous experience in Circular Economy projects with the valorisation of agri-food waste (see Following Table 22).

Table 22 – Lombardy technological providers for biomolecules extraction and cosmetic / nutraceutical applications

Technological provider	Location	Operating sector	Previous R&D experiences / CE applications
Indena https://www.indena.com/	Milan	Identification, development and production of high-quality active principles from plants, for pharma and health food	The Product Research Unit was established upon Indena's foundation, with highly qualified R&D resources entrusted with the mission to design and develop new, premium botanical ingredients for health and nutrition. Thanks to a coordinated, multi-disciplinary research approach, Indena can successfully offer innovative solutions in the botanical complex market with a proven track record of approximately 100 patent families. An example of innovative products from circular value chains is Mirtoselect®, fully circular bilberry extract: all fruit waste, water and ethanol used are upcycled and reused in a cycle of endless value. In addition, the energetic impact has been optimized thanks to the investments in highly efficient energy production plants including solar panels and steam boilers, that allow Indena to self-produce up to the 75% of energy needed by its Italian main plant [86].
Res Pharma https://www.respharma.com/	Trezzo sull'Adda (MI)	Selection and development of ingredients for the cosmetic, pharmaceutical, food and nutraceutical industry sectors	Within Res Pharma catalogue there are two Upcycled Beauty products derived from plant product waste <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Liftiss</i>, obtained from Baobab pulp with a smoothing and plumping effect ○ <i>Hydralys M</i>, extracted from cantaloupe melon from Provence, with hydrating and anti-aging effect
BioRESTART https://www.f6s.com/company/biorestart#about	Pavia	Production of functional ingredients (phytochemicals, plant extracts) from fruit and vegetable waste and by-products for the food industry (functional foods, food	BioRESTART set up an innovative, original, and sustainable technology aimed at valorising fresh vegetable agro-food waste and by-products by recovering bioactive compounds using an enzyme-assisted extraction process.

		supplements, fortified foods...) and for agrochemicals companies (phytosanitary products, plant biostimulants)	
Roelmi-HPC https://www.roelmihpc.com/	Origgio (VA)	Sustainable innovations for actives and functionals in Health and Personal care market	By-products from juices and industry concentrates are used for the extraction of cosmetic ingredients, such as biologically active waters rich in "trace elements" and active ingredients for skin treatments. By-products of olive oil processing not intended for food use (lampante olive oil and olive pomace) are used to produce standardized substances, specifically reconstructed as similar to olive oil for cosmetic purposes, with elimination of classic impurities of natural origin. These ingredients are currently marketed in Europe, America and Asia Pacific [87].
Etichub https://www.etichub.it/	Pavia	Functional cosmetics from agricultural waste	In collaboration with the University of Pavia, phenolic and lipid ingredients (tocopherols in particular) intended for the cosmetics industry were developed starting from the processing waste of Oltrepò Pavese grapes [88].
FlaNat Research https://www.flanat.com/index.php/en/	Rho (MI)	Identification and development of innovative raw materials and active ingredients of botanical origin to be used as supplements, cosmetic and veterinary products	PRIME Project from FlaNat Research aims to the development of functional ingredients from vegetable matrices obtained from purple corn processing waste with a beneficial effect on carbohydrate and lipid metabolism. In particular, anthocyanins from pigmented corn Moradyn variety, has demonstrated to inhibit the formation of adducts deriving from the advanced glycation reaction [89].
BiCT https://bict.it/	Villanova del Sillaro (LO)	Research and development to produce cosmetic and nutraceutical ingredients	

A2C – Deliverable D7.17

Tecnoalimenti engaged an operator of a potential innovative circular supply chain in Lombardy and bearer of technological interests (see paragraph **3.8.1 Private stakeholders' involvement**): the replicability potential of A2C model in Lombardy was discussed in order to identify interests, challenges and facilitators for the adoption of the proposed circular value chain.

It was revealed that the company is pioneering research on sustainable cosmetic molecule production. While significant strides are being made in academic research, scaling up to large production remains to date challenging in particular because of cost/benefit balance and logistics. The main obstacle to industrialization identified is related to the logistic challenges from waste collection to the final production of cosmetic products with natural compounds but the territoriality (with the whole value chain concentrated in the Lombardy region) can be a strength by limiting transport costs and facilitating trade; by operating autonomously on two points of the supply chain (extraction and application), the contacted company can further facilitate logistics and shorten the supply chain.

In addition, the cosmetic sector requires replicability of molecules, often posing difficulties when agrifood waste is provided by farmers or food companies. However, Agro2Circular experimental protocols for the extraction and stabilization of polyphenols from apple and grapes guarantee a purity compatible with internal requirements. In conclusion, despite these challenges, the company demonstrates a commitment to innovative waste treatment technologies in its pursuit of sustainable cosmetic ingredient production and the greatest interests are linked to (i) the territoriality of the supply chain supporting logistics and (ii) to the completely green extraction technology able to give added value to the specific final application product (with specific declarations on the label) but also to the company in general in terms of environmental impact.

Summarizing, the replicability potential of the Agro2Circular supply chain emerged during the interview can be summarized in the following Table 23.

Table 23 - Potential for replicability in Lombardy of the A2C chain for the valorisation of horticultural waste

Challenges	Facilitators	Strengths to be exploited
Logistic aspects	Regional territoriality	Short value chain
Extracts specifications	High purity of phenols compounds from A2C protocols	Green extraction protocols

Beyond the biomolecule extraction phase, the main applications of the extracts in Lombardy can be the **functional cosmetic industry** and the **nutraceutical industry**.

In both cases, technological transfer can be supported by the presence of business associations.

For the cosmetics sector, there is a Lombard partnership created to encourage cross-sector collaborations and share strategic interventions in research, development and training: it is the “**Lombard Cosmetic System**” (<https://sistemicosmeticolombardo.com/ricerca-e->

[sviluppo-cosmetico/](#)). In addition, the decision to create a “*Regional Cosmetics Cluster*” with the support of the Lombardy region was recently announced: it will be based in Cremona. Similarly, “**Lombardy Health Bio**” (<https://lombardyhealthbio.it/>) is an association born from the desire of Lombardy companies to create a virtuous system to enhance innovation in the nutraceutical sector.

Lombardy is the leading region of Italian cosmetics: more than half of the cosmetics companies present in the national territory are concentrated in Lombardy and they produce two thirds of the total revenues of the sector. According to the report of the “Cosmetics Observatory of the Assolombarda Study Center and Cosmetica Italia”, in 2023 the Lombard beauty turnover reached 8.8 billion (+13.3%) equal to 66.2% of the national total of 13.3 billion [90]. More in detail, most of the companies are located between Milan, Bergamo, Crema and Brianza.

Below is a non-exhaustive list of the most important cosmetic and nutraceutical companies in the region:

Lombardy functional cosmetics industries	Lombardy nutraceutical industries
<p>FineFoods (https://www.finefoods.it/) located in Bergamo and also operating in nutraceutical sector</p> <p>Biofarma (https://www.biofarmagroup.com/) located in Gallarate (VA) and also operating in nutraceutical sector</p> <p>Pierre Fabre Spa (https://www.pierre-fabre.com/it-it) located in Milan</p> <p>SG Cosmetici (https://sgcosmetici.com/) located in Arsago Seprio (VA)</p> <p>Istituto Ganassini (www.ganassini.it) located in Milano</p> <p>Sirpea Srl (https://sirpea.com/) located in San Giuliano Milanese (MI)</p> <p>Valetudo s.r.l. (https://www.valetudo.com/) located in Presezzo (BG)</p>	<p>Sharper (https://www.scharper.it/) located in Sesto San Giovanni (MI)</p> <p>Sanofi (https://www.sanofi.com/it/italia) located in Origgio (VA)</p> <p>Inpha (https://www.inpha.it/) located in Mariano Comense (CO)</p> <p>FineFoods (https://www.finefoods.it/) located in Bergamo and also operating in functional cosmetic sector</p> <p>Biofarma (https://www.biofarmagroup.com/) located in Gallarate (VA) and also operating in functional cosmetic sector</p> <p>Mc Stone Italia (https://mcstoneitalia.com/) located in Milan</p> <p>EMGI (https://www.emgi-srl.com/) located in Milan</p> <p>Rottapharm Biotech (https://rottapharmbiotech.com/) located in Monza</p> <p>Fitomedical Srl (https://www.fitomedical.com/) located in Binasco (MI)</p>

On the other hand, as previously anticipated, the agri-food system of Lombardy is the most important in Italy and one of the most relevant in the European context and in particular the province of Milan is the first in Lombardy in the transformation sector: with 2.397 food and beverage industries out of 8.150 present in Lombardy (2021 data).

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In this context, however, the sectors of the food industry identified in the A2C model as applications for fibre extracts from vegetable wastes are not relevant: the production of fruit juices occurs in Lombardy mainly at an artisanal or small-scale level and do not justify the use of fibre-based additives.

Despite that, some different **applications in the food sector** have been identified:

1. Diemme Food Srl (<https://www.diemmefood.com/index.html>) based in Cinisello Balsamo near Milan specializes in the production of 100% plant-based and gluten-free preparations; they commercializes with the brand “*Altrofood*” two different types of **vegetable hamburgers** (beef flavour and chicken flavour) but they also produce meatballs, sausages and vegetable cutlets. To date the main ingredient used is pea protein. Diemme Food Srl is also a company particularly attentive to environmental sustainability and to Circular Economy principles: the packaging is made of 100% recyclable material and uses 100% self-produced energy from renewable sources.
2. Salgar Srl (<http://salgar.it/it/home>) based in Palazzo Pignano near Cremona produces and markets **jams**, fruit-based semi-finished products and confectionery semi-finished products intended for professional use
3. An application in **fruit-milk drink** Lombardy sector can be *Resource 2.0+Fibre*¹ produced by Neslè (<https://www.nestle.it/>) in Assago near Milan. Resource 2.0+Fibre is a food for special medical purposes, nutritionally complete: available in different flavours (Vanilla, Coffee, Strawberry), it is a ready-to-drink liquid supplement, nutritionally complete, high in calories, rich in proteins and fibres with prebiotic activity.

On the other hand, if we extend the focus from the Lombardy Region to the entire Po Valley/Northern Italy area, we can identify leading companies for each application tested in Murcia

<p>Veggie burgers</p> <p>Valsoia (https://www.valsoia.it/) based in Bologna</p> <p>Kionè (https://www.kioene.com/) based in Villanova near Padova</p>	<p>Vegetable dessert</p> <p>Valsoia (https://www.valsoia.it/) based in Bologna</p>
<p>Fruit juices</p> <p>Conserve Italia (https://www.conserveitalia.it/it/) based in San Lazzaro di Savena near Bologna with the brands <i>Valfrutta</i>, <i>Yoga</i> and <i>Derby</i></p> <p>Parmalat (https://www.parmalat.it/) based in Collecchio near Parma with the brand <i>Santal</i></p> <p>Zuegg (https://www.zuegg.it/) based in Verona with the brand <i>Skipper</i></p>	<p>Jam and composte</p> <p>Santa rosa (https://santarosa.it/) based in Bologna</p> <p>Zuegg (https://www.zuegg.it/) based in Verona</p> <p>Rigoni di Asiago (https://www.rigonidiasiago.it/) based in Asiago near Vicenza</p>

¹chrome-extension://efaidnbmninnbpcjpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.nestlehealthscience.it/sites/default/files/2020-06/RESOURCE-2.0-FIBRE.pdf

Alce nero (<https://www.alcenero.com/>) based in Castel San Pietro Terme near Bologna and specialized in organic food

Hero (<https://www.hero.it/home>) based in Verona

Alce nero (<https://www.alcenero.com/>) based in Castel San Pietro Terme near Bologna and specialized in organic food

A different consideration can instead be performed about Route A for the valorisation of tomato waste (see paragraph **3.3.5 Tomato waste valorisation**).

R&I related to lycopene supercritical CO₂ extraction is very advanced, numerous efforts have involved the Lombard research centres but to date industrial applications on a medium/large scale are still limited and not available in the regional territory.

In Italy, leader in the sector of lycopene supercritical CO₂ extraction is located in Puglia, Southern Italy and it is territorially very distant from Lombardy not allowing the creation of a territorial circular value chain: Licofarma srl (<https://www.licofarma.com/>) is a research and production company with over twenty years of experience in the field of natural antioxidants and their use in the development of food supplements and functional cosmetics.

3.4 Analysis of plastic wastes from the agro-industry sector in Lombardy

3.4.1 Wastes from plasticulture

The use of plastics in agriculture has revolutionized the growing landscape, creating new opportunities and challenges for the modern farmer. The use of plastic materials such as greenhouses, sheeting and film has made it possible to modulate and optimize the growing environment for crops in an unprecedented way.

However, it has also raised crucial questions about environmental impact and economics. Exploring the ups and downs of this practice presents a complex picture that requires careful and balanced evaluation to reap the full benefits without neglecting environmental and financial responsibilities.

As shown in Table 23, a very large number of crops can benefit from plasticulture, mainly vegetables and small fruit, where the quality of the final product is important and where adverse weather conditions can severely damage production. Greenhouse production of some of these crops also makes it possible to obtain off-season products and to increase the number of harvests per year, thus making optimal use of the soil.

Table 23 - Main cultivations using agricultural plastic films in Europe
Source: Briassoulis et al. [91]

Film Type	Crops
Greenhouse films	Melon, watermelon, strawberry, tomatoes, cucumbers, lettuce, eggplants, peppers, strawberry, melon, watermelon vegetables, carrot, cotton
Low tunnel films	Tomatoes, lettuce, marrow, onion, eggplants, beans, strawberry, watermelon, melon, asparagus, cotton
Mulching films	Leaf and root vegetable crops, vineyard, tobacco, tomatoes, potatoes, melon, watermelon, strawberry
Direct cover films	Flowers, ornamental plants, nursery

Italy makes extensive use of plastic in agriculture: although no updated statistical data is available, in 2011, Italy's hectares of tunnels, mulching and direct cover represented more than 20% of the European total.

The following Table 24 quantifies the applications in Italy and Europe for each type of plasticulture.

More in depth, the plastics used in agriculture are extremely diverse. The composition of the material itself, as well as the presence of any additives or dyes, creates a highly variable landscape of applications (see Table 25)

Table 24 - Main agricultural application of plastics for protected cultivations in Italy

Source: Scarascia-Mugnozza et al. [92]

Application	ha (IT)	ha (EU)	% IT/EU
Greenhouses and large tunnels	25000	111550	22
Low tunnels	26000	68991	38
Mulching	85000	427059	20
Direct covers	12000	61800	19

Table 25 - Plastic material applications and consumption in Italian agriculture

Source: Scarascia-Mugnozza et al. [92]

Application	Basic Composition	Additives	Consumption (t)
Greenhouse film	LDPE, LDPE.IR, EVA, LLDPE	Anti-fog, Photo-selective, UV stabilizers, Long Infra-red properties enhancer master-batch	60
Low Tunnel film	LDPE, EVA, LLDPE, PVC	UV stabilizers, Infra-red properties enhancer	31,2
Mulching film	LDPE	Coloured pigments, UV stabilizers, Carbon black	42
Covering vineyards, orchards	LDPE, EVA	UV stabilizers, Coloured pigments	25
Nonwoven /Floating covers	PP, perforated LDPE		2,5
Nets for collecting	PP, HDPE	Coloured pigments	2
Woven nets (hail, wind, bird, shade)	HDPE	Coloured pigments	3,3
Silage films and protective covering	LDPE	Coloured pigments	8,5
Irrigation and drainage	LDPE, HDPE, PVC, PRFV	Coloured pigments	91,7
Pesticide cans	LDPE, HDPE	Coloured pigments	
Fertilizers bags	LDPE, HDPE	Coloured pigments	12
Other (rigid shets, pots, twine, etc.)	LDPE, PP, PS, HDPE, PRFV, PVC, PMMA	Coloured pigments	91
Total			369,7

Impermeable **films** analysed in the Agro2Circular valorisation systems are used to create a barrier controlling the movement of gases, water, and other substances between the soil and the atmosphere.

However, it is necessary to distinguish two different types of impermeable films with different characteristics and different applications: Virtual Impermeable Film (VIF) and Total Impermeable Film (TIF).

Both virtual impermeable films and total impermeable films play roles in enhancing agricultural productivity by providing a means to control and manipulate the soil environment. The choice between the two depends on the specific needs of the crops, the agricultural practices employed, and the desired level of control over environmental factors.

The primary distinguishing factor of a barrier film is its "*permeability*". An effective film should have a permeability barrier not surpassing 0.02 g/m²h. The lower the permeability of a VIF is, the better the barrier effect is. TIF have a permeability lowered up to 20 times of its average, and with a better heat capacity [93].

Virtual Impermeable Films

- They are a covering able to restrict the movement of certain substance but they are not completely impermeable.
- They are used to regulate the exchange of gases, particularly oxygen and carbon dioxide, between the soil and the atmosphere so they can be crucial in certain agricultural practices where the concentration of these gases needs to be controlled.
- They are **used in controlled environment agriculture, greenhouses** or within specific crop management systems where precise control over environmental conditions is essential.

Total Impermeable Films

- They are covering able to completely prevent the movement of gases and liquids.
- They are used to create a complete barrier, preventing the penetration of gases, water, or other substances..
- They find applications in various agricultural practices, such as **soil fumigation** or the prevention of water and nutrient leaching in certain crops. They are also used in scenarios where the containment of pollutants or chemicals is necessary.

To date specific quantitative information about the use and the consumption of impermeable films in Italy in general and in Lombardy in particular are not available but on the other hand, some reflections and estimations can be derived from the contextual analysis of regional agricultural practices and from the study of fumigants regulations in Italy.

Italy is subject to a very stringent regulation about the use of chemical substances for fumigation. For example, 1,3-dichloropropene is non-approval for use in the European Union, but it is possible only through a temporary deregulation process lasting 120 days; in 2017 [94], 1,3-dichloropropene usage was authorized for crops such as tobacco, melon, potato, watermelon, carrot, strawberry, tomato, eggplant, zucchini, flowers, lettuce, baby leaf, radicchio, herbs, sugar beet, red beet, cucumber, and in 2021 [95] for basil and other abovementioned crops.

In 2023, a deregulation [96] for the use of the two active substances used in fumigants, defines the following:

Chloropicrin

The emergency use has been granted for basil and fresh herbs, floral crops, and strawberry nurseries against agents causing tracheofusariosis (*Fusarium oxysporum f.sp. basilici*), basal and root rot agents (*Rhizoctonia solani*, *Pythium spp.*, *Plectosphaerella cucumerina*, *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*, *Scelrotium rolfsii*), totaling 1214 hectares across 101 municipalities in four regions **not including Lombardy** (Liguria, Emilia-Romagna, Basilicata, Campania).

1,3-dichloropropene

Emergency approval has been granted for nematode control in watermelon, basil, seed chard, cantaloupe, greenhouse florals, strawberry, nursery strawberry, lettuce and greenhouse salad, eggplant, melon, potato, bell pepper, radicchio, and tobacco. The involved municipalities are 326 across 7 regions **not including Lombardy** (Campania, Umbria, Veneto, Lazio, Emilia-Romagna, Liguria, and Sardenia), totaling 12.216 hectares.

Based on this information, we can assume that in Lombardy, the use of impermeable films for fumigation is either non-existent or occurs only under extremely exceptional conditions, in a few years' time.

However, TIF could be used for solarization; this agricultural practice is based on the exploitation of solar to raise the temperature of the surface layers of the soil to levels capable of devitalizing some pathogens or phytophagous pests. The best results can be obtained in southern Italy (where environmental temperatures are typically higher than in Lombardy) or in protected crops, where solarization in a closed greenhouse allows the soil temperature to be further increased, improving the treatment effect.

So, we can estimate TIF use in Lombardy region starting from the diffusion of greenhouse cultivations. As reported in the following Table 26, greenhouse farming is radically widespread in Lombardy, particularly in the province of Mantova (with the production of melons) and in the Bergamo and Brescia district devoted to the salad cultivation.

Table 26 - Greenhouse cultivated hectares in Lombardy

Source: ISTAT data (2017)

Province	Greenhouse cultivated hectares (ha)
Mantova	968,2
Bergamo	800,3
Brescia	307
Milano	111,6
Cremona	91
Lodi	18,7
Monza Brianza	18,5
Lecco	14,9
Como	5
Varese	2,1
Sondrio	0
Pavia	0
Total	2.337,3

Another factor to take into consideration to estimate the use of TIF in Lombardy is the emergent tendency, in line with EU recommendations, to replace these products with **compostable/biodegradable films**. They are made of natural polymers and polyesters and can be used for vegetables both in open fields and in greenhouses. They guarantee the same performance as conventional impermeable films but do not necessarily have to be collected and disposed of at the end of the crop cycle, but they can be incorporated into the soil where they biodegrade, without any toxic effects. Alternatively, they can be recycled in special environments and under certain conditions, such as producing compost directly on the farm by combining it with other vegetable waste. Taking into account the typical Lombard greenhouse crops, potentially involved in the use/waste of TIF/VIF, are for example currently available on the market:

- biodegradable and compostable films in thermoplastic material based on starches, cellulose and vegetable oils suitable for the cultivation of both melons and lettuce [97].
- Mater-bi films (based on corn starch), compliant with the EN 17033 standard, OK biodegradable Soil certified and suitable for growing lettuce [98].

Starting with these considerations it is possible to identify a potential case study for the valorisation of agricultural plastics in the district of Bergamo and Brescia specialized in the cultivation of lettuce and salads in general.

The quantity of waste, although not precisely estimable in Lombardy, is still limited to date and does not justify the implementation of recycling technology as in Murcia

However, it is also worth noting that an innovative technology as bio sustainable alternatives to traditional fumigation could in the future increase the use of impermeable films in agriculture: **biofumigation integrated with solarization.**

The biofumigation method involves growing glucosinolate producing plants as a cover crop between crops in the rotation. Biofumigant plants are broken down thoroughly and mixed into moist soils to induce the production isothiocyanates [99]. The combination with solarization allows to exploit the synergistic effects of high temperatures and the development of isothiocyanates, with interesting responses also in this case, especially in the southernmost areas of Italy or in greenhouses.

3.4.1 Aseptic Bag-in-Bag

Aseptic Bag-In-Bag and Bag-in-Box solutions are widely utilized in aseptic packaging, especially within the food and beverage industry. They are favoured for their ability to maintain product quality, extend their shelf life, and provide convenient dispensing options, making them particularly suitable for products requiring aseptic conditions and those benefiting from prolonged shelf life without refrigeration.

The Bag-in-Bag system typically comprises an outer laminate barrier bag and an inner bag. The inner bag securely holds the liquid product, sealed to prevent contamination. The outer bag adds an extra layer of protection and often features handles for easy transportation.

Aseptic Bag-In-Bag system is designed to accommodate food products with a liquid consistency and high acidity: the most common use is in the fruit juice industries which buy concentrated juices to dilute or mix different types of juices to obtain multifruit juices.

A Tecnoalimenti study in collaboration with the regional Chamber of Commerce allowed us to affirm that in Lombardy there is a very limited number of fruit juice industries: these are mainly small industries (almost artisanal) or large industries with a different core business (in general dairy products) and a collateral production line devoted to fruit juices. In both cases any Aseptic Bag-In-Bag solution is used.

We identified a potential case study in a big company with a production site in Agrate (province of Monza and Brianza), offering a wide range of products including ready-made sauces; they buy tomato pulp in aseptic Bag-In-Bag with a volume of 200 kg

Approximately 16.000 Aseptic Bag-In-Bag are annually used and discarded with the waste code CER 020304 “*Waste unusable for consumption or transformation*”

As well as for impermeable films from plasticulture also for Aseptic Bag-In-Bag the quantity of waste produced in Lombardy is still limited and does not justify the implementation of a recycling technology as in Murcia.

3.5 Waste management solutions

3.5.1 Current waste management solutions

3.5.1.1 Management of biological wastes from the agrifood sector

Today in Lombardy the management systems of agrifood waste are in most cases cumulative and independent from the specific origin of the waste.

Except for some specific cases (limited to a few companies or a few products) or small-scale experimental situations, the fate of waste from agri-food supply chains is composting or biogas production.

Composting

In Italy the composting process takes place in specially dedicated plants using aerobic, anaerobic or mixed cycle processes: agricultural waste but also and above all livestock waste are transformed into high quality organic fertilizer.

According to ERSAF (Regional body for agriculture and forestry services), in Lombardy in 2019 there were 78 composting plants: the annual production was equal to 550.419 tons of compost with a dry matter content is between 62 and 70% [100].

The following Figure 19 describes the territorial distribution and the type of plants while in Table 27 for each province the number of plants, the capacity and the type of waste treated are reported.

Figure 19 - Composting plants in the Lombardy region
Source: ARPA, 2017

Table 27 - Characteristics of composting plants in the Lombardy Region

Province	Plants (N)	Tot waste treated (t)	Waste from collective catering (t)	Waste from agriculture (t)	Production of compost (t)
Bergamo	12	240.270	47.173	117.773	172.850
Brescia	10	229.368	28.037	162.920	114.147
Como	8	95.522	10.221	71.149	43.391
Cremona	3	5.079		221	7.752
Lecco	1	26.985	20.690	6.065	7.338
Lodi	3	29.949	21.816	7.896	7.139
Mantova	7	75.882		30.156	40.821
Milano	14	111.814	40.317	23.438	60.777
Monza e Brianza	1	25.232		24.956	14.951
Pavia	3	55.215	41.342	26.748	45.900
Sondrio	0				
Varese	16	50.592		49.478	35.354
TOT	78	945.907	209.595	520.800	550.419

The largest number of composting plants is in the province of Varese, but they are plants of quite limited size which exclusively treat organic agricultural waste and more specifically gardening cuttings. Then there is the province of Milan with 14 plants and a strong specialization in waste from collective catering and the province of Bergamo with 12 plants. The provinces of Bergamo and Brescia are at the first places in terms of quantity of waste treated and compost produced and in both cases it is mainly agricultural waste.

Biogas and biomethane

Biogas is produced from the anaerobic digestion by methanogenic bacteria of biomass such as agro-forestry waste, dedicated crops, livestock sewage, agro-industrial processing waste, urban organic waste. Biomethane is obtained by refining and purifying biogas. This upgrade occurs by removing water, CO₂, contaminants such as siloxanes, sulphur dioxide and ammonia, to make it directly useful as natural gas without changes to the distribution system.

Lombardy is the first Italian region for biogas production, with more than 500 plants out of the 2.000 present throughout Italy in 2022: 451 plants treat wastes from agriculture and in this case, **Lombardy is the first in Italy, with a third of all "agricultural" biogas production plants present in our country.**

At provincial level, biogas plants are concentrated in the provinces of Cremona and Brescia, territories with the greatest livestock breeding vocation in the region.

Below are the numbers for each province:

- 154 plants in Cremona territory
- 86 plants in Brescia territory

- 59 plants in Mantova territory
- 59 plants in Lodi territory
- 44 plants in Pavia territory
- 30 plants in Bergamo territory
- 16 plants in Milan territory
- 3 plants in Sondrio territory

Overall, these plants produce over 330 MWe and generate an annual turnover of 700 million euros for the companies and owner consortia. Over the last 15 years, the overall turnover of "agricultural" biogas/biomethane production plants in Lombardy has amounted to 10.5 billion euros [101].

From the primary sector, the production of biogas/biomethane increasingly involves also the management of biological waste from the food industry.

A virtuous example is Mutti (a leading company in tomato processing based in Parma, Emilia Romagna, in the Po Valley district of tomato production and processing) which recovers or recycles 81% of waste, allocating the raw material to livestock farms or biogas fresh, unsuitable for processing.

Lombardy is also at the forefront for the step of converting biogas into biomethane: several plants are under construction. From the point of view of administrative simplification, in Lombardy it is not necessary to request any environmental authorization to transform a biogas plant into a more modern biomethane plant.

3.5.1.2 Management of wastes from the catering sector

Food waste from the collective catering system is completely comparable to municipal wastes so they are subject to municipal regulations for separate collection. Their collection and disposal occur periodically through the local environmental service. Depending on the quantity of waste generated and on the number of collections necessary, the collective catering operators are subject to increasing taxes for the delivery of urban wastes.

Lombardy Region applies for the delivery of urban wastes punctual pricing based on the *Pay-As-You-Throw* (PAYT) principle. PAYT is a system aimed at promoting Circular Economy and waste reduction and is based on the application of European Regulation 2018/851/CE [102] about special tariff regimes based on the actual quantity of waste produced and about incentives for the separation of recyclable waste.

The fee is made up of two main items:

- fixed fee is used to cover the operating costs (i.e. street sweeping costs, investments in works and so on)
- a variable portion instead depends directly on the waste produced by the users.

On the other hand, a growing sensitivity towards the minimization and the valorisation of food waste is leading to the identification of alternative paths for the management of waste from collective catering.

The general trend is to combine environmental sustainability with social sustainability: the surplus from collective catering is increasingly used for charitable purposes and initiatives.

The first steps at national level were the Italian Law n. 155, 25 June 2003 (known as "*Buon Samaritano Law*") [103] and the Italian Law n. 166, 19 August 2016 (known as the *Gadda Law*) aimed at social solidarity and the limitation of waste [104].

These two laws were created to encourage donations of prepared and uneaten food from collective catering (destined to become waste) and facilitate the activity of organizations distributing meals and food to the poor, free of charge.

In particular, the *Good Samaritan Law* equates the "final consumer" with non-profit organizations that carry out, for charitable purposes, free distribution to the needy, relieving them of all those bureaucratic obligations which, in fact, complicate assistance to the poor.

In practice, non-profit organizations that recover food from organized catering to deliver it to poor people are not required to comply with the rules on food safety, because they are equal to the final consumer. In addition, the *Gadda Law* introduces administrative benefits for donors through the simplification of donation procedures with respect to destruction and offers municipalities the possibility of encouraging those who donate to non-profit organizations with a reduction in the waste tax.

At regional level, every 5 years the Lombardy region formulates its "*Regional Waste Prevention Program*" including a specific prevention plan for food waste related to the whole food value chain (from field production to transformation, distribution, catering and domestic consumption) [105]. Below are the most important initiatives developed by the Lombardy Region in the last five years.

"ABC of Food Waste" project

In collaboration with the Regional Environmental Education Table and the schools and the Regional School Office, in the 2015-2016 school year, teaching material and a handbook were developed with a training path for teachers, students and families

Regional hygienic-sanitary guidelines for the recovery of food for the purpose of social solidarity

They provide operational indications to facilitate the recovery and distribution of food for social solidarity purposes

Virtuous territorial networks against food waste

From 2015 to 2017, 17 territorial networks were established from the creation of an active collaboration between the Lombardy Region and 16 Municipalities, 9 large-scale retail chains and 21 non-profit organizations and non-profit structures.

The following municipalities were involved: Bergamo, Castelmella (BS), Castenedolo (BS), Chiari (BS), Gussago (BS), Lentate sul Seveso (MB), Lodi, Milano, Pavia, Pioltello (MI), Rescaldina (MI), Rezzato (BS), San Giuliano (MI), S. Martino Siccomario (PV), Sesto San Giovanni (MI), Settimo Milanese (MI), Seveso (MB). In the 12 months, 830.5 tonnes of food were recovered through donation, half of which (435 tonnes) at the Milan vegetable market. These quantities make it possible to estimate, approximately 1.661.000 meals supplied through surpluses recovered in 2016. The economic operators involved in the project were then rewarded with a reduction in waste taxatio.

More in depth, every single municipality also develops plans for the reduction and the valorisation of food waste

For example, the Milan Municipality, approved in 2015 in collaboration with "Fondazione Cariplo" the "*Guidelines of the Milan Food Policy*" [106]. Some of the projects within Milan Food Policy initiatives are listed:

- *Mid-Morning Fruit*: thanks to this program, the fruit traditionally served in schools at the end of the meal (and often not consumed) was brought forward as a mid-morning snack to limit waste. Beneficiaries were approximately 20.000 children
- *Save snack bag*: reusable and washable bags were distributed to children to take home leftovers from meals, in particular bread, fruit and yogurt. Beneficiaries were approximately 50.000 children
- *TARI Reduction for the Donation of Food*: reduction of tax price for urban waste for food system operators active in food donation. Beneficiaries were 55 active sales points in Milan city
- *Neighbourhood Hub against Food Waste*: creation of networks between supermarkets, company canteens and beneficiary organizations in the neighbourhoods which, pivoting on a physical space (hub), can recover and donate the still edible surpluses. Beneficiaries were 15 supermarkets, 4 company canteens, 21 organizations, 4500 people for each hub.

The most significant initiative in Milan city for the management of wastes from catering sector is “**lo non spreco**” project.

"lo non spreco" project

Thanks to the normative context of *Buonsamaritano law* and *Gadda law*, the project “*lo non spreco*” was born in the city of Milan, in collaboration between the non-profit association “*Banco Alimentare della Lombardia – Siticibo*” and the collective catering operator “*Milano Ristorazione*”. It aims at the recovery of bread and fruit not consumed in school canteens to be redistributed to non-profit organizations and charitable structures in the area.

In the 2022/23 school year, over 50 schools in Milan city were involved, recording the withdrawal of over 17.100 kg of bread and almost 39.000 kg of uneaten fruit.

It is interesting to note that “*In non spreco*” project combines environmental sustainability with social sustainability and the inclusion of the poor population.

In addition to the city of Milan, other cities in Lombardy also developed their own Food Policy plans for the reduction and management of waste from collective catering:

- Cremona and the surrounding municipalities defined their own Food Policy aimed at school catering system with the involvement of food companies and with food education projects against food waste.
- Lodi is carrying out a specific action to reduce food waste in school canteens in collaboration with local cooperatives that deal with the collection and distribution of waste.
- Varese established a Scientific Committee aimed at raising awareness among citizens in general and users of the school canteen system in particular (parents and students) on issues related to food and waste. Varese also implemented the “*Green School*” project, then extended to a regional level in 2020. The first step of the project was a study about the school canteen system with the aim of highlighting the critical issues. The following aspects were taken into consideration: waste quantification, correlation between the menu and waste, satisfaction about the food proposed (based on a questionnaire to users), management practices of the canteen (based on interviews with the operators of the collective catering). The summary report of this study was then discussed with the whole school community and finally an operational group drew up guidelines for the reduction of food waste and established short and long-term actions, defining the timing and roles of the individual actors.

3.5.1.3 *Management of plastic wastes from the agricultural sector*

Agricultural impermeable films

The waste management of VIF and TIF films is affected by several challenges related to the material contamination and variability in composition.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838

First, plastic films can be contaminated with soil residues, fertilizers, pesticides, various chemicals and so on; this problem is more serious in the case of fumigation. So, to responsibly dispose of a traditional mulch film, it is first of all essential to remove it from the soil, wash it, and store it in designated temporary collection centers for proper treatment and recovery. In addition, agricultural plastic films exhibit various different chemical and physical compositions depending on the manufacturer and material type. This diversity adds complexity to waste management and possible recycling processes.

Within this complex framework, VIF and TIF film management in Italy is not easy and there are regional variations in waste handling. Lombardy farmers interested in disposing of agriculture plastic wastes, have several options depending on the amount of waste to be managed:

- contact the local municipal solid waste collection service.
- deposit the waste at designated collection centers.
- turn to authorized private operators registered in the Environmental Managers Register. **Cascina Pulita** (<https://www.cascinapulita.it/>) is one of Italy's leading agricultural waste management companies and have an operational headquarters in Lombardy (Cremona). Cascina Pulita prioritizes the responsible handling of plastic waste generated by agricultural and zootechnical operations, actively collecting and recovering various plastic materials, including sheets, sacks, and nets, through specialized services such as “Door-to-Door” initiative. Cascina Pulita's innovative Mobile Multicollection Platform addresses the needs of smaller agricultural enterprises, while tailored services cater to larger volumes of plastic waste from extensive agricultural operations. The company's focus extends beyond collection to the recovery and valorisation of plastic waste, aiming for a remarkable 90% recovery rate.

In addition, regarding waste from polyethylene films and other polyethylene goods from primary sector, it is important to note they are classified “*non-hazardous special wastes*” To facilitate the management of such waste and reduce the amount destined for disposal, the **POLIECO Consortium** (<https://www.polieco.it/>) has been established, in accordance with Article 48 of Legislative Decree 22/97 [107]. The task of the POLIECO Consortium is to collect polyethylene goods at the end of their life cycle, avoiding dispersion and promoting recycling and recovery whenever possible. Disposal is considered only as a marginal option. Waste from polyethylene goods must be delivered to the Consortium, either directly or through entities appointed by the Consortium.

Similarly, **ECOPOLIETILENE Consortium** (<https://ecopolietilene.it/>) deals with the collection, recovery and recycling of waste polyethylene goods, including agricultural films.

Although it pertains to a sector other than plasticulture, it is worth to analyse the coffee capsule waste management system from a technological point of view because also in this case the main technological challenge is linked to the separation of multi-serials.

“**Da Chicco a Chicco**” initiative led by Nespresso Spa [108] supports both Circular Economy and social engagement. The goal is to implement circularity, technological innovation, and

social commitment by giving a second life to used capsules and transforming coffee wastes into fertilizer for rice cultivation.

- The metal is sold to foundries to initiate the recycling process that will transform it into new objects such as pens, bicycles, etc.
- The used coffee, on the other hand, is sent to a composting plant for transformation into compost, which is then subsequently donated to a rice field in the province of Novara.
- The rice produced with this natural fertilizer is later repurchased by Nespresso and finally donated to the “*Banco Alimentare della Lombardia*” and “*Banco Alimentare del Lazio*”, becoming a support for needy people.

This initiative is possible thanks to a dedicated collection system: Nespresso has implemented its own collection system, encompassing Nespresso Boutiques, ecological islands, and specialized services in the respective provinces. Additionally, throughout the province of Lecco and in municipalities managed by the same municipal company in the provinces of Monza Brianza, Milan, and Lodi, a collection service is active. This service allows consumers to dispose of the capsules in the lightweight multimaterial bag without the need to return them to designated collection points.

The initiative now involves also another major coffee seller, Illy Caffè, with a new linked initiative “*Alliance for the recycling of aluminum capsules*” [109]: capsules from both brands are collected with the same system.

From a technological point of view, two actors of the circular value chain operate in the Lombardy area:

- Seruso Spa (<https://seruso.com/>) plant in Verderio (LC) is devoted to waste recognition and separation. Aluminium recovery is carried out using a screening system capable of dividing the waste stream into three fractions: fine, intermediate, and coarse. Coarse, using magnetism, collects aluminium, separating it from non-conductive materials such as glass, plastic, paper, or wood. Of the total small and light aluminium fraction, capsules represent approximately 2.5% of the material in the undersize fraction, which also includes blister packs, lids, aluminium closures, and laminated materials. Once separated, these materials are directed to the recycling process.
- GARM S.r.l (<https://www.garmsrl.com/>) plant in Gavardo (BS) carries out recovery activities of metal scrap and waste materials that can be used for other productions. GARM works with the following types of waste material: (i) multi-materials containing metals deriving from municipal waste separate collection operations; (ii) coffee capsules; (iii) metal caps from recycled glass bottles. Before being recovered, each material is subjected to rigorous quality and radiometric controls and constant monitoring is conducted during each processing phase to obtain and guarantee recovered products with high standards of use.

In addition, two other actors for the recycling of coffee capsules were identified not in the Lombardy region but in closely neighboring territories.

It is interesting to note an overlap, with the same technological needs at these points, between the coffee capsule recycling chain and the A2C demonstrators for the valorisation of plastic waste from agro-industry:

- Ecoplasteam (<https://www.ecoplasteam.com/>) is in Piedmont, in Spinetta Marengo near Alba. They use Seperatec patented manufacturing process allowing them to generate a secondary raw material called *EcoAllene* starting from the elements of plastic-aluminium poly laminates. EcoAllene has high customization and molding characteristics, with high repeatability of the characteristics in all the transformation technologies used. This allows EcoAllene to be comparable, in terms of workability and molding, to the most common plastics: it avoids the problematic continuous adjustments typical of a "recycled" product from heterogeneous plastics and for this reason is a first-choice product with constant parameters for transformation companies.

SAPERATEC technology used in A2C, separates the aluminium from plastic layers, so it removes aluminium coating from aluminised packaging or aluminium foils in packaging (for example Bag-in-Bag).

- Plastic Sort (<https://plasticsort.com/it/home/>) was born in Emilia Romagna, in Imola near Bologna as an innovative startup in 2010, initially conceived as a research project within the Engineering Multiprojecta studio. Plastic Sort aimed to develop a technology capable of effectively separating plastics based on their individual polymers using their inherent electrical properties; an intersection point with A2C technologies is in the optical technology developed by IRIS for separating flexible packaging by colour (metallised and non-metallised). Plastic sort idea stemmed from the need for an alternative to existing methods for plastic separation, which include flotation, optical scanning using infrared spectroscopy cameras, and electrostatic methods, with flotation and optical methods being most used, particularly for identifying and sorting PET bottles. The focus was on refining the triboelectric effect, an electrical phenomenon involving the transfer of positive and negative charges between different materials when rubbed together. In 2019, Plastic Sort achieved a solution capable of consistently producing 100% purified polymers from diverse plastic sources, including PET, PA, ABS and others. Today, Plastic Sort also provides contract services, processing materials from other companies for transformation. Its primary focus remains on secondary raw materials sourced from industrial plastic waste and separate collection.

In A2C project, IRIS has developed an optical technology for separating flexible packaging by colour (metallised and non-metallised).

Aseptic Bag-in-Bag

In parallel to what is observed for agricultural films, waste management of aseptic Bag-in-Bag solutions offers similar challenges related to materials separation and presence of food residues. Aseptic Bag-in-Bag packaging often involves layers of different materials so before recycling, it is essential to separate these layers to facilitate the recycling process. Some

recycling facilities have the capability to handle multi-layered materials, while others may require separation. In addition, food residue can contaminate the recycling stream and affect the quality of recycled materials: contamination can lead to difficulties in processing and recycling materials, reducing the overall efficiency of recycling efforts.

To date, there is no specific system in Lombardy for the management of this type of waste which is destined for landfill.

Although in some sectors, such as dairy or bakery, there is an attempt to recondition and return bags (especially large ones to the supplier), this process is not always completely successful.

From the interview with a company producing ready-made sauces (**paragraph 3.4.4 Aseptic Bag-in-Bag**) it emerges that aseptic Bag-in-Bag are disposed of as waste **CER 02.03.04**. *'Waste unusable for consumption or processing'* without a preliminary rinsing step.

3.5.2 Innovative waste management solutions

To broaden and complete the overview of waste management systems, innovative projects and practices are analysed at a regional but also national level. The management systems described below are not now widespread on a large scale (for example for logistical and territorial reasons, or for application limitations) so they do not currently represent a real "barrier" to the replicability of the Agro2Circular system but in a medium/long term vision they can be taken into consideration as competitive and/or as complementary solutions.

3.5.2.1 Innovative management solutions for agro-industrial wastes

Initiatives for the valorisation and circularisation of agri-food waste are always increasing in Lombardy and more in general in Italy.

In the following synoptic table, the projects most consistent with the A2C approach (for example for territorial, technological or matrix reasons used) are reported without claiming to be exhaustive.

A2C – Deliverable D7.17

Name		Geographic location	Waste valorised	Valorisation method	Description	Website
Orange Fiber	Start-up	Catania (Sicily)	Citrus by-products, specifically orange peels	Transformation into valuable fabrics	Orange Fiber employs a patented process for extracting cellulose from orange peels, turning it into a fine powder, and subsequently transforming it into a liquid that can be spun into fibres. These fibres are then blended with other sustainable materials like silk, cotton, or lyocell to create high-quality fabrics for the fashion and textile sectors. The resulting textiles offer a sustainable alternative to traditional materials, reducing reliance on non-renewable resources. Orange Fiber's fabrics possess unique characteristics such as breathability, moisture-wicking properties, and a luxurious feel. The company collaborated with renowned fashion brands, including Salvatore Ferragamo, H&M, and Ermanno Scervino, highlighting the desirability and versatility of sustainable materials in the fashion industry.	https://orangefiber.it/it/
Mogu	Start-up	Inarzo (Varese)	Agro-industrial residues	Transformation into innovative materials suitable for applications in furniture, packaging, construction, and interior design	The company specializes in using mycelium, the vegetative part of mushrooms, to create environmentally friendly materials as alternatives to traditional plastics, foams, and composites. Mogu's materials are known for their unique properties, including being lightweight, fire-resistant, and biodegradable.	https://mogu.bio/

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Bioplast	Start-up	Salerno	Agrifood waste including restaurants, food processing facilities, and catering services	Bioplastics and biogas production	Bioplast utilizes anaerobic fermentation processes to produce both biodegradable bioplastics and biogas for energy generation.	https://www.bioplast.it/
Duedilatte	Start-up	Pisa	Milk surplus from the dairy sector	Production of eco-friendly textile fibres	<p>The company utilizes amino acids from casein; the extracted casein undergoes a sustainable and eco-friendly recycling process using modern bio-engineering techniques. Duedilatte's innovative process involves changing the shape of casein molecules, starting as small spheres that then arrange themselves in a line. The dried powder is used in the wet spinning process, resulting in a string that is transformed into fabric using industrial textile machinery. The final fabric is then washed without detergents, coloured and refined to achieve a classic milky white appearance.</p> <p>To further enhance sustainability, Duedilatte has established a certified supply chain, allowing for the exploration of other solutions such as whole milk fabrics (100% milk), semi-skimmed milk (blended with cellulose yarn), and a fibre obtained from 100% rice milk.</p>	https://www.duedilatte.ch/

Caviro group	Consortium of companies	Faenza (Ravenna)	Grape and wine by-products	Transformation into high-value ingredients and biobased products	<p>Extra Alcohols: Caviro Extra leads in biobased alcohol production, deriving ethyl alcohol from agricultural sources, responding to the needs of pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and food industries.</p> <p>Extra Musts and Extracts: This sector involves producing must, grape juices and extracts from wine-making by-products. It extracts dried grape seeds from marc, an essential by-product, catering to the food, pharmaceutical and nutraceutical industries.</p> <p>Extra Tartarica (natural tartaric acid): Using wine-making by-products, the group produces natural tartaric acid, a preferred product for baby food producers, pharmaceuticals, supplement manufacturers and functional drink producers.</p> <p>Bioenergy: Caviro Group generates thermal and electrical energy from grape processing waste, producing bioethanol from agricultural sources and biomethane from waste in the Italian agri-food sector. The group has produced an estimated 88.4 million KWH of electricity so far.</p>	
Novamont	Big enterprise	Novara	Agricultural and agro-industrial residues	Production of bioplastics and biochemicals	<p>Mater-Bi®, Novamont's flagship product, represents a family of bioplastics composed of biodegradable polymers obtained from renewable raw materials like starches, cellulose, vegetable oils, and their derivatives. These materials find applications in packaging, agriculture films and disposable products, showcasing versatility and environmental benefits.</p>	https://www.novamont.com/
Naste Beauty	Small enterprise	Torino	Waste from apple juice production (apple peels and seeds)	Production of apple paste, a functional and naturally antioxidant ingredient for cosmetics	<p>The main ingredient of the NASTE Beauty cosmetic line is apple paste obtained by recovering the peels and seeds of Slow Food Presidium apples. Thanks to advanced technological processes, a functional and naturally antioxidant ingredient is obtained due to the certified presence of natural nutrients, including polyphenols, fibre, catechins and sugars. The benefits of apple paste on the skin are multiple: naturally purifying and antioxidant, its natural properties guarantee brightness and firmness to all skin types.</p>	https://nastebeauty.com/

Kymia	Start-up	Catania	Pistachio husk	Production of anti-age cosmetics	Pistactive-F® is the hyper-fermented product protected by patent and obtained from pistachio waste through an innovative transformation technology allowing the strengthening of the phytocomplex naturally contained in the plant, transforming it into an extremely effective antioxidant active capable of counteracting the free radicals responsible of skin aging.	https://www.kymiacosmetics.com/
Bi-rex	Start-up	Milano	Beer, orange and coffee wastes	Cellulose	Bi-rex uses eutectic solvents specifically designed to treat agricultural and food biomass, allowing the extraction of cellulose; in addition, the same technology allows the extraction of chitin from shrimp shells. The final products are recyclable packaging and bioplastics	https://www.bi-rex.net/
Circular fiber	Start-up	Pordenone	Artichoke wastes	Functional flour	Karshof is a functional flour capable of contributing to the protection of the liver and the normal metabolism of fatty acids: it is very rich in fibre, proteins and antioxidants, with a low glycemic index and highly digestible. It can be used for example as an ingredient in the preparation of bread, pizza, pasta, desserts and products for celiacs.	https://circularfiber.it/
Vivita pharma	Start-up	Roma	Agricultural and agro-industrial residues, grapes in particular	Extraction of antioxidants to produce supplements and cosmetics		https://vivitapharma.it/
FlaNat Research	SME	Rho (Milan)	Agricultural and agro-industrial residues	Functional ingredients, biodegradable plastics and biological fertilizers.	Stem, bracts, inflorescences, skins, roots are used	https://www.flanat.com/index.php/en/

Oltree	Innovative SME	Vignola (near Modena)	Food waste from Vignola cherries	Production of functional cosmetics	Oltree products are based on hyper-fermented Vignola cherries; hyperfermentation increases the effectiveness of the extract and its cosmetic action and is obtained by combining bioliquefaction and fermentation.	https://www.oltree.it
Tomapaint	Start-up	Canneto sull'Oglio (MV)	Tomato peels	Extraction of cutin intended to produce a natural paint to be applied to the internal and external surfaces of metal food containers	The extraction process is completely patented and does not use solvents This process consists of the separation of the peels by flotation, the thermal treatment of the peels in an alkaline solution, the separation by centrifugation of a liquid solution, where the cutin is precipitated by acidification and separated by centrifugation.	https://www.it.tomapaint.com/
Grapey	SME	Padova	Pomace, seeds and unripe grapes, wine processing residues	Production of functional cosmetics	The polyphenol content is exploited to produce oxidizing and anti-aging products	https://grapey.bio/it

Start-up

Reggio
EmiliaAgricultural
and agro-
industrial
residuesProduction of
functional flours
and bioactive
compounds

Wastes are subjected to a green *three-level upcycling* process, which results in the generation of new raw materials with increasing value

1. A low temperature drying process allows the water to be quickly removed without degrading the most delicate compounds such as aromas and antioxidants and obtaining high quality vegetable flours
2. A patented physical-mechanical extraction allows to obtain fibres and bioactive compounds starting from flours
3. In a study step is the use of natural extracts for the creation of biodegradable and edible food coatings and films able to increase the shelf-life of fresh products

<https://www.packtin.com/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838

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In addition, as example of innovative system for management and valorisation of agro-industrial wastes, it is worth noting the **TripleW** technology (<https://www.triplew.co/>) currently applied in Belgium in the Port of Antwerp but in a planning phase also in Lombardy. TripleW technology treats abundantly available food waste as a 3rd generation renewable feedstock to produce pure lactic acid for personal care, home care, food and beverage, industrial applications and as a building block of polylactic acid (PLA bioplastic).

TripleW technology is based on a fermentation process through the following five steps:

1. *Food Waste Collection*: TripleW collects food waste from commercial and industrial sources, such as supermarkets and food processing plants.
2. *Separation and Grinding*: Wastes are separated and ground into a pulp, ready for fermentation.
3. *Fermentation*: Using selected microorganisms (subject to patent), food wastes are fermented to produce lactic acid. This process is highly efficient and can convert a variety of food waste streams.
4. *Purification*: The lactic acid produced is then purified to produce a clean, high-quality product; the purification process is also patented.
5. *Bioplastic Production*: Purified lactic acid can be used to generate polylactic acid as a sustainable alternative to conventional fossil fuel-based plastics.

This whole process not only helps reduce food waste, but also helps reduce CO₂ emissions, supporting a Circular Economy.

The optimal location of the new plant in Lombardy is close to food producers (ideally no more than 5 km) and feeding needed to start the process is the following:

- At least 10.000 tons per year of bakery waste (bread, fresh pastries, rusks and biscuits, pasta, couscous)
- At least 20.000 tons per year of dairy waste including ice cream
- At least 40.000 tons per year of mixed food waste from mass catering or large-scale retail trade

3.5.2.2 *Innovative management solutions for wastes from catering sector*

Within the context of the regional study for the determination and the valorisation of waste from the agri-food sector in general and from collective catering in particular, a promising case study for the Lombardy region seems to be **FeedFromFood**, based in Lodi, (<https://www.feedfromfood.com/>).

It is a spin-off founded by researchers from the University of Milan's Department of Veterinary Sciences and developed an innovative plant developed with the industrial partner Norwegian Waister S.r.l able to efficiently treats agrifood surplus and by-products, transforming them into a safe and valuable powder used as raw material for animal feed.

The FeedFromFood plant utilizes a combination of high temperatures and mechanical processes to treat wastes from the catering sector, ensuring an efficient and sustainable conversion into high-quality powder. The output coming is a final product with high nutritional quality, in accordance with food and feed safety aspects required by the EU legal framework.

The final product can be used as feed (ingredient and/or pet food and/or snack) for pet animals.

The main technological advantage is related to the "non-specificity" of the treated waste. The FeedFromFood system can be fed by any type of agri-food waste without any preliminary pre-treatment, selection or fractionation step so it is particularly suitable for application in the collective catering waste sector.

After an initial test in 2020, FeedFromFood activated an agreement with the Municipality of Novate Milanese (near Milan) and Elixor Ristorazione (leading company for collective catering) and installed a system in 2021 at the Novate Milanese Cooking Center devoted to the collection and the transformation of the production surplus of meals intended for school catering.

In adherence to the Food Waste Hierarchy (see Figure 20) the former foodstuff processing sector plays a special role. A significant contribution towards the successful implementation of these targets is possible through the processing of food losses into safe ingredients destined to animal feed, which is recognised as a means of food waste prevention.

Figure 20 – FeedFromFood position in Food Waste Hierarchy
Source: European Former Foodstuff Processors Association [110]

Perfectly in line with Circular Economy principles, FeedFromFood has been recognized and certified since January 2019 as a "*benefit company*", a company with profit-making purposes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838

and using profit to also create a benefit for other categories (for example employees, suppliers, environment and society in general).

More in detail, the common benefit objectives pursued by FeedFromFood are the following:

1. reduce the production of food waste and surplus by increasing recovery activities,
2. encourage knowledge and use of virtuous practices in the recovery and reuse of food surpluses,
3. raise awareness, spread and promote the culture of food safety and quality, the Circular Economy and animal protection, also with participation in public and private initiatives (conferences, seminars), with training courses and/or with direct support.

Within a multidimensional vision, Feed from Food responds to the concepts of sustainability expressed not only as environmental sustainability but also as social and economic sustainability

- **Environmental sustainability:** the FeedFromFood process and technology have been designed and developed to guarantee minimal impact on the environment and low energy consumption. In addition, FeedFromFood mission involves the valorisation of food surpluses (now treated as waste) into new food resources.
- **Social sustainability:** FeedFromFood involves the creation of a distribution channel for the product to be used for charitable purposes, for example by introducing the FeedFromFood product inside the food package distributed by Charitable Organizations to poor families (who own a pet in the family unit) and/or directing it to kennels/cats.
- **Economic sustainability:** FeedFromFood product allows to create value starting from a raw material that otherwise would become a cost (waste to be disposed of), also allowing the cost-effective production of pet food.

3.5.4.3 Innovative management solutions for plastic wastes

In the realm of plastics, there has been a long-standing effort to set up innovative solutions for waste management able to integrate Circular Economy principles into the industry but to date the focus has predominantly been on energy valorisation rather than the remanufacturing of polymers. Despite this, numerous challenges persist, particularly concerning the production system, which stands as a significant barrier to achieving greater sustainability within the plastic industry.

One of the most pressing challenges for innovative waste management solutions is the limited utilization of recycled plastics compared to virgin plastics. This discrepancy arises from a combination of technological limitations and market dynamics. Recycled plastics often undergo performance tests that yield lower results than their virgin counterparts, reflecting issues with composition and contamination levels. Moreover, the scarcity of high-quality recycled plastics in local markets drives up costs, making them less economically viable, particularly when compared to virgin polymers. Additionally, plastic

processors demand large quantities of recycled plastics that meet precise specifications at competitive prices, further complicating the adoption of recycled materials.

A notable constraint on the widespread adoption of recycled plastics is their limited use in certain applications, notably in food packaging. **Stringent directives on food safety and hygiene standards understandably prioritize the use of virgin materials in this context.** The EU regulation 2022/1616 [111] lays down criteria for the safety assessment of recycling processes to ensure they cannot harm human health, and it evaluates processes for which applications for authorization are submitted against these criteria. Under these rules, EFSA provides an opinion on whether novel recycling technologies are suitable to be used for recycling processes based on the kind of plastic input they are intended for, and the principles they apply for decontaminating that input.

Although EFSA evaluates and assesses the safety of recycling processes since 2010, national legislation was still applicable to the use of these processes to manufacture recycled plastic. The EU regulation 2022/1616 ensures that all rules for authorization and enforcement are fully harmonized, to regulate all aspects relevant to the manufacture and safety of recycled plastics. This will result in a big development in the market of recycled plastics. In addition, it is expected that the availability of other types of recycled plastic polymers will increase on the market in the coming years.

In this context, not only technological aspects need to be considered but also effective waste management practices are essential. Collection, sorting, and proper waste management are critical steps in maximizing polymer separation and ensuring the purity of recycled materials. Moreover, establishing robust connections between recyclers and converters is crucial for optimizing the demand for recycled plastics across various applications. Only by adopting a life cycle thinking approach, product design can be optimized to facilitate easier recycling and promote sustainability throughout the product's life cycle. Through concerted efforts and innovative solutions, the plastic industry can move closer to achieving greater circularity and sustainability [112].

About this, it is interesting to analyse “***The new life of the agricultural film***” project led by ECOPOLIETILENE Consortium: the project took place in a territory other than Lombardy (southern Italy) but is very close to the Agro2Circular approach both from a strategic and technological point of view.

"The new life of the agricultural film" project

Ecopolietilene Consortium activated a project for the production of polyethylene goods deriving from the transformation of secondary raw materials through waste collected and recycled, in particular impermeable agricultural films.

The project took place in the period from april 2021 to may 2021. The collection activities took place at two agricultural companies located in the areas of Castellaneta (Taranto, Puglia) and Bernalda (Matera, basilicata), in the sorting and pressing plant of Metaponto (Matera, Puglia), in the recycling plant of Montella (Avellino, Campania) and in the consequent industrial processing plant in Fontanellato (Parma, Emilia Romagna).

The value chain was so organized:

- *Consorzio Ecopolietilene* <https://ecopolietilene.it>
- *Ecolight Servizi Srl* (<https://ecolightservizi.it/>), waste management consultancy company
- *Eiffel Spa* (<https://eiffel.it/>), polyethylene film manufacturing company
- *Aniplast Spa* (<https://aniplast.it/it/>), company expert in the production and marketing of films for greenhouses and sheets for covering vineyards and orchards
- *Metaplast Srl* (https://www.metaplast.it/it/default.asp?page_id=1), environmental services company specializing in the collection, selection, sorting and transport of waste from polyethylene goods in agriculture
- *Plastimontella Srl* (<https://plastimontella.com/>) company specialized in the recycling of polyethylene and in the production of secondary raw material for film extrusion and injection molding

Following the operational steps:

- 1. Waste collection** The plastic waste collection phase was carried out by the Metaplas company at two different farms in Puglia (Castellaneta) and Basilicata (Bernalda); once the different fractions of plastic product waste were brought together in a single loading unit, the various loose loads of material were conveyed, for a total of 34.100 kg of agricultural greenhouses, to the Metaponto-Bernalda plant (Basilicata region).
- 2. Sorting** The sorting activities by Metaplas operators made it possible to eliminate any fractions extraneous to the agricultural greenhouses collected from Aniplast Srl customers. Once the sorting phase was completed, the pressed material (30.850 kg) was sent to the recycling plant in Campania
- 3. Recycling** Plastimontella carried out industrial tests aimed at producing different types of granules suitable for being transformed by Eiffel for the production of different polyethylene goods. At the initial grinding and washing phase, an intense odor was found and a further tendency for the material to take on a dark amber color tending was reported. After the drying and extrusion phase, the result was a homogeneous, non-swollen granule, black in color and suitable for bubble filming with a degree of density between 0.5 and 0.8 g/cm³.
- 4. Transformation** Eiffel carried out the industrial test for the production of vapor barrier films using the secondary raw material produced by Plastimontella. The behavior of the two types of regenerated material was different. "R-LDPE 100%" was used, not without difficulty, at 50% on two layers of 30%, therefore on the total film it was dosed at 30%; "R-LDPE cut at 20%" was used at 80% on two layers of 30%, therefore it was dosed at 48% of the total film. R-LDPE mixed at 20% was selected for the transformation of all material generated within the project

The total amount of PE goods recovered within the project was 30.850 kg, totally from transparent "neutral" agricultural greenhouses applied in agriculture; the granule obtained, black in colour, will be used in the building film and geo-membrane sectors.

3.6 Local legislative framework

The following chapter outlines the Italian regulatory framework for the application of the Agro2Circular solutions and, more in general, for the innovation on Circular Economy.

It is important to stress that to date most of the aspects relevant for Agro2Circular replication are not regulated at regional level, but the legislation has national value (and often refers to European legislation).

The first and most important Italian law about CE is the legislation on the waste cycle: law n.221, 28 December 2015, known as the “**Environmental Bill**” [113]. In general, it promotes the green economy and sustainable development and acts on a broad scale on everything related to the environment, from waste management to sustainable mobility.

For example, it contains measures aimed at incentivizing the purchase of products derived from recycled "post-consumer" materials or from the recovery of waste and materials resulting from the disassembly of complex products (Article 23).

On the other hand, about composting, Article 37 contains provisions aimed at encouraging aerobic composting, (both individual and community level), thanks to the reduction in the waste tax, and thanks to the simplification of the authorisation regime for plants dedicated to the so-called community composting of biodegradable waste deriving from agricultural and nursery activities or from kitchens, canteens, markets, gardens or parks.

At national level the Italian government with the National Law n. 141, 12 December 2019 [114], n. 141 (in G.U. 13/12/2019,) **established a specific fund to support investments in environmental sustainability aimed at promoting the transition to the Circular Economy**. Moreover, the Budget Law for 2020 foresees a considerable public investment plan supporting the development of a Green Deal. The initiative encourages the development of sustainable companies and projects through two new investment funds. The main goal is to activate urban regeneration and energy conversion projects and to encourage the use of renewable sources, as well as the issue of green government bonds, the "green bonds". The Ministry of Economy and Finance may also intervene, through the granting of one or more guarantees, to support specific investment programs, also in public-private partnerships, aimed at realizing economically sustainable projects. In this framework, also the “Industry 4.0 Plan” adopted by the Italian Government could be an opportunity to support the transition to a CE, both by generally enhancing investments in research, development, innovative technologies and by encouraging the diffusion of systems based on collection and analysis of large amounts of data. All this with the aim of making production processes more efficient in terms of time and resources used.

From a strategic point of view, following the 2030 Agenda, the **Italian Strategy for Sustainable Development** [115] released in 2022 shapes a new vision towards a circular, low-emission economy, resilient to climate impacts and to other global changes endangering local communities, prioritising the fight against biodiversity loss, alteration of the fundamental biogeochemical cycles (carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus) and land-use change. Italy is working, together with the European Union and its Member States, to define a

common framework for addressing and reflecting the challenges of the 2030 Agenda. In this context, the EU Green Deal provides the main reference for Member States in setting their internal strategic objectives.

In 2022 Italian Ministry of Ecological Transition also adopted a **National Strategy for the Circular Economy** [116]. It intends to define new administrative and fiscal tools to strengthen the market of secondary raw materials with the purpose to make them competitive in terms of availability, performance and costs compared to virgin raw materials. To this end, the National Strategy produces its effects on the material purchase chain (Minimum Environmental Criteria for green purchases in the Public Administration), on the criteria on the basis of which a waste shall cease to be a waste (End of Waste), on the extended producer responsibility, on the role of the consumer and on the widespread of sharing practices and "product as a service".

The strategy emphasizes eco-design and eco-efficiency and the following six of intervention areas are recognized as priorities:

1. electronics
2. packaging
3. plastics
4. textiles
5. construction
6. food, water and nutrients

In 2022 Italian Ministry of Ecological Transition also established the **Circular Economy Observatory** [117] with the following roles:

- monitor the implementation status of the measures defined in the National Strategy for the Circular Economy, identify any obstacles and propose initiatives aimed at resolving them;
- ensure the discussion with stakeholders and associations through involvement in thematic tables and consultation on programmatic documents;
- carry out communication and dissemination actions;
- prepare summary documents on the implementation status of the measures and any critical issues;
- monitor, define and quantify the intermediate targets of the measures contained in the National Strategy for the Circular Economy.

3.6.1 Regulation of food surplus

As previously anticipated, (**paragraph 3.5.1.3 Management of wastes from catering sector**), Italy adopted a consolidated approach toward food loss and waste, through the redistribution of food surplus to those in need.

This policy was instituted with the national laws n. 155, 25 June 2003 (known as "**Buon Samaritano Law**") and n. 166, 19 August 2016 (known as the "**Gadda Law**")

Summarizing, these laws established that:

- food sector operators can donate their surpluses free of charge to people in difficulty;
- food no longer suitable for people can alternatively be donated to feed animals or to create composting materials;
- unsold bread (or other bakery products) can be donated within 24 hours from their production;
- donors must respect all control procedures and comply with hygiene and health requirements and are responsible for them until the moment of donation.

In parallel, the Gadda law provides incentives to encourage and promote virtuous behaviours:

- virtuous behaviours and positive models about food waste are promoted to raise awareness among citizens, companies, restaurants and schools with the adoption of anti-waste systems able to help people, food and the environment;
- incentives are available for restaurants using containers to allow consumers to take home leftovers from their meals (so called “*doggy bags*”);
- food operators donating excess products will be able to count on tax relief regarding the waste tax.

This normative framework also provided for the establishment of the **National Observatory on Food Surplus, Recovery, and Waste** (OERSA) [118]. It is a technical independent entity tasked with collecting and disseminating information and statistics, policy, and best practices related to (i) surpluses along the food supply chain; (ii) food recovery and reuse for human consumption; and (iii) food waste at the household level. Data collected by the OERSA are aimed to provide a benchmark assessment as a reference for further monitoring as well as to improve policy and intervention actions.

3.6.2 Regulation of compost, biogas and biomethane production

The main national legislative documents regulating **compost** production and use are:

- Legislative Decree 3 April 2006, no. 152 - “*Environmental regulations*” known “**Consolidated Environmental Act**” [119]. It coordinates environmental legislation about procedures for integrated environmental authorizations, soil and water protection, fight against desertification and waste management.
- Legislative Decree 29 April 2010, no. 75 “*Reorganization and revision of the discipline on fertilizers*” [120].

According to these laws, compost is defined as: “*the product obtained from composting, or from integrated processes of anaerobic digestion and composting, of separately collected organic waste, other organic materials not classified as waste, by-products and other organic waste that complies with the requirements and characteristics established by the current legislation on fertilizers and composting at the place of production*”.

More in depth, “community composting” is an activity carried out collectively by several domestic and non-domestic users of the organic fraction of waste produced by them, for the

purpose of using the compost produced by the conferring users; community composting can only be considered as an activity in which the waste producer coincides with waste deliver, and compost user.

At regional level, Decree no. 7/12764 of the Lombardy Region, 16 April 2003 [121] indicates the guidelines for the construction and use of compost production plants.

The main national legislative documents regulating **biogas** production and use are:

- Legislative Decree 29 December 2003, no. 387 - "*Implementation of Directive 2001/77 on the promotion of electricity produced from renewable energy sources in the internal electricity market*" [122]. It establishes the admissible sources of energy production: biomasses for biogas production are the biodegradable section of agricultural and livestock residues and solid urban and industrial waste.
- Legislative Decree 3 April 2006, no. 152 - "*Environmental regulations*" known "**Consolidated Environmental Act**" (also regulating compost production). According to this decree, plants up to 3 MW can be considered totally non-polluting so they can be installed in rural contexts.

From a technical point of view, the national reference document is the **UNI 11922 standard** [123]. The standard defines the characteristics of agricultural, food and agro-food waste to be sent to anaerobic biodigestion plants and provides a technical reference to facilitate the implementation of legislation on food/biomass for use in anaerobic digestion.

In this context, it is also worth noting a regional legislative framework including:

- Decree 11/2006 n. 8/3439 "*Adaptation to the Lombardy Region Action Program for the protection and remediation of water from pollution caused by nitrates of agricultural origin*". It regulates criteria and general technical standards for the use of biomass in areas vulnerable to nitrates [124].
- Decree 12/30/2003 n. 7/15944 [125] delegating to the provinces the administrative functions (projects approval, construction and operation authorizations) about biogas plants.

At regional level, in July 2014 the Lombardy Region also released the "*Guidelines for the safe management of electricity production plants from renewable sources, through anaerobic digestion of organic matrix substrates, commonly known as biogas*" (Decree no. 6463 [126]).

According to this regional law, the Province is the territorially competent authority for issuing construction and operation authorizations and the digestate can be used for agronomic purposes if the following are input to the plant: (i) livestock effluents or (ii) crop residues and residues produced by agricultural businesses or (iii) by-products limited organic matrix and wastes from agricultural and agri-food activities or (iv) agricultural products or (v) matrices recognised as suitable for animal feed.

Biomethane production is regulated and incentivised at national level with the *Interministerial Decree 2 March 2018* [127]. It represents a strategic measure aiming to promote the use of renewable sources through the development of Circular Economy initiatives and virtuous management of urban waste and agricultural waste.

In particular, the Decree has the following objectives:

- to promote the use of biomethane,
- to promote the reconversion of biogas plants,
- to promote the incentives for production plants of other advanced biofuels other than biomethane.

The *Ministerial Decree 15 September 2022* [128] supports investments for the construction of new biomethane production plants and for the total or partial reconversion of existing biogas plants. It promotes the incentive of biomethane fed into the natural gas network through capital support (equal to a maximum of 40% of the expenses incurred) and an energy account incentive (incentive tariff applied to the net production of biomethane).

Newly built biomethane production plants, agricultural or waste-based, and interventions for the reconversion to biomethane (total or partial) of existing agricultural electricity production plants fuelled by biogas can benefit from these incentives.

As anticipated at chapter 3.5.1.1. “**Management of biological wastes from agrifood sector**”, Lombardy region implemented a bureaucratic simplification for the conversion of biogas plants to biomethane. With regional decree no. 4803 of 31/5/2021, “*Regional guidelines for the authorization of electricity production plants from renewable energy sources and biomethane*” [129] were approved: it is not necessary to request any environmental authorization to transform a biogas plant into a more modern biomethane plant.

3.6.3 Regulation on recycled packaging

Italian legislation about plastic recycling mainly refers to European laws, receiving it and evolving with them.

At national level we must take into account the two following Decrees:

- *Legislative Decree 152 of 3 April 2006* (known as the “**Environmental Code**”) [130] describes the approach to waste and aims at the correct management and recycling according to the principles of precaution, prevention, sustainability and cooperation along the whole waste management chain.
- *Legislative Decree 116 of 30 September 2020* (known as the “**New Environmental Code**”) [131] indicates the recycling objectives for the next few years and precisely: (i) recycling of 55% of urban waste by 2025, 60% by 2030 and 65% by 2035, (ii) recycling of 50% of plastic packaging by 2025 and 55% by 2030 (iii) recycling of 60% of packaging (of any material) by 2025 and 65% by 2030

More in general, Italian law discourages the use of plastics and other non-recyclable materials; Italian companies are invited to limit the use of disposable products and to adopt

separate waste collection systems. In addition, use of biodegradable and compostable packaging is encouraged with tax relief for companies using products based on recycled materials.

In addition to national laws, there are also voluntary regulations developed by the UNIPLAST technical commission (UNI 10667-1:2017 standard [132]), classifying primary and secondary plastic materials obtained from the recovery and recycling of plastic waste and establishing the requirements that these materials must have, the methods for their recycling and the possible uses after recycling.

To facilitate and coordinate all plastic packaging recycling activities, CONAI (National Packaging Consortium) published **Plastic Recycling Guidelines** in 2020 [133]. In line with European indications, they are based on the principle of hierarchical waste management. The waste management hierarchy is a conceptual framework designed to guide and rank waste management decisions both at individual and organisational level. It establishes a decreasing order of preferability of the management methods: in first place is the concept of upstream prevention, aimed at improving packaging from the point of view of containing the environmental impact and the use of resources, to then move on to reuse, recycling, recovery (for example energy recovery) up to disposal, considered the last possible solution only if all the others are not practicable.

In this context, the prevention levers applied by CONAI Plastic Recycling Guidelines are:

- saving raw materials.
- reuse.
- use of recycled material.
- optimization of logistics.
- facilitation of recycling activities.
- simplification of the packaging system.
- optimization of production processes.

With specific reference to plastic packaging intended for contact with food, European legislation is in force: according to **(EU) 2022/1616** [134] the European Food Safety Authority lays down criteria for the safety assessment of recycling processes to ensure they cannot harm human health, and it evaluates processes for which applications for authorization are submitted against these criteria. Under these rules, EFSA provides an opinion on whether novel recycling technologies are suitable to be used for recycling processes and it depends on the kind of plastic input they are intended for. Although EFSA evaluates and assesses the safety of recycling processes since 2010, national legislation was still applicable to the use of these processes to manufacture recycled plastic. (EU) 2022/1616 will ensure that all rules for authorization and enforcement are fully harmonized, to regulate all aspects relevant to the manufacture and safety of recycled plastics.

In Italy, the New Environmental Code also introduced the obligation to label packaging environmentally to facilitate collection, reuse, recycling by providing clear information to consumers on the destination of packaging at the end of its life: According to this regulation,

producers will have to identify and classify the packaging by reporting on it the nature of the packaging materials. The minimum information to be reported on packaging are:

- type of packaging (e.g. bottle, flask, tray, etc.)
- specific identification of the material with alphanumeric coding
- family of the reference material (e.g. steel, aluminium, plastic, etc.)
- indication of the type of collection (whether separate or undifferentiated) and, in the case of separate collection, the indication of the reference material

In addition to this minimum information, it is possible to associate other environmental information such as:

- instructions to the consumer to support separate collection
- graphic symbol for quality separate collection, recyclability, environmental brands, compostability.

3.7 Environmental assessment

According to the replicability analysis for the Lombardy Region carried out in the previous chapters, replicability opportunities were investigated regarding the horticultural and plastics waste valorisation (see Section 3.3. **Case studies and routes for the valorisation for horticultural wastes in Lombardy** and Section 3.4. **Analysis of plastic wastes from agro-industry sector in Lombardy**).

Grapes, apples, tomatoes and lettuce were identified as viable waste streams for replicability purposes due to their occurrence in Lombardy. Regarding the plastic chain, the technological assessment of replicability reveals that the limited quantity of agricultural films and aseptic Bag-in-Bag products does not justify the implementation of recycling technologies as in Murcia (see 3.4.1. **Wastes from plasticulture** and 3.4.2. **Aseptic Bag-in-Bag**). However, the environmental screening carried out in the following is applicable to both the horticultural and plastics waste stream valorisation.

Replicating a complex production process in a different region possibly implies differences in environmental impacts. These can be linked to several factors, such as the electricity mix used locally, the transport modes and engine technologies employed in the supply chain and the distances covered, the water availability in the region under study, and potential modifications made to the production systems. The most relevant thereof are summarized below.

Main factors affecting the environmental impact in case of business model replication in another location

- The electricity mix used in production processes
- Engine technology and fuel used in transport processes
- The distance from the waste/resource collection to the production site
- The water availability in the region/country under study
- Potential modifications to the production model

In the following sub-section, VTT analysed the replicability context with respect to the factors highlighted. The comparison of region-specific environmental impacts is carried out using publicly available, comparable datasets at a country or regional level.

3.7.1 Electricity mix used in the production processes

Electricity is a relevant input of most production processes, independently of their location. At the same time, the environmental impacts of electricity production strongly diverge depending on the electricity production technology used.

Considering available average country data on the most often reported impact of electricity production, i.e., climate change, **a higher environmental impact can be expected in Italy**, where according to the latest data released by the European Environment Agency average GHG emissions by electricity consumption are 225 gCO_{2e}/kWh, 42% higher than in Spain (158 gCO_{2e}/kWh) [135].

3.7.2 Engine technology and fuel used in transport processes

During a product's life cycle, different transport processes take place, for example in the supply chain to bring (recycled) raw materials to the production site, or downstream, to allow for further processing or distribution to wholesalers or customers.

Depending on the distance to be covered, the available infrastructure and the driving environment (urban or rural), different transport modes can be used. For the Agro2Circular application case, which addresses production streams in rural areas, road transport via heavy duty vehicles can be assumed, which is, from a climate perspective, more damaging than railway and water transport on average, although the engine used in railway transport in the specific route should be considered as well, being electric engines less emission intensive than combustion engines [136].

Being both the case study region Murcia and the replicability regions Lombardy and Central and Western Lithuania located in the EU, the freight transport sector is subjected to the same emissions standards, i.e., EURO 6 for lorries registered after 2013 for both oil and diesel fueled vehicles (according to Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/1362 of 1 August 2022 implementing Regulation (EC) No 595/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the performance of heavy-duty trailers regarding their influence on the CO₂ emissions, fuel consumption, energy consumption and zero emission driving range of motor vehicles and amending Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/683). Given the common regulatory framework, **no differences in environmental performances due to engine technology can be assumed between the Murcia application case and replication in other EU countries**.

In any case, it should be noted that transport processes are generally not the main contributor within a product's environmental impact, although specific values need to be calculated case by case.

3.7.3 Distance from waste collection (supplier) to production site

Another factor affecting the environmental impact of transport is the distance travelled.

Given the regional character of the investigated streams, theoretical transportation distances can be estimated based on the extension of the region. According to Eurostat data, the surface area of the Murcia region amounts to 11.314 km [137], while that of Lombardy amounts to 23.864 [138]. Using the square root of the area as a proxy for the comparison of travelled distances in the region, travelled distance in Lombardy can be assumed to be 45% longer than in Murcia, thus **theoretically causing higher environmental impacts**.

However, specific considerations can be devoted to individual case studies.

As previously described, the production of apples, grapes, tomato and lettuce are concentrated in restricted and delimited territories, and this is an advantage not only from a logistic point of view logistical also in environmental terms for the movement of waste. On the other hand, the production of grapes is localized in 4 different territorial clusters and greater logistical efforts are necessary to cumulatively use the waste.

3.7.4 Water availability in the region/country under study

If production processes involve water consumption, their environmental impact can vary depending on the water resource availability in the area. A recognized screening tool for water related physical risk is the Aqueduct Water Risk Atlas [139], which estimates among others the water stress as “*the ratio of total water demand to available renewable surface and groundwater supplies*”. Water demand includes domestic, industrial, irrigation, and livestock uses. Available renewable water supplies include the impact of upstream consumptive water users and large dams on downstream water availability [140].

According to this indicator, the Murcia region is attested an extremely high water stress level (>80%), while in Lombardy the risk level depends on the minor basin level, varying from high (40%-80%) in the eastern part (Oglio sub-basin) to mid-low (10%-20%) in central Lombardy around Milan (Lambro, Olona and Trebbia sub-basins) and very low in the lake regions (Lago di Como and Lago Maggiore sub-basins). All in all, **the risk related to water stress is lower in Lombardy than in the Murcia region**, although it needs to be taken into account in high-risk basins, where the use of water saving technologies and processes needs to be taken into account.

3.7.5 Potential modifications to the production model

According to the replicability analysis, not all production processes used in Murcia can be transferred one-to-one to the Lombardy case. While grapes and apples waste can be processed applying the Agro2Circular model, tomato and lettuce waste require slightly modified processes.

Tomato waste requires additional processing to achieve the separation of peels from seeds, which can be conducted through a dry or a wet route, **the former leading to an increased energy consumption and the latter impacting water consumption and subsequent water scarcity impacts**. For a following treatment step, as alternatives to solvent extraction, which implies the use of hazardous products, emerging technologies were analysed and ultrasonic assisted extraction and supercritical CO₂ extraction were identified as viable alternatives, given the limited energy consumption and because they do not require the use of solvents.

3.7.6 Summary and recommendations

The following Table 28 juxtaposes the main local conditions affecting the environmental impacts of the proposed production systems in Murcia and Lombardy.

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Table 28 - Main local conditions Agro2Circular solution affecting environmental impacts in Lombardy

Factor affecting the environmental impact in case of business model replication	Murcia	Lombardy	Remarks
Electricity mix used in production processes	Average CO ₂ e/kWh: 158 gCO ₂ e/kWh	Average CO ₂ e/kWh: 225 gCO ₂ e/kWh	Data are available only at national and not at regional level. Company-specific impact can diverge e.g. depending on own plants installed and/or choice of supplier.
Engine technology and fuel used in transport processes	Lorry, EURO 6 compliant engine, diesel	Lorry, Euro 6 compliant engine, diesel	No differences expected
Distance from the waste/resource collection to the production site	Area: 11,314 km ²	Area: 23,864 km ²	Longer distances to be expected in Lombardy on average due to larger area. Strongly case dependent.
Water availability in the region/country under study	Extremely high-water stress level	Between very low (lake region) to high water stress (Oglio sub-basin) depending on the minor basin	Impact on water scarcity is expected to be lower in Lombardy, strongly dependent on the sub-basin where production takes place.
Potential modifications to the production model		Tomatoes need additional treatment, possibly increasing energy and water consumption	

According to the results obtained in the environmental screening, **the following conditions are expected to have a positive influence on the environmental impacts of the business model replication:**

CONDITIONS WITH POTENTIAL POSITIVE INFLUENCE ON THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF THE BUSINESS MODEL REPLICATION

Avoiding establishing water intensive production processes in particularly water scarce regions

Relying on electricity from renewable energy via company's own production or renewables certificates

Reducing transport distances by establishing industrial clusters at a sub-regional area

Considering the effect of modifications to the production model on specific local conditions

3.8 Stakeholders' involvement

In line with the dual approach used for the replicability study, the stakeholder engagement activities were also developed on two different levels:

1. On the one hand, technological solutions and a circular value chain implemented in Murcia for the horticultural and plastic waste from agri-food sectors were discussed with individual **private stakeholders** (or category representatives) operating in potentially circularizable value chains in Lombardy. Private stakeholders from the collective catering sector were also involved to discuss the potential valorisation and circularisation of waste.

A double objective was pursued: (i) the discussion increased operators' awareness about technologies, innovations and potential of the EC and (ii) their knowledge about territory and sector and their point of view supported the replicability assessments of the Agro2Circular supply chains in the Lombardy region.

2. On the other hand, a devoted working group supported the involvement of key **public stakeholders** with the aims to analyse the territorial application of the multidimensional Agro2Circular model, to cross complementary points of view and opinions, and collect common ideas and reflections on the potential actions to be implemented for a more circular Lombardy.

Further public decision makers engagement activities in the Lombardy region were carried out with specific seminars and events.

3.8.1 Private stakeholder involvement

Following Table 29 summarizes, for each potential circular value chain analysed in the replicability study, the private stakeholders involved, the related supply chain point and the main outputs emerged from the discussion.

Full minutes of private stakeholder involvement activities are in **Annex 3 - Minutes of private stakeholders' involvement activities**

Table 29 – Private stakeholders' involvement

Private stakeholder involved	Related supply chain point	Main outputs from the discussion
Horticultural waste valorisation		
Primary producers' organization	Horticultural production and waste generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • According to the latest estimations only 28% of the fruits and vegetables produced are sold directly by the producers, while up to 72% reach the retailer system, passing through different stakeholders and several selection steps. From each of these selection steps, some products are discarded, so that only the best ones reach the consumers. • The discarded products may have different fates according to their quality level; the less damaged ones are given to non-profit organizations for the less well-off, while the fruits and vegetables that do not comply with food safety standards, are normally reported to producers, who use them to produce biogas or for the feed sector, or used for the production of side products such as juices and jams • Considering all these already existing alternative ways to treat the discarded products and the residues from the production and commercialization of fruits and vegetables, and that this system is applied on a national basis, the real waste from this sector counts for about 1% of the entire production
Scientific and technological representative of "green technology" providers	High value molecules extraction / waste valorisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main future trends for horticultural waste valorisation are: (i) production of biopolymer composites from vegetable oils and oil waste and (ii) study of complex natural polymers already carrying interesting functionalities. • Main problems are related to the possibility of scaling up from the lab scale to the industrial one. In particular, logistics and economic feasibility constitute the main issues. Logistics needed for ensuring the right execution of all the phases from waste collection to the purification and treatment of the compounds produced from it. Although several food matrixes have been proven to be a valuable source of oils or active compounds, even the logistics at the lab scale seem to be difficult because the stability of the raw materials needs to be ensured. The problem is that being waste, this material is usually treated like that, therefore changing its natural properties. In addition, according to the cost-benefit analysis of the biorefinery processes, most of these extraction, purification, and valorisation processes are economically unfeasible on a large scale. This is mainly related to the very low yield of valuable compounds finally purified from these food waste matrixes. An important point is also related to the fact that most of the compounds synthesized or extracted from these matrixes are not in the proper conditions to be used in the industry and need more purification or conjugation processes, therefore increasing the final costs • At Lombardy level the most interesting sources are tomatoes, rice and coffee

Cosmetic industry	High value molecules application in cosmetic sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main problems concerning the industrialization of most of the innovations implemented at the lab scale are related to the cost/benefit balance and to logistics. • Most of the time, the industrial scale of these processes wouldn't be possible considering the low yield of the compound synthesized or extracted from the specific agri-food waste matrix • The logistics of the whole process, from waste collection to the final production of cosmetic products with natural compounds, need to be enforced. According to the company opinion, one of the main gaps is the absence of organizations involved in the first treatment of the waste material, including collection and stabilization. One of the main needs of the cosmetic sector is the replicability concept. The products, as well as the molecules used, need to be always the same. This is not possible if the logistic of this process is not fixed, and, most importantly, if there are no players able to collect, stabilize, and treat the waste material following specific protocols. Within this supply chain, cosmetic companies will be involved just at the final point, when the natural products are added to the formulation.
	Recycling plastic waste from agri-food sectors	
	Fruit juice industry	Waste generation (Bag-in-Bag)
Sausage industry	Waste generation (Bag-in-Bag)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The company buys tomato pulp in aseptic Bag-In-Bag with a volume of 200 kg; approximately 16.000 Aseptic Bag-In-Bag are annually used and discarded with the waste code CER 020304 "<i>Waste unusable for consumption or transformation</i>"
Scientific and technological representative of plasticulture users	Waste generation (plasticulture waste)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The end-of-life management of agricultural films is closely influenced by the specific region (in Italy an excellence is Sicily) but in general this represents a large cost in terms of taxes for farmers and the collection service is often unsuitable. The biggest challenge is linked to the presence of soil residues and/or chemical additives that make recovery expensive. • At a national level approximately 30.000 kg of film are used for solarization, and 3000/4.000 kg of film are used for fumigation, but the use is almost completely concentrated in the regions of southern Italy (Sicily and Campania in particular).

Collective catering waste valorisation

Collective catering representative

Waste generation

- Canteens usually produce a set number of servings per day. The quantity of food and meals produced is in fact correlated to the specifications, which refer to the number and type of customers in that specific canteen. This system ensures that excluding unpredictable events (strikes, simultaneous absence of several consumers, etc.), the overproduction of food is reduced to a minimum
- If the portions are more numerous than the consumers, the excess portions remaining on the trays are collected and prepared to be given to a non-profit organization for the less well-off. For this step to take place, it is essential that food safety is guaranteed, therefore the excess portions must respect the cold chain and be collected within a time limit, otherwise, they cannot be consumed and are eliminated.
- The organic waste produced by the canteen is collected by the local waste management authority daily.
- Schools and companies' canteens normally generate three types of waste, at three steps of the collective restoration system: (i) processing waste, (ii) extra serving and (iii) food left on the dishes
 Processing waste is generated during the servings' preparation. Since the canteens only serve fresh food, they must process it. This phase includes washing, cutting, elimination of inedible parts, cooking, and other operations that naturally produce waste. This type of waste can't be prevented but represent a small percentage of the total food produced and consumed in a canteen.
 Extra servings are the extra portions remaining on the trays that are promptly stored and maintained for poor people. This type of waste is generated in all cases when food security during this step is not ensured and these extra servings can't be eaten by other people (not ensured cold chain, contaminations, logistic problems). In these cases, the portions are eliminated.
- Food left on the dishes represents the real waste generated by the collective restoration system, especially in canteens in the schools, where children normally leave more food on the dish, even when the food provided has been selected following their specific needs and preferences. This type of waste is variable, even though there are specific food preparations that are less preferred by the children and generate more leftovers on the dishes. Moreover, some canteens give the children the possibility of having two portions of the "first serving", with the inevitable consequence that the "second serving" will be left at least in part on the dishes. This type of waste is inevitable; as it has been touched by consumers, its only destiny is the bin.

Start-up
involved in the
production of
animal feed from
collective
catering sector

Waste valorisation

- The startup is already operative in the market with its own patented plant for turning different types of residues into pet feed. The business model is based on three main services: (i) selling the plant to the company, (ii) providing technical assistance and consultancy, (iii) providing possible clients.
- As many tests have been already done using different inputs (mono- or poly-ingredients), there are several possible applications in the food industry, including food processing companies (vegetables, meat, fish), supermarkets, schools' and companies' canteens. In particular regarding the supermarkets and canteens sectors, the main inputs may be residues from the preparation of food dishes, residues coming back from canteens (not consumed) and residues remaining on the dishes.

3.8.2 Public stakeholder involvement

3.8.2.1 Regional event with key public stakeholders

Tecnoalimenti SCpA in collaboration with the “*Luigi Bocconi*” Commercial University of Milan organized a **regional event with the objectives of disseminate Agro2Circular approach and systematizing the views and opinions of key stakeholders in Lombardy and gathering insights and common reflections on potential actions that could be implemented for a more circular Lombardy region.**

The event took place on 26 September 2024, online via Microsoft Teams and it was held in Italian language.

Key stakeholders from Lombardy region were involved, including the regional public authority and several regional technology clusters, who contributed to providing a broader and more integrated perspective on the topic discussed. More in deep the participants included:

- General Directorate for Universities, Research, and Innovation of Lombardy Region
- General Directorate for Environment and Climate of the Lombardy Region,
- Intelligent Factory Association of Lombardy (Associazione Fabbrica Intelligente Lombardia, AFIL),
- Lombardy Energy Cleantech Cluster (LE2C),
- Lombardy Green Chemistry Association (LGCA),
- High Technology Agrofood Cluster of Lombardy (Cluster Alta Tecnologia Agrofood Lombardia, CAT.AL),

Also, National Consortium for Packaging (Consorzio nazionale Imballaggi, CONAI) was involved.

The first part of the event was devoted to the presentation of Agro2Circular project in terms of goals, partnership, activities, main output and to the presentation of the multidimensional model in terms of approach and structure.

Then the model was used as a tool to stimulate discussion and evaluated the current situation in Lombardy in terms of CE and identify potential improvement actions.

All the dimensions of the model were discussed and evaluated with the stakeholders selecting one element more relevant for each dimension; Technology, R&I and Capacity building dimensions were merged so a total of 7 aspects were discussed.

The agenda of the event is reported in **Annex 4 “Working group with key public stakeholders”**.

The working group was facilitated by two moderators (Mariantonella Palermo from Tecnoalimenti and Tania Molteni from Bocconi University) who posed stimulating questions to guide the discussions. Interventions were organized in a “roundtable” format, covering topics related to the seven dimensions of the Circular Economy, thus promoting constructive and focused dialogue.

In addition, to facilitate co-creation, online collaboration tools were employed. MentiMeter was used to gather real-time opinions and ideas from participants regarding the current

situation in Lombardy. Jamboard provided an interactive environment for visualizing and organizing ideas related to the collaborative identification of barriers, facilitators, and potential actions for improvement.

Finally, the results were elaborated and shared with the stakeholders to collect additional feedback and comments.

Following the main results of the working group for the single analysed dimension: the discussion emerged from the initial prompt proposed is summarized, then the results of the votation and the output of the co-creation moment are below summarized in tables.

Mentimeter voting report is also attached in **Annex 4 “*Working group with key public stakeholders*”**.

	<p>Socio economic dimension</p>
<p>Initial prompt proposed</p>	<p><i>Based on your perception, do regional stakeholders trust in the environmental sustainability of the local economy? What are the economic actors' expectations regarding the transition to a Circular Economy?</i></p>
<p>Round table discussion</p>	<p>The transition toward a Circular Economy in Lombardy involves a wide and varied group of stakeholders, including companies from various sectors, waste recycling facility operators, citizens, and public administrations. Consequently, confidence in this process depends on the context and sector. There is undoubtedly a growing awareness among citizens regarding the CE, although understanding of its various aspects remains limited. In general, citizens tend to focus on the more immediate elements of circularity, such as waste management (e.g., waste sorting), often overlooking more technical aspects like waste reuse and eco-design.</p> <p>The activities of technology clusters indicate strong interest in CE topics among businesses (evidenced by the increasing number of companies joining related webinars); however, a deeper analysis reveals a lack of comprehensive understanding of the subject. Numerous funding requests and a willingness to make direct investments reflect growing multi-sector interest in the Circular Economy. Additionally, some companies that have built their business models on sustainability see circularity as an economic opportunity more than others. However, in general, businesses still tend to focus on aspects promising immediate economic returns, such as reducing energy costs and reusing materials, rather than on long-term initiatives. Thus, while we observe a shift towards reducing production costs over the medium to long term, it remains essential to balance efforts for sustainable transition with other objectives (e.g., cost savings for companies and municipalities).</p> <p>Specifically, in the manufacturing sector, there is a preference for refunctionalization over material circularity to ensure high-quality standards. Nonetheless, the potential of the manufacturing supply chain lies in its ability to develop functional machinery that supports circularity in other sectors, such as bioplastics production, contributing to a more sustainable economic system.</p> <p>A significant obstacle is the cost, both for companies and consumers, so actions that do not entail direct expenses tend to develop more easily, driven by citizen interest. Despite this, Lombardy is witnessing numerous Research and Innovation initiatives, both in production chains and downstream sectors related to CE (new materials, waste management, and reuse).</p> <p>Additionally, Lombardy stands out for a high rate of innovation in the bioeconomy, with a significant presence of companies within the Italian Cluster for the Circular Bioeconomy (SPRING). To harness this momentum toward transition, it is therefore crucial to support companies both economically and through public-private collaboration.</p>
<p>Co-creation output</p>	<p>BARRIERS/ CHALLENGES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Decreasing of the average income levels of citizens ● Initial investment costs

Figure 21 report the perception of the working group participants on the current situation in Lombardy starting from the initial prompt proposed for socio-economic dimension and using the following Likert scale.

No trust: No trust by stakeholders in environmental sustainability of the local economy

Low trust: Minimal trust by stakeholders in environmental sustainability of the local economy

Moderate trust: Moderate trust by stakeholders in environmental sustainability of the local economy

Discreet trust: Discreet trust by stakeholders in environmental sustainability of the local economy

Full trust: Full trust by stakeholders in environmental sustainability of the local economy

Mean value of perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard socio-economic dimension of CE is 3.8.

Figure 21 - Perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard socio-economic dimension of CE

	Governance dimension
Initial prompt proposed	<p><i>Are you aware of regional strategic initiatives (e.g. targeted campaigns on the benefits and impacts of CE, specific topics, information systems with public data, etc.) aimed at fostering a cultural change towards sustainable practices and increasing trust in the Circular Economy? Are there spaces for dialogue and exchange of good practices and success stories?</i></p>
Round table discussion	<p>Lombardy Region implemented several initiatives to support environmental sustainability and promote CE.</p> <p>Through the Directorate General for Environment and Climate, it established the "<i>Observatory for Climate, Circular Economy, and Ecological Transition</i>," a forum bringing together public institutions, universities, research entities, and production organizations (such as trade associations, unions, and environmental groups). This Observatory, coordinated by an institutional committee, organizes into thematic working groups to discuss specific sectors (e.g., construction and demolition waste, sewage sludge, smelting slag, plastics, and textile and food waste).</p> <p>Additionally, the Waste Prevention Program 2022–2027 portal is one of the online platforms through which the Region shares best practices carried out by both public and private entities.</p> <p>In the area of smart mobility, with the European project TRANSFORM, the Region has created an effective dialogue system with citizens by facilitating discussions in small groups, it is an approach that could also be applied to Circular Economy topics, particularly in directly relevant areas such as waste management. Among the CE Region's activities also include campaigns against food waste, which include initiatives in schools, and plastic reduction initiatives, such as the installation of water dispensers in the Lombardy Regional Government building (2020 campaign).</p> <p>In terms of territorial and cross-border collaboration, regional clusters such as the LE2C Energy Cluster actively participate in ICEI (Industrial Circular Economy Investment), a network connecting 150 regions and countries with the aim of setting shared priorities for the Smart Specialisation Strategy, promoting industrial modernization projects, and facilitating the exchange of best practices and funding, including European funds. The clusters are also interested in conducting regular surveys to gather successful experiences from their members, which are then shared internally and externally (e.g., via newsletters).</p> <p>One concerning aspect in the case of the bioeconomy, a "metasector" by nature that spans multiple supply chains, is the governance challenges present at the regional level. The absence of a clearly defined institutional interface results in uncertainty and fragmentation.</p>

Co-creation output	BARRIERS/ CHALLENGES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transversality of the theme • Difficulty in reaching numerous stakeholders and involving all institutional actors • Lack of a specific directorate for the bioeconomy sector • Need for regular technical updating
	ENABLERS/ FACILITATORS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical discussion with stakeholders • Collaboration with the associations
	POTENTIAL ACTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional Bioeconomy Council • Investment in intangible support/networking actions • Better coordination between different actors in the area

Figure 22 reports the perception of the working group participants on the current situation in Lombardy starting from the initial prompt proposed for governance dimension and using the following Likert scale.

No initiatives: No initiatives to promote the culture of CE, no space for dialogue or information campaigns

Minimal and insufficient initiatives: Few initiatives to promote the culture of CE, few spaces for dialogue or information campaigns

Some initiatives: Initiatives exist to promote the culture of CE but need to be increased/improved

Good initiatives: Discrete number of initiatives to promote CE and spaces for dialogue and/or information campaigns

Excellent initiatives: Excellent system of initiatives, dialogue and information spaces to generate significant positive impact on the CE.

Mean value of perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard governance dimension of CE is 3.7.

Figure 22 - Perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard governance dimension of CE

	<p>Policy and regulatory dimension</p>	
<p>Initial prompt proposed</p>	<p><i>In your opinion, is national and EU legislation on Circular Economy (e.g., waste management) effectively implemented at regional level? Are there simplification schemes to avoid excessive bureaucracy?</i></p>	
<p>Round table discussion</p>	<p>Italian law 152/2006 regulates waste recycling and the use of by-products ("end of waste"), but practical complexities remain. In the absence of specific national or European regulations, a case-by-case authorization is required, leading to a lengthy and complex bureaucratic process. To support companies Lombardy Region, through the <i>Observatory for Climate, Circular Economy, and Ecological Transition</i>, has approved guidelines defining when a waste or by-product can be used as a raw material or managed as a by-product. Among these, a particularly appreciated example is the guidelines developed for managing steelworks slag in collaboration with the sectoral association.</p> <p>The Lombardy public administration also promotes CE and the use of recycled raw materials also through Green Public Procurement. This is an environmental policy tool aimed at fostering the development of a market for products and services with a reduced environmental impact through public demand.</p> <p>Another notable initiative in Lombardy is the spontaneous aggregation of municipalities to introduce homogeneous waste management practices, thereby meeting EU and national directives on optimal territorial areas. However, pay-as-you-throw (PAYT) pricing, which would replace a flat tax with differentiated rates to incentivize good management practices, is still limited, with only 25% of Lombardy municipalities implementing it.</p> <p>Lastly, the Lombardy Region has allocated €120 million from ERDF funds to various topics, including environmental sustainability, in line with the EU STEP regulation, which supports strategic technologies and environmentally sustainable biotechnologies. However, there is a noticeable lack of local financial interventions to support large enterprises under State aid regulations, which could also generate market benefits for SMEs.</p>	
<p>Co-creation output</p>	<p>BARRIERS/ CHALLENGES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Difficulties in enforcing regulations ● Complexity and articulation of national legislation
	<p>ENABLERS/ FACILITATORS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Guidelines for enterprises ● Accompanying actions for enterprises in the application of regulations ● Collaboration between local authorities, enterprises and citizens ● Concrete success stories
	<p>POTENTIAL ACTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordination between different regulations ● Bureaucratic simplification

Figure 23 reports the perception of the working group participants on the current situation in Lombardy starting from the initial prompt proposed for policy and regulatory dimension and using the following Likert scale.

Ineffective implementation: Laws and regulations are not applied consistently and have no positive impact on the EC

Poor implementation: Gaps in legislative implementation exist

Moderate implementation: There are areas where law enforcement could be improved to be more effective

Good implementation: There are strong legislative enforcement mechanisms in several areas

Excellent implementation: Laws and regulations are applied consistently with excellent environmental impacts.

Mean value of perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Policy and regulatory dimension of CE is 3.2.

Figure 23 - Perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Policy and regulatory dimension of CE

	<p style="text-align: center;">Funding & financial elements dimension</p>
<p>Initial prompt proposed</p>	<p><i>Could you comment on regional public investment mechanisms that promote research and development in the field of CE (both in terms of public calls for research projects and implementation of pilot cases and in terms of assessing environmental sustainability and circularity in public procurement procedures)?</i></p>
<p>Round table discussion</p>	<p>Lombardy Region provides financial support for the Circular Economy through various General Directorates (DGs): DG University, Research, and Innovation for industrial research and experimental development, DG Environment and Climate and DG Economic Development for implementation at production sites. Utilizing structural funds, the Region offers direct contributions and low-interest financing, with additional investments from selected venture capitalists. These funds cover current programming and reinvestment (i.e., funds from the repayment of low-interest loans), characterized by reduced reporting requirements and alignment with ERDF objectives.</p> <p>All Circular Economy initiatives proposed by the Lombardy Region are cross-sector funded in areas like manufacturing, food, and high science- Within the 2021-2027 EU budget, a specific objective for the CE was introduced for the first time, which the Lombardy Region has integrated by launching the "<i>Ri-circolo</i>" funding calls. Among these calls, one already closed (€8 million in grants) received 68 applications from SMEs in the textile plastics sector, while a second call, currently open (October 2024), is aimed at local entities for preventive actions, such as creating solidarity hubs and stores, reuse centres, waste prevention in canteens, and specific recycling initiatives. In addition, a third "<i>Ri-circolo</i>" call (€10 million in grants) is also being designed to support the recovery of critical raw materials (e.g., phosphorus as a fertilizer, extracts from end-of-life batteries, and Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment). It is worth noting that even during the 2017-2021 programming period, the Lombardy Region promoted calls to reduce food waste and support reuse centres, using funds from the eco-tax ("<i>Ecotassa</i>").</p> <p>The Lombardy Region's funding activities align with the actions of technology clusters, as demonstrated by the "<i>Manifestazione di Interesse per lo sviluppo delle filiere e degli ecosistemi industriali</i>" (literally, "expression of interest for the development of value chains and industrial ecosystems"), which recognized certain value chains, including those for sludge and hydrogen energy communities. Although these value chains are not currently funded under the regional programming, this recognition could lead to future incentives or indirect benefits.</p> <p>Moreover, alongside the Lombardy Region, other entities like the Cariplo Foundation support research funding (e.g., two projects respectively focused on the valorisation of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment and the recycling of plastics and lithium-ion batteries).</p>

Co-creation output	BARRIERS/ CHALLENGES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Very specialised interventions ● Lack of calls entirely dedicated to the bioeconomy ● Tight deadlines and constraints ● Low visibility of funding ● Small number of cases in the agri-food sector
	ENABLERS/ FACILITATORS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Guidelines for calls ● Resonance in the communication of notices issued ● Seminars for the presentation of calls ● Meetings between the regional body and regional stakeholders for the dissemination of calls and opportunities
	POTENTIAL ACTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Post-call discussion to identify areas for future improvement ● Comparison with the territory since the planning of calls for tenders ● Simplification ● Direct dialogue with the regional authority to establish project proposals in the bio-economy area ● Supporting actions in the agri-food sector

Figure 24 reports the perception of the working group participants on the current situation in Lombardy starting from the initial prompt proposed for Funding & financial elements dimension and using the following Likert scale.

No economic instrument: *There are no regional public investment mechanisms to promote R&D in CE*

Scarce economic instruments: *Some regional economic instruments exist but are insufficient and/or ineffective*

Moderate financial promotion: *The effectiveness of the economic instruments implemented is moderate and can be improved*

Good financial promotion: *Economic instruments for the promotion of CE are effective*

Excellent economic instruments: *There are comprehensive and well-used financing mechanisms*

Mean value of perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Funding & financial elements dimension of CE is 3.9.

Figure 24 - Perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Funding & financial elements dimension of CE

	Technology, R&I and Capacity building dimensions	
Initial prompt proposed	<p><i>How far do you think advanced technologies are available in the Lombardy region for the implementation of circular value chains? Is the local education system able to develop the knowledge and technical skills to face and overcome the challenges associated with the CE?</i></p>	
Round table discussion	<p>In Lombardy, there is a noticeable wave of technological activity, accompanied by a significant increase in startups and university spin-offs. However, public initiatives for technology transfer and scale-up are lacking and often rely solely on private efforts led by companies.</p> <p>To support greater circularity in the manufacturing sector, the Lombardy Region and the AFIL cluster have developed a roadmap to map out advanced technologies already in place and the companies utilizing them, highlighting the gaps that could be addressed through public funding. This analysis reveals that, despite numerous opportunities for an integrated vision of the supply chains and value chains, these efforts remain fragmented.</p> <p>From a agrifood point of view, the experience of CAT.AL indicates that, although the region is highly dynamic in innovations for material recycling and the valorisation of agricultural waste and by-products, three key organizational and logistical challenges persist in the food sector: (i) the geographical dispersion of by-products and waste, (ii) the seasonality of raw materials from which waste is derived, and (iii) the presence of existing and competitive management systems, such as animal feed and fertilization.</p> <p>The Lombard educational system has launched a series of specialized degree and master’s programs in bioeconomy and circularity, with institutions such as Bocconi University, the University of Milan, and the University of Milano-Bicocca, as well as various technical institutes, incorporating CE issues into their curricula. However, there is a need to better integrate technical and academic training to meet the needs of companies, which struggle to find qualified personnel with new technical and managerial skills. To this end, the Lombardy Region is planning a cross-cutting financial measure aimed at developing skills oriented toward environmental sustainability, though not exclusively dedicated to the Circular Economy, with the goal of addressing this training gap more effectively in line with market demands.</p>	
Co-creation output	BARRIERS/ CHALLENGES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited public initiatives to support technology scale-up ● Limited financial resources ● Difficult implementation of new technologies due to the intrinsic characteristics of agribusiness ● Training system not aligned with the evolution of technologies
	ENABLERS/ FACILITATORS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Large presence of universities and training institutes
	POTENTIAL ACTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More investment in training ● “Train the trainer” ● More training on technical skills

Figure 25 reports the perception of the working group participants on the current situation in Lombardy starting from the initial prompt proposed for Technology, R&I and Capacity building dimensions and using the following Likert scale.

No technology available: *There are no tools and infrastructures for the valorisation of waste and the creation of circular value chains*

Lack of technological availability: *There is a minimal and ineffective presence of technological applications for the valorisation of discards*

Moderate technological availability: *Applications of advanced technologies for waste valorisation are present but circular value chains are still lacking*

Good technological availability: *There is a well-developed regional network of technologies, tools and infrastructure*

Excellent technological availability: *Advanced technology applications are widespread and cover all value chains in a highly integrated and accessible system.*

Mean value of perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Technology, R&I and Capacity building dimensions of CE is 4.1.

Figure 25 - Perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Technology, R&I and Capacity building dimensions of CE

	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Environmental dimension</i></p>	
<p>Initial prompt proposed</p>	<p><i>Based on your experience, do you think that the Lombard production system provides for resource use planning and/or the adoption of measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions? Have strategies been developed to optimise the use of resources (such as agricultural land, water, fossil raw materials, etc.)? Are there measures and infrastructures in place to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, for example by limiting the use of virgin raw materials and waste valorisation?</i></p>	
<p>Round table discussion</p>	<p>In the context of environmental sustainability, significant progress has been made in Lombardy, although a balanced approach between innovation, functionality, and ecological impact is still required.</p> <p>The sector of recycled and/or recyclable plastics still offers room for improvement, considering that the use of advanced technologies in certain packaging, such as multi-materials made up of 7-8 different polymers, limits recycling possibilities. Therefore, when designing plastic packaging, it is essential to evaluate both recyclability and the overall functionality and performance of the product.</p> <p>In the specific context of the food industry, there is a strong tendency among companies to prefer recycling over the use of biodegradable materials, which often do not meet the required performance standards. For this reason, there is a tendency to prioritize the production of mono-materials, which are generally easier to recycle.</p> <p>In Lombardy, the Regional Waste Management Plan follows the principle of waste hierarchy, but it is also integrated with a comprehensive environmental assessment, potentially supported by analyses such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), which allows for exceptions in the hierarchy when these lead to greater overall sustainability</p>	
<p>Co-creation output</p>	<p>BARRIERS/ CHALLENGES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Performance constraints required by products ● Difficulties in evaluating the effectiveness of resource optimisation actions ● Regulatory constraints
	<p>ENABLERS/ FACILITATORS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tools for analysing and measuring environmental impacts ● Use of LCA ● Research and development activities

Figure 26 reports the perception of the working group participants on the current situation in Lombardy starting from the initial prompt proposed for Environmental dimension and using the following Likert scale.

Unmet environmental challenges: *There are major gaps in production optimisation, raw material demand management and consequently in greenhouse gas emission reduction systems*

Environmental challenges addressed ineffectively: *There is resource use planning with efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, but it is inconsistent and ineffective*

Moderate effectiveness of environmental measures: *The region is moderately committed to the substitution of virgin materials with raw materials for waste valorisation, contributing to moderate reductions in greenhouse gas emissions*

Good implementation of environmental measures: *Recycled materials contribute to a significant rate of raw material demand and effective waste management practices have significantly reduced greenhouse gas emissions*

Excellent implementation of environmental measures: *Lombardy excels in resource use planning and greenhouse gas emissions mitigation efforts.*

Mean value of perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Environmental dimension of CE is 3.8.

Figure 26 - Perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Environmental dimension of CE

	<h3>Standardization</h3>	
<p>Initial prompt proposed</p>	<p><i>In your opinion, does the Lombardy Region actively support the creation of EU standards and certifications for products made from secondary materials? Does the Region cooperate with standardisation agencies in the development of standards for the Circular Economy? Is the assessment of circularity in enterprises using existing standards promoted?</i></p>	
<p>Round table discussion</p>	<p>Currently, there is a practice regarding circularity that companies can adopt to monitor changes in their business circularity over time and directly compare themselves with competitors. This practice could be integrated into procurement tenders by assigning scores based on the level of circularity achieved. In this context, the UNI (Italian Standardization Body) has engaged the production sector, receiving numerous endorsements from companies in Lombardy.</p> <p>In the regional tenders being designed, quality certifications offer a dual advantage. The expenses for the registration and development of trademarks, patents, and quality certifications, such as REACH registration, can be accounted for. Furthermore, companies already holding recognitions (e.g., LCA studies and sustainability labels, agreements with research institutions) can benefit from incentives during the evaluation phase.</p>	
<p>Co-creation output</p>	<p>BARRIERS/ CHALLENGES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs • Validity and updating of standards and assessments
	<p>ENABLERS/ FACILITATORS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for companies that use certification
	<p>POTENTIAL ACTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enforce existing quantifiable circularity standards • Increase visibility of standards • Promote European harmonisation

Figure 27 reports the perception of the working group participants on the current situation in Lombardy starting from the initial prompt proposed for Standardization dimension and using the following Likert scale.

No support for standardisation: *The use of standards and circularity assessments in companies are not promoted in any way*

Poor support for standardisation: *There are some initiatives to support the creation and adoption of circularity standards, but they are limited and ineffective*

Moderate support for standardisation: *The region moderately promotes the use of standards and circularity assessments in companies*

Good support for standardisation: *The region regularly and effectively promotes the use of standards and evaluations of circularity in companies*

Excellent support for standardisation: *The region excels in promoting the creation of standards and evaluations of circularity in companies.*

Mean value of perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Standardization dimension of CE is 2.6.

Figure 27 - Perception of stakeholders on the current situation in Lombard Standardization dimension of CE

3.8.2.2 Additional involvement of public stakeholders

Further involvement of public stakeholders Lombardy Region was possible in collaboration with AFIL and in synergy with **Plastix project** (<https://www.interregeurope.eu/plastix>) an InterReg project aimed to facilitate industrial transition towards a resource-efficient economy, circular economy growth and eco-innovations in participating regions including Lombardy.

1. On 20 November 2024 TCA attended the PLASTIX Open Seminar “*Lombardy initiatives and best practices in the Circular and Sustainable Plastics Value Chain*”. Mariantonella Palermo presented the Agro2Circular project, the Multidimensional model for adoption, replicability and scalability of A2C systemic solution at regional and EU level and the main output of the related working group with the aim to collect additional idea and reflection on Lombard transition towards CE. The event was in English language and the agenda is reported in **Annex 5 “Public stakeholders’ involvement activities”**.
2. On 4 February 2025, Tecnoalimenti presented the Agro2Circular project and the multidimensional model to the Lombardy Strategic Community “Secure and Sustainable Food Manufacturing”. Around 25 stakeholders from politics, academia and industry attended the event and this was a further opportunity to involve and sensitize regional decision makers, to introduce them to the multidimensional model and to discuss and explore fresh insights and strategies for advancing toward Circular Economy initiatives. The event was in Italian language and the agenda is reported in **Annex 5 “Public stakeholders’ involvement activities”**.

3.9 Multidimensional replicability analysis

The Multidimensional model described in deliverable D.7.10, being one of the main outputs of task **T7.5** “*Multidimensional model for adoption, replicability and scalability of A2C systemic solution at regional and EU level*”, was applied to the specific territorial context of the Lombardy Region to stimulate in-depth reflection and facilitate the following drafting of the CEAP.

The analysis of each element proposed in the multidimensional model was based on the following sources:

1. Analysis and elaboration of feedback from the working group involving public stakeholders in Lombardy (see paragraph **3.8.1. Public stakeholder involvement**)
2. Targeted interviews with private stakeholders (see paragraph **3.8.2. Private stakeholder involvement**)
3. Context study (from Chapter **3.1** to Chapter **3.7**) with specific reference to the circular supply chains of horticultural waste and agoplastics analysed in the Agro2Circular project
4. Desk research targeted on specific elements of the multidimensional model
5. Previous experiences and knowledge within the TCA research team and its related industrial network: with this goal, periodic brainstorming sessions were organized among Tecnoalimenti researchers (both directly involved in the project and external to the A2C team) to discuss the local situation from a general point of view and related to each dimension and/or elements of greater relevance in Lombardy.

In addition, TCA conducted a specific survey to investigate the Lombardian citizens' attitudes and actions towards sustainable consumption, production, and waste management practices with a specific focus on recycled plastic materials.

Numeric results obtained from the evaluation of each element were then analysed with SAT (*Agro2Circular Self-Assessment Tool, Deliverable 7.10*): global evaluation radar charts of the eight dimensions obtained from the Self-assessment tool are reported below.

To complete and optimize the replicability activity of the multidimensional model in the Lombardy region, a moment of comparison was organized with the LPK team engaged in parallel in the model application to the Lithuanian case study.

The element able to impact on the of replicability output were taken into account (in particular territorial differences among regions and different composition of the working group) and it was decided to address the moment of comparison between the two cases of replicability in a “*cross-fertilization*” perspective by analysing the strengths and potential improvement actions proposed in Lithuania as further food for thought for the implementation of the Lombardy CAEP.

3.9.1 Environmental dimension

Due to the presence of large urban centres, the high population density and the high rate of industrialization, the environmental dimension is a big challenge for the Lombardy region.

Despite the great commitment at political level (in terms of planning activities) and the high technical efficiency in waste management and valorisation, a big critical point is linked to climate change and to the emission of greenhouse gases.

The environmental dimension was evaluated, as an average of the 5 aspects considered, with a score of 3.6. The spider chart in Figure 28 summarizes the evaluations on each single aspect; the specific aspects are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 28 – Environmental dimension global evaluation in Lombardy

3.9.1.1 Efficient waste and water management

Lombardy's **URBAN WASTE MANAGEMENT** infrastructure ensures near self-sufficiency in handling urban waste.

Over 98% of the waste produced is managed directly in the regional territory. The main recovery and/or disposal plants for the treatment of urban waste located in the Lombardy Region are:

- Composting and integrated aerobic/anaerobic treatment plants
- Mechanical biological treatment plants
- Landfills
- Waste-to-energy plants

Following Table 30 summarizes the number of plants devoted to the management of urban waste.

According to ARPA data [141] in 2021, the overall recovery percentage (matter and energy) was 84% respect to the quantity of urban waste produced, with:

- 62.8% of material recovery
- 21.2% direct energy recovery

Table 30 – Number of plants devoted to the management of organic waste (provincial data)
 Source: Elaboration from ARPA Report on Waste Production and Management in the Lombardy Region
 [142]

Province	Anaerobic digestion plants	Composting plants	Anaerobic digestion + composting plants	Waste-to-energy plants	Other incineration and energy recovery plants
Bergamo		10	1	2	8
Brescia		10		1	4
Como	1	7		1	17
Cremona	2	2	1	1	3
Lecco		1		1	3
Lodi	2		2		1
Monza		1		1	5
Milano	1	1	3	2	9
Mantova	2	5			6
Pavia	2	4	2	2	4
Varese		13		1	5
TOT	18	55	9	12	65

Alongside the plants with “routine” activity, there are experimental plants able to test innovative waste management systems: they do not generate economic profit, and the potential does not exceed 5 tons per day.

Below is the list of experimental plants authorised by the Lombardy Region [143]:

- *IRLE S.r.l.* – Sarezzo (BS) – Production of liquid and gaseous fuel from waste treatment by non-combustible 142uildin-catalytic treatment.
- *Rymyc S.r.l.* – Parre (BG) – Carbon fiber recovery through pyrolysis from non-hazardous waste
- *Metropolitana Milanese S.p.A.* – Località Ronchetto delle rane (MI) – Treatment/recovery of sewage sludge
- *Tecnoservizi Ambientali S.r.l.* – Cortenuova (BG) – Recovery and disposal of hazardous and non-hazardous special waste
- *Cap Holding S.p.a.* – San Giuliano Milanese (MI) – Experimental plant for the valorization of sewage sludge
- *Cap Holding S.p.a.* – Robecco sul Naviglio (MI) – Experimental plant for the anoxic carbonization of sludge at high temperatures
- *Tregenplast S.r.l.* – Cernusco sul Naviglio (MI) – Experimental plant for the recovery of plastic waste
- *3V Tech spa* – Grassobbio (BG) – Pilot plant for the transformation of sodium chloride
- *A2A Ambiente S.p.a.* – Corteolona e Genzone (PV) – Experimental plant for the recovery of phosphorus from ashes resulting from the thermal recovery of dried sludge
- *Zetadi S.r.l.* – Ferno (VA) – Heat treatment with a melting furnace based on oxy-combustion technologies for inertization through the vitrification of rock wool

- *Ambiens II S.r.l.* – Bagnolo Mella (BS) – Research and experimentation for the treatment of non-hazardous special waste by thermal oxidation for energy recovery purposes.
- *Gr3n Italia* – Albese con Cassano (CO) – Experimental plant for the treatment and recovery of plastic waste.
- *Seco S.r.l.* – Rovello Porro (CO) – Experimental plant for the processing of pocket springs resulting from the management of out-of-use mattresses
- *Previero N. S.r.l.* – Alzate Brianza (CO) Experimental plant for the treatment and recovery of plastic waste.

Actions to improve waste management efficiency in the Lombardy region are summarised in the programmatic document “**Waste management and remediation in Lombardy Region Plan – Toward the Circular Economy**” [144].

Since 2005, Lombardy Region has established a Regional Waste Management Programme, including the Regional Programme for Polluted Areas Remediation consistent with the relevant regulatory provisions. With Regional Council Resolution No. 6408 of 23/05/2022[145], the update of the Regional Waste Management Program (PRGR), including the Programme for Polluted Areas Remediation, was approved. The programme contributes to the implementation of Community sustainable development strategies, as well as being the programming instrument through which Lombardy Region defines in an integrated way policies on the prevention, recycling, recovery and disposal of waste, and the management of polluted sites to be cleaned up.

Main objectives of the PRGR can be summarised as follows:

- Getting to high qualitative standards for separate collection, to comply with the new ambitious high EU standards such as preparation for reuse and recycling, net of rejects generated
- Confirming the common waste management scheme, which performed well encouraging synergies between municipalities.
- Ensure and confirm self-sufficiency for waste treatment, not only for municipal waste and those related to their treatment, but also for industrial waste, with a view to the “proximity principle”
- Shrinking the need for landfills

Following Figure 29 reports the detailed targets for 2027 about municipal waste

Figure 29 - Targets for 2027 about municipal waste
Source: Lombard Waste Management Programme

More in depth, the amount of municipal waste generated in 2019 was approximately 480kg per capita per year, so the target for 2027 is 440kg (-8.9%). Intervention areas for municipal waste prevention are: (i) prevention plan for food waste, (ii) promotion of preparation for reuse, (iii) reduction of single use items. (iv) “*PayAsYouThrow*” tax system.

Baseline for separate collection analysis is excellence with regional average of 73,2% in 2021 and a lot of cases of municipalities with more than 80% separate collection; target in 2027 is 83.3% at regional level.

The target of the EU Waste Framework Directive [146] is to reduce the rejects generated by the fractions of municipal separated waste collected separately (so called “net recycling”). Rejects are due to: (i) wrong behaviour of citizens, (ii) collection scheme not aiming at quality, (iii) recycling plants not aiming at the reduction of rejects. Lombard net recycling is 67,8% by 2027 with respect to the EU target of 55% by 2025 and 65% by 2035.

During the preparation of the WMP, a specific Working Group on plastics was also set up. Here some outcomes and recommendation emerging:

- better separation of plastics during the collection step
- ensure the effective closure of the management of separate collection
- value of chemical recycling of plastics as complementary to mechanical recycling
- separate collection of bioplastic items
- collection of plastic waste from construction and demolition like PVC and EPS

WMP also include programmatic actions to reach the target such as campaign to fight food wastage for citizens (see “*Don’t waste a love story*” at next paragraph **3.9.1.2 Waste valorisation channel**), calls for proposals for SME and local authorities (see **3.9.5.1 Specific financial line for Circular Economy**) and a portal collecting examples of good practices for waste prevention reporting actions to be shared and disseminated, spread the results of the actions promoted by the Region, spread of main sensitization campaigns (as also discussed during stakeholders working group meeting).

On the other hand, when analysing **WASTEWATER MANAGEMENT**, it is more difficult to find updated data from an infrastructure point of view: according to ISTAT data, in 2015 in Lombardy there were 1.498 urban wastewater plans in operation (725 primary plants, 400 secondary plants and 373 tertiary plants, respectively) [147].

It is however possible to identify some examples of excellence towards the circular transition in the Lombardy region.

A virtuous example of rational and sustainable management of water resources is the *New sewerage collection and purification system of the municipalities of Gavardo, Villanuova sul Clisi and Vallio Terme (near Brescia) by A2A Ciclo Idrico* [148]. It allows for the reintroduction into nature of approximately 9 million litres/day of water available for agricultural reuse. Part of the purified water is also reused within the plant itself, reducing the use of drinking water and allowing a virtuous circular system. In addition, the plant guarantees a reduction in contaminants present in wastewater exceeding the limits prescribed by current legislation. Other positive examples are *CAP Group Treatment Plants* [149]: in keeping with Circular Economy principles, the Group promotes the reuse of treated water for non-domestic uses, such as street cleaning and field irrigation. For example, at various plants such as Assago,

Basiglio, Rozzano and Peschiera Borromeo, treated water is used for civil and agricultural uses. Even the sewage sludge is seen as a resource from a Circular Economy perspective. Among the most notable projects, we would like to highlight the following plants:

- Sesto San Giovanni, for the innovative BioPlatform waste-to-energy plant and purifier
- Robecco sul Naviglio, for the recovery of food processing waste
- Cassano D'Adda, for the transformation of waste into renewable biofuels
- Bresso-Niguarda, to produce biomethane
- Truccazzano, for the recovery of cellulose

More in general CAP Group aims to become a multi-purpose urban biorefineries able to serve the citizens and to treat and valorise municipal waste streams, such as wastewaters and organic waste, towards a coherent urban strategy. Combination of eco-innovative technologies with anaerobic co-digestion allows for the integrated recovery of biomethane, phosphorus, biopolymers.

In Lombardy it is also possible to observe a great interest in terms of basic research towards sustainability and the circular transition in wastewater management.

Below are some projects from Lombardy aiming at the circular transition in wastewater management:

- *DIGITAL-WATER.city* (<https://www.digital-water.city/>) is an international project active in the period 2019-2022 aimed at digital solutions for the management of the water service, regarding the reuse of purified water for irrigation purposes. A specific case study was devoted to the city of Milan: the goal was to create a risk-based water management system sharing the risks between the integrated water service manager and the end user. From the point of view of the treatment plant manager, online analysers of physical-chemical and microbiological parameters were validated to establish an Early Warning System able to monitor, in real time, the quality characteristics of the water supplied. From the farmer's point of view, the combined use of drones and field probes was studied to understand the water and nutrient needs of the fields to be irrigated. These two aspects were connected by a web app, called "match-making tool".
- *CE4WE Circular Economy for Water and Energy* (<https://www.ce4we.eu/>) funded by Lombardy Region aims to implement the concept of Circular Economy to the integrated water cycle: water enters as a processing material generating different reusable products on the market. At the same time *CE4WE* aims at the energetic valorisation of the wastes. More in deep *CE4WE* innovations refer to the development of analysis procedures and numerical models for the detailed mapping of emerging pollutants harmful to human health, as well as to predict variations in the water cycle in response to different climate scenarios, based on the modelling of the behaviour of the physical-chemical-biological interface constituted by the soil. The geographical focus of the project is within the areas of Brescia, Como, Milan, Monza and Pavia.
- *PerFORM WATER 2030 – Platform for Integrated Operation Research and Management of Public Water towards 2030* (<https://www.openinnovation.regione.lombardia.it/it/b/30638/progetto-perform-water-2030>) is a project funded by Lombardy Region within the Regional Operational

Programme of the European Regional Development Fund 2014-2020 and includes 4 interconnected thematic areas. The first theme concerns Water, with a focus on the quality control of supply water and the optimization of distribution networks, the monitoring and removal of emerging pollutants, the optimization of wastewater treatment processes; the second aspect is related to Sewage sludge, with a focus on the design and implementation of measures to reduce the quantity produced and thermal valorisation with the simultaneous recovery of energy and matter; the third and consequent theme concerns the Recovery of Energy and Material within purification plants with biogas and biomethane production; last but not least is Economic and Social Valorisation of the technologies, through the involvement of all stakeholders and the advanced analysis of the costs and pricing of the water service.

- *AQUARES* (<https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/aquares/>) is an international project active from 2018 to 2023 and co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund through the European transnational cooperation programme Interreg Europe. It aimed to identify, promote and implement water reuse policies to make European regions more efficient and sustainable in the management of water resources. It included partners from 9 different countries and in Lombardy *AQUARES* contributed to raising awareness among regional decision makers on the use of innovative solutions in the protection of water resources starting from water reuse; the focus has been on the ability to prevent excess water resulting from intense rainfall from ending up in the sewer system.

The analysis of the existing plants in Lombardy for the waste and water waste management both in terms of number and in terms of efficiency and innovation allow us to affirm that there are enough infrastructures and facilities to treat the wastes, so **the waste and water management is evaluated weak (score 4)**.

Many R&I activities are also implemented in the Lombardy region to improve circularity in these sectors.

The following table summarizes the factors potentially useful to improve Lombard readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning efficient waste and water management.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Separate waste collection systems sometimes neglect the quality of separation ○ Very often the current sewerage networks are not able to separate civil wastewater from industrial and first rainwater 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Large number of plants and experimental plants ○ Large number of R&I project
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Encourage synergies between municipalities ○ Further R&D effort to increase efficiency in existing plants ○ Implement separate collection systems for bioplastic items ○ Modernization of existing purification plants, aiming at maximizing the reuse of wastewater and application of CE processes applied in all steps of the purification cycle 	

3.9.1.2 Waste valorisation channels

To analyse and evaluate the regional channels able to valorise wastes we considered the Agro2Circular case study in the agri-food sector related to wastes/byproducts from horticulture.

As previously described in chapter **3.5.1.1 Management of biological wastes from agrifood sector**, Lombardy is an excellence in biogas/biomethane production from agricultural waste: this is a circular value chain efficiently implemented and supported at regional level.

An additional point of excellence at national level but with strong prevalence in the Po Valley area including Lombardy for the valorisation of organic waste with the production of biogas and biomethane is the presence of a strong community organization.

CIB (Biogas Italian Consortium) represents the Italian sector of biogas and biomethane production in agriculture and intends to be the point of reference for the whole sector. It is the first voluntary aggregation bringing together agricultural companies producing biogas and biomethane from renewable sources, companies supplying plants, technologies and services to produce biogas and biomethane, public stakeholder involved into social goals, dissemination and promotion of anaerobic digestion technology for the agricultural sector. CIB has more than 800 members and, as shown in the following Figure 30, they are mainly located in the Po Valley area.

Figure 30 - Geographical location of CIB members

Source: <https://www.consorziobiogas.it/>

In addition, several emerging solutions are proposed by Lombard start-up for the extraction of valuable components from horticultural wastes (in paragraph **3.5.2.1 Innovative waste management solutions for agro-industrial wastes** are reported some examples such as Mogu, Bi-rex, Tomapoint, Flanet Research) and several technological providers for cosmetic and/or nutraceutical applications operates in regional territory (see **3.3.6 Mapping of technological providers**). However, these solutions need a more advanced technology and are in competition with the prevalent use of biogas/biomethane.

Basing on the biogas/biomethane sector we can observe in Lombardy **highly effective valorisation channels (score 5)**: there is comprehensive understanding of agrifood waste, with optimised strategies to convert it into valuable products like biogas/biomethane and a wide range of synergies operating, closing or narrowing value chains are present.

Following table summarizes the factors potentially useful to improve Lombard readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning waste valorisation channels (with specific reference to biogas/biomethane production from agrifood wastes).

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Seasonality of agricultural waste ○ Territoriality of agricultural waste and difficulty of transportation (especially for high humidity products) ○ Competitive use as animal feed and/or fertilizer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Territorial association (CIB) ○ Bureaucratic simplification in the Lombardy region (for example for the conversion of biogas plants to biomethane plants) ○ Financial incentives (also at national level)
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ R&I actions to improve plant efficiency, to search for new feeds, to design plants that can be fed with multimaterials 	

3.9.1.3 Territorial exploitation level

The Lombardy Region shows a growing political sensitivity towards the issues of Circular Economy and intelligent management of natural resources. In recent years this led to the drafting of official documents such as the “*Regional Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change*” (following described in the paragraph 3.9.1.5 “**Climate change mitigation and adaptation measures**”) and the *Water Protection Plan*.

More in deep **WATER PROTECTION PLAN** [150] is the planning tool for the qualitative and quantitative protection of waters.

Strategic goals are:

- increase territorial resilience with respect to climate change (to worsening of water emergencies)
- promote the rational and sustainable use of water resources
- ensure quality water, in quantities adequate for needs and at sustainable costs for users
- recover and safeguard the environmental characteristics of aquatic ecosystems and the areas of relevance of water bodies
- promote the increase in the conscious and sustainable use of aquatic environments
- promote the implementation of projects and good management practices aimed at restoring or maintaining the ecosystem services of water bodies and the areas of relevance
- restore and safeguard a good hydro morphological state of water bodies, balancing with the prevention of hydrogeological instability and floods

- promote the good level of ecological and chemical state of surface waters and the good level of quantitative and chemical state of underground waters.

From a **FOOD POINT OF VIEW** in terms of surplus redistribution is worth to cite “*lo non spreco project*” the management of wastes from catering sector in Milan municipality with the collection of the surplus and the redistribution to poor people (see paragraph **3.5.1.2 Management of waste from catering sector**).

Last but not least, from **A MATERIAL (IN PARTICULAR PLASTICS) POINT OF VIEW** emerged from the working group with regional stakeholders a major limitation in the use of secondary raw materials (limiting the exploitation of virgin raw materials) due to their inefficient functional performances. On the one hand companies (especially food companies) prefer recyclable packaging to biodegradable ones aiming at single-material systems but on the other hand the choice and design of plastic packaging always requires an evaluation considering the recyclability but also the functionality and performance of the product.

In line with regional stakeholders’ opinion, it is possible to **assess the territorial exploitation level as good implementation (score 4)**: there is a good political and social awareness on resource use planning and recycled materials contribute to satisfy materials demand but there are limitations due to logistical challenges.

Following table summarizes the factors potentially useful to improve Lombard readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning territorial exploitation in terms of water exploitation, material exploitation and surplus redistribution.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<p>ABOUT WATER EXPLOITATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ High concentration of population and productive activities ○ Intense exploitation for hydroelectric production and irrigation ○ Uneven quality levels of service across the territory <p>ABOUT MATERIAL EXPLOITATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Regulatory constraints on the use of secondary raw materials ○ High performance requirements 	<p>ABOUT WATER EXPLOITATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ High scientific and technical knowledge on water systems <p>ABOUT SURPLUS REDISTRIBUTION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Administrative benefits for donors through the simplification of donation procedures (at national level with <i>Gadda law</i>) ○ Political sensitivity not only at regional level but also at local level (municipalities) with specific plans and projects (see 3.5.1.2) ○ Volunteers’ involvement <p>ABOUT MATERIAL EXPLOITATION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Using LCA as a general environmental assessment: for example, it is preferable to go further down the waste hierarchy if this leads to greater overall sustainability.

Actions

ABOUT WATER EXPLOITATION

- Sharing knowledge of water systems and applying it to specific territorial realities
- Increase efficiency in the management of the integrated water service
- Protect all sources of supply for drinking purposes
- Increase awareness, knowledge and competence among citizens and among all public and private operators.

ABOUT SURPLUS REDISTRIBUTION

- Information campaigns

ABOUT MATERIAL EXPLOITATION

- R&I to improve the performance of secondary raw materials

3.9.1.4 Land and biodiversity degradation processes

Regenerative **AGROFORESTRY PRACTICES** are particularly suited to the Lombardy region, providing a concrete and broad-spectrum response to address the current ecological crisis of the Po Valley agricultural landscape. Through the introduction of complex agroforestry systems, diversified in time and space, it is possible to intervene on the reactivation of the ecological functions of the agro ecosystem, from the conservation and production within the same field of the resources that the production system needs to the regeneration of soil fertility.

Towards this direction, two virtuous examples are now present in Lombardy region: Soulfood Forestfarms Hub, a non-profit active both in agricultural and socio-cultural projects with a focus on local development and the public project “Forestami”.

Soulfood Forestfarms Hub (<https://soulfoodforestfarms.it/#top>) applies in the Lombardy region, mainly in the province of Milan, the “*successive agroforestry*” techniques providing technical and management skills for the ecological transition. They sell, plant and cultivate trees on behalf of the companies financing their planting. Following some Soulfood Forestfarms Hub projects:

- **CasciNet Farm** (2019)

This company manages 10 hectares of land located in the Vettabbia Park, Corvetto area and Chiaravalle districts in Milan. Thanks to Soulfood Forestfarms, 2 hectares of agroforestry systems have been implemented starting with 650 fruit trees of 8 different species in 30 varieties; to support the ecosystem, approximately 2000 trees and shrubs of forest species are associated. The second hectare of regenerative agroforestry system is designed and created for the phytoremediation of heavy metals, with the production of biomass used in a short cycle (Short Rotation Forestry) as a source of heating for the “Cascina Sant’Ambrogio” with a thermocomposting system.

Some numbers of CasciNet Farm project:

- More than 12.000 trees
- 52 tons CO₂ eq / year sequestered

- More than 1000 volunteers involved in three years of activity
 - 2 residential laboratories with the University of Milan
 - 15 classes of primary and secondary schools involved with Scuola ForestaMi
 - 3 training courses carried out
 - 5 cultural events in collaboration with local associations and the University of Milan
- **Davide Longoni farm (2021)**
 This company grows cereals in the Vettabbia Park using organic methods, without the use of herbicides or fertilizers and following a three-year rotation. Thanks to “*MadreProject*”, the first bread-making school is starting up and the additional goal of transformation of 6 hectares into an agroforestry system in alley cropping with integration of grazing.
 Some numbers of Davide Longoni Farm project:
 - More than 2.000 trees
 - 27 tons CO₂ eq / year sequestered
 - More than 200 volunteers involved in sowing and soil preparation activities
 - **Tuetera farm (2022)**
 It is a territorial regeneration project implemented in a privately owned area in the Valle del Lambro Regional Park, located in the municipalities of Inverigo, Nibionno and Veduggio con Colzano. The project involves the definition and creation of a settlement and production model that is at the same time innovative, ecological and holistic: a true living laboratory of agroecological, cultural and social practices aimed at developing healthy and generative communities. Over the course of a year, adopting a transdisciplinary and systemic methodology, Soulfood Forestfarms has created a participatory design process with the property and other actors involved in order to define the approach, objectives and strategies for starting the agricultural activity. The result of the first step is the implementation of a complex agroforestry system of about 2 ha, designed around medicinal and ornamental production focuses.

Soulfood Forestfarms Hub is also involved in activities related to the protection of biodiversity: the “*Biodiversity Path*” is being developed within the Agricultural Park in Milan, offering the possibility of experiencing nature within the city.

Forestami is a project born from research by the Polytechnic of Milan and promoted by the Metropolitan City of Milan, the Municipality of Milan, the Lombardy Region, Parco Nord Milano, Parco Agricolo Sud Milano, ERSAF and Foundation Comunità Milano.

Forestami’s activities arise from scientific research with the census of existing green systems, the mapping of the urbanized territory and the areas of greatest criticality from the point of view of the urban heat phenomenon.

Then with the related planting interventions, Forestami intends to create an ecosystem rich in ecological connections and biodiversity in the territory of the Metropolitan City of Milan,

systematizing the planted trees in a single, large urban and peri-urban green infrastructure. The final objectives are afforestation projects integrated with the existing green system to become a new piece of the network of urban and metropolitan green infrastructures and connections.

All interventions are guaranteed in the implementation step and with maintenance in the 5 years following planting. Beneficial effects of the planting are maximized thanks to in-depth knowledge of the planting site, choice of the most suitable species based on the micro-climatic and soil characteristics and specific treatments where necessary.

According to this described framework, it is possible to say that despite significant impacts on habitats and biodiversity due to overexploitation of resources and pollution, several renaturalisation efforts contribute positively to recover ecosystem health and species preservation. **The status of land and biodiversity degradation processes is evaluated as neutral (score 3).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning land and biodiversity degradation processes.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ At urban level the main challenge is to integrate typical city approaches and “schemes” with rural needs ○ At rural level the main challenge is the economic barrier done to the initial investment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ At urban level, the metropolitan city of Milan is an ideal scenario to activate urban reforestation projects thanks to a string network of public, private actors and to citizen sensitive to the issue ○ At rural level, reforestation can represent an additional income for the farmer in terms of carbon credits
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reforestation projects should be born from a co-creation approach in order to answer both to the environmental needs of the territory and the needs of local communities: so, it will be possible also to promote a socio-territorial cohesion ○ Effective reforestation should involve, from the design to the realization, scientific experts, farmers, company teams and citizens through on-field training activities at all levels ○ A long-term planning is needed considering all the resources available (skills, technologies, economic availability ...) 	

3.9.1.5 Climate change mitigation and adaptation measures

The actions implemented by the Lombardy Region to counteract climate change and its effects on human society and the environment are developed along two directions: (i) mitigation and progressive reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and (ii) adaptation to reduce the vulnerability of natural and socio-economic systems and increase their capacity to answer the inevitable impacts of a changing climate.

Already in 2012, Lombardy Region concluded, with the support of the Lombardy Foundation for the Environment, the drafting of the *Guidelines for a Climate Change Adaptation Plan*; then during 2013 and 2014, in collaboration with the Lombardy Foundation for the Environment, the **Regional Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change** was developed in line with the recommendations of the European institutions and in harmony with the parallel Italian National Strategy (Directorial decree no. 86/2015 [151]).

The Regional Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change defined the role of regional institutional stakeholders through specific internal consultation mechanisms in the Lombardy Region, deepened and updated the climate bases (past and ongoing climate changes) at the regional level, conducted quantitative assessments on sectoral impacts and the analysis of vulnerabilities to climate change in the 8 key sectors.

Starting from the Strategy, the “**Regional Action Document on Adaptation to Climate Change**” [152] was developed in order to identify priority areas of intervention responding to the needs of sector planning. About 30 measures have been identified for the following priority areas: (i) human health and air quality, (ii) soil and land protection, (iii) water management and quality, (iv) agriculture and biodiversity, (v) tourism and sport.

The general goal of the Regional Strategy can be summarized in the following points:

- to harmonize and integrate the national and community strategic lines for adaptation to climate change.
- to develop the regional climate bases, analysing in detail the past and future climate variability.
- to define weaknesses of the territory, identifying the impacts, analysing the sectoral sensitivity, the relative resilience capacity and assessing the risks with an integrated analysis.
- to analyse the regional policies in place and the possible interventions for adaptation.
- to promote stakeholders’ involvement from different sectors.
- to propose sector-specific and intersectoral adaptation measures.
- to guide a continuous and efficient process of information and monitoring

The related measures are then divided into three categories:

1. *Soft or non-infrastructurel measures* concern interventions in increase in knowledge, dissemination of information, promotion of monitoring actions or changes in current legislation.
2. *Grey or infrastructurel measures* indicate tangible interventions in the adaptation or design of the infrastructures necessary for adaptation.
3. *Green or ecosystemic measures* intervene directly on the environment to exploit natural ecosystem services to contain the current and future pressures of climate change.

As examples, the measures in the agricultural sector are following reported:

- efficiency of irrigation systems,
- conservative agriculture practices
- dissemination of ICT systems in more marginalized and more fragile areas
- conservative soil management
- diversify crops by adapting them to new climatic conditions (introduce more resistant varieties and adapt current varieties by modifying the distribution areas).

With specific reference to **GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS**, according to Italy for Climate data, per capita greenhouse gas emissions in Lombardy in 2021 were 7.5 tons of CO₂ equivalent per inhabitant [153]: this is a slightly higher value than national average and this is easily attributable to the high rate of industrialization.

The following Figure 31 compares greenhouse gas emissions in Lombardy in the different sectors with the relative national data.

- Final energy consumption per capita is slightly higher than the national average and this is also affected by the strong industrialization and the high heating needs of buildings; on the other hand, the performances of new renewable energy plants are the best in Italy, with 18.2 kW per square km installed in 2022 and the number of energy communities activated in 2022 is also excellent (7).
- Good performances are in the transport sector: the number of cars is the third lowest in Italy (629 cars per thousand inhabitants, against a national average of 681), per capita emissions from transport and the share of electric car registrations are better than the national average. Less positive is the result on passengers moved by public transport in relation to the population.
- The percentage of class A buildings is very good (14%), among the highest in Italy, while the performances in terms of per capita emissions, per capita energy consumption and electricity consumption are less positive, all on average worse than the national average also due to the high heating needs for climate reasons.
- Industrial performance is very positive in relation to the added value produced by Lombardy; on the other hand, in the agricultural sector the performances are worse than the national average on all indicators (number of cattle raised in relation to the population, use of fertilizers and incidence of organic farming).

Figure 31 - Greenhouse gas emissions in Lombardy and in Italy
 Source: Elaboration Italy for Climate on Ispra and Istat data

In this specific context, Lombardy Region is involved in the fight against climate change by signing the international protocol Under2Mou [154] with two main goals: (i) the adoption of a target for the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and (ii) the monitoring of greenhouse gas emission data. Final goals are a 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to 2005 by 2030 and an 80% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to 2005 by 2050.

Similarly, the City of Milan with the publication of the “**Air Climate Plan**” [155] has committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions on its territory by 45% by 2030 compared to 2005 emission levels and to becoming Carbon Neutral by 2050. Other objectives of the Air Climate Plan are: (i) to return within the limit values of the concentrations of atmospheric pollutants such as fine dust and nitrogen oxides, (ii) to contribute to containing the local increase in temperature by 2050 within 2°C, through urban cooling actions.

In conclusion, despite the strategic effort of the Lombardy Region in planning measures to mitigate climate change and its effects, greenhouse gas emissions still represent a sensitive issue for the Lombardy region and significant improvements are necessary. **The status of climate change mitigation and adaptation measures is evaluated with score 2 (Improvement is needed).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning climate change mitigation and adaptation measures.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Demographic and productive characteristics of the region make it difficult to reduce greenhouse gas emissions ○ Orographic features make the territory particularly vulnerable to the effects of climate change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Presence of a mechanism already implemented for consultation and dialogue with institutional stakeholders
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Each prevention/mitigation action with the relative allocation of the necessary resources should include a careful assessment of the relative investment and management costs also through cost/benefit and cost/effectiveness analyses ○ Prevention/mitigation actions should be in synergy with all regional green economy actions in the sectors of production of goods and services, combining the strategies of prevention and management of risks deriving from climate with economic competitiveness ○ Regional strategies must be coordinated with the political and economic choices at national and community level 	

3.9.2 Socio economic dimension

Lombardy is an excellence both from a social point of view (it is the Italian region with the highest efficiency of the separate waste collection system) and from an economic point of view in terms of the strength of the production ecosystems (it is the most industrialized region in Italy). **The overall evaluation of the socio-economic aspects has reached a very high score: 4.5 as average of the 6 aspects considered.**

The spider chart in Figure 32 summarizes the evaluations on each single aspect; the specific aspects are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 32 - Socio-economic dimension global evaluation in Lombardy

3.9.2.1 Business reinvention capacity

Lombardy production system has proven over the years to be very skilled in addressing the challenges of the EC and transforming in a sustainable way to promote economic, social and environmental development.

To our best knowledge, there are no updated statistics available describing the number of Lombard companies operating in the Circular Economy sectors, but according to data from Symbola Foundation and Cariplo Foundation (2019) [156] with 77.691 companies, **Lombardy was in first place in Italy in the regional ranking for the absolute number of companies that have invested, or will invest within the year, in green technologies.** At the provincial level, Milan with 21.547 green companies was the most virtuous province in Lombardy, Brescia was second with 10.201 companies and Bergamo was third with 8.095; followed by Monza and Brianza with 5.932 and Varese with 5.867 companies. Also, in terms of “green job” contracts, Lombardy was the first Italian region (137.097 contracts in 2019) and Milan the first province in Italy (74.062 equal to 14.2% of the national total).

Lombard productive system is also heavily involved in **BIOECONOMY INNOVATION PROCESSES**: out of 160 members of the Italian Cluster of Circular Bioeconomy (Spring – <https://www.clusterspring.it/>) 34 are from Lombardy (21%).

A specific **STRUCTURE WAS CREATED TO FACILITATE COORDINATION BETWEEN INDUSTRY, ACADEMIA, FINANCE AND CITIZENS FOR CIRCULAR SOLUTIONS.** In

2021 Lombardy Region, University of Pavia, Polytechnic University of Milan, University of Milan, University of Milan-Bicocca, and CNR signed a collaboration agreement to promote the transition to a circular economy model. The main objective is the creation of a **Hub for the Circular Economy** [157], a research, innovation and technology transfer infrastructure able to push the development of sustainable strategies for the recovery of raw materials and their reuse in production processes of highly innovative compounds. To date, the main activities concern zero-emission electric mobility and the recycling of lithium batteries.

In addition, Lombardy Region supports business reinvention and CE transition through **AWARENESS-RAISING EVENTS AND INVOLVEMENT OF PUBLIC AND PRIVATE STAKEHOLDERS.**

An example is the **Regional Forum for Sustainable Development** organized by Lombardy Region and Lombard Foundation for the Environment: it includes sections spread throughout the region in order to discuss issues of territorial interest. The 5th edition of the forum (2024) was specifically focused on CE and included 5 events:

1. “*Lombardy Land of Business and Work – The circular future of business*” took place in Brescia and focused on productive sectors and new circular business models
2. “*Lombardy Land of Knowledge – Circularity between research, innovation and cultural change*” took place in Varese and was specifically devoted to science and culture as tools to increase awareness and promote behavioural change.
3. “*Lombardy Protagonist – The circular economy at the service of sustainable sports and tourism*” took place in Sondrio with the aim of discussing the role of sport and tourism in health, social cohesion and well-being towards sustainable lifestyles.
4. “*Lombardy Green – the views of a circular model*” took place in Mantova and was dedicated to the themes of circularity in the agri-food supply chain, air quality, renewable energy production and local development.
5. The final day “*New horizons for a circular economy*” took place in Milan and was focused on political visions, investments and future initiatives.

In the overall assessment of the business reinvention capacity, the presence of “green companies” and the support offered by the Region towards the circular transition with dedicated infrastructures and/or awareness events have to be taken into account: from both points of view, Lombardy represents an excellence. Businesses are highly capable of adopting and transforming sustainably in response to the challenges and opportunities present in the region, actively promoting local economic, social, and environmental development. **Business reinvention capacity is evaluated as strong (score 5).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning business reinvention capacity.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Resistance to overcome old business models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collaboration between companies and research institutions ○ Strength of the productive ecosystem with structured supply chains

- Financial support from the Region

Actions

- Increase collaboration between companies and research institutions
- Increase training and information in companies with a focus on the advantages (including economic ones) of EC

3.9.2.2 Strength of the Productive Ecosystem

According to the NUTS2 classification of the European Union, Lombardy is the first industrial region in EU; it is also the second European region in terms of Gross Domestic Product size with 440 billion euros in 2022 after the Ile de France (783 billion) and the second region in Europe also in terms of added value of the industrial sector with 88 billion euros in 2021, after the Irish region of Southern.

An interesting tool to evaluate the robustness, efficiency, and resilience of the region is the “*Regional Competitiveness Index*” measuring the territory’s ability to offer enterprises and residents an attractive and sustainable environment where live and work, seeking a balance between economy and well-being: Lombardy ranks 98th in the ranking of European regions in the 2022 edition of the Regional Competitiveness Index [158].

From the Position Paper published by the Lombardy Region in March 2024 [159], it is also possible to analyse the regional strength of specific production ecosystems.

Lombardy Region is the most specialized in Europe in the sectors of Energy Intensive Industry (including mechanics, steel, but also chemistry and the home industry) and Textile (clothing and fashion sector); also in the ecosystems of the Cultural and Creative Industry (media, press, publishing, video and television, music, art, architecture, museums, advertising) and Digital (telecommunications, information services, software and consultancy and publishing), Lombardy is positioned in European excellence.

The agri-food sector is still anchored to tradition and craftsmanship with a relatively low level of specialization, but Lombardy is firmly positioned among the top five European regions in terms of number of companies and employees in the food and beverage sector.

Following Figure 33 shows for each single industrial ecosystem the level of specialization and the number of employees.

Figure 33 – Strength of the Lombardy production ecosystems
 Horizontal axis: Specialization in Lombardy vs. EU
 Vertical axis: Specialization in Lombardy vs. Italy
 Bubble size number of employees
 Source: Eurostat, ISTAT

From a governance point of view, Lombardy Region supports and promotes productive ecosystems with the recognition of the **Lombardy Technology Clusters** as aggregations between the different subjects active in the field of Research and Innovation (companies, universities, research centres, public and private institutions and other subjects, including financial ones) [160].

Lombardy Technology Clusters have legal personality, and they actively participate in the implementation of innovative processes able to contribute to regional competitiveness. Among the main fields of action of Lombardy Technology Clusters: (i) to support collaboration between scientific and industrial actors and to facilitate the inclusiveness of small entities; (ii) to support Lombardy Region in definition and updating of R&I strategies; (iii) to map regional skills and promote the excellence of the territory in the creation; (iv) to enhance the results of the R&I actions.

Nine Technological Clusters are recognized by the Lombardy Region: they represent the strategic areas identified at a national level

1. Cat.Al., Cluster High Technology Agrofood Lombardy (www.clusteragrofoodlombardia.eu) operates in the **agri-food sector** and includes 6 different value chains: fresh and semi-finished products, cereal, pork, dairy, wine, industrial supply chain.
2. **Aerospace** – Lombardy Aerospace Cluster (<https://www.aerospacelombardia.it/chiamo/>) encompasses a sector with more than 200 companies for approximately 21.800 employees, generating approximately 6.3 billion in annual turnover and exports worth approximately 1 billion, equal to almost a quarter of the national exports of the sector. Lombardy aerospace includes 3 complete production chains (i) the

- helicopter industry (ii) the assemblers of aircraft for military training (iii) the complete production of satellites with scientific payloads for Earth observation or space exploration
3. Lombardy Green Chemistry Association, LGCA (<https://www.chimicaverdelombardia.it/>) is the reference point of the Lombard bioeconomy at national and European level; it operates in the **green chemistry sector** promoting wider use of renewable resources to support sustainable growth. LGCA includes 47 members organized in 8 thematic groups: industrial organic waste, innovative materials, biogas, wood, high added value substances, energy valorisation of biomass, sustainable chemistry, strategy and promotion.
 4. Lombardy Mobility Cluster, CLM (<https://clusterlombardomobilita.it/>) promotes the development of the competitiveness of the regional **land and water mobility industry** through pre-competitive research and identification of business scenarios at a global level. A specific thematic table is devoted to environmental sustainability with objectives such as the use of alternative fuels, the use of renewable energy sources, the reduction of the 'carbon footprint', the reduction of 'well to wheel' emissions.
 5. Lombardy Energy Cleantech Cluster, LE2C (www.energycluster.it) represents the Lombardy production system for **energy and the environment** and develops projects to support innovation with particular reference to the following technological areas: (i) Smart Energy Systems, (ii) Sustainable Manufacturing, (iii) Green Building, (iv) Water Energy Nexus, (v) Clean Air. The Circular Economy cuts across all technological areas.
 6. Smart Factory Association Lombardy, AFIL (<https://afil.it/>) is the technological cluster for the **advanced manufacturing sector** and includes 137 members
 7. Cluster Technologies for Smart Cities & Communities Lombardy, Cluster SCC (<https://clusterscclombardia.it/>) brings together companies, research centres and stakeholders with the aim of promoting research and innovation in the **integrated management of urban and metropolitan scale systems** of renewable energy, energy efficiency, security and monitoring of the territory, mobility, health, well-being, e-government, e-justice, cultural heritage and tourism.
 8. Cluster Technology Caring People, Cluster TAV (www.cluster.techforlife.it) operates in the sector of **technologies for living environments**. The aim is to promote and encourage inclusion, safety, well-being, health and eco-sustainability through Ambient Intelligence and Ambient Assisted Living schemes. Cluster TAV members are 10 production companies, 6 universities and 12 healthcare companies.
 9. Lombardy Cluster **Life Sciences** (www.lombardialifesciences.it) operates in the following sectors: (i) pharmaceutical, (ii) medical devices, (iii) digital health, (iv) biotechnology, (v) health and wellness sectors.

Technological Clusters increase the strength of Lombardy's production ecosystems because they allow representativeness and inclusiveness of supply chains creating interaction between different sectors also in terms of Circular Economy. Technological Clusters support the aggregation of companies even outside of existing networks,

encouraging the establishment of new connections and collaborations and enriching mutual knowledge within the entire regional ecosystem.

In addition, from an economic perspective, Lombardy Region aims to consolidate, through public funding, the relationships between the productive companies, Universities and Research institutes to create ecosystems that allow a continuous exchange between these subjects for common growth. For the year 2024, a financial endowment of 34 million euros has been allocated (FERS resources 2021-2027) to strengthen the supply chains and production ecosystems with respect to the following areas: innovation and production autonomy, green and digital transition, updating and retraining of the workforce, internationalization and attractiveness through the enhancement of the territorial, reshoring, capital strengthening [161].

Both in terms of industrialization and diversification level and in terms of associations and governance, **we can assess a strong productive ecosystem strength and resilience (score 5)**: Lombardy shows an exceptionally robust and highly resilient productive system with a very efficient support to the networking and the R&I.

In the analysis and synthesis of Lombard readiness to adopt CE practices concerning the strength of the productive ecosystem (following table) we will consider the case study of the agri-food sector (with the experience of the Cluster High Technology Agrofood Lombardy).

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Low penetration of advanced technologies in agri-food processing industries ○ Low propensity to introduce technologies in a sector where craftsmanship is predominant ○ Low propensity to automation due to the variability of raw materials (e.g. seasonality) ○ Unstable and fluctuating costs of energy and raw materials ○ Difficult procurement due to the dependence on foreign countries for many raw materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Presence of excellence in the food production sector ○ Growing foreign demand for quality Italian products ○ Opportunities for cross-fertilisation between the food sector and the ICT sector
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Monitoring and optimization of production processes through the introduction of digitalization and automation technologies along the supply chain ○ Support the productive system with specific public fundic 	

3.9.2.3 Professional and technical skills related to the Circular Economy

The Lombardy system of university education and higher education is the largest in Italy, offering the greatest selection to students and boasting the highest number of enrolled students in our country. According to data from the Ministry of University and Research, elaborated by the Milan Higher Education Observatory of the University of Milan [162], from the academic year 2011-2012 to the academic year 2022-2023, Lombardy was always the first Italian region in terms of number of enrolled students at the 15 universities located in the territory.

Specific university education related to the EC themes is also wide and varied; following Table 31 reports the degree courses and university master's active in Lombardy related to the themes of EC or more generally of environmental sustainability.

Table 31 – Lombardy University offer about Circular Economy

Course of study	University	Aims of the course	Website
Three-year degree courses			
<i>Sustainable agriculture</i>	University of Milan	Graduates in “ <i>Sustainable Agriculture</i> ” manages the main aspects of herbaceous and arboreal plant production and animal production, combining the needs of profitability with environmental sustainability.	https://agricoltura-sostenibile.cdl.unimi.it/it
<i>Management for sustainability</i>	“Sacro Cuore” University in Piacenza	The course of study offers multidisciplinary knowledge and skills (economic, legal, biological, philosophical and pedagogical) useful for addressing the challenges of environmental sustainability.	https://www.unicatt.it/corsi/triennale/management-per-la-sostenibilita-piacenza.html
Master’s degree courses			
<i>Agricultural sciences for sustainability</i>	University of Milan	Graduates in “ <i>Agricultural sciences for sustainability</i> ” take care at the management level of agricultural companies of any production type combining the needs of profitability with environmental sustainability.	https://sas.cdl.unimi.it/it
<i>Sustainable natural resource management</i>	University of Milan	Graduates in “ <i>Sustainable natural resource management</i> ” can take on tasks of organization, evaluation, management and responsibility for problems that may involve an interaction between human activities and environmental systems.	https://snrm.cdl.unimi.it/en
<i>Environmental Change and Global Sustainability</i>	University of Milan	The main peculiar quality of “ <i>Environmental Change and Global Sustainability</i> ” graduates is their ability to tackle environmental change and sustainability from a multidisciplinary perspective.	https://ecgs.cdl.unimi.it/en
<i>Biotechnology for the bioeconomy</i>	University of Milan	It aims to train graduates with advanced knowledges of the molecular and cellular bases of biological, plant and microbial systems, able to manage, develop and improve processes in the various sectors of biotechnology applied to the bioeconomy.	https://www.unimi.it/it/corsi/laurea-magistrale/biotechnology-bioeconomy
<i>Sustainable and precision agriculture</i>	“Sacro Cuore” University in Piacenza	It is a course aimed at sustainability in agriculture with a strongly interdisciplinary approach to address modern issues aimed at precision agriculture and attention to climate change.	https://www.unicatt.it/corsi/magistrale/agricoltura-sostenibile-e-di-precisione-piacenza.html

<i>Transformative Sustainability</i>	Bocconi University in collaboration with Polytechnic of Milan	This course provides the knowledge and tools necessary to guide companies in the transition process towards sustainable business models with an integrated approach to strategic and organizational innovation	https://www.unibocconi.it/it/corsi-di-studio/lauree-magistrali/transformative-sustainability-0
Post-university specialization courses			
<i>International master's in environmental sustainability & circular economy</i>	Polytechnic of Milan	Thanks to this course it is possible to learn to manage a sustainable company from the ground up: from understanding why sustainability matters to implementing sustainable practices across functions; it is possible to gain expertise in managing sustainability projects strategically, entrepreneurially, organizationally and technologically.	https://www.polimi.it/formazione/formazione-oltre-la-laurea/master-universitari-e-corsi-post-laurea/dettaglio-master/2652
<i>Circular Economy - From waste to resources: an economy in transition</i>	Polytechnic of Milan	it is a training course aimed mainly at the management of companies most directly involved in the Ecological Transition, with particular attention to innovative management of material and waste flows, as well as energy strategies to address the crisis,	https://www.poliedra.polimi.it/corso_ecl/
<i>Bioeconomy in the Circular Economy</i>	Bicocca University	It offers an extensive training program for professionals interested in working within the bio-based goods and services industry using biological resources and bio-technological processes	https://masterbiocirce.com/
<i>Master in Sustainability and Energy Management</i>	Bocconi University	Main topics of the course are sustainability, climate change, renewable energy, energy efficiency and sustainable urban development are considered	https://www.unibocconi.it/it/corsi-di-studio/master-universitari/masem-master-sustainability-and-energy-management
<i>Circular Economy Strategy & Management Program for New Talents</i>	Bocconi University	It aims to create new professional figures in the CE sector, with a focus on the supply chains of electronic products, batteries, packaging, tobacco products and textile products.	https://erion.it/it/formazione/circular-economy-strategy-management-program-for-new-talents/

Despite the large number of university courses, a misalignment between the needs of companies and the available skills is observed in the Lombardy region, with great difficulties for the selection of professional personnel.

As emerged during the working group with regional stakeholders, a challenge for the near future is to promote greater coordination between universities and production sectors. Lombardy Region wants to answer to this challenge through a specific financial measure on

the development of skills: it will be a transversal measure not strictly dedicated to the CE, but it will include issues relating to environmental sustainability.

In conclusion, in Lombardy, thanks to the wide range of university courses there is good availability of qualified personnel to support the transition from a linear to a Circular Economy, but a further effort is needed to respond to the needs of companies. **Labour force professional & technical skills related to Circular Economy are evaluated as weak readiness (score 4).**

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the professional and technical skills related to the Circular Economy.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Misalignment between the needs of companies and the available skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Wide range of university courses active in Lombardy ○ Cooperation between universities for multidisciplinary courses
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Promote greater coordination between universities and companies ○ Promotion university training courses about Circular Economy 	

3.9.2.4 Trust in the productive system

As previously reported in chapter **3.8 Stakeholders involvement**, the aspects related to confidence and reliance that regional stakeholders have in circular transition was in deep discussed during the working group event.

In particular, regional technological clusters are in close contact with the companies of the Lombardy region, and they are able to perceive a great interest in the activities of sustainable transition and CE: for example, a great participation in webinars on the topics of Circular Economy was found with a much higher number of registrations compared to similar events on different topics. On the other hand, from an internal evaluation of circularity in cluster member companies, it is possible to notice that there is no global awareness on CE, but entrepreneurs are more interested in activities offering tangible economic return (e.g. reduction of energy used, reuse and recycling of products and waste).

A special case is the highly specialized manufacturing sector. This sector is not very suitable to the direct transition to the Circular Economy because the tendency is to refunctionalize materials while maintaining a high guarantee on quality and performance. On the other hand, the potential of the manufacturing chain is to participate in the circularity of downstream actors, conceiving, designing and building functional machinery in activities aiming for circularity (e.g. construction of plants to produce bioplastics).

To analyse economic operators, trust in circular transition, we can also consider the requests for access to public funding. The growing number of requests for financing from companies

operating in various production sectors (soft loans or co-financing) demonstrates that companies, if supported, are willing to co-invest in CE activities. So, although the critical point of additional costs is present, companies are changing the approach at CE looking at the possibility of reducing their production costs in the medium-long term.

From a consumer point of view, general trust in the circular transition is very high and citizens are aware only of some aspects of CE (typically the aspects at the end of the supply chain such as waste management) but they do not perceive more technical aspects such as the ecodesign of products. Similarly, although Lombardy is an excellence for separate waste collection with a very high public awareness, there is little knowledge and confidence about waste reuse.

Summarizing the evidence emerged from the discussion with stakeholders and their opinion on the current trust towards a circular transition, **it is possible to assess a weak confidence (score 4)**: regional stakeholders have considerable confidence in the efficiency, fairness, and sustainability of the local economy and its industries.

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve stakeholders' trust in the Lombard productive system and circular transition.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Initial investment costs ○ Difficulty in penetrating the market due to decreasing citizens' spending capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Innovative technologies ○ Innovation networks with public-private collaboration ○ Public funding ○ Growing attention from consumers
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Improve the cooperation network between companies and research institutions ○ Specific regulations ○ Guidelines to support companies in the circular transition 	

3.9.2.5 Regional/local cultural aspects

Northern Italy regions are excellent not only from an economic and institutional points of view but also in terms of sustainability.

According to the Green City Network ranking [163], Lombardy, together with Veneto and Trentino Alto Adige, is an absolute excellence in **CIRCULAR WASTE MANAGEMENT**: these three regions can boast the highest recycling rates and have already reached and exceeded the European target set for 2025.

More in deep, according to the Legambiente dossier "*Comuni ricicloni*" [164], in 2022 71 kg of waste was produced per year per inhabitant in Lombardy and 82% was destined for separate waste collection (average values): in only 363 municipalities (mainly in the province of Sondrio and in the province of Pavia) the percentage of separate waste collection

remained below the critical threshold of 65% defined in European standards and in Regional Waste Management Programme.

The following Figure 34 shows for each province the percentage of separate waste collection and the number of “waste free” municipalities in which all waste is recycled.

Figure 34 – Separate waste collection percentage in Lombard provinces
Source: Legambiente, 2022

A further investigation into Lombardy citizens behaviour, with specific reference to the valorisation of plastic waste was possible thanks to a survey conducted by Tecnoalimenti (see **Annex 6 “Citizens attitudes and actions towards sustainable consumption, production, and waste management practices: waste management behaviours and awareness of recycled plastic materials”**).

The targets of the survey were the Lombard consumers, considering different age groups and social classes. Not only the waste management habits were analyzed but also the awareness of recycled food packaging material in the market and the availability to pay more or to change the shopping habits for a more sustainable food product. The final goal was to evaluate the **WHOLE ATTITUDES AND ACTIONS TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION**.

As expected, 71% of Lombard consumers are aware of the waste management rules of their city and, the vast majority (81%) look at the packages before throwing them away, searching for information on the material and the type of disposal required for it.

On the other hand, the survey reveals low attention to the recyclability and sustainability of the packaging when buying a food or beverage product. But although consumers might not be interested or might be little aware of the current innovation of food packaging related to having more recyclable, the majority of them are willing to pay a little bit more for their food if in presence of recycled packaging material: the vast majority of the consumers are ready to pay from 5% to 10% more for their food, more precisely, 70% of young consumers and 63,5% of the older ones would bear the surcharge.

In conclusion, we can affirm that Lombard citizens show on average an excellent behaviour in waste management but evaluating the overall approach to the circular economy (with specific reference to plastic intended for food packaging) there is still little awareness and attitude to change. **The status of adequacy of citizens' beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours is evaluated as weak (score 4):** citizens' beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours show some potential for supporting a transition to a Circular Economy, but there are significant gaps or areas needing improvement.

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning local cultural aspects.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Different methods of separate waste collection in different municipalities can confuse citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In Lombardy there are some initiatives to motivate citizens (also from an economic point of view) to correctly separate waste collection (see next paragraph)
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Improve information related to the correct disposal on the packaging (food and beverage packaging) ○ Increase initiatives to engage and motivate citizens 	

3.9.2.6 *Circular Economy citizenship participation*

The importance of citizen involvement in waste sorting is fundamental to the success and effectiveness of waste management process. Citizens are the link between the collection system and the correct separation of materials, and their active involvement can make the difference in reducing environmental pollution and promoting a sustainable lifestyle. In the Lombardy region, numerous initiatives have been implemented in this direction to increase citizens' awareness and reward virtuous behaviour from an economic point of view.

First, it is worth mentioning the “**Pay-As-You-Throw**” system: it is based on the quantification of waste produced by the individual user with the aim of determining a tariff proportional, for the variable part, to the use of the service by the user. The tariff is composed of two main items: (i) the fixed quota is useful to cover operating costs (such as street sweeping costs and investments in works) and (ii) the variable depends directly on the waste produced by the user.

Another economic initiative to encourage citizen participation is the installation of reverse vending machines or eco-compactors: these are collection systems (in most cases plastic but also glass or aluminium) that reward the consumer, for example, with vouchers to be used at specific shops. The network of eco-compactors extends throughout the country and is constantly expanding. Today, many projects are active with large-scale distribution and Italian municipalities, but Lombardy is excellent from this point of view.

Taking into account only the PET eco-compactors installed in collaboration with Esselunga (a well-known large-scale distribution chain) we have 30 reverse vending machines distributed throughout the Lombardy region as reported in the following Table 32.

Table 32 – Number of PET eco-compactors installed in collaboration with Esselunga in Lombardy

District	
Bergamo	3
Brescia	2
Como	2
Mantova	1
Milano	14
Monza e Brianza	3
Varese	4
TOT	30

In 2021, in the city of Milan an eco-compactor was also installed in a metro station (Cascina Gobba).

A similar initiative (not linked to a financial reward but rather to a social project) is the collection of aluminium coffee capsules “**Da Chicco a Chicco**” previously described in section **3.5.1.3 Current waste management solution**. It is a national initiative, but Lombardy is the first region in Italy for the collection. In 2023, 50 tons of aluminium and 520 tons of coffee were collected, with an increase of 16% compared to 2022. The most significant increases were in the provinces of Brescia, Bergamo and Como with over 150 tons of capsules and a growth rate of 30%; the province of Milan, on the other hand, recorded a growth of 4% with almost 230 tons of capsules.

In conclusion, considering both the number of initiatives proposed by the Lombardy Region and the response from citizens we can affirm that citizens demonstrate high levels of engagement and involvement in initiatives and campaigns promoting the goals of the CE. **The level of citizenship participation is evaluated as strong (score 5).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning citizenship participation.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<i>No barrier or challenge has been identified</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Strong propensity of citizens to the proposed initiatives ○ Existence of numerous strategic political actions
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase the number of municipalities applying “pay-as-you-throw” system 	

3.9.3 Governance dimension

Lombardy Region owns a very good presence and effectiveness of governance structures and mechanisms at various levels of government, as well as collaboration between stakeholders, to facilitate the transition towards a Circular Economy.

The overall evaluation of the governance has reached a very high score: 4.4 as average of the 5 elements considered.

The spider chart in Figure 35 summarizes the evaluations on each single aspect; the specific aspects are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 35 - Governance dimension global evaluation in Lombardy

3.9.3.1 Promotion of Circular Economy culture and trust enhancement

Lombardy Region takes in place several strategic initiatives to cultivate a cultural shift towards sustainable practices both in citizens and in productive companies.

As examples of regional initiatives and campaigns for citizen awareness we can mention the following (not exhaustive list):

- “*The World is a Wheel. Plastic Recycling and the Circular Economy in Lombardy*” [165] is a free book for primary school children. Through stories and illustrations, young readers can discover the path of plastic as waste and how it can be recovered.
- “*Don’t waste a love story*” is a recent campaign of the Lombardy Region promoting, through videos and public documents broadcasted on social channels of Lombardy Region, with media influencer and videos, the respect for food and the adoption of good individual and collective habits. More in depth 4 simple ways to save the “love

- story with food*” are suggested: (i) to pay attention to the expiration date, (ii) to plan food shopping, (iii) to prefer seasonal or “zero km” products, (iv) to store food correctly. In addition, a decalogue of good actions for the citizens has been developed and disseminated.
- Slightly broadening the perspective from citizens only to economic operators, among the awareness campaigns on Circular Economy organized by the Lombardy Region it is possible to mention an activity aimed at the food market sector [166]. The municipality of Milan in collaboration with AMSA (the company responsible for waste management and separate waste collection) aims to raise awareness among commercial operators active in food markets to implement more attentive and environmentally friendly behaviours and habits involving over 4.500 stalls with particular attention to organic waste, such as food scraps, plants and flowers, and paper, plastic and wood packaging. To facilitate waste sorting operations, operators were given a kit consisting of a supply of 70-litre bio compostable bags and a steel bag holder; the larger benches were also equipped with lateral fixing rings. At the same time, AMSA distributed an information leaflet with correct behaviours and actions to be taken such as: (i) throwing organic waste only in the appropriate compostable bags (ii) folding the boxes to reduce their volume (iii) separating and stacking the plastic and wooden boxes next to your stall and (iv) cleaning the area used for sales (see the following Figure 36).

Figure 36 - Awareness campaign for market operators in the municipality of Milan

In addition, as discussed during the working group with regional stakeholders, Lombardy Region owns a devoted online communication system to disseminate good practices implemented by public bodies and/or private citizens. This activity is included into the “**Waste Prevention Program 2022 – 2027**” (see following **3.9.3.5 Holistic regional systemic approach**)

During the working group with regional stakeholders also emerged an intense activity of technological clusters in sharing good practices and success stories. LE2C cluster, for

example, conducts periodic surveys with its members with the aim of collecting information on good practices already implemented: these are then disseminated internally and externally to the cluster itself via newsletters.

Lombardy Region has good initiatives to promote Circular Economy culture and trust and there are in place dialogue spaces contributing positively to the Circular Economy. **Promotion of Circular Economy culture and trust enhancement is evaluated weak (score 4).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the promotion of Circular Economy culture and trust enhancement.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Difficulty in reaching numerous stakeholders and involving all institutional actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Great sensitivity of citizens and good adhesion to campaigns
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ It would be interesting to implement a system of direct comparison with citizens through discussions in small groups (in particular on Circular Economy topics where there is a more direct perception such as, for example, waste management) ○ Better coordination between different actors in the territory 	

3.9.3.2 Dialogue promotion in the decision-making process

A significant initiative of the Lombardy Region (Environment Directorate) to promote dialogue between private actors and public stakeholders towards the circular transition was the creation of the “**Observatory for climate, circular economy and ecological transition**” [167]. It is a meeting place between the public sector (Region and Provinces), universities, research institutions and production entities (trade associations, unions, environmental organizations).

The Observatory is organized in permanent coordination tables with the aim to define directions, objectives and expected results of the process of common construction of regional policies and strategies for the environment and climate.

Institutional Table has the function of addressing and sharing general strategies; Technical Secretariat works to provide technical-scientific support for the development of regional strategies for the coordination of the thematic tables and for the monitoring of activities; the following thematic tables have been activated to analyse critical issues and opportunities, to develop legislative and regulatory proposals, financing and support measures, and supply chain collaboration methods:

- In the Circular Economy Area
 - Sewage sludge
 - Construction and demolition waste
 - Melting slag
 - Food waste

- Plastics
- In the Energy Transition Area
 - Energy efficiency
 - Renewable energy sources

More in general, as previously reported in the paragraph **3.9.2.2. Strength of the Productive Ecosystem**, Lombardy Region established an effective system of technological clusters to promote dialogue and collaboration between companies and research institutions and to involve the production sector in decision-making processes. A cluster is specifically devoted to green chemistry, environmental sustainability and Circular Economy (LGCA).

In addition, as a concrete example of **COLLABORATION BETWEEN PRIVATE AND PUBLIC STAKEHOLDERS**, we can cite a collaboration protocol between the Lombardy Region and Eni Spa (the main Italian company in the energy sector) signed in July 2024 on the themes of the EC [168] and more precisely on the following aspects:

- development and diffusion of more sustainable technologies,
- development of renewable energy sources,
- study and experimentation of integrated solutions for more sustainable mobility,
- development of new production chains,
- research and innovation to promote digitalization processes and the application of Artificial Intelligence on technologies and analyses, for example, in the field of decarbonization.

Region Lombardy implemented several and efficient activities to stimulate dialogue between the quintuple helix with active and meaningful representation of private actors in the decision-making process. **Promotion is evaluated as excellent (score 5).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the dialogue promotion in the decision-making process.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
○ Coordination difficulties between different production sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Territorial production system already organized in clusters ○ Existence of a practical and strategic approach for the exchange of information
Actions	
○ Starting from existing collaborative initiatives, new development models could be proposed for the circular transition also in similar/complementary sectors	

3.9.3.3 Existence and implementation of an effective multi-level governance

In the Region Lombardy **A SPECIFIC BODY FOR THE GOVERNANCE OF CE** was implemented: it is the “**Circular Economy and Natural Resources Protection Organizational Unit**” [169].

Its main competences are:

- actions for sustainable development;
- environmental protection of soil resources, regulation and monitoring and implementing agreements;
- remediation of polluted waters;
- regulatory, planning and regional programming proposals on quarries and mines and related implementing acts;
- regional authorizations, opinions and agreements on quarries, mines, hydrocarbons and geothermal energy;
- transversal functions and support for the directorate's activity;
- regional planning on waste and contribution to state programming;
- environmental authority for community programs;
- coordination of projects and initiatives to promote CE.

Lombard Governance structures and mechanisms are effective, with continuous collaboration across all levels of regional government and stakeholders, driving significant progress towards a Circular Economy but collaboration at national level can be improved. **Overall implementation of multi-level governance is evaluated as good (score 4).**

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the existence and implementation of an effective multi-level governance.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
○ Interface difficulties at national level	○ Specific body for the governance of CE
Actions	
○ Greater synergy with national planning	

3.9.3.4 Adoption of functional approach

URBAN REGENERATION POLICIES are the most concrete application of synergies between urban and rural areas in Lombardy. They are community-based initiatives starting from a co-creation approach and able to involve different actors along the supply chains and create opportunities for industrial and urban symbiosis.

The adoption of this functional approach is very interesting in Milan city: because of the very high rate of urban density, territorial regeneration projects are needed.

The municipality of Milan implemented several projects and initiatives with the active participation of the local population with the aim of spreading culture and respect for the environment and landscape and restoring at least in part, the destroyed naturalness.

Despite this, these are individual initiatives not organised in an organic plan, and they are difficult to interconnect and/or scale-up. In addition, these are voluntary initiatives that do not generate any economic profit.

Below the main project and initiative are listed:

1. Quite widespread in the Milan area are **urban gardens** created within municipal property spaces and managed by volunteer associations or individual citizens. The assignment of territories occurs on a voluntary basis following a specific call for tenders: the municipality makes free areas available to citizens requesting them and the beneficiaries are mainly elderly people or residents in the municipality for a pre-established period or volunteer associations. Many crops are allowed: it is only required that they are not produced for profit purposes. The concession lasts up to nine years, free of charge, and can be renewed for another three, upon payment of an annual fee of 300€.

769 urban gardens were active in Milan city in 2018, and they were distributed as in Figure 37.

Figure 37 – Urban gardens in Milan
Source: Italia Nostra, 2018 [170]

The greater number of urban gardens are in the southern area of Milan in correspondence with the “Parco Agricolo Sud Milano”. The “Parco Agricolo Sud Milano” has been active for years in the promotion and enhancement of local agriculture and in its numerous projects it involves not only local administrations, but above all the local population. The greater demand and availability of urban gardens is therefore explained by the greater habit of the activity as well as in the promotional involvement activity carried out by an institution particularly attentive to this type of initiative [171].

Lombardy Region also supports the creation of urban gardens. In February 2024, a call for proposals was published for the allocation of funds for the creation of educational, urban and collective gardens; call for proposals was intended for Municipalities, public and private schools, and protected area management bodies [172].

2. “**Out-of-soil gardens**” project was born from the collaboration between the municipality of Milan, T12 Lab Association (<https://www.t12-lab.it/>), Foundation Comunità Milano (<https://www.fondazionecomunitamilano.org/>), Caritas Ambrosiana (<https://www.caritasambrosiana.it/>) and Legambiente (www.legambiente.it). Thanks also to the scientific support of the Department of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences of the University of Milan, vertical or horizontal hydroponic cultivations and cultivations in soil crates have been implemented in several peripheral areas on the outskirts of the city. The vegetables produced (salads, aubergines, tomatoes) are donated to the Milan Food Bank or to Caritas and then redistributed to poor people [173].
3. “**Recycle and grow, the vertical garden at school**” is an initiative promoted by the Municipality of Milan in association with Milano Ristorazione (<https://www.milanoristorazione.it/>), Corepla (<https://www.corepla.it/>) and Amsa (<https://www.amsa.it/it>) to generate Circular Economy products starting from plastic plates and dishes, used in nursery school canteens. In 175 nursery schools, a kit was distributed consisting of a multi-tier shelf, 12 vases and a watering can, all in recycled plastic. Together with soil and compost, they will be used to grow horticultural and aromatic plants [174].
4. **Agricity** was a collaborative project between the Municipality of Milan and the Politecnico of Milan (Department of Architecture, Construction Engineering and Built Environment) with funding from Cariplo. The aim was to analyse urban agriculture in Milan by highlighting aspects such as the landscape, companies, points of sale up to defining the micro-supply chains (in some cases circular supply chains). The website collected images, publications and information providing citizens and interested parties with a timely information and dissemination tool [175].
5. “**Adopt a hen**” is a project of the association Soulfood Forestfarms also involved in agroforestry activities (see **3.9.1.4 Land and biodiversity degradation processes**). In the southern area of Milan, in the context of the Agroforest managed by Soulfood Forestfarms, a mobile social and shared chicken coop has been built, and it houses 150 hens. Families deciding to adopt a chicken will give it a name and collect its eggs at the Agroforesta or decide to give them to needy families in the adjacent neighbourhoods. The project also involves students from the Polytechnic of Milan for the design of the chicken coops and researchers and professors from the University of Milan (Department of Cultural and Environmental Heritage) for the monitoring of cultural ecosystem services.
6. The municipality of Milan promotes specific agreements with neighbouring municipalities for a more efficient and rational management of the land and the implementation of urban regeneration policies. The “**Framework Agreement for**

Territorial Development” [176] involves, in addition to the Municipality of Milan, the following public and private actors: (i) Lombardy Region (specifically Directorates General “Agriculture, Food and Green Systems”, “Environment and Climate”, “Territory and Civil Protection”), (ii) Metropolitan City of Milan, (iii) Consortium of the Milanese Agricultural District bringing together 34 Milanese agricultural companies, (iv) Agricultural District of the Olona River Valley, (v) Neo-rural District of the Three Waters of Milan including the presence of two regional parks (Ticino Park and South Milan Agricultural Park) and two local parks of supra-municipal interest (Gelso Park and Roccolo Park), (vi) Adda Martesana Agricultural District bringing together 21 agricultural and non-agricultural companies, (vii) Olona River Consortium. The agreement aims to consolidate the process of strengthening the rural matrix of the Milanese metropolitan settlement.

Summarizing, Lombardy Region and Milan city in particular, implemented efficient urban regeneration policies leading to good connectivity and collaboration between urban and rural areas. **Adoption of functional approach element is evaluated as good (score 4).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning practices concerning the adoption of functional approach

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Small-scale initiatives difficult to integrate and/or scale up ○ Regulation on food production and transformation are difficult to respect at very small scale (e.g. urban gardens) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Municipal strategies for promoting regional food systems ○ EU strategies (for example Farm to Fork, Food 2030, etc.)
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Exchange of information and cross fertilization not only at local level but also at national and international level ○ Policy planning taking into account complementary knowledge and skills available in the territory 	

3.9.3.5 *Holistic regional systemic approach*

Lombardy Region implemented a systemic strategy to drive the circular and sustainable transition both with a holistic approach and with focus on relevant topics.

From a general point of view, it is first of all relevant to cite the “**Regional Sustainable Development Program**” [177]: it is the official document defining the objectives, strategies and policies that the Region intends to implement during the legislature, to promote the economic, social and territorial development of Lombardy. The Regional Sustainable Development Program is presented by the Regional Council at the beginning of each legislature and every year, the main results achieved, and the progress of the strategic objectives are reported.

A specific pillar of the Regional Sustainable Development Program is devoted with the aim of promoting mitigation and adaptation to climate change, supporting the development of renewable energy sources and incentivizing energy efficiency, promoting environmental education and the culture of sustainability.

More in depth, a specific objective is focused on the develop the Circular Economy with the aim of reducing the consumption of raw materials, promoting the circular transformation of supply chains according to the principles of eco-design and promoting sustainability certifications among companies. In addition, the Lombardy Region intends to adapt waste policies with an “*End of Waste*” perspective, to promote the saving of mineral raw materials and to support the development of innovative and experimental plants, also by promoting impact measurement mechanisms.

The following Table 33 summarizes the main aspects of the Strategic Objective “5.1.4 *Developing the circular economy in the territory*” from Regional Sustainable Development Program.

Table 33 Strategic Objective “5.1.4 Developing the circular economy in the territory” from Regional Development Program

Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies, associations (waste management companies, innovation clusters, certification bodies, startup accelerators and investment funds) • Training and research bodies • Citizens
Entities of the regional system involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARPA, Regional Agency for Environmental Protection (https://www.arpalombardia.it/) • Regional Company for Innovation and Purchasing (https://www.ariaspa.it/wps/portal/Aria/Home) • PoliS Lombardia, Regional Institute for Policy Support in Lombardy (https://www.polis.lombardia.it/wps/portal/site/polis) • Lombardy Foundation for the Environment (https://flanet.org/) • Finlombarda S.p.A., the financial company of the Lombardy Region supporting the economic development of businesses, public administrations, research institutions and professionals in the region (https://www.finlombarda.it/) • ERSAF, Regional Agency for Agricultural and Forestry Services (https://www.ersaf.lombardia.it/)
Other entities involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chambers of Commerce • Provinces • Municipalities • Italian State • ARERA, National Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment (https://www.arera.it/)
KPI	529 CE projects funded in 2027 (starting from a baseline of 129 in December 2023, +400 projects in the legislature)
Funding sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional Resources • State Resources • European Regional Development Fund (FERS)

In July 2024, the “**Progress report on the Regional Sustainable Development Programme**” [178] was published describing the results achieved by the regional administration. About the specific CE objective, in 2024 the “*Ri.Circo.Lo*” measure was opened, aimed at Local Authorities for the prevention of waste production and the implementation of waste collection systems aimed at increasing material recovery (see next paragraph **3.9.5.1 Specific financial lines for Circular Economy**). In addition, to promote an effective and rational use of raw materials, regional law 1/2000 was amended in order to guarantee and ensure the impartiality of public tender procedures in the field of competition for the supply of raw materials.

Strictly related to the Regional Sustainable Development Program is the **“Regional Protocol for Sustainable Development”** [179]. The goal of the Protocol is to bring together local actors, to create opportunities for dialogue and exchange of practices and to strengthen convergence on a shared vision and on jointly designed policies, so that their implementation is actively participated in and becomes a shared responsibility. The Protocol is open to public and private stakeholders, such as associations, trade associations, territorial networks and non-profit organizations and aims to strengthen, thanks to their collaboration, the ability to implement sustainable development actions and policies.

The commitment undertaken with the signature is expressed in the presentation of a path of activities and the signatories plan to involve their respective reference subjects in achieving the objectives of the Regional Sustainable Development Program.

The protocol was signed on 26 October 2023 by 56 subscribers offering their commitment to:

- apply the principle of sustainable development in their economic, social and environmental dimensions,
- contribute to the sustainability objectives of the program
- formulate proposals for regional policies and take part in consultations conducted by the Region for participatory programming.

Below are reported, by way of example, some of the commitments undertaken for the current year that are most closely related to the CE.

Support to circular supply chain support of battery
Lombardy Association of Industries

The aim of the initiative is to promote the creation of a supply chain on the circularity of electric vehicle batteries. Lombardy Association of Industries will identify the actors who can be part of the circular supply chain and will set up tables to intercept the needs and requirements as well as possible support measures

Solutions for the territorial deployment of the circular economy with a focus on plastic waste streams
LE2C

Definition of new protocols and standards for the collection and sorting of plastic waste, the development of new recycling technologies and practices and the creation of circular solutions for product design

Training on sustainable development
Lombard General Labour Union

The aim is to raise awareness among union delegates on CE through targeted training courses, leading to a reduction in waste and a decrease in waste production

Strategic Community for Circular Economy
AFIL

- The aim is to create an active community on CE topics in the advanced manufacturing sector to promote innovation, share best practices and seize funding opportunities

The efficiency of the regional strategy to drive the circular and sustainable transition can be described not only at a general level but also on specific topics:

1. Actions to improve waste management efficiency in the Lombardy region are summarised in the programmatic document “*Waste management and remediation in Lombardy Region Plan – Toward the Circular Economy*” as described in paragraph in **3.9.1.1 Efficient waste and water management**.
2. Similarly, “*Water Protection Plan*” aim to strategic planning of action for qualitative and quantitative protection of waters (see paragraph **9.3.1.3 Territorial exploitation level**).

3. “Waste Prevention Program 2022 – 2027” [180] defines objectives and actions to reduce waste production. In particular, it focuses on the following lines of intervention: (i) Prevention of food waste, (ii) Promotion of reuse, (iii) Prevention of single-use and plastics and (iv) Industrial symbiosis and by-products.

In conclusion, Lombardy excels in a holistic approach, with highly defined long-term objectives and unwavering political commitment. **Holistic approach can be evaluated as excellent (score 5)**

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the holistic regional systemic approach.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<i>No barrier or challenge has been identified</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Public stakeholders are very sensitive on CE issues ○ Active involvement of private stakeholders ○ Existence of clear and defined programmatic objectives
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Expand the network of collaboration at national level 	

3.9.4 Policy & regulatory dimension

The analysis of policy & regulation elements in the Lombardy Region showed an uneven situation: on one hand the implementation of a specific Circular Economy Action Plan is excellent, but on the other hand improvements are needed on other elements such as Secondary raw materials market and Effective implementation of the existing legislation. Overall evaluation of policy & regulatory dimension was **3.75** as average of the 4 elements considered.

The spider chart in Figure 38 summarizes the evaluations on each single aspect; the specific aspects are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 38 - Policy & regulatory global evaluation in Lombardy

3.9.4.1 Circular Economy Action Plan

Lombardy Region implemented a systemic strategic approach to move towards a circular system with the publication of the “**Lombardy Roadmap for Research and Innovation on Circular Economy**” [181]. It intends to provide a framework for the development of a sustainable, low carbon, resource efficient and competitive strategy for the transition to a more Circular Economy in the Lombardy Region, under a smart specialization perspective. This Roadmap also contributed to the definition of the Smart Specialization Strategy of the Lombardy Region 2021-2027, within which the achieved results in terms of Circular Economy will also be valued [182].

The Lombardy Roadmap for Research and Innovation on Circular Economy represents a versatile cultural and technical reference that can stimulate the cooperation between public and private stakeholders, with the aim to build strategic initiatives on Circular Economy. Based on the priorities of the roadmap, widely shared among regional stakeholders, private and public investors can cooperate to support emerging initiatives with financing instruments.

The elaboration of this roadmap started in 2019, seeking the challenge of Lombardy’s Smart Specialization Strategy to give answers and, where possible, anticipate market changes, to address new social and cultural needs.

In particular, Circular Economy has been introduced as one of the main drivers to foster the development of mature into emerging industry in the Region. Accordingly, the Roadmap has been recognised as an opportunity to define a structured strategy to boost Circular Economy in the region starting from the needs and the priorities collaboratively pointed out by diverse regional stakeholders.

Going beyond the regional dimension, the document is well suited as a reaction of Lombardy Region Government to the climate and environmental world challenges settled by ONU

Agenda 2030 and to drive the sustainable transition on the territory. It is also the result of the long-lasting effort of Lombardy Region to cooperate with other Italian and European Regions in the definition of cooperation strategies, which reinforce regional competitiveness by exploiting synergies and complementarities to achieve wider critical mass for global competition (for example in the “4 Motors of Europe”, “Vanguard Initiative”, “S3 Platforms on Smart Specialization” of the European Commission). Thus, the implementation of roadmap priorities leads to the reinforcement of inter-regional cooperation for the establishment of new European value chains.

Moreover, the roadmap includes the lessons learnt from the COVID-19 emergency that generated tremendous impacts globally and, in particular, in Lombardy Region. Such a crisis showed that R&I, coupled with the flexibility and entrepreneurial vocation of companies, can be the major response to face the challenges of this type of disruptive unpredictable events. Circular Economy can play an important role in these situations and the roadmap highlights some specific priorities to be pursued to make the regional system more robust, resilient, and faster in the economy restarting phase.

This document, which was realized in close cooperation with the Lombardy Technology Clusters as organizations supporting regional governance, is supposed to significantly influence national policies, being Lombardy the first Region in terms of contribution to Italian Manufacturing volume and performance.

Lombardy Region is following the path of sustainable development reacting through its own legislative framework and supporting the measures targeting new market opportunities and emerging social needs for a smarter and safer territory.

This road mapping initiative, activated by Lombardy Region as a cross-sectorial action involving multiple directorates and stakeholders, was launched by DG Research with the need to complement the S3 with transversal key approaches.

The Road mapping Group was led and coordinated by the Research section of Lombardy Region, AFIL and Finlombarda, the regional finance in-house company. Representatives of the 9 Lombardy Technological Clusters participated in the road mapping process, represented the priorities of their specialization areas and invited also their key stakeholders (companies, universities and research bodies) to suggest new or confirm the identified priorities. Thus, the definition of the Regional Circular Economy Roadmap is based on a relevant inter-cluster cooperation process.

In conclusion, Lombardy implemented a comprehensive strategy with a clear roadmap, action agenda, identification of key actors and drivers, and analysis of benefits and challenges. **The policy and regulatory dimensions related to the Circular Economy Action Plan is so evaluated as excellent (score 5).**

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the existence of a Circular Economy Action Plan.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<i>No barrier or challenge has been identified</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Strong cooperation between public and private stakeholders (through the structure of technology clusters)

Actions

- Support cooperation with other Regions and/or at national level
- Integration of needs from different sectors

3.9.4.2 Regulatory instruments adopted

Lombardy Region implemented, with the resolution of the Council of 26 May 2020 [183], a specific “**Regional Action Plan for green procurement**” [184] with the aim of promoting the **APPLICATION OF GREEN PROCUREMENT** in the regional territory.

The Green Procurement Plan (GPP) is based on national and international guidelines and is applied at all sectors of the Regional Administration and at the bodies and contracting stations active in the Lombardy territory but more in general at all stakeholders with the aim of promoting the culture of sustainable consumption.

Through 6 operational objectives and 4 lines of action, the *Regional Action Plan for green procurement* aims to improve the sustainability of the Lombardy Region and the broader the GPP application through the improvement of knowledge and skills.

To date, the Lombardy Region’s tenders take into account energy efficiency and environmental sustainability criteria (both through minimum environmental access criteria and through non-mandatory technical reward criteria).

According to the above criteria, the following suppliers have already been selected:

- interior furnishings
- printer cartridges
- paper in reams
- stationery products
- collective catering and foodstuffs
- laundry service
- armed and unarmed security
- disposal of medical waste
- facility management
- plant maintenance
- electricity
- travel agency service

Lombardy Region has a specific regional company for innovation and purchasing (ARIA <https://www.ariaspa.it/wps/portal/Aria/Home>). Its objectives include the creation of innovative procurement with an ever-increasing focus on the issues of environmental and social sustainability of purchases. In this perspective, it promotes and implements GPP at three different levels: (i) planning and implementation of sustainable purchases through aggregated tenders; (ii) relationship with stakeholders and (iii) internal organizational processes.

The commitment to orienting towards sustainable production and consumption has earned the Company an important recognition within the Compraverde Buygreen 2024 Forum: ARIA obtained a special mention for the GPP policy with the following motivation: “*For the inclusion of green purchases in the activities of the central purchasing body with in-depth*

courses for the benefit of the demand of the Public Administration, the supply of the market and the needs of Citizens and Businesses”.

There is no updated information on the percentage of contracts carried out in compliance with GPP policies but, according to a 2019 ISTAT statistic [185], Lombardy stands at values very close to the Italian average with the specific percentages for each sector reported in Table 34.

Table 34 – Public procurement carried out in Lombardy according to GPP policies
Source: ISTAT, 2019

Sector	%
Electronic equipment	36.2
Furniture	9.9
Stationery	44.8
Building cleaning	29.6
Energy services	33.4
Building materials	8.8
Textile products	2.9
Urban services	16.4
Catering	24.0
Transport	6.3
Urban waste management	31.5

In addition, it is worth to notice that Lombardy Region has also participated in the GPP4GROWTH Project (<https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/gpp4growth/>), approved under the European program InterregEurope 2014/2020, with the aim of promoting and increasing green purchasing in Lombardy through the exchange of experiences, the harmonization of processes and the analysis of technical-scientific evaluation tools.

Summarizing, Lombardy supports the adoption of green procurement practices so the **element “Regulatory instruments adopted” is evaluated ad good (score 4).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the adoption of regulatory instruments.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Companies must innovate (and sustain investments) to meet GPP requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ GPP represents an opportunity for companies in terms of pushing for technological innovation as it provides for the direct involvement of Lombard companies in increasing knowledge and awareness on the topics ○ The “virtuous” behaviour of the Public Administration can represent a driving example to induce changes in the consumption patterns of citizens and businesses towards greater environmental sustainability.

Actions

- GPP policies should include not only environmental aspects but also social and ethical aspects such as the recognition of a fair wage, the avoidance of child labor, worker safety and healthy working environments.
- Actions dedicated to communication, awareness and dissemination towards the population.

3.9.4.3 Secondary raw materials market

The concept of a secondary raw materials market aligns closely with the EU's Green Taxonomy, emphasizing the certification, valorisation and standardization of recycled materials to ensure compliance with environmental and safety standards.

In Lombardy, while no regional-specific regulations currently exist, national and EU frameworks provide a robust basis for fostering this market.

At the European level, **Directive 2008/98/EC** [186] introduced the concept of by-products, promoting waste as a resource and positioning disposal as a last resort in waste management. In Italy, this directive has been transposed into national law, yet challenges in its practical implementation remain. To address these, Italy enacted **Decree No. 264 of October 13, 2016** [187], along with an explanatory circular. However, the decree excludes by-products of animal origin, which are subject to separate regulations. Overcoming these challenges and promoting replicable industrial symbiosis practices are critical to advancing the Circular Economy in sectors such as food.

For recycled plastics, **Regulation (EU) 2022/1616** [188] provides specific guidelines for materials intended to come into contact with food, ensuring their safety and encouraging their integration into new applications. Regulation (EU) 2022/1616 aims to strengthen the resilience of critical sectors like energy, transport, and digital infrastructure. It establishes requirements for risk management, incident reporting, and cross-border cooperation to ensure continuity of essential services and enhance EU preparedness against disruptions.

The "**Lombardy Roadmap for Research and Innovation on Circular Economy**," as discussed in paragraph 3.9.4.1 "**Circular Economy Action Plan**", outlines three key Strategic Research & Innovation Priorities aimed at advancing CE practices in the region. These priorities are pivotal in shaping the future of sustainable production and consumption within Lombardy, and they align with broader European initiatives that drive innovation in the field of Circular Economy. Priorities are:

- *A.1.2 Design targeted to increase the percentage of secondary raw materials in new products*
- *A.2.3 Enhanced process robustness and flexibility for reusing components and materials from post-use products as production inputs for new products*
- *F.1.5 New recycling and recovery technologies.*

From a technical point of view, secondary raw materials and production waste often exhibit higher variability in properties, such as mechanical strength, contamination levels, and

colour, compared to virgin materials. Addressing this variability requires robust and flexible manufacturing systems capable of adapting to mixed input flows. Scalable technologies, combined with advanced inspection, tracking, and labelling systems, are critical enablers. So, hardware innovations, such as flexible production equipment and sensors, and software solutions, including downstream compensation and cyber-physical systems, could facilitate closed-loop manufacturing and circular value chains in Lombardy.

The profitability of recycling systems in Lombardy depends heavily on the quality, volume, and value of recovered materials.

Lombardy's transition toward a Circular Economy and the establishment of a secondary raw materials market requires targeted actions to address existing barriers. By leveraging legislative tools, promoting innovation in design and recycling technologies, and enhancing process adaptability, the region can unlock the full potential of secondary materials. **The policy and regulatory dimensions related to the secondary raw materials market is then evaluated as neutral (score 3).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the secondary raw materials market.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Variability in the quality and return flows of recovered raw materials. ○ Lack of certification protocols for secondary raw materials. ○ Inadequate standardization and characterization techniques for secondary raw materials. ○ Higher recovery costs of materials and the perception of lower quality for circular products compared to conventional ones. ○ Production technologies are not always sufficiently robust or flexible to manage the variability of mixed and secondary material flows. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Legislative support (e.g., eco-design directive, GPP criteria). ○ Innovative design methods to assess the impact of secondary materials on performance. ○ Production systems that adapt to material variability (hardware: sensors, flexible equipment; software: compensation, cyber-physical systems).
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Co-design methodologies for products with significant secondary material content. ○ Fast design and certification technologies for circular products. ○ Building a market network for secondary raw materials, ensuring quality and compliance. ○ Customized marketing and pricing strategies to boost competitiveness. ○ Promoting short value chains for local flow of secondary materials and sustainable products. ○ Push the manufacturers to recognize the value of reusing materials instead of landfilling, incinerating, or downcycling them. 	

3.9.4.4 *Effective implementation of the existing legislation*

As emerged during the working group with regional stakeholders, the implementation of environmental legislation in Lombardy, particularly in relation to waste management and Circular Economy practices, demonstrates a strong commitment to achieving desired outcomes while minimizing bureaucratic hurdles. While national and EU legislation, such as the *Legislative Decree 152/2006* (also known as Environmental Code), regulates waste recycling and generation of secondary raw materials (“*end of waste*”), practical challenges remain in its application. Notably, some “*end of waste*” material area not fully regulated at the national or EU level, requiring a complex, case-by-case authorization process, which can be both time-consuming and cumbersome. To address these issues, Lombardy Region has proactively supported businesses through the establishment of specific guidelines.

In addition, Lombardy promotes the use of recycled raw materials through Green Public Procurement, an environmental policy tool designed to foster the development of a market for products and services with a reduced environmental impact.

Lombardy stands out as a model of territorial aggregation for waste management. The EU and national frameworks encourage regional authorities to identify optimal territorial areas for uniform waste management practices. In Lombardy, however, these optimal territorial units have emerged organically, thanks to the voluntary aggregation of municipalities and the creation of large waste management centres.

Furthermore, Lombardy has made significant strides in aligning with the EU’s STEP regulation, which supports strategic technologies, including biotechnologies aimed at environmental sustainability. Through the reallocation of resources in the ERDF (European Regional Development Fund), Lombardy has secured €120 million for projects that promote sustainability and technological innovation. This commitment underscores the region’s dedication to addressing key environmental challenges while fostering economic development.

An exemplary implementation of existing legislation in Lombardy is the application of the Gadda Law (Law No. 166/2016), which encourages the reduction of food waste and promotes food recovery. One of the most successful initiatives under this law is the “*Io Non Spreco*” (I Don’t Waste) project, managed by Milano Ristorazione, the company responsible for providing school meals in the city (see **3.5.1.2. Management of wastes from catering sector**).

Continued investment in waste management practices, territorial aggregation and sustainable technological development will be crucial in ensuring the long-term success of Lombardy’s environmental policies. **The policy and regulatory dimensions related to the effective implementation of the existing legislation is so evaluated as moderate (score 3).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the effective implementation of the existing legislation.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Complex authorization processes (e.g., for “end of waste” materials) ○ Limited scope of some regulations (e.g., regulatory gaps for certain waste streams) ○ Insufficient local financial support (e.g., lack of state aid interventions for large enterprises, which could drive market momentum and indirectly benefit SMEs) ○ Administrative burden and lack of harmonization (e.g., bureaucratic complexity in GPP). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Proactive regional guidelines ○ Successful GPP initiatives ○ Territorial aggregation for waste management ○ Legislative support for food waste reduction (e.g., the Gadda Law and the “Io Non Spreco” project) ○ Commitment to technological innovation (e.g., regional implementation of the EU’s STEP regulation).
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Streamline authorization processes (e.g., clearer regulations and fewer bureaucratic steps for “end of waste” materials) ○ Incentivize municipalities to implement the system (e.g., expand the adoption of variable waste tariffs) ○ Increase local financial interventions for the enterprises ○ Reduce administrative burdens and improve coherence in procurement practices ○ Broaden the scope of food waste reduction initiatives. 	

3.9.5 Funding & financial elements dimension

From the analysis of the Funding & Financial elements, the need for substantial improvements in the Lombardy Region emerges, in particular with regards to the use of economic instruments for incentivizing or discouraging specific behaviours and the adequate disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities at regional/local level.

Overall evaluation of policy & regulatory dimension was **3.3** as average of the 3 elements considered.

The spider chart in Figure 39 summarizes the evaluations on each single aspect; the specific aspects are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 39 - Funding & financial elements global evaluation in Lombardy

3.9.5.1 Specific financial lines for Circular Economy projects

Lombardy Region actively supports Circular Economy initiatives through dedicated financial instruments and funding channels, established both within its governance and in alignment with broader EU and national frameworks (a not exhaustive list of financial instruments related to CE initiatives and active in 2024 is reported in Table 35).

In general, and in line with stakeholders' point of view, key funding mechanisms include the allocation of EU structural funds, delivered as grants, subsidized loans, or investments through venture capitalists pre-selected by the region. Importantly, the financial resources are derived not only from current EU programming but also from reinvestment funds (returns from subsidized loans) that operate under fewer constraints in terms of accountability and alignment with specific EU objectives (FESR). This flexible funding structure allows for cross-sectoral financing of Circular Economy projects in manufacturing, food, and high science industries. However, it also highlights a critical gap: the lack of structured, value-chain-specific initiatives, which limits the systemic integration of Circular Economy principles across industrial sectors.

In alignment with the 2021–2027 EU programming, Circular Economy now benefits from a dedicated objective for the first time. Within this context, Lombardy has launched the “*Ri-circolo*” funding calls, strategically designed to address key challenges:

1. The first *Ri-circolo call*, targeting SMEs in the textile plastics sector, attracted 68 applications requesting €8 million in grants [189].
2. A second ongoing *Ri-circolo call* supports local authorities in prevention initiatives, including the creation of hubs and solidarity emporiums, reuse centres, waste prevention in canteens, and specialized waste collection systems [190].
3. A third *Ri-circolo call* is under development, backed by €10 million under the STEP reprogramming objective, to recover critical raw materials such as phosphorus for

fertilizers and valuable components from end-of-life batteries and WEEE (Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment).

Future funding calls will focus on additional supply chains, including construction and demolition waste, organic waste, and food waste reduction, demonstrating Lombardy's long-term commitment to advancing Circular Economy goals. Notably, during the previous 2017–2021 programming cycle, similar initiatives were implemented, including funding for food waste reduction projects and reuse centres, leveraging resources generated from eco-tax revenues.

Additionally, Lombardy's Circular Economy research benefits from external funding sources, such as Fondazione Cariplo, which for example, supported in the recent period two major regional projects: one focused on WEEE valorisation (*Re Tech Life* - <https://ambienteoccupazione.retechlife.com/>) and another on the recycling of plastics and lithium-ion batteries (*Tech4lib*).

Table 35 – Main calls related to Circular Economy in the Lombardy region active in 2024

Call title	Funding body	Beneficiaries	Type of financial intervention	Sector
<i>RI.CIRCO.LO</i> : call for Lombardy SMEs to develop circular economy actions.	Lombardy Region	Regional SMEs	Non-repayable fund (max 50% and max 300.000€)	Plastic and textile supply chains
Investment Package (<i>Green line</i>)	Lombardy Region	Regional SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fee regional guarantee • Non-repayable capital contribution (max 3.000.000€) 	Energy efficiency of production facilities in all sectors
Call for Environmental Sustainability (<i>AGEF 2406</i>)	Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Crafts and Agriculture of Brescia	MSMEs in the province of Brescia	Non-repayable fund (max 50% and max 5.000€)	Services and expert advice on environmental sustainability in all sectors
<i>Bando SI4.0 2024</i> - Support the development of digital 4.0 technologies by SMEs in a dual digital and ecological transition.	Unioncamere Lombardia	MSMEs in Lombardy	Non-repayable fund (max 50% and max 30.000€)	All sectors
Call for Renewable Energy Communities (<i>RECs</i>)	Chamber of Commerce of Cremona	RECs in the province of Cremona	Non-repayable fund (100% and max 12.500€)	Renewable Energy Communities
<i>Call – Chimica verde Lombardia per un futuro sostenibile 2024</i>	Lombardy Region	Aspiring entrepreneurs, start-ups, innovative SMEs	Award of six prizes of 25.000€ euros	Chemical sector and chemical user sectors

Training for business development in the double transition: digital and ecological	Chamber of Commerce of Varese	Self-employed and employees of MSMEs in the province of Varese	Non-repayable fund (50% and max 5.000€)	All sectors
<i>Impresa sostenibile: Investimenti linea energia 2024</i> – support for the investments by SMEs aimed at greater sustainability and energy efficiency.	Chambers of Commerce of Milan, Monza-Brianza and Lodi	SMEs in the province of Milano, Monza-Brianza and Lodi	Non-repayable fund (50% and max 40.000€)	All sectors
Basket Bond Filiere Lombardia – support for the strengthening of business networks and aggregations, and the adoption of sustainable production models	Lombardy Region	Aggregation of SMEs in Lombardy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guarantee covering 100% of first losses up to 25% of each minibond portfolio value A grant for structuring and issuance costs of minibond 	All sectors
Measure for the transition of Lombardy's SMEs towards circular and sustainable production models	Lombardy Region	Aggregation of MSMEs in Lombardy	Non-repayable fund (60% and max 300.000€)	All sectors
Measure for strengthening production chains and industrial ecosystems	Lombardy Region	Aggregation of enterprises in Lombardy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subsidised financing of up to 60% (maximum 2.500.000€) Non-repayable grant of up to 10% 	All sectors
Greentech and Circular Economy Innovation	Eni	Start-ups and innovative SMEs – national and international	Support to the development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Refinery waste management Contaminant remediation Energy system efficiency in highly complex industrial contexts

In conclusion, Lombardy demonstrates a robust commitment to supporting Circular Economy initiatives through structured financial channels and innovative funding programs. By integrating cross-sectoral funding strategies, aligning with EU objectives, and fostering collaboration with regional research clusters (contributing to the identification of supply chains), the region creates a fertile ecosystem for the advancement of Circular Economy principles. However, opportunities remain to address value-chain-specific gaps and ensure systemic, long-term impacts through more structured and targeted financial interventions. **The funding & financial elements dimension related to the specific financial lines for Circular Economy projects is so evaluated as good (score 4).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the existence of specific financial lines for Circular Economy projects.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Limited punctual scope of Circular Economy funding in the agri-food sector ○ Highly specialized interventions (narrow eligibility criteria and focus) ○ Rigid timelines and stringent requirements (administrative and reporting constraints) ○ Low visibility of funding opportunities (insufficient outreach to potential beneficiaries). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Existence of clear funding guidelines (facilitating participation and compliance) ○ Effective communication strategies for issued calls (enhancing awareness and outreach) ○ Organization of seminars to present funding opportunities (providing guidance and clarifications) ○ Regular engagement between regional authorities and stakeholders (ensuring dissemination of calls and opportunities).
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Post-call evaluation and feedback sessions to identify areas for future improvement ○ Early stakeholder involvement in the planning of funding programs ○ Simplification of funding processes (reducing bureaucratic burdens and enhancing accessibility) 	

3.9.5.2 Use of economic instruments for incentivizing or discouraging specific behaviours

In addition to specific financing tools and financial support for recycling (such as “Ri.Circo.lo call described in the previous paragraph **3.9.5.1 Specific financial lines for Circular Economy projects**”, the main instrument for incentivizing positive behaviours toward CE is the **PAY-AS-YOU-THROW** (PAYT) system for urban wastes taxes.

As previous anticipated, punctual pricing is applied both to citizens (see **3.9.2.6 Circular Economy citizenship participation**) and restaurants (see **3.5.1.2 Management of wastes from catering sector**).

However, the implementation of this system still needs improvement. As also underlined by the public stakeholders involved during the working group, it is necessary that the PAYT system is more widespread among the municipalities of Lombardy.

According to ARPA data, in 2021 the “pay-as-you-throw” system was implemented in 171 Lombard municipalities (11.4%), equal to 1.257.271 inhabitants. In addition, there are at least 30 other municipalities adopting systems that are not strictly of measurement and punctual pricing, but of limits on the delivery of bags for undifferentiated waste, beyond which the user must pay a variable fee to buy more (prepaid bags).

The following Figure 40 shows the number of Lombard municipalities adopting, from 2015 to 2021, the pay-as-you-throw system: the most virtuous province is Mantova with 45 municipalities in 2021, followed by Bergamo and Brescia with 43 and 42 municipalities, respectively.

Figure 40 – Lombardy municipalities with pay-as-you-throw system
Source: Legambiente, 2022

An additional system of incentives for positive behaviours is linked to the **SOCIAL ASPECT OF FOOD WASTE RECOVERY**. Commercial activities that produce and/or distribute food products and that directly or indirectly give their surpluses to people in need are granted a reduction in the variable part of the tariff. This reduction will be established annually with the resolution approving the TARI tariffs and may be up to 50% of the variable part: for example, in 2018 and 2019, the municipality of Milan established a 20% reduction in the variable part. The reduction applies to the premises where production begins, or the goods are distributed and is calculated in proportion to the quantities actually given and compared to the quantities of waste produced. The reduction is applied as a balancing and is subject to certain obligations. To support restaurants and commercial activities, the “*Volunteer Service Center of Milan*” in collaboration with the association of accountants also developed a guide to the requirements and tax breaks for those who donate excess food [191].

In 2021 Lombardy Region published a call for proposals to support non-profit organizations in purchasing instrumental equipment for the recovery and distribution of food surpluses for social solidarity purposes. For example, eligible expenses are isothermal and/or refrigerated vehicles, blast chillers, isothermal containers for transporting food, thermal food trolleys, cold storage rooms, hardware and software for recording donated food, kitchen equipment for food processing, instruments for measuring food temperature [192].

In conclusion, in Lombardy Region the use of economic instruments to incentivise behaviour related to Circular Economy objectives is moderate: tax incentives, subsidies or differentiated tariffs are in place but are limited to a still insufficient number of municipalities. So, **the element related to the use of economic instruments for incentivizing or discouraging specific behaviours is evaluated as moderate (score 3).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the use of economic instruments for incentivizing or discouraging specific behaviours.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Technical, technological and economic difficulties in applying PAYT system (difficulty in quantifying waste from each user) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Great response from citizens and restaurateurs ○ Effective information campaigns
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase the number of municipalities applying the PAYT system 	

3.9.5.3 *Adequate disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities at regional/local level*

Disclosure of funding opportunities in Lombardy Region encompasses both digital platforms and physical events.

A cornerstone of Lombardy’s dissemination strategy is the “**Bandi e Servizi**” platform (<https://www.bandi.regione.lombardia.it/servizi/home>), an online service designed to simplify access to funding opportunities for citizens, businesses, and public or private entities. The platform allows users to consult funding calls financed by regional, national, and European funds, submit applications online, and monitor their status throughout the process.

Key features include the ability to personalize notifications by selecting areas of interest, ensuring that users receive timely updates on relevant funding opportunities. To access the service, users must register, gaining access to a personalized information space tailored to their needs. This centralized, user-friendly platform enhances transparency and accessibility, empowering stakeholders to engage effectively with funding initiatives [193].

Lombardy further strengthens its coordination of funding opportunities through a series of in-person events aimed at engaging diverse stakeholders. One prominent initiative is the PR FESR 2021-2027 Tour, launched to present funding opportunities under the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) program, which allocates €2 billion to foster sustainable growth and competitiveness in the region [194].

Starting in November 2023 in Erba (CO) and continuing across several provinces in 2024, this tour featured tailored presentations for local stakeholders, for potential beneficiaries and more in general for the public. This decentralized approach ensures that funding information reaches even the most remote areas of the region, fostering inclusivity and encouraging participation across all sectors.

By combining accessible digital tools with targeted physical outreach, Lombardy has the potential to establish a strong foundation for the effective disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities. Indeed, these efforts not only can enhance transparency but also promote collaboration and alignment among stakeholders, laying the groundwork for the successful implementation of CE projects and sustainable regional development.

However, insights gathered from the working group have highlighted areas for improvement, particularly regarding the visibility of funding calls. Stakeholders have pointed out the need for enhanced publicity to ensure broader awareness and engagement with funding opportunities. Additionally, a critical issue has been identified in the alignment between the management of regional and national funds. This misalignment, especially in the context of policies and regulations governing fund distribution, poses a challenge that could hinder the efficient and seamless flow of resources to projects.

In conclusion, Lombardy demonstrates a commitment to provide a good dissemination framework for funding opportunities. However, issues were identified in the alignment of fund management and call visibility. **The funding & financial elements dimension related to the adequate disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities at regional/local level is so evaluated as moderated (score 3).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the adequate disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities at regional/local level.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lack of direct engagement with businesses at the local level ○ Insufficient visibility of funding calls (limited awareness among stakeholders) ○ Misalignment between the management of regional and national funding streams, creating inefficiencies ○ Challenges in coordinating funding initiatives at the national level. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Centralized online platform offering streamlined access to funding calls, notifications, and updates ○ Physical events enhancing stakeholder engagement and geographic coverage ○ Collaboration with local entities and authorities, providing localized insights and support.
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increase the frequency and geographic reach of physical dissemination events to enhance visibility and participation ○ Utilize non-institutional channels (e.g., clusters, business associations) to better reach companies and stakeholders at the local level. ○ Foster alignment between regional and national funding management ○ Facilitate stakeholder feedback mechanisms (e.g., post-event surveys) to refine dissemination strategies and address gaps in coordination. 	

3.9.6 Technology, research & innovation dimension

Overall evaluation of Technology, research & innovation dimension was 3.8 as average of the 6 elements considered but a wide range of values has been attributed to each single element: Lombardy Region excels in terms of available technologies and participation of SMEs in R&I activities but on the other hand great improvements are necessary in terms of traceability of secondary raw materials.

The spider chart in Figure 41 summarizes the evaluations on each single aspect; the specific aspects are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 41 – Technology, research & innovation dimension global evaluation in Lombardy

3.9.6.1 Availability of valorisation technologies

As previously described, Lombardy is the main Italian industrial region with great technological maturity and large availability of technologies.

As examples of **AVAILABILITY OF VALORISATION TECHNOLOGIES** for CE application, we can take into account circular value chains analysed in the Agro2Circular project: namely horticultural waste and plastics waste.

A mapping of technological providers for the valorisation of biological waste from horticulture is reported at paragraph 3.3.6 “**Mapping of technological providers**”: 8 different technological providers for biomolecules extraction and cosmetic / nutraceutical applications were identified in Lombardy.

On the other hand, to identify the Lombard technology providers operating in the end-of-life treatments of plastics (collection, classification, mechanical recycling, energy recovering) we can take advantage of the “*Report on the state-of-play of the plastic sector*” published by the **Plastix project** (https://www.interregeurope.eu/sites/default/files/2023-12/State-of-play_PLASTIX_final.pdf). Following Table 36 reports 12 operators were identified in the

whole plastic sector, so it offers a broader view than the technological situation analysed in the paragraph 3.5.1.3. **Management of plastic wastes from the agricultural sector** and related only to the management of agroplastics.

Table 36 – Lombard technology providers operating in the end-of-life treatments of plastics

Technological provider	Location	Operating sector
Erion https://erion.it/it/	Milan	They provide regulatory and technical support to the management of different types of waste (for example electronic products, batteries, packaging, tobacco products and textiles).
European Recycling Platform https://erp-recycling.org/it-it/	Cassina De' Pecchi (MI)	The activity is related to the collection, recovery and recycling of waste from electrical and electronic equipment, batteries, batteries, accumulators exhausted.
Coripet https://coripet.it/	Milan	It is a voluntary non-profit consortium: it collects used PET bottles and sends them for recycling to generate the secondary raw material (rPET) used to produce new bottles.
Caldara plast https://www.caldara.it/	Erba near Como	Its core business is plastic waste recovery and extrusion of technopolymer compounds
Corepla https://www.corepla.it/	Milan	It is the National Consortium for the Collection, Recycling and Recovery of Plastic Packaging with headquarters in Milan and 2.456 consortium companies throughout Italy; it is a non-profit organization bringing together companies along the whole packaging supply chain (collection, selection, recycling, research and development, energy recovery, communication).
Syncro Group https://syncro-group.com/it/	Busto Artizio near Varese	Syncro Group is a holding of six complementary companies that operate in the automation sector of plastics production lines and together they synergize to close the circle of the Circular Economy.
ICMA San Giorgio https://www.icmasq.com/it/	San Giorgio sul Legnano near Milan	It produces extrusion and compounding plants, also dedicated to the ecological transition.
Simap https://www.simapsrl.com/	Albino near Bergamo	It offers solutions for the management of plastic materials production scrap: it handles uptake and transport followed by upgrading to produce secondary raw materials for use in new manufacturing cycles.
Foreverplast https://www.foreverplast.it/	Lograto near Brescia	It deals with the recycling of high-density polyethylene, polypropylene and polystyrene to allow their reuse in new finished products.
Valli gestioni ambientali https://www.valli-ambiente.it/	Gorlano near Bergamo	It operates two waste storage and disposal plants for plastic recycling.
Mirex https://www.mirexspa.com/	Bellusco near Monza	It is specialized in the recovery, collection and grinding of plastic waste derived from industrial processes such as moulding, blowing, thermoforming and extrusion products.

To the previous list of providers, it also is useful to add **Breplast** (<https://breplast.it/>) located in Emilia Romagna (in the province of Pavia) but very close to the Lombardy region with easy geographical and commercial connections. It is a company specialized in extruded and printed products in high density polyethylene completely recycled from separate waste collection.

Also, in terms of **RESEARCH AND/OR TECHNOLOGICAL CENTRES ORIENTED TO CE** a large availability is noticeable in Lombardy. Following a couple relevant examples:

- **Circular Economy Lab** located in Milan is a training and network generation hub. In a logic of open and inclusive innovation, it aims to involve large companies and transformative agents, such as startups, innovative SMEs, universities, research centers, technology transfer centers. The mission is to support local companies in designing a “*Circular Journey*”, a path of intervention starting from the acquisition of skills and awareness in the Circular Economy field and continuing with the identification of an innovation path thanks to targeted projects and constant support. (<https://www.circulareconomylab.it/content/circularEconomy/it.html>).
- Bicocca University of Milan organized a **Circular Economy Laboratory** within the Research Centre in Economics and Regulation of Services, Industry and the Public Sector. It is a reference point for actors operating in the waste management sector and for the scientific community. It is a working group including some of the most important Italian industrial, financial and associative entities. The Circular Economy Laboratory focuses on sustainability and CE with particular emphasis on waste management (<https://www.diseade.unimib.it/it/ricerca/centri-ricerca/cesisp>).
- The **Institute of Chemical Sciences and Technologies “Giulio Natta”** (SCITEC) of the National Research Council (CNR) with headquarters in Milan is part of the Department of Chemical Sciences and Materials Technologies (<https://www.scitec.cnr.it/>). It addresses aspects of sustainability with particular reference to the Circular Economy by developing/formulating new materials and processes for the recycling of biomass and polymer waste.

In Lombardy there is an excellent implementation of valorisation technologies and related support structures (score 5): the region excels in providing comprehensive and advanced technologies, tools, and infrastructures for the valorisation of waste and by-products. And numerous private and public research centres dedicated to CE offer extensive and well-coordinated services to companies.

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the availability of valorisation technologies.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
No barrier or challenge has been identified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Great technological maturity and large availability of technologies
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fostering connections between providers to create circular value chains 	

3.9.6.2 Public investment in R+D+I

To analyse the element of public investment in R+D+I three aspects can be taken into account: (i) presence of public universities and research centres with chairs/departments in the field of Circular Economy, (ii) public stimulation of demand for R+D results through tenders, pre-procurement and pre-procurement mechanisms, and (iii) level of implementation of pilot cases through public calls for projects.

Lombardy hosts a variety of **PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES AND RESEARCH CENTRES ENGAGED IN CIRCULAR ECONOMY INITIATIVES** (Table 37). These institutions offer specialized courses and research programs, fostering innovation and providing a foundation for academic and industrial collaboration.

Table 37 Overview of departments with academic programmes on sustainability and the circular economy in Lombardy.

Department	University
Department of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences	University of Milan
Faculty of Economics and Law	“Sacro Cuore” University in Piacenza
Department of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences	University of Milan
Department of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences	University of Milan
Department of Environmental Science and Policy	University of Milan
Department of Biotechnology and Biosciences	University of Milan
Faculty of Agricultural, Food, and Environmental Sciences	“Sacro Cuore” University in Piacenza
Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering	Polytechnic of Milan
Service and Consulting Center at Politecnico di Milano	Polytechnic of Milan
Department of Biotechnology and Biosciences	Bicocca University

Lombardy also stands out as a pioneer in implementing **PRE-COMMERCIAL PROCUREMENT** (PCP) mechanisms to stimulate innovation [195]. This approach, rooted in European directives, allows public entities to procure services related to applied research and experimental development without exclusivity. The PCP process involves shared risk and benefits under market conditions, enabling multiple enterprises to concurrently develop innovative solutions tailored to public sector challenges.

Key highlights of Lombardy’s PCP system include:

- Launch of Italy’s first pilot PCP in 2013, emphasizing the region’s role as an “intelligent client” and “co-innovator.”
- Introduction of regional legislation (*Law 29/2016, Art. 2, Paragraph IV* [195]) mandating a minimum allocation of 3% of annual procurement budgets towards innovative solutions and research products.
- Strategic alignment with the Green Public Procurement Action Plan, which underscores sustainable practices in public investments.

Despite these advancements, implementation remains limited, with only one notable initiative addressing automation in the healthcare sector.

Last but not least, Lombardy exhibits a vibrant ecosystem of technological innovation, marked by a proliferation of start-ups and university spin-offs. However, as emerged during the working group, public initiatives for technology transfer and scaling up remain scarce, often leaving these critical steps to private sector initiatives. Strengthening public support mechanisms for scaling innovative solutions could significantly enhance the region's R&D landscape and foster broader adoption of cutting-edge technologies.

In conclusion, in Lombardy, public investment in R+D+I demonstrates strong potential, underpinned by a robust research infrastructure and pioneering initiatives such as pre-commercial procurement. However, addressing challenges like limited technology transfer mechanisms and sectoral fragmentation is crucial to fully harness these opportunities. **The technology, research & innovation dimension of public investment in R+D+I is so evaluated as neutral (score 3).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the public investment in R+D+I

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Limited public initiatives for scaling up and technology transfer ○ Low adoption of pre-procurement mechanisms ○ Fragmentation in research-industry connections. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Robust research infrastructure and access to advanced technologies ○ Pioneering implementation of pre-commercial procurement
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Expand pre-procurement mechanisms to Circular Economy sectors ○ Enhance public funding for technology transfer (bridge the gap between research outputs and market-ready solutions) ○ Foster collaborative platforms between academia, industry, and public authorities to strengthen scaling and integration processes. 	

3.9.6.3 Research-industry connection

Active collaboration between research institutions and industry has recently led in Lombardy to the birth of numerous **SPIN-OFFS OPERATING IN THE CE SECTORS**: a not exhaustive list in following Table 38.

Table 38 – Lombardy spin-offs operating in Circular Economy sectors

Name	Location	Connection with research institutes	Main activity	Website
Ecometrics	Brescia	Università Cattolica Sacro Cuore	Environmental and territorial consultancy for sustainable management of natural resources	https://dipartimenti.unicatt.it/dmf-altre-strutture-di-ricerca-e-servizi-ecometrics
bioRestart	Pavia	Pavia University	Production of cosmetics, nutraceuticals and phytosanitary products from plant waste with a low solvent consumption extraction process (enzymatic extraction from bacterial strains)	https://dbb.dip.unipv.it/it/ricerca/innovazione-e-public-engagement/spin/biorestart
EtichHub	Pavia	Pavia University	Functional cosmetics from agricultural waste	https://www.etichub.it/
Feed From Food	Lodi	Milan University	Animal feed production from food waste	https://www.feedfromfood.com/

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In Lombardy are also present several **INCUBATORS TO SUPPORT SPIN-OFF** and promote Circular Economy projects. A couple of examples are given below:

- **Innovative contamination hub – CSMT** (<https://www.csmt.it/it>) is a sustainable innovation ecosystem located in Brescia that promotes collaboration between research and business in the fields of engineering, physics, Circular Economy and management. Main activities are related to technology transfer, project financing (support in the evaluation of innovative proposals, search for funding, at European, national and regional level, preparation of technical and administrative documentation and design and development phases), hosting spin-offs and start-ups.
- **PoliHub** (<https://polihub.it/>) is an innovation park and start-up accelerator of the Politecnico of Milan. Polihub operates a continuous scouting activity of Deep Tech projects and supports the birth and development of startups through technology management strategies, incubation paths and acceleration programs, enabling access to knowledge, the market and investors. In addition, PoliHub accompanies national and multinational companies in the Lombardy region in the exploration of new products, services and business models through collaboration with startups
- In addition, Polihub in collaboration with Politecnico of Milan and the Chamber of Commerce of Milan and Monza, organized the program **Encubator** (<https://startupencubator.com/it/home-ita/>) to accelerate the maturation of projects in the field of Climate Tech and sustainability. In particular, Encubator supports university Spinoffs or those from Italian, European and international research centres and Italian, European and international early-stage Startups, both established and not. The goal is to accelerate the energy transition towards a “carbon free” model, to make cities and the ways of moving people and goods more sustainable, to reduce all types of waste towards a circular economy model that respects the life of plants, humans and animals.

An additional parameter to evaluate the connection between industry and research aimed at the circular transition could be the implementation of **DEVOTED PhD COURSES** and in particular of executive PhD courses in collaboration between universities and private companies. The executive PhD candidate has the possibility to set up the PhD path taking into account the company vision and related trends. This seems to give guarantees regarding the research-oriented training product linked to the growth of the executive PhD, as well as, according to the conditions of collaboration, the interaction and integration between the university research of the group in which the PhD candidate is involved and the development and innovation of the company for which the PhD candidate works.

In recent years there has been a notable increase in attendance at PhD courses in Lombardy: for example, for the University of Milan alone, there has been an increase from 482 first-year students for the academic year 2019/2020 to 832 for the academic year 2023/2024 courses (Figure 39). The employment rate one year after the PhD title, for the University of Milan, has remained at levels close to 90% in the last 5 academic years.

Following some examples of PhD courses and executive PhD courses active in Lombardy and related to CE challenges:

- **PhD Management Engineering at the Polytechnic of Milan. Research Field: Circular economy and manufacturing education: challenges and approaches.** This PhD research project may seek to foster collaboration between academia, industry, and other stakeholders in the manufacturing sector. By bringing together diverse perspectives and expertise, the project aims to catalyse collective action towards achieving sustainable and circular practices within the industry [197].
- **PhD in Engineering on Sustainability and efficient use of resources in the perspective of Circular Economy for the agro-industrial sector of Lombardy.** It was born from the collaboration between ENEA, the University of Brescia and the companies of the agro-industrial sector of Lombardy and aims to train an expert in the efficient use of resources in the agro-industrial sector and at the same time carry out a feasibility study for the sustainability of this sector in the Lombardy region [198].
- **Executive PhD in Strategic Innovation for Sustainable and Smart Ecosystems** organized by the University Bicocca of Milan in collaboration with ENI, Intesa Sanpaolo, Italfarmaco and other companies [199].

Figure 42 – Number of first-year PhD students at University of Milan (in blu male and in fuchsia female)

Source: Report on PhD courses 2023, University of Milan [200]

According to the reported data **research-industry connection in Lombardy can be evaluated as good (score 4)**: spin-offs and start-ups are common, and several incubators support Circular Economy projects, PhD courses are varied and well structured, employment rates of PhDs and postdocs in industry R&D positions are high.

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning research-industry connection.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ No barriers were identified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Increasing number of Phd and Executive Phd ○ Presence of incubators
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Financial support to spin-offs ○ Promote connection between incubators operating in different sectors 	

3.9.6.4 Participation of SMEs in R+D activities

As emerged from the discussion during the Lombardy working group (see **3.8.1 Public stakeholder involvement**), a large participation of local enterprises and in particular SMEs, is observed for regional calls for research and innovation in suitability and CE. Enterprises are willing to invest in R&I and participate in the funded projects with their own share of funding.

More in general, according to the twelfth GreenItaly report, produced by the Symbola Foundation and Unioncamere [201], Lombardy is in first place in Italy in the regional ranking for the absolute number of companies that have invested in green technologies. Following Table 39 reports the specific data on a provincial scale.

Table 39 – Number of Lombard companies that invested in green technologies in 2022

Province	Number of companies
Milan	35.352
Varese	11.712
Monza	9.480
Como	7.868
Bergamo	6.598
Brescia	5.911
Pavia	2.801
Mantova	2.691
Lecco	2.403
Cremona	1.921
Sondrio	1.383
Lodi	1.244
TOT	89.784

The excellent result of the province of Milan is also confirmed on a national scale: Milan is in first place in Italy in the provincial ranking for the number of green companies.

In addition, with 265.563 contracts stipulated in green jobs, Lombardy is also at the top of the regional ranking (data 2020).

A 2023 Assolombarda analysis on the labor market [202] offers an overview of the creation of jobs for R+D activities. According to the data available on the Wollybi platform in Lombardy in 2022, job advertisements published on the web amount to approximately 900.000, with over a third (more than 300.000) concentrated in the metropolitan city of Milan. In the Executives and Managers category, the most sought-after figure overall (18.000) in Lombardy is that of R&S Manager.

Summarizing, many SMEs participate in R&D projects aimed at Circular Economy and there is a high rate of employment in R&D activities, so **the element related to the participation of SMEs in R&D activities is evaluated as excellent (score 5)**.

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the participation of SMEs in R+D activities.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Difficulty in matching supply and demand for labor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Regional (but also national and European) financial support in R&D investments
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Coordinate and align R&D efforts and investments from a supply chain perspective 	

3.9.6.5 Traceability

Traceability represents a critical weakness in Circular Economy supply chains, both at the regional level in Lombardy and across Italy. Indeed, one of the significant barriers is the lack of standardized traceability mechanisms able to ensure the sustainability and proper management of materials throughout their life cycle. This deficiency presents a major challenge to meeting the ambitious recycling goals set by the European Union and poses a risk to achieving the full potential of the circular economy model.

In Italy, the situation is particularly complex. There is no universally codified or applied model for traceability, and no comprehensive technical guidelines are in place that all operators and stakeholders can rely on. While the Italian government has passed legislation, such as *Legislative Decree 152/2006* (Environmental Code), which establishes the minimum standards for waste management, these regulations focus primarily on compliance and the prevention of legal liabilities rather than promoting best practices in traceability across the entire recycling chain. As a result, most operators act independently, primarily concerned with fulfilling the minimum legal requirements, rather than striving for innovation or improvements in circular practices.

Moreover, traceability systems have remained rudimentary in nature. Current practices mainly involve paper-based documents such as waste transport forms, environmental declaration forms, and input/output registers, which are often insufficiently detailed and poorly monitored. These documents typically focus on the initial stages of the recycling process, such as collection, but rarely track the end destination of the materials or provide a clear picture of the actual recycling process and its effectiveness. Consequently, there is limited oversight or transparency in tracking how much material actually ends up being recycled, making it difficult to assess progress toward meeting national and EU recycling targets.

In response to these shortcomings, there have been efforts at the national level to improve waste traceability systems. One such initiative is the publication of the *Reference Practices UNI/PdR 132:2022* [204], introduced in September 2022. This reference practice, developed by Utilitalia in collaboration with the Higher Institute for Environmental Protection and Research, Conai, and other key stakeholders, provides guidelines for tracking waste materials intended for recycling.

The primary objective of the UNI/PdR 132:2022 is to monitor data and ensure compliance with the European Circular Economy Directives [203]. The EU's targets, such as achieving a 65% recycling rate by 2035, require a shift from merely tracking the volume of collected recyclable materials to ensuring the actual recycling of those materials. By adopting this reference practice, operators in the recycling industry can certify the final destination of

recyclables, ensuring greater transparency in waste management operations and adherence to best practices.

Another significant effort in the field of traceability is **RENTRI** National Register of Environmental Product Traceability [205], which is a governmental initiative designed to streamline the tracking of waste throughout its life cycle. RENTRI aims to centralize information on waste management and ensure that materials are properly handled, recycled, and disposed of according to regulatory requirements. This initiative is essential in moving towards more integrated and traceable waste management systems, enhancing accountability and supporting the achievement of sustainability goals at both the national and European levels.

At the regional level, the situation is characterized by a mix of public and private initiatives. While there is limited institutional support for the widespread implementation of traceability systems, several consulting firms (especially in Milan) are providing valuable assistance to businesses in navigating the complexities of waste management and traceability.

These consultancy services are crucial for companies looking to improve their waste handling processes and align with both legal requirements and best practices in the circular economy. For example, a typical valuable consultancy support includes:

- a preliminary analysis of the relevant regulatory context and operational, environmental and economic aspects.
- the identification of the best scenarios for the collection, recovery and recycling of end-of-life materials.
- the design of a pilot project for the best practices identified.
- support in the drafting and presentation of innovation projects at national and European level.

Companies like *Circularity* (<https://circularity.com/>) offer a range of services to promote sustainability, such as creating sustainability reports, developing strategic sustainability plans, conducting Life Cycle Assessments (LCA), and communicating sustainability efforts effectively to stakeholders.

Similarly, *ERP Italia Servizi* (<https://erpitaliaservizi.it/>) provides specialized consultancy services focused on environmental regulations, including waste management and electronic waste (RAEE) compliance. These firms help businesses design customized strategies for waste collection, recovery, and recycling, while also offering support in drafting and submitting innovation projects at the national and European levels.

In conclusion, traceability in the Circular Economy in Lombardy and Italy is still fragmented and underdeveloped. Although initiatives like UNI/PdR 132:2022 and RENTRI are positive steps, they are in the early stages, and the lack of a standardized traceability model remains a key challenge. Regional consultancy firms are crucial in supporting businesses toward more sustainable practices. **The technology, research & innovation dimension related to traceability is so evaluated as ‘improvement is needed’ (score 2).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning practices concerning traceability

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lack of shared, widely accepted traceability standard model ○ Fragmented Implementation: operators act independently, focusing only on minimum legal compliance ○ Insufficient Monitoring: existing systems lack detailed oversight and transparency on final recycling outcomes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Standards for monitoring waste and ensuring recycling, improving transparency. ○ Consultancy Support: regional firms assist businesses in adopting best practices. ○ Stakeholder Collaboration: involvement of organizations to create common practices.
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Supply Chain Approach and LCA for better material flow monitoring. ○ Industrial Symbiosis: certify material quality and recyclability through measurement and verification. 	

3.9.6.6 Availability of regional and local R+D funding

As emerged during the working group with public stakeholders, Lombardy region has its own resources for R+D that are mobilised to foster CE and, with the latest economic planning (2021-2017), a specific objective for the CE was introduced for the first time, which the Lombardy Region has integrated.

On 8 February 2021, the Regional Council approved, with regional government resolution 4275/2021, the document “*Main challenges and priorities for the use of the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) 2021-2027*” [206] and a specific goal was devoted to CE transition: Priority 2 “*A greener, low-carbon Europe in transition towards decarbonisation and resilience*” – Specific objective 2.6) “*Promote the transition towards a resource-efficient and circular economy*”. It includes 2 actions:

1. Action 2.6.1. “*Support for the adoption of sustainable production models*”

Support for the adoption of sustainable production models is aimed at the gradual transition towards a circular and resource-efficient economy, as a lever for competitiveness and sustainability, and to adopt a new paradigm based on the valorisation of resources and materials. This action will also be carried out by encouraging the involvement of non-profit entities, as well as consumer representatives both in the design and testing step and in the distribution step, to encourage the transition towards CE also in demand. Specifically, this action may concern support for:

- product innovation (eco-design) and application of new technologies starting from the recovery of materials and design based on the concepts of modularity, reuse and repairability, recyclability and sustainability of materials (with reference for example to bio-based materials), also encouraging new distribution and consumption models and providing for the use of energy vectors with low environmental impact.
- implementation of process innovations for the introduction of international “green” standards in companies in all phases of the product life cycle, the reduction of dangerousness and the quantity of waste, promoting the purchase

of sustainable supplies and efficiency in the use of natural resources and materials and the recovery of materials.

- transition of commercial strategies from the purchase of products to the use of rental and use services.
- support to processes and technologies with high innovative value dedicated to products and materials which, due to peculiar performance decay and excessive reprocessing costs, pose high challenges in terms of sustainability (environmental and economic) of recovery operations and reinsertion into circular economy processes.

2. *Action 2.6.2. “Support for industrial symbiosis actions, waste prevention, recycling and reuse to close the cycle”*

The reduction of environmental impacts, from a territorial production system perspective, is supported with an action aimed at overcoming operational, system and supply chain barriers for the implementation of the circular economy in businesses and local authorities. Specifically, this action may consist of:

- design and management of integrated supply chains and public-private partnerships facilitating adherence to sustainable production and service processes, according to the “*Life Cycle Thinking*” approach.
- promotion of industrial symbiosis as an eco-innovative system approach able to support the transfer of matter, energy, water and/or by-products between traditionally separate industries, also thanks to the synergistic possibilities offered by geographical proximity.
- support and promotion of reuse and preparation for reuse, also through the development of reuse networks.
- support and promotion of techniques and practices for reducing food waste at all points of the supply chain (primary sector, distribution, catering, large-scale retail trade, families).
- support for innovative technologies and models for the collection, recycling and reintroduction of plastic into the production cycle, as well as for the selective interception and initiation of recycling and reuse of single-use plastic products and reusable alternatives.
- application and dissemination of innovative recycling technologies and business models, conceived starting from the needs of the destination market of the product, with reference to fractions of waste that are quantitatively or qualitatively critical or containing critical raw materials

In relation to Regional Plan ERDF 2021-2027, after a consultation procedure with the territorially competent bodies, the competent environmental bodies and the interested public, the ***Strategic Environmental Assessment document*** [207] was also published with the aim of determining in advance the significant direct and indirect effects of the actions envisaged by the Programme on the population, human health, biodiversity, territory, soil, water, air, climate, material assets, cultural heritage and landscape.

With respect to the specific objective 2.6 the following results and output indicators are reported in the Strategic Environmental Assessment (Table 40).

Table 40 – Results and output indicators related to CE as reported in Strategic Environmental Assessment or the Regional Plan ERDF 2021-2027

Indicator	Unit of measurement	Intermediate target (2024)	Final target (2029)
Supported enterprises	N. of enterprise	104	1070
Investments in separate waste collection systems	€	0	20.000.000
Investments in circular economy projects	€	10.450.000	139.600.000
Waste used as raw materials	Tons/year		5.500
Waste subject to separate collection	Tons/year		1.165

Also taking into account the output of working group with regional stakeholders and the data presented and discussed in the paragraph 3.9.6.2 “Public investment in R+D+I” the element related to the availability of regional and local R+D funding can be evaluated as good (score 4): Lombardy Region effectively supports R+D in the field of CE with programmed and well-developed mechanisms for funding proposals and initiatives.

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning practices concerning availability of regional and local R+D funding.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<i>No barrier or challenge has been identified</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cooperation between stakeholders to identify priorities of action
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Simplified funding processes 	

3.9.7 Standardization dimension

Among all the 8 dimensions analysed in the application of the multidimensional model to the Lombardy Region, standardization is the dimension with the greatest need for improvement. Both elements analysed received a score of 3.

This can generally be attributed to a lack of information both among public stakeholders and among companies operating in the Circular Economy sector.

Figure 43 - Standardization elements global evaluation in Lombardy

3.9.7.1 Creation of standards and norms at the EU level

To date there are nine standards on the Circular Economy under development, at national and international level.

At international level:

- **ISO 59004 – Circular economy, Vocabulary, principles and guidance for implementation** [208]. It was published in May 2024 and introduces a shared terminology and establishes the definitions and fundamental principles on which the CE is based. These include the traceability of resources and “secondary raw materials”.
- **ISO 59020 – Circular economy, Measuring and assessing circularity** [209]. It was published in May 2024 and aims to standardize the methodologies for measuring and evaluating the performance of organizations with respect to the CE. In addition to principles and guidelines for measuring and evaluating performance, the standard provides methodologies for collecting data and selecting indicators useful for monitoring progress towards circularity objectives.
- **ISO 59010 – Circular economy, Guidance on the transition of business models and value networks** [210]. It was published in May 2024 and provides a roadmap to identify areas for improvement, define objectives and develop strategies to create a more sustainable value chain.
- **ISO 59014 Environmental management and circular economy, Sustainability and traceability of secondary materials recovery, Principles and requirements** [211]. It was published in 2024 and provides principles, requirements and guidance for organizations in fostering the sustainability and traceability of activities and processes for the recovery of secondary materials.

- **ISO/TR 59031 – Circular economy, Performance-based approach, Analysis of cases studies** [212]. Under development, it will provide a collection of good practices of circular economy of the “*product as a service*” type.
- **ISO/TR 59032 – Circular economy, Review of business model implementation** [213]. It provides a set of business models, including enabling factors for their implementation.
- **ISO 59040 Circular Economy, Product Circularity Data Sheet** [214]. Under review, it will provide a general methodology for improving the accuracy and completeness of CE related information based on the usage of a Product Circularity Data Sheet when acquiring or supplying products.

At national level:

- **UNI/TS 11820 Measurement of circularity, Methods and indicators for measuring circular processes in organizations** [215]. Published in 2022, it defines a set of indicators able to evaluate, through a rating system, the level of circularity of an organization or group of organizations
- **UNI/TR 11821 Collection and analysis of good practices of circular economy.** [216]. Published in 2023, it proposes a method of collection and analysis of 41 good practices of circular economy that allows an analytical and systematic picture of their characteristics.

As emerged during the discussion with the regional stakeholders, Lombard public entities do not collaborate with standardization agencies in the elaboration of norms for products and processes but for the definition of national standard the UNI (Italian Standardization Body) has engaged the production sector, receiving numerous endorsements from companies in Lombardy. Tecnoalimenti Scpa promoted these activities.

Moreover, Lombardy Region fosters the adoption of environmental standards with financial support tools. The expenses for the registration and development of trademarks, patents, and quality certifications, such as REACH registration, can be accounted for.

In addition, companies already holding recognitions (e.g., LCA studies and sustainability labels, agreements with research institutions) can benefit from incentives during the evaluation steps of public call and tenders.

In addition, the Lombardy Region makes available to public bodies (Region, Provinces and Municipalities) and to proposers of public tenders an Information System Environmental Impact Assessment (SILVIA) [217]. It allows to consult procedures, documentation, cartography, reporting and regulations regarding Environmental Impact Assessment.

SILVIA includes 5 sections:

1. *Regulatory section* contains the main legal references regarding Environmental Impact Assessment at regional, national and community level.
2. *Environmental impact assessment section* helps the proponent and the interested bodies to identify the procedure to which a certain work is subject. This section also makes available the list of protected natural areas of the Lombardy Region and allows their geographical location through a WEB GIS service.

3. *Procedures section* makes available the data and documents regarding the environmental impact assessment procedures.
4. *Documentation section* provides all the documents useful for preparing the Environmental Impact Study and some guidelines for evaluating the impacts generated on some environmental components and some types of works (transport, hydroelectric energy, impacts on biodiversity).
5. *The cartographic section* is the WEBGIS section that allows the consultation of the summary project data, and the territorial analysis of the main projects filed in the Lombardy Region.

Also, according to the stakeholders' point of view, **creation of standards and norms at the EU level is evaluated as moderate (score 3)**: Lombardy Region promotes in a moderate circularity assessment in businesses through rewards in public tenders and the collaboration with standardization agencies is limited to private companies.

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning traceability.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Costs ○ Validity and updating of standards and assessments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Incentives for companies that use certification
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Enforce existing quantifiable circularity standards ○ Increase visibility of standards ○ Promote European harmonisation 	

3.9.7.2 Digital tools to improve product traceability

In Lombardy, the transition towards a Circular Economy is being actively supported through various digital tools aimed at improving product traceability.

First of all, the regional government has recognized the importance of such tools for enhancing supply chain transparency and efficiency. In 2023, Lombardy launched a call for proposals under the “*Expression of Interest for the development of industrial production chains and ecosystems*” [218] which aims to strengthen the resilience and competitiveness of local industries. This initiative is focused on fostering interconnections between businesses, research entities, training institutions, financial intermediaries, and other strategic players to promote economic and territorial development. A key area of intervention is the intersection between sustainability, circularity, and digitalization, particularly in reorganizing the activities of procurement, production, and distribution through the development of competitive supply chains that reduce dependence on imported technologies and raw materials, thus enhancing local autonomy.

While current applications of digital traceability in circular supply chains are still limited and institutional support is often seen as insufficient, there are significant technological advancements being offered by private companies operating in Lombardy. For example, **Antares Vision Group** (<https://antaresvisiongroup.com/it/>) based in Bergamo, is a leader in providing innovative solutions to ensure complete transparency across supply chains. The company offers technologies that improve the efficiency, productivity, and sustainability of various sectors, including life sciences, cosmetics, food & beverage, and rigid containers. Their solutions enable real-time tracking of products throughout the entire supply chain, promoting greater visibility and trust in the circular economy.

Another key initiative in Lombardy is the promotion of the **DIGITAL PRODUCT PASSPORT**. The regional government is actively disseminating information on European proposals for the adoption of digital traceability systems, including through its official website and the cluster system [219].

To further promote the use of digital product passports, regional initiatives have included educational activities such as the “*Webinar Digital Product Passport*” [220] organized by Netcomm in October 2024. This event focused on the transparency, traceability, and sustainability benefits of digital product passports for both businesses and consumers.

Although the practical implementation of digital product passports in Lombardy is still in its early stages, there are companies in the region with the technological expertise to drive further adoption. For example, Knobs (<https://knobs.it/>), a Milan-based provider specializing in blockchain technology, offers services related to the implementation of digital product passports. Their expertise in blockchain enables secure and transparent product tracking, which is essential for the successful application of digital traceability tools in circular economy models.

In conclusion, while digital traceability tools such as the digital product passport are still in the early stages of implementation in Lombardy, significant steps are being taken to promote their adoption. **The technology, research & innovation dimension related to digital tools to improve product traceability is so evaluated as moderately implemented (score 3).**

The following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the use of digital tools to create a better product traceability.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Blockchain use limited only in certain sectors (e.g., pharmaceuticals, energy). ○ Lack of Interoperability: different sectors use separate blockchains; efforts are mainly company-specific, not across the entire supply chain. ○ High digitalization costs ○ Absence of official standards: there is no universally accepted standard for digital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Advanced technological know-how ○ Regional government support

traceability, hindering consistency and scalability.

Actions

- Economic support for digitalization

3.9.8 Capacity building dimension

The assessment of the capacity building dimension led to a rating of **3.5** as average between the Capacity of the education system to meet the challenges of the Circular Economy (score 4) and the Balanced match between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries in the region (score 3).

Figure 44 - Capacity building elements global evaluation in Lombardy

3.9.8.1 Capacity of the education system to meet the challenges of the Circular Economy

Lombardy Region actively participates in **EXCHANGE PROGRAMS BETWEEN REGIONS** with the aim of sharing knowledge, skills and training systems on EC. Below are some examples of INTERREG projects that have involved Lombardy Region directly or through other public stakeholders:

1. **CRESCENTO** (<https://crescento.adrioninterreg.eu/>) project aims to create a transnational cooperation network on Circular Economy, defining an education and training program and developing a joint master's program on Circular Economy. The project is based on a partnership of 11 partners led of Politecnico of Milan: a network of more than 60 stakeholders from academia, research, business and policy makers was created and the education and training program of the CE concept was defined on the exchange of experiences and mutual learning through a Summer School via online / face-to-face education and training courses, as well as open learning. CRESCENTO consortium is strongly committed towards a joint master's program

definition and implementation to be undertaken by at least 2 universities and an internship of up to 6 months for business and research attendees.

2. **REUSE2030** (<https://www.interreg-central.eu/projects/reuse2030/>) aims to increase the adoption of Circular Economy principles by the mechanical sector, with the introduction of instruments and tools facilitating the application of CE models to both production and product phases of mechanical companies. REUSE2030 is based on a transnational cooperation of business supporting organisations, universities, chamber of commerce, competence centres and development agencies of 9 different CE countries. Lead partner is ECOLE Lombardy Industrial Associations for Education.
3. The Interreg **Alpine Space** (<https://www.alpine-space.eu/>) programme finances cooperation projects across the borders of seven Alpine countries. Among the objectives, develop and test transnational training programs to improve skills for the green and digital transition and contribute to expanding innovation capabilities. The Lombardy Region is directly involved.

In addition, in Lombardy are active **TRAINING COURSES** for sectors with specific reference to standardization.

For example, the Italian standardization body UNI organizes a course dedicated to the standard *UNI/TS 11820:2024, Measurement of circularity. Principles, methods, measurement and practical application simulations* (described in the previous paragraph **3.9.7.1. Creation of standards and norms at the EU level**). Starting from the reference regulatory context, the key concepts on which the technical specification is based are explored (such as the circular economy principles on which the set of indicators and the criteria for measuring and evaluating circularity are based) and the set of indicators prepared for calculating the level of circularity of an organization. The course also includes some practical examples of application of the method.

Similarly, Assolombarda organizes the course “*AFNOR XP X30-901 (2018): The Circular Economy Project Management System*” devoted to the French standard establishing the requirements for implementing a Circular Economy Project Management System in a company. The course analyses the high-level structure of the standard (consistent with the main management standards 9001-14001-45001), the areas of application and the guidelines for the management of circular economy projects.

Summarizing, we can estimate **moderate implementation related to the regional Capacity of the education system to meet the challenges of the Circular Economy (score 4)**: there are a few accreditation and certification programs, and sector-specific training is available, but not widespread. There is some knowledge exchange with regions/cities with a stronger educational system.

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve Lombardy readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the capacity of the education system to meet the challenges of the Circular Economy.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Few sector-specific courses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Participation in inter-regional exchange programmes
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Greater promotion of training courses 	

3.9.8.2 *Balanced match between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries in the region/city.*

In Lombardy, as the region increasingly embraces the principles of the CE, the demand for skilled labour in related sectors has grown. However, matching this demand with an adequate supply of qualified workers remains a challenge. Despite the wide range of training programs available, including both professional and highly specialized courses, the alignment between the workforce needs of CE industries and the skillsets offered by educational institutions is often not seamless.

To address this, the Lombardy Region is implementing specific financial measures aimed at developing skills, particularly in environmental sustainability, with a broad focus that extends beyond just the CE to cover general sustainability issues. This initiative, although not exclusively tailored to Circular Economy, seeks to improve the overall skillset of the workforce to better meet the evolving demands of the green economy.

The regional education and training offerings are varied, providing multiple pathways for professional development. Among the programs directly managed by the Lombardy Region are:

- *Three-year Vocational Education and Training* aimed at providing foundational skills.
- *Higher Technical Institutes* offering two-year programs following the completion of Vocational Education and Training
- *Advanced Technical Education*: one-year post-diploma courses to deepen specific technical skills.

Following Table 42 summarized training courses related to CE and active in Lombardy in the 2024/2025 school year

These programs are aligned with the principles of **dual vocational education and training**, combining theoretical knowledge with hands-on practical experience such as apprenticeships, work-study schemes, and school-business partnerships [221].

The dual approach of integrating theory with practical training ensures that graduates are better equipped to enter the workforce, particularly in sectors related to CE.

Table 42 - Vocational training courses active in Lombardy in the 2024/2025 school year

Type of course	Institute	Location
Vocational education and training		
Water management and environmental remediation worker	Professional Institute “Stern”	Bergamo
Water management and environmental remediation worker	Professional Institute “Dandolo”	Bargnano di Corzano (Brescia)
Water management and environmental remediation worker	Professional Institute “Argentia – Majorana”	Gorgonzola (Milano)
Water management and environmental remediation worker	Professional Institute “Bonomi-Mazzolari”	Mantova
Higher Technical Institutes		
Sustainable mobility infrastructure and digital applications	GREEN Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for Energy, Environment and Sustainable Building	Vimercate and Lissone (Monza-Brianza)
Head of Innovation, Energy and Environment	GREEN Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for Energy, Environment and Sustainable Building	Vimercate and Lissone (Monza-Brianza), and Milano
Industrial Process Sustainability Expert	GREEN Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for Energy, Environment and Sustainable Building	Milano
Higher Technician for Sustainable Logistics	Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for the Transport and Intermodal Logistics Supply Chain	Somma Lombardo (Varese) and Milano
Higher Technician Chemistry, Industry 4.0 and Sustainability	Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for New Life Technologies	Lainate (Milano)
Higher Technician for the Green Economy	Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for New Life Technologies	Bergamo
Higher Technician for Bio Green Productions and Technological Innovation	Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for New Life Technologies	Lainate (Milano)
SUSTAINABLE & INNOVATIVE FOOD TECH: Advanced technician specializing in innovation and sustainability of food processing processes	Higher Technical Institute for New Technologies for Made in Italy – the Agri-food Chain	Lodi
Specialized Higher Technician in Sustainable Enogastronomic Productions of the Territory.	Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for the Innovation of the Agri-food System	Lecco
Sustainable Construction & Green Building Design	Foundation Higher Technical Institute for New Technologies for Made in Italy	San Paolo d’Argon (Bergamo) and Pavia
Automation and Innovation for Ecological Transition	Istituto Tecnico Superiore per le Nuove Tecnologie per il Made in Italy	Cremona

Cosmetics and Sustainable Packaging	Higher Technical Institute for New Technologies for Made in Italy	Paderno Dugnano (Milano)
Design digitale della moda Sostenibilità e innovazione per le collezioni di alta moda	Higher Technical Institute for New Technologies for Made in Italy – Fashion section	Milano
Specialista della sostenibilità: Design e marketing del prodotto nell'industria 5.0	Foundation Higher Technical Institute New Technologies for Made in Italy Leonardo Academy	Bergamo
Higher Technical Education and Training		
Biobase design techniques: creative innovation in the service of environmental sustainability	School of Applied Arts “Andrea Fantoni”	Bergamo
Techniques for designing innovative and sustainable collections (women’s wear)	Higher Technical Institute for New Technologies for Made in Italy – Fashion section	Busto Artizio (Varese)
Techniques in sustainable agriculture: between innovation 4.0 and agribusiness management	Foundation Higher Technical Institute agrifood symposium	Rodengo Saiano (Brescia)
Techniques for ecological transition	GREEN Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for Energy, Environment and Sustainable Building	Lissone (Monza-Brianza)
Techniques for environmental sustainability	GREEN Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute for Energy, Environment and Sustainable Building	Lissone (Monza-Brianza)
Management techniques for the multifunctionality of the sustainable agricultural enterprise 4.0	Foundation of the Higher Technical Institute “Minoprio”	Vertemate con Minoprio (Como)
Techniques in travel designing tourism, hospitality and sustainability	Foundation Higher Technical Institute agrifood symposium	Rodengo Saiano (Brescia)

Additionally, there are various specialized programs aimed at enhancing professional competencies for adults. These are designed to support both individuals seeking re-entry into the job market and those currently employed but looking to upgrade their skills in line with the growing demand for green jobs. For example, courses such as “*Sustainability in Environmental Processes*” and “*The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Sustainability*” offered by institutions like Fondazione Mazzini ETS Monza and Time Vision SCARL play a key role in helping workers transition to more sustainable roles [222].

Moreover, private educational institutions such as ITS Academy in Cremona offer specific courses tailored to the CE, such as “*Energy Sustainability in the Environment and Circular Economy*” [223]. These courses cater to the need for more specialized skills in sectors directly impacting the circular economy, thus contributing to filling the skill gap in the region.

In conclusion, Lombardy’s educational offerings are diverse and increasingly aligned with the needs of the circular economy. While there is a clear focus on addressing the skills gap, the challenge remains to improve the alignment between labor demand in CE industries and the competencies provided by educational institutions. **The technology, research & innovation dimension related to the balanced match between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries in the region/city is so evaluated as well implemented (score 4).**

Following table summarizes factors useful to improve readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning match between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mismatch between skills and company needs ○ Fragmented educational offer: too many scattered programs, making it hard to navigate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Wide range of educational programs ○ Dual Vocational Education and Training ○ Regional financial support
Actions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Enhance coordination between education and industry. ○ Increase visibility of relevant educational options. 	

3.9.9 Global evaluation

Figure 45 summarises and outlines the 8 Circular Economy dimensions previously analysed in Lombardy, reporting for each dimension the average of the elements taken into consideration.

As previously discussed, the numerical evaluation of each element/dimension, although based on objective data, is influenced by the interpretation of the research group that applied the model and by the composition of the working group of stakeholders. However, some general conclusions can be drawn that are useful for the subsequent definition of the regional CEAP.

Figure 45 – Global evaluation of CE in Lombardy

With an average value of 3.7 among all elements, Lombardy shows a good level of progress towards the circular transition.

Best dimensions are socio-economic dimension and governance dimension (4.5 and 4.4, respectively). The factors of excellence in Lombardy are the strength of the production system, the participation of citizens (in particular with reference to separate waste collection) and the holistic and multidimensional approach to innovation with the involvement of all decision makers.

On the other hand, the worst dimension is the standardization, but a very low score was also given to traceability (a technological element related to standardization). These are aspects which are still little known among stakeholders.

The main findings emerging from the application of the multidimensional model in terms of **Strengths**, **Weaknesses**, **Opportunities** and **Threats** are reported and outlined below.

Generally speaking, Lombardy region is ready for the circular transition thanks to the great technological maturity and the great sensitivity of the citizens (for example with very high rates of separate waste collection); on the other hand, the high demographic and industrial rate make it very susceptible to environmental problems.

3.9.10 Lombardy/Lithuania comparison and cross-fertilization

Lombardy and Lithuania were selected for the replicability study of the Agro2Circular solutions because of their territorial and organizational characteristics very different between them and with respect to Murcia: this allows to identify the potential for innovation and applicability on a wide range of conditions, drawing from its insight and cross-fertilization.

From an agri-food production point of view, different climatic and territorial conditions in Lombardy and Lithuania impact agriculture both in terms of types of crops and in terms of cultivation methodologies.

Lithuania has a strong agricultural industry, one among the fastest growing in the EU and both types of Agro2Circular potential value chain (valorisation of biological waste and valorisation of plastic from agriculture) were considered replicable from LPK contextual analysis; on the other hand, level of cooperation in the Lithuanian agrifood sector is relatively low and this is a barrier for the implementation of CE solution.

In Lombardy, the systemic replicability of Agro2Circular value chains was evaluated as effective only for horticultural waste valorisation with the extraction of biomolecules to be applied to the nutraceutical and cosmetic sector but the existence of producer organizations

and companies with a high rate of innovation represents a strength for converting linear value chains into circular value chains in these sectors.

From a multidimensional point of view, it is worth underlining how the structural organization in the two territories analysed has a strong impact on the replicability assessments: on the one hand the CE governance, policies and regulations are rather centralised at national level in Lithuania while on the other hand, the Italian organization is less centralized with a fair amount of autonomy at regional level. For these reasons TCA applied multidimensional replicability to the specific context of the Lombardy region that is characterized by its own specifics on almost all the dimensions and elements assessed in the model. Regional autonomy represents an excellence for the Lombardy Region and for the implementation of CE solutions, but trans-regional cooperation and coordination at national level are an essential point for a successful circular transition.

Starting from different territorial realities (both productive and organizational) but also from a different composition of the working group that applied the multidimensional model as an evaluation tool, the comparison between Lithuania and Lombardy on the 8 dimensions of the CE is reported below (Figure 46). For example, in the Lombardy case study only public stakeholders were involved in the working group (private stakeholders were engaged with private interviews) while the Lithuanian working group included both public stakeholders and private companies. In addition, the Lithuanian working group included a large academic component while in Lombardy case study the university representation (UBocconi) worked as a moderator giving its contribution with the results elaboration.

Figure 46 - Evaluation of the 8 dimensions of the EC in Lithuania and Lombardy (average data of the evaluation by the territorial working groups)

Both in Lombardy and Lithuania the best evaluation score is for the Socio-economic dimension, but good evaluations were found in both territories also for the aspects of Technology, Research and Innovation (second place in Lithuania, third place in Lombardy).

It is interesting to note how “Standardization dimension” which represents the greatest weakness in Lombardy is higher in the ranking in Lithuania: Lithuania has standardisation Technical Committees working in the identified broad technical areas of Agro2Circular while in Italy this aspect is not covered at regional level but only at national level. Therefore, great efforts are still needed to push the circular transition. An element of interest for Lombardy arises here from cross-fertilization with Lithuania: **the optimization of the standardization dimension and the overcoming of the related challenges is only possible by addressing the issue on a broad national (or even international) level.** TCA is working in this direction by participating in the agri-food commissions and the thematic tables of the national standardization body (UNI).

Across the 8 dimensions analysed, two main actions for potential improvement emerge from the Lithuanian working group as well as from the multidimensional replicability analysis in Lombardy, also outlined below in the policy recommendations: (i) closer cooperation between science, business, and government and (ii) financial support overcome the investment gap for innovation.

More in general, it is worth noting that Lithuania has its Circular Economy Action Plan with programmatic action until 2035 so D7.18 was developed focusing on the LPK community to elaborate a “**cluster CEAP**” more specific for a group of companies.

Furthermore, in Lombardy there is a specific government body responsible for the CE and several programmatic documents on specific sectors (for example water management, waste management etc..) were implemented, however, there is no global Circular Economy Action Plan. In connection with the Italian National strategy for the Circular Economy and with the European Circular Economy Action Plan, TCA developed a regional document with a 360°C vision able to cross systemic aspects and multidimensional assessments. The final objective was to provide “**a wide-ranging CAEP**” with the aim of providing strategic information (political guidelines, key actors to involve, drivers to monitor) and suggesting a roadmap to Lombardy decision makers.

3.10 Circular business models

Starting from the replicability study aimed at the application of technological solutions and circular value chain tested in Murcia and from the application of CE Multidimensional Model, University of Bocconi defined the Circular Business Models (CBMs) that can be applied in the Lombardy with a particular focus on agri-food sector initiatives that prioritize the upcycling of their waste and byproducts.

The following 4 operative step were performed:

1. Circular business models in the agri-food sector relevant to the Agro2Circular project were identified drawing from academic literature.
2. Key drivers, enablers, and barriers of circular business models in the agri-food sector were identified, grouping them into different categories.
3. With particular reference to the working group with key public stakeholders (see **3.8.2 Public stakeholders' involvement**) specific context of the Lombardy region was analysed in order to detect the replicability of CBMs and assess the relevance of identified drivers, enablers, and barriers in the region.
4. Two CBM canvas tailored to the unique characteristics of Lombardy were designed upon the above-mentioned information.

3.10.1 Circular Business Models relevant to Agro2Circular

The implementation of the Circular Economy in business has been extensively analysed in the literature. Central to this discussion is the concept of business model, which defines how a firm operates, creates value, and organizes its activities. It serves as an architectural framework to describe the company's operations [224].

Business models can be represented using different types of tools and visualizations. Among them, the Business Model Canvas is one of the most widely used, for its effectiveness in representing visually the different components of a business model. Furthermore, business models sharing common characteristics can be categorised into different "archetypes". According to Rask et al. [225] definition "*a business model archetype refers to an original pattern of value creation and capture (dimensions: customer engagement, value delivery and monetization), which is often copied by many firms in an industry and presents the dominant logic of the industry*": these are examined in greater detail in **Deliverable 6.5 A2C business cases**, which focuses on business cases and their associated financing mechanisms, specifically within the context of the Agro2Circular project.

The principle of value creation is central to the conceptualization of both archetypes and business model canvases and applies not only to linear business models but also to circular ones. To achieve circularity, Geissdoerfer et al. (2023) [226] identifies several strategies that companies follow to pursue a new circular path, by transforming an existing traditional model into a circular one or setting up a completely new process:

- *Starting up*: the business is developed starting with a circular background.
- *Diversifying*: the focus is in integrating CE principles within an existing business model.
- *Transforming*: it modifies the existing business to adopt circular strategies.
- *Acquiring*: a company adopts circular business model through external growth by acquiring firms with existing circular practices.

These pathways reflect different approaches to integrating circular principles into business operations and ensuring long-term sustainability.

The academic literature provides several categorizations of circular business models. Vermunt et al. (2019) [227] identify four main CBM categories:

1. *Product as a service*: the product is owned by a company that lends it to users.
2. *Product life extension*: the main objective is developing solutions to reuse the product.
3. *Resource recovery*: the material of an object is recovered to exploit the residual value.
4. *Circular supply*: it involves substituting linear input with non-virgin raw material.

Geissoderfer et al. (2020) also provides a similar categorization based on value chain principles:

1. *Intensify*: the use phase of products is optimized and intensified, for example, through sharing economy models.
2. *Dematerialising*: this involves substituting physical products with services or software solutions.
3. *Extending*: the use phase of products is prolonged through better design, maintenance, and repair practices.
4. *Cycling*: this category includes activities that recycle materials or recover energy, reintroducing them into the system.

The following Table 40 provides an overview of such categorizations, putting in relation business model categories that share comparable definitions. Each author, relying on different frameworks and focusing on various aspects, has developed their own specific Circular Business Model (CBM). However, despite the diverse methodologies adopted, common aspects can be identified. These shared elements enable the grouping of CBMs, facilitating comparisons and providing a more comprehensive overview of the current state of this topic.

In line with the previous definition, Table 43 highlights this grouping by categorizing models into three main types: (i) those that transform a product into a service, (ii) those that aim to prolong the product's lifespan as much as possible and (iii) those that implement a recycling process. Two models identified by the respective authors were not eligible to be associated with any of the other categories.

Finally, based on the characteristics of each business model and evidence from the literature, the next step identified the models that are particularly suitable for application in Agro2Circular projects. Specifically, these include models focused on recycling processes and those that base their production on recycled or secondary raw materials.

Table 43 – Overview of CBM categories identified from literature (*UBocconi elaboration*)

	<i>Vermunt et al. 2019</i>	<i>Geissdoerfer et al 2020</i>
General Circular Business Models	Product as a Service	Intensifying
	Product life extension	Dematerialising
		Extending
Suitable business models for agri-food sector	Resource recovery	Cycling
	Circular supply	

Waste-based business models are quite common in the agricultural sector, specifically those classified as “*Resource recovery*” and “*Cycling*”.

The *Resource Recovery* business model aims to transform and enhance the residual value of resources. New forms of value are derived from agro-wastes and byproducts in a context of collaboration within companies, that share materials, energy and byproducts to achieve competitive advantage [228].

Similarly to Resource Recovery, *Cycling* consists in the recycling within the system of the material, through reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishing, and recycling (*Geissdoerfer et al., 2020*).

CBMs in the agri-food sector can also be categorized based on specific activities that are performed within the model, such as in the study by Donner et al.(2020) who identify the following six BM archetypes:

1. *Biogas plant*: energy production from agricultural waste streams.
2. *Upcycling entrepreneurship*: transformation of low-value product waste or by-products into high value materials.
3. *Environmental biorefinery*: production of marketable products or energy by maximizing the added value of raw materials.
4. *Agricultural cooperatives*: jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprises, typically within one specific production sector, which aim to achieve a critical quantity of byproducts or waste to make investments in circularity that are economically sustainable.
5. *Agropark*: a cluster of companies that benefit from joint waste management, natural resources, and logistics. It follows the same principles as industrial symbiosis, consisting of mutually dependent businesses that leverage many synergies.
6. *Support structures*: enhancing cooperation between different players in the sector.

These categorizations can suggest relevant models for the definition of Lombardy CBM in the replication of Agro2Circular territorial solutions.

3.10.2 Drivers, enablers and barriers for the implementation of CBMs in the agri-food sector

In the Circular Economy context, a **DRIVER** is defined as a factor that motivates organizations to implement circularity practices [229]. In this section, the main drivers of CBMs in the agri-food sectors are identified from a set of studies (in particular, Donner and Radić, (2021) [230], Geissdoerfer et al. (2023) [226] and Lit et al. (2024) [231] and organized into three main categories: (i) market, (ii) organisational and (iii) social (see Table 44).

Table 44 – Main drivers for CBM implementation identified for each category

Market	Organizational	Social
New business opportunities	High volume production	Customer positive perception of sustainable products
Diversification of the product offer	Closed loop thinking	
	Specialisation in the product management	

Considering the market dimension, companies are driven to pursue a circular business model by the possibility to benefit from new business opportunities, as well as to diversify the products they offer in the market, with higher appeal to potential customers (Donner et al. 2021). From the organisational point of view, high production volume along with achieving cost efficiency can drive companies to begin a circular path (Lit et al. 2024), along with the implementation of a closed loop thinking and specialisation in product management (Donner et al., 2021), three activities that make easier a transition path toward more sustainable way of production. Finally, considering the social dimension, a further motivation to the transition is a common perception among customers of the benefits related to sustainable products, mainly related to a better environmental performance (Rao et al. 2024).

While a driver is a factor that motivates the transition to circularity, an **ENABLER** is an element that facilitates its implementation. In the agri-food sector, the literature identifies key enablers across market, financial, legal, organisational, technical, and social categories (see Table 45).

Table 45 – Main enablers for CBM implementation identified for each category

Market	Financial	Legal	Organisational	Technical	Social
Positive market sensitivity to sustainability issues	Financial support	Clearness of policies and regulator context on circularity	Network and engagement between similar business and along supply chain	Challenges in scaling up innovative circular technologies at industrial level	Effective communication to customers on features and benefits of circular products.

Considering the market dimension, a positive sensitivity and perception of the market concerning circularity is important, and for this reason information about the topic and

sensibilisation activities can be considered as a relevant enabler. Along with a positive perception, there is also the need for financial support, particularly from authorities that recognise the importance for the development of circular paths (Rao et al. 2024). To be effective, financial aid should be supported by clear policy and regulatory contexts (Geissdoerfer et al. 2023), to achieve a collaborative environment. Indeed, a good network and a high level of engagement between actors along the supply chain is an important facilitator for the implementation of circular business models, not only with institutions but also between similar businesses through partnerships. Considering the technical dimension, an important enabler toward circularity is the existence and affordability of innovative circular technologies and the ability to scale up the process (Geissdoerfer et al. 2023). Considering the specific context of the plastic sector, the ability to make a linear and circular production process coexist helps in the success during the transition (Lit et al. 2024). Finally, effective communication to customers can be an enabler as it connects with the market sensitivity to circular issues, facilitating the acceptance of new sustainable products.

On the other hand, the literature also highlights several **BARRIERS** to the implementation of circular business models, which vary across different sectors. In this section, the focus is on barriers that are particularly relevant to the sectors of the A2C project, specifically agriculture and plastic management. Barriers can be broadly categorized into two main types: internal (*"barriers that pressure within a company that hinder the implementation of their business model"*) and external (*"external forces that hinder companies from developing their CBMs"*) (Vermunt et al., 2019).

Starting from internal pressures, a relevant market barrier is linked to the higher costs associated with circular production processes, reducing competitiveness and making it more difficult for businesses to adopt sustainable models effectively (Lit et al., 2024). In addition, from a financial perspective, companies engaging in circular businesses usually face high upfront investments and, at the same time, longer payback periods, which represent an important barrier when deciding whether to implement a circular production process (Donner et al. 2021; Barros et al., 2023).

In addition to internal barriers, impediments can also come from outside the company. An example are political and regulatory issues that limit the expansion of CBMs. The main concern is about "context uncertainty," which complicates the implementation and growth of circular practices in the sector. Moreover, implementing a circular path can lead to challenges related to the supply chain. In agriculture, the sector often faces issues with a low and inconsistent resource flow, which is also subjected to spoilage and can disrupt efficiency of circular practices [232]. Within the social dimension, barriers can be related to communication issues and relationships within different partners. Furthermore, customers may have some difficulties in accepting circular products, even though there is a demand for more sustainable products, as they may perceive them as lower quality compared to traditional alternatives (Geissdoerfer et al. 2023).

Main barriers to the implementation of circular business models are summarised in Table 46.

Table 46 – Main barriers for CBM implementation identified for each category

Market	Financial	Legal	Organisational	Technical	Social
Low competitiveness of circular products due to high production costs	High upfront investment	Lack of legal standardization and policy clearness	Unstable communication and cooperation with commercial partners and suppliers	Availability of new technology	Low quality perception
	Long payback period		Inconsistent flow of waste material and susceptibility to spoilage		
			Variable flow in terms of timing, quantity, and type of wastes		

3.10.3 Assessment of CBM drivers, enablers and barriers in Lombardy

As previously reported and confirmed by literature analysis, Lombardy region is recognized for having an excellent technological maturity, the highest number of best practices in eco-design, particularly in the use of secondary raw materials [233]. Moreover, concerning the Agro2Circular projects, **this region shows to be ready from the technological point of view to implement circular processes.**

As emerges from the contextual analysis and the application of the multidimensional model, the Lombardy region exhibits alignment between general and specific factors influencing circular business models. Key elements driving the region's shift toward circularity include positive social perceptions by the participants of the initiative to the transition and a strong emphasis on innovation and research, which enhance new market and business opportunities. Moreover, a specific project about industrial symbiosis practices in Lombardy companies (Sigma project [234]) highlighted a closed loop thinking within companies, particularly concerning plastic and agriculture, whose wastes are the main materials recycled and reused for other purposes. This highlights the region's positive capacity to recognize and take advantage from the potential drivers that literature has identified.

Shifting to the CBM enablers, the Lombardy private and public stakeholders involved in Agro2Circular project highlighted a positive market sensitivity to sustainability issues and products, and this is supported by an increasing demand for financial support. From an **organizational perspective**, a key enabler can be represented by the high potential volume of agricultural wastes that could be available for transformation in the region, as 44.2% of the regional territory is used for agricultural purposes. Even though Lombardy can rely on a big agricultural surface, on the other hand, the contextual optimisation of the production process led to waste reduction. The availability of waste for transformation can reduce the barrier posed by the variable quantity of materials for such purposes, even though as above mentioned, in the last years waste production is decreasing. At the same time, the Sigma project shows the existence of symbiotic behaviours between companies working together to reach circular paths through the exchange of waste and byproducts, as well as sharing infrastructure and services, even across different sectors. However, such symbiotic behaviours remain limited [234]. It is also relevant to point out that agricultural and food industry waste, along with plastic waste, are the primary raw materials used in upcycling

processes. However, the report highlight that companies rely also on waste coming from other regions [234].

Institutional support plays a significant role in Lombardy, both from a **financial and regulatory** point of view. This commitment toward circularity is exemplified by initiatives like the Observatory for Climate, Circular Economy, and Ecological Transition, an institutional discussion forum for sharing the strategic objective of regional policies on sustainability with stakeholders (discussed in the element “*Dialogue promotion in decision making process*” of Governance dimension) and the introduction of green public procurement policies along with financing programs for industrial research and the development of experiments [235].

On the other hand, barriers identified in the Lombardy region mirror those found in broader literature. These include challenges related to competitiveness, such as high initial costs for companies and higher prices for products derived from circular processes, compounded by declining income levels. Moreover, despite the availability of financial support, one of the major concerns is the low awareness of companies on available funding opportunities. This confirms that there are gaps in stakeholder communication. Additionally, even though Lombardy has a strong agricultural sector able to provide a high volume of wastes, as previously reported, organizational challenges arise due to seasonality and not constant flow of waste materials for Circular Economy implementation [236].

From a **regulatory perspective**, the lack of clear regulatory frameworks, particularly concerning waste management, end-of-waste criteria, and other regulatory constraints remains a significant obstacle also in Lombardy. This generates a common request from the main regional stakeholders for guidelines on this topic, as emerged during the regional event with key public stakeholders.

3.10.4 CBM canvases for Lombardy

In relation to case studies identified for the valorisation of agricultural waste in Lombardy, it is worth highlighting the importance of the cosmetic sectors in Lombardy regional economy, identifying many B2B companies that develop formulations for B2C brands. Through an analysis of the companies' websites and information provided in paragraph 3.3.8 “**Mapping of Technological providers**”, a clear interest emerges in delivering sustainable and high-performance products. This reflects the **interest of the Lombardy companies for the research and development of solutions that respond to market demands, both in terms of supply chain, management and specific production processes.**

Based on information emerged from the analysis of A2C circular value chains replicability in Lombardy, with specific focus on cosmetics and nutraceutical applications, two main types of circular business model innovations have been identified.

1. The first CBM for the Agro2Circular solution replicability in Lombardy focuses on companies that are implementing **diversification strategies of production and consequently also of products offered in the market**

2. The second CBM for the Agro2Circular solution replicability in Lombardy refers to companies that **directly implement their activities with a circular approach, without the need to modify an existing internal product or process.**

Two distinct archetypes of a circular business model can therefore be identified within the context of Lombardy potential technology providers. Although the common objective of these companies is to offer technical solutions and products derived from the upcycling of agro-food waste, their different approaches align with two different circular business model archetypes, as described in previous paragraphs:

- *Circular supply*: mainly used by technology providers that have an internal R&D department that, in addition to the core focus on developing cosmetic formulations, also works on integrating a circular supply chain in their production process.
- *Dematerializing*: mainly used by technology providers that develop and find solutions for introducing circular strategies but lack of internal industrial production facilities.

3.10.4.1 Lombardy CBM 1: Component producers

Considering the first model, the R&D performed by technology providers is carried out internally through in-house research centres and facilities equipped to implement these new technologies. As a result, the production process diversifies to deliver a new circular product, where the company's traditional business model coexists with a circular one, with a particular emphasis on the circular supply archetype.

The canvas outlines the key features that define this business model.

Key partnerships	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationships	Customer segments
Providers of waste for upcycling Universities B2C cosmetic industries Industry association	Research Development of solution to upcycle agro wastes to generate secondary raw material Integration of new ingredients: development of new components for cosmetic formulators	Offering components from wastes, to ensure waste valorisation through circular extraction routes Diversification of the catalogue of components offered to customers to meet the demand for more sustainable products deriving from circular supply chain	B2B	B2B sales streams: customers are cosmetic industries with a B2C sales segment
	Key resources		Channels	
	Researcher Facilities Knowledge Wastes collection Waste transformation plants		Commercial network	
Cost structure		Revenue streams		
Personnel Plants & equipment to extract components from wastes Production facilities Energy & Water operational costs		Product sales		
Environmental costs/benefits		Social costs/benefits		
Use of sustainable ingredients Shorter supply chain		Job creation Sustainable products for the market facilitating sustainable consumption		

The primary value proposition that motivates companies to invest in research projects in this field is the extraction of valuable active principles from agro-food waste. To achieve this objective, partnerships are often established between companies and research centres,

particularly those specializing in developing solutions through the upcycling of by-products. The implementation of circular pathways is frequently supported by a combination of both private and public funding, with companies participating in research projects to generate synergies among partners.

Key partnerships extend beyond fund providers, suppliers, and customers to include industry associations that connect companies within the supply chain. These companies primarily operate in a B2B market, supplying products to B2C companies. Delving into these firms' websites an increasing commitment to demonstrate the company sustainability through environmental certification or labelling is also observed, likely driven by growing market demand for sustainable products.

An important factor to consider is the cost associated with implementing circularity in the supply chain. This includes personnel expenses, costs related to upcycling and the extraction of components from waste, as well as logistical needs in sourcing and managing waste materials.

3.10.4.2 Lombardy CBM 2: Spin-off companies based on dematerialization

The second business model for the replicability of A2C solutions in Lombardy, can be identified as relevant for spin-off-companies, the other type of technology providers identified thanks to the activity of mapping of technological providers.

Spin-off companies are characterized by strong expertise in the research field on technologies for circularity, but they often lack production capabilities. In this business model, knowledge is commercialized, allowing spin-off companies to recover research costs by providing their expertise to multiple customers. The following section provides a description of a possible business model canvas for spin-off companies, structured following the BM Canvas framework.

Key partnerships	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationships	Customer segments
Universities Developers of cosmetic and nutraceutical formulations Providers of waste for upcycling	Research Consultancy Integration of new ingredients: development of new components for cosmetic and nutraceutical formulators	Providing knowledge and technological solutions to produce components from wastes, to ensure circular extraction routes valorising waste	B2B	B2B cosmetic formulators
	Key resources		Channels	
	Researchers Knowledge Research laboratories		Commercial network	
Cost structure		Revenue stream		
Personnel Laboratories (facilities)		Consultancy/training/support activities based on knowledge		
Environmental costs/benefits		Social costs/benefits		
Use of sustainable ingredients		Job creation		
Energy & water consumption optimisation (strongly case-dependent)		Knowledge development		

The primary objective of university spin-offs like ETICHUB and BioRestart is to deliver knowledge on circularity to businesses operating within a traditionally linear production framework. Their value proposition is to develop new technologies and provide sustainable solutions to companies that outsource research activities related to their supply chain. Most customers of these spin-offs are cosmetic or nutraceutical formulation companies that engage with them through joint research projects. With a strong emphasis on research and development, spin-off companies often rely on public or European funds dedicated to innovative projects. Their ability to secure funding is a key characteristic of the Lombardy region, as identified by the focus group. Additionally, they benefit from a supportive research ecosystem and strong academic partnerships.

3.11 Lombardy Circular Economy Action Plan

The convergence points between the two lines of replicability study (systemic analysis of circular value chains implemented in Murcia and multidimensional model for the circular transition) is the development of a strategic document aimed to support the effective transformation of linear economy models into circular economy systems in the Lombardy Region.

A Circular Economy Action Plan was developed starting from the analysis of the current territorial situation (analysed through the multidimensional model and discussed with regional stakeholders) and from the strategic documents already available at regional, national and community level; it replicates in the context of the Lombardy region the circular systems implemented in the Agro2Circular taking into account results from technological, environmental and economic evaluations.

The CEAP strongly stresses interdisciplinary cooperation and cooperation between science and practice and include the following key information

- identification of key actors and drivers of the transition to circularity
- exempling of circular systemic solutions (based on Agro2Circular technologies)
- providing of policy recommendations
- definition of a roadmap to move towards circular systems.

3.11.1 Key actors and drivers

According to the multidimensional and holistic approach to the circular transition, the key actors for the implementation of an effective and efficient Circular Economy Action Plan should be identified according to the quintuple helix model (see Figure 47). Below are the key Lombard players for each element of the quintuple helix.

Figure 47 - Quintuple helix model

Research and education

- Universities are innovation drivers, fostering new technologies, solutions, and business models for CE, while serving as hubs for applied research and circular solutions. They also play a key role in training future professionals.
- In Lombardy, 11 universities address CE across multiple disciplines (engineering, economics, law, environmental sciences, design). The most involved universities in the circular transition are: **Politecnico of Milan, Bocconi University, University of Milan-Bicocca, University of Milan.**
- In addition to universities, other public research institutions (in particular CNR and ENEA) are also actors in the research and education helix. The most relevant are, **CNR-IREA, CNR-SCITEC, Environmental Sustainability Technologies Laboratory at ENEA Brescia.**

Industry

- The industrial propeller in Lombardy is effectively represented by the system of 9 technological clusters. Key actors for the CE are: **Cluster High Technology Agrofood Lombardy, Lombardy Aerospace Cluster, Lombardy Green Chemistry Association, Lombard Mobility Cluster, Lombardy Energy Cleantech Cluster, Smart Factory Association Lombardy, Cluster Technologies for Smart Cities & Communities Lombardy, Cluster Technology Caring People, Lombardy Cluster Life Sciences.**
- Other key actors for CAEP implementation are: **Confindustria Lombardia** (bringing together the 11 territorial industrial associations of Lombardy), **Assolombarda** (association of companies operating in Milan, Lodi, Monza and Brianza, Pavia), **Green Economy Network** (promoted by Assolombarda to stimulate new alliances between companies offering products, technologies, and services for sustainability).
- A specific relevant company is **AMSA waste management company.**

Environment

- Relevant bodies and associations for the implementation of the Circular Economy Action Plan in Lombardy are: **ARPA, ERSAF, Legambiente Lombardia, Lombardy Foundation for the Environment.**

Civil society

- Citizens play a key role in CE, actively contributing to waste reduction (particularly food waste), material reuse, and sustainable practices. Relevant citizen associations are: **Lombardy Food Bank, Lombardy Active Citizenship, Soulfood Forestfarms Hub.**

Public administration

- The administrative “engine” for the territorial transition towards CE is the Lombardy Region, which has a specific organizational unit dedicated to CE within the **General Directorate for Environment and Climate**. A holistic approach requires involvement from multiple units, including: **Directorate General for Environment and Climate** (Environmental Policies and Tools, Environmental Assessments and Remediation), **Directorate General for Agriculture, Food Sovereignty, and Forests** (Supply Chains, Plants, Livestock, Agri-environment, Agroenergy, Sustainability), **Directorate General for Local Authorities, Mountains, Energy Resources, Use of Water Resources** (Energy resources, Water resources), **Directorate General for Economic Development** (Support for Investments, Innovation of Businesses, Ecosystems), **Directorate General for University, Research and Innovation.**
- Additionally, key regional institutions and companies include: **Regional Company for Innovation and Purchasing, PoliS Lombardia, Finlombarda S.p.A.** Bidirectional collaboration with other local bodies (**Provinces, Chambers of Commerce, Municipalities**) and the **Italian State** is essential.

As well as for the identification of key actors, a holistic and multidisciplinary approach was also applied for the definition of the drivers. Starting from the analysis of CBMs applied to agrifood sector (paragraph **3.10.2 Drivers, enablers and barriers for the implementation of CBMs in the agri-food sector**) the perspective was broadened on the whole regional ecosystem so considering the application of the multidimensional model and the feedback obtained from stakeholders involved, the following 5 drivers towards the circular transition of the territory have been identified.

1. **Economic opportunities.** Reducing waste and use of resources allows for an immediate economic return; in addition, consumers are increasingly seeking sustainable and ethical products, incentivizing companies to adopt circular principles.
2. **Regulatory and policy push** Local, national and international legislation is increasingly stringent in terms of environmental requirements and policies mandate extended producer responsibility, recycling targets, and eco-design standards; on the other hand, grants, subsidies and tax benefits for circular initiatives motivate industries to transition. Green public procurement also represents an excellent political tool to support CE.
3. **Environmental Pressures:** Lombardy is a leading region in Italy in waste sorting and treatment, but the high production of industrial and urban waste requires a more circular management. Also, the Lombardy region suffers from serious problems of air and water pollution pushing for a more sustainable management of natural resources.
4. **Supply chain pressure:** Companies are incentivized to secure their supply chains by using secondary materials and designing for reuse: the industrial density of the Lombardy region favours synergies between companies to develop industrial symbiosis projects.
5. **Consumer awareness.** Lombard citizens are among the most sensitive in Italy to environmental issues, with a growing demand for sustainable products and sharing economy services.

3.11.2 Replicability of Agro2Circular systemic solutions

Two different systemic solutions for the circular transition can be successfully replicated starting from the Agro2Circular model.

considering the generation of biological waste from Lombardy horticulture, the strong territorial vocation to the cosmetic/nutraceutical industry and the great advancement in terms of research, two business models have been analysed for replicability in the Lombardy region (see paragraph **3.10.4 CBM canvas for Lombardy**).

1. The first business model is related to cosmetic/nutraceutical companies able to use biological waste from horticulture to produce functional products This innovative transition within the cosmetic and nutraceutical industries is facilitated by a collaborative environment in the Lombardy region, characterized by a high concentration of companies in this sector, research centres, and a substantial local stream of waste that can support circular supply initiatives. Additionally, this

favourable environment is further strengthened by the presence of industry associations and partnerships that foster connections across the supply chain, encourage collaboration toward a shared vision, and support the broader business community.

2. The second potential systemic solution replicable in Lombardy involves companies able to implement directly their activities with a circular approach, without the need to modify an existing internal product or process. With a strong emphasis on research and development, spin-off companies often rely on public or European funds dedicated to innovative projects. Their ability to secure funding is a key characteristic of the Lombardy region, as identified by the focus group. Additionally, they benefit from a supportive research ecosystem and strong academic partnerships. From an environmental perspective, spin-off companies play a crucial role in advancing resource upcycling from agricultural waste. Due to the specificity of this research field, such innovations might not otherwise be developed within the industry. By making knowledge accessible and fostering collaborations between different sectors - such as waste providers and cosmetic manufacturers - these businesses contribute significantly to sustainability and Circular Economy initiatives.

3.11.3 Policy recommendations

From the discussion with public and private stakeholders and from the application of the Agro2Circular Multidimensional Model to the Lombardy region emerge specific policy recommendations transversal to the individual dimensions and elements analysed beforehand.

The most relevant policy recommendation can be summarized into two main aspects related to holistic approach and to public financial support (see Figure 48).

Figure 48 - Main policy recommendation categories to foster CE transition

1. A successful transition to a CE requires engagement at all levels, from decision-making to implementation, bringing together policymakers, economic operators across supply chains, consumers, and citizens. So, the first policy recommendations group is related to the **active engagement of all stakeholders and key actors**. More in deep, the involvement must take place on various levels.
 - All stakeholders and key actors need to be **informed** about CE potential actions in terms of benefits (both for the individual actor, the entire supply chain and for the community) and related costs.
 - The second level of involvement is the **consultation** of the stakeholders and key actors so the information flow initially going from the “CE engine” to actors and stakeholders (information), in this second level goes back to from actors and stakeholders to the “centre” to collect needs, requirements, opinions and points of view.
 - The third level of involvement is the **co-creation** based on a two-way exchange that allows for the collaborative and shared implementation of Circular Economy actions bringing benefits to the whole supply chain and all stakeholders.
 - The highest level of involvement is the **collaboration** between individual actors and between actors and institutions. It is important to stress that collaboration must be both horizontal and vertical. In a horizontal manner, all the actors identified according to the quintuple model will be involved. Implementation at regional level must also be enhanced in a vertical manner

upwards with synergies at national and European level and downwards in collaboration with Provinces and Municipalities.

2. The second policy recommendation group is linked to the **public financial support for circular transition actions**.

Economic operators are increasingly aware of the potential and advantages (including economic ones) deriving from the CE but often they are not able to sustain investments, especially if long-term. So public financial support appropriately addressed can effectively boost circular transition: the most relevant public financial support can be directed towards prospective actions such as Research & Development activities as well as Training & Education. It is essential for a rapid and effective transition towards the Circular Economy that public institutions share with private companies the risk of long-term investments both in supporting technical and professional training capable of responding to the challenges of the CE and in the entire R&D cycle starting from basic research up to scale up and industrialization.

3.11.4 Roadmap towards circular systems

As a final point of replicability activities of the Agro2Circular systems in the Lombardy Region, a roadmap was defined to support the regional transition towards the Circular Economy.

In line with the whole Agro2Circular approach, it is a roadmap **centred on interdisciplinary cooperation and stakeholder engagement**: it would like to provide a reference able to stimulate the cooperation between public and private stakeholders with the aim to build strategic initiatives on Circular Economy as an opportunity to define a structured strategy to boost Circular Economy in the region starting from the needs and the priorities collaboratively pointed out by diverse regional stakeholders.

By combining data from systemic and territorial analysis with the reflections emerged from the discussion with the stakeholders and from the application of the multidimensional model, **5 objectives considered priority for the implementation of effective EC solutions were identified**.

The following synoptic Table 44 outlines the Lombardy CAEP reporting for each of the 5 key objectives: the potential actions to be implemented, the estimated timing (in the short, medium and long term) and the key actors among those previously identified to be involved in the implementation of the action.

In addition, 2 focuses were devoted to the two key sectors of the Agro2Circular project, namely the plastic and agro-food sectors, identifying programmatic actions for the circular transition in Lombardy.

As emerged from the territorial analysis, these are in fact relevant sectors for the Lombardy Region but above all they are key sectors for the circular transition also identified at community level as policy areas of interest (European Circular Economy Action Plan [237]).

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Table 46 – Lombardy roadmap towards circular systems

Objectives	Actions	Timing	Key actors
1.Reduce Waste	1.1 Strengthening separate waste collection for example improving the door-to-door waste collection capabilities	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society (in term of citizens awareness and participation) • Public administration • Industry (AMSA in particular) • Environment
	1.2 Introducing incentives for companies that adopt waste reduction practices	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administration • Industry
	1.3 Promoting sustainable packaging using biodegradable or recyclable materials for packaging and reducing over-packaging.	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Civil society • Environment
	1.4 Developing new recycling and recovery technologies	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support to R&D)
2. Promote eco-design and resource efficiency	2.1 Introducing sustainability criteria in public procurement	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administration • Environment
	2.2 Introducing product design criteria for increase the percentage of secondary raw materials in new products	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administration (financial support to R&D and eco – design directive)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry
3. Encourage the use of secondary materials	3.1 Developing circular technologies, for example Incorporate reusable materials and avoid harmful chemicals that hinder recycling	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support to R&D)
	3.2 Re-valorisation of secondary products and by-products through implementation of circular value chains	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support to R&D)
	3.3 Developing certifications and quality labels for circular products	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Environment
	3.4 Using technology to track materials and components in the supply chain allowing for efficient recovery and reuse.	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support to R&D and to industrial symbiosis)
4. Foster interdisciplinary collaboration	4.1 Strengthening stakeholder engagement	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society • Public administration • Industry • Environment • Research and education
	4.2 Creating opportunities for interaction and knowledge sharing	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administration • Industry

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environment • Research
	4.3 Promoting collaboration in R&D processes from the design phase to the industrialization phase	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support to R&D)
	4.4 Supporting industrial symbiosis	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support)
	4.5 Fostering collaboration with governments at territorial, national and international level to establish policies able to support circular practices	Long term (< 5y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administration
5.Spread Circular Economy Culture	5.1 Design of specific university/training courses closely connected with the industrial environment and targeted to key topics able to provide students with the required skills and competencies.	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and education • Industry • Public administration
	5.2 Developing and implementing sustainable practices for example through awareness campaigns	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society • Environmental • Public administration
	5.3 Empowering consumers and public purchasers to make informed choices	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society • Environmental • Public administration (legislation about label)

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Each action identified and described in the roadmap can be traced back to a (or more) specific element(s) previously analysed in the validation and replication study of the multidimensional model (Table 47).

Table 47 – Relation between Lombardy roadmap actions and elements from multidimensional model

Actions	Dimension	Element
1.1 Strengthening separate waste collection for example improving the door-to-door waste collection capabilities	Environmental	Efficient waste and water management
1.2 Introducing incentives for companies that adopt waste reduction practices	Environmental	Efficient waste and water management
1.3 Promoting sustainable packaging using biodegradable or recyclable materials for packaging and reducing over-packaging.	Environmental Socio-economic	Territorial exploitation level Regional/local cultural aspects
1.4 Developing new recycling and recovery technologies	Technology, research & innovation	Availability of valorisation technologies
2.1 Introducing sustainability criteria in public procurement	Policy & regulation	Regulatory instruments adopted
	Technology, research & innovation	Public investment in R+D+I
2.2 Introducing product design criteria for increase the percentage of secondary raw materials in new products	Technology, research & innovation	Research-industry connection Participation of SMEs in R+D activities
3.1 Developing circular technologies, for example Incorporate reusable materials and avoid harmful chemicals that hinder recycling	Technology, research & innovation	Availability of valorisation technologies
3.2 Re-valorisation of secondary products and by-products through implementation of circular value chains	Technology, research & innovation	Availability of valorisation technologies
	Socio-economic	Business reinvention capacity Strength of the Productive Ecosystem
	Policy & regulation	Secondary raw materials market
3.3 Developing certifications and quality labels for circular products	Standardization	Creation of standards and norms at the EU level
3.4 Using technology to track materials and components in the supply chain allowing for efficient recovery and reuse.	Standardization	Digital tools to improve product traceability
	Technology, research & innovation	Traceability
4.1 Strengthening stakeholder engagement	Governance	Dialogue promotion in the decision-making process Existence and implementation of an

		effective multi-level governance Holistic regional systemic approach
4.2 <i>Creating opportunities for interaction and knowledge sharing</i>	Governance	Dialogue promotion in the decision-making process Existence and implementation of an effective multi-level governance Holistic regional systemic approach
4.3 <i>Promoting collaboration in R&D processes from the design phase to the industrialization phase</i>	Technology, research & innovation	Research-industry connection Participation of SMEs in R+D activities
4.4 <i>Supporting industrial symbiosis</i>	Policy & regulation	Secondary raw materials market
	Socio-economic	Strength of the Productive Ecosystem
4.5 <i>Fostering collaboration with governments at territorial, national and international level to establish policies able to support circular practices</i>	Governance	Dialogue promotion in the decision-making process Existence and implementation of an effective multi-level governance Holistic regional systemic approach
5.1 <i>Design of specific university/training courses closely connected with the industrial environment and targeted to key topics able to provide students with the required skills and competencies.</i>	Capacity building	Capacity of the education system to meet the challenges of the Circular Economy Balanced match between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries in the region/city
5.2 <i>Developing and implementing sustainable practices for example through awareness campaigns</i>	Governance	Promotion of Circular Economy culture and trust enhancement
5.3 <i>Empowering consumers and public purchasers to make informed choices</i>	Governance	Promotion of Circular Economy culture and trust enhancement

3.11.4.1 *Plastic case study*

In the plastic sector, innovation is strongly driven by the optimisation of production processes through acquisition, sharing, management and processing of data generated at all stages of the product life cycle.

Lombardy already has significant rates of use of recycled plastic materials, thanks to the R&I work that the converting sector has been carrying out for several years, but there is still room for improvement.

The challenges of CE transitions could lead in Lombardy to the adoption of digital technologies developed ad hoc according to the specific needs of the supply chain, in order to promote traceability, strengthen the entire ecosystem and accelerate the ecological transition itself.

In line with the Plastix project and several complementary exchanges with the Agro2Circular project, the following programmatic actions are identified for the plastic sector in Lombardy:

- *Applying eco-design principles* would allow to extend the useful life of products and simplify recycling at the end of their life, for example by favouring the production of single-polymer products
- *Expanding the range and quantity of reused recycled polymers* supporting targeted R&D actions
- *Applying CE principles based on industrial symbiosis* could unlock new business models based on sustainability awareness and culture
- *Improving the quality of polymers derived from recycling* would allow a full substitution of virgin materials, in economic terms for competitiveness in the market (lower supply chain cost) and in qualitative terms for the actual value of the material
- *Educating consumers, whether businesses or private citizens*, to manage plastic waste correctly

3.11.4.2 Agrifood case study

In line with European CEAP, the main drivers in the agrifood sector are the sustainability of food distribution and consumption and the recovery/ application of bioactive molecules.

Lombardy region is an excellence in this sector with the publication in 2022 of a specific Food Waste Prevention Program and several EC actions implemented.

Some additional programmatic actions can be suggested for circular transition in agrifood sector:

- *Increasing citizens education and awareness* for example with public campaigns to inform consumers about food waste and its impact and/or with school programs to teach students about food sustainability
- *Fostering redistribution and donation programs* also with government incentives for companies that donate excess food
- *Improving Policy & Regulation* with tax benefits for food donations but also with standardized date labelling to reduce confusion between “Best Before” and “Use By” dates
- *Investing in waste recovery and/or recycling technologies* (composting food scraps at the household and industrial levels, biogas production from organic waste, upcycling food waste into animal feed or secondary food products).

4. Conclusions

In line with the two lines of replicability pursued within Task 7.6, **two main results have been obtained** and described in D7.17

1. From a systemic point of view, a replicability model was applied the circular value chains for the valorisation on horticulture waste.
Grapes and apples wastes (second and fourth types of horticulture waste in Lombardy in terms of abundance, respectively) were selected for the application of Agro2Circular technological model. In addition, tomato and lettuce wastes are the first and the third most important waste flows from Lombardy horticulture and they present strengths for circularization: application of the same Agro2Circular model and technologies is possible with slight modification. Beyond the biomolecule extraction and stabilization phases, the main applications of the vegetable extracts in Lombardy can be the functional cosmetic industry and the nutraceutical industry: in both cases, technological transfer can be supported by the presence of business associations. Circular value chain so implemented was analysed with environmental and economic assessments and two potential circular business models were described. Main challenges to be addressed are related to logistic aspects and extracts specifications but facilitator and strengths to be exploited are related to the territoriality with a short value chain and to the low environmental impact of the extraction technologies, respectively.
2. Multidimensional replicability analysis according to the Agro2Circular model allowed us to evaluate the regional level of progress towards the circular transition. Lombardy is ready for the circular transition thanks to the great technological maturity and the great sensitivity of the citizens (for example with very high rates of separate waste collection); on the other hand, the high demographic and industrial rate make it very susceptible to environmental problems. From the analysis of the 8 dimensions and the 33 elements impacting on the Circular Economy it emerges that in Lombardy best dimensions are socio-economic dimension and governance dimension while the worst dimension is the standardization, but a very low score was also given to traceability (a technological element related to standardization).

Final output of Deliverable 7.17 is a Lombardy Circular Economy Action Plan.

It was elaborated from the evidence emerging with the discussion with regional stakeholders and from the application of the Agro2Circular self-assessment model but also taking into account the systemic aspects analysed, and the strategic directives already implemented at regional, national and community level.

The final strategic document includes the identification of regional key actors and drivers of the transition to circularity, policy recommendations and examples of circular systemic solutions with 2 circular business models; a roadmap with 5 key objectives to move towards circular systems was elaborated.

The achievement of results and impacts was maximized by dissemination actions at national and international level as well as by clustering activities with local associations and other funded projects (PLASTIX in particular).

At national level, dissemination activities were closely interconnected with stakeholder engagement actions. A specific working group was implemented with selected public stakeholders and technological clusters representatives to introduce the project and the multidimensional model, and the model was then applied as a self-assessment tool to stimulate discussion and co-creation on the CE opportunities in the Lombardy Region. In collaboration with the AFIL cluster and the PLASTIX project, two additional dissemination and stakeholder engagement events were organized to broaden the discussion to other regional public actors and gather insights and reflections.

At international level dissemination activities were addressed to present both the multidimensional model and the replication activities in Lombardy and the advances and innovations on the supply chains of interest of the A2C project (respectively agro-food sector and plastic sector).

Table 48 summarizes TCA dissemination activities.

A2C – Deliverable D7.17

Table 48 - TCA dissemination activities

Event	Date	Place	Description
19th International Symposium on Waste Management and Sustainable Landfilling “SARDINIA 2023”	09-13 October 2023	Cagliari	TCA presented a speech: “ <i>The hidden value of agri-food residues, revealed and boosted through a circular approach: Agro2Circular</i> ”. It introduced the project with upcycling examples of agri-food and plastic wastes
Conference “ <i>Technological advancements in waste treatment and resources recovery</i> ” within ECOMONDO event	7 November 2023	Rimini	During the event, one slide was dedicated to present the A2C project to the audience: technological solutions for bioplastic production from agro-food waste were introduced.
International Conference “ <i>Sustainable Bioeconomy Development 2024: Theory and Practice</i> ”	8 May 2024	Virtual event	TCA together with CETEC, LPK, VTT, and UB held a theory and practice synergy session “ <i>Territorial Circular Systemic Solutions for Sustainable Bioeconomy Development</i> ”. In particular, TCA presented the A2C replicability method (both at systemic and at multidimensional level)
7th Symposium on Circular Economy and Urban Mining: “SUM 2014”	15 – 17 May 2024	Capri	TCA presented a speech: “ <i>Simplifying complexity for adoption and replication of circular economy systemic solutions: the A2C multidimensional model</i> ”. It described the multidimensional circular model and replicability method.
Regional working group “ <i>The 7 dimensions of the circular economy in a new validation model. From the Region of Murcia (Spain) to the Lombardy Region</i> ”	26 September 2024	Virtual event	Selected public stakeholders and technological clusters representatives were involved to introduce the project and the multidimensional model and then the model was applied as a self-assessment tool to stimulate discussion and co-creation on the CE opportunities in the Lombardy region
PLASTIX Open Seminar “ <i>Lombardy initiatives and best practices in the Circular and Sustainable Plastics Value Chain</i> ”	20 November 2024	Milan	Within the context of Plastix project Open Seminar, TCA presented A2C and its multidimensional model to support CE transition and the results from the Lombardy working group. This was an opportunity for further involvement of public stakeholders from the Lombardy Region.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Lombardy Strategic Community “ <i>Secure and Sustainable Food Manufacturing</i> ”	4 February 2025	Milan	TCA presented the project and the multidimensional model stakeholders from politics, academia and industry; it was then possible to discuss about explored fresh insights and strategies for advancing toward CE initiatives in Lombardy.
Hack for food – the Event!	13 – 14 March 2025	Copenhagen	Participation to the Event provided an opportunity for peer-to-peer discussions between innovators and stakeholders on the results of the A2C project. Exchanges took place during the World Café sessions on “ <i>Food System and Circularity</i> ,” “ <i>Food and Health</i> ,” and “ <i>Food Waste reduction</i> ,” fostering dialogue on sustainable and fair food systems. The event facilitated knowledge sharing and collaboration on innovative solutions for transforming the food value chain.
3rd Annual World Biopolymers and Bioplastics Innovation Forum	19 – 20 March 2025	Berlin	TCA presented a speech “ <i>PHBV-based Materials for Food Packaging Applications</i> ” and presented Agro2Circular as case study
The 5th International Congress on “ <i>Advances in the Packaging Industry</i> ”	27 -28 March 2025	Milan	TCA attended the event with the paper “ <i>Biobased and biodegradable materials for packaging</i> ”.

5. Evaluation of the results

The Lombardy region owns the national leadership in the transition towards Circular Economy both at technological and a political level. But, although a specific government body has been established (*Circular Economy and Natural Resources Protection Organizational Unit*), emerged from the contextual and multidimensional replicability analysis a lack of holistic approach able to address CE challenges from both a strategic and a technological point of view and to reconcile needs and expectations from different sectors and stakeholders promoting a constructive dialogue between them.

In this context, the Lombardy CAEP provided in D7.17 **wants to offer support to the circular transition by systematizing the available data and evidence with a useful strategic document consistent with regional, national and international trends and able to address all the actors potentially involved in the CE, promoting cooperation between them.**

Analysis and systematization of the factors able to impact the circular transition in Lombardy took place both at the systemic and the multidimensional level.

Specifically, replicability of circular value chains for the valorisation of agro-food waste was based on an in-depth study of the sector with a qualitative-quantitative estimations of waste amount and typology, territoriality, seasonality and aggregation potential. Although data on regional production are annually available and updated, there are no official studies about waste generation and fate: D7.17 provides specific analysis on the matter, so it represents the first milestone for the effective systemic valorisation of the waste from agri-food with the implementation of circular value chains.

Similarly, studies on the circularity in Lombardy are available at several levels (for example there are many data on the effectiveness of separate waste collection or biogas production) but there is not an overall vision with an analysis of the regional potential through the simultaneous evaluation of all the factors impacting on the circular transition. Also, in this case D7.17 represents a "lens" offering a complete view of the current regional situation with an analysis and an evaluation of 8 dimensions and 33 elements of interest for CE development.

Summarizing, Lombardy CAEP offers regional stakeholders and decision makers a comprehensive guide to raise awareness on CE opportunities and stimulate cross-sectorial collaboration with practical examples of circular systemic solutions and with key objectives for a more circular region.

In conclusion, results and output from D1.17 contributed to following Agro2Circular expected impact:

Table 49 - D7.17 contribution to agro2Circular expected impact

Objective	Expected impact	D7.17 contribution
2: Providing to the A2C technological solution the circular systemic approach by building a multidimensional model enabling the solution territorial deployment and its replication and scalability	3. Emergence of circular business opportunities and a structured pipeline of investment projects	Two circular business models have been hypothesized for the application in Lombardy of A2C technologies for the valorisation of horticultural waste applied to the cosmetic and nutraceutical industry sectors
	6. More effective development of circular solutions through knowledge transfer	Replicability and transfer of A2C technological solutions to the territorial context of the Lombardy was analysed by identifying barriers, strengths to exploit, technological providers. Involvement of private stakeholders operating in key value chains promoted knowledge transfer and increased awareness of CE benefits.
3: Maximizing project impacts and facilitating A2C systemic solution replication & scalability	7. More effective widespread uptake and easier replication, scalability and visibility of circular systemic solutions	Multidimensional replicability analysis according to the A2C model and the public stakeholder's engagement led to the identification and analysis of challenges, enablers and barriers for the regional circular transition.

After the end of the project, TCA will continue to disseminate and share the evidence emerged within Agro2Circular replicability activities even beyond the project lifespan. First, the final document will be distributed to regional private and public stakeholders involved in the preliminary discussion.

TCA will also disseminate Lombardy CAEP highlights within its network with specific actions based on the identified target.

- Qualitative and quantitative estimations about the generation of waste from the agro-food sector will be shared with representatives of the Lombardy Region and with category representatives. This study can be the starting point for further studies and insights towards valorisation solutions (even different from those proposed in Agro2Circular project)
- Roadmap towards a circular system is a document of great political and strategic interest and will be shared with representatives of the Lombardy Region, stressing the collaborative and multidimensional approach that led to the identification of priorities for key objectives. In order to carry on this exploitation activity, TCA elaborated a specific leaflet (in Italian language) and a booklet summarizing main A2C activities and results in Lombardy (in English language) (see **Annex 7**)

“**Exploitation activities**”). The roadmap will be able to guide and support decision makers towards the elaboration of official strategies and action starting from needs and reflections already shared with stakeholders from different sectors.

- Technological solutions and related circular business models will be proposed within the industrial network internal and external to Tecnoalimenti members and within the Lombard technological clusters. TCA will use its vocation as a think tank towards collaborative and inter-company research to stimulate cooperation between the research sector and the industry sector and/or between different industrial sectors with an approach of industrial symbiosis and collaboration along the supply chain.
- With specific reference to the research sector, Tecnoalimenti is strongly involved in R&D networks both at regional, national level and international and will use the Lombardy CAEP as an “acceleration tool” to push innovation towards CE but above all towards collaboration and co-creation. For example, TCA participates in Onfoods, a national research partnership focused on the sustainable development of food and nutrition, funded under Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan, and within this network will discuss the evidence and findings emerged from Agro2Circular in a perspective of inter-regional collaboration.

The knowledge acquired and the network consolidated thanks to the A2C replicability activities could be a starting point for the implementation of new R&D projects at national or international level.

- Tecnoalimenti is part of the Agri-food Commission of the Italian Standardization Body (UNI) and participates in the sectoral working tables bringing its experience acquired in Agro2Circular. From the results of the multidimensional replicability analysis, a weakness emerges in the Lombardy region (but more generally at a national level) on the elements related to standardization: in this context, TCA will be able to act as a spokesperson for the needs and expectations of stakeholders to overcome this challenge in the implementation of the CE.

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ANNEXES

A2C – Deliverable D7.17

Annex 1 - Agricultural products in Lombardy in 2024

Cereals

	BG	BS	CO	CR	LC	LO	MN	MI	MB	PV	SO	VA	TOT
	Cultivated area (hectares)												
Wheat	4.268	6.503	569	10.440	280	2.710	20.480	4.254	1.004	12.251	2	342	63.103
Durum wheat	13	1.120	1	2.365	-	194	9.640	100	-	2.870	4	1	16.308
Barley	2.260	3.687	183	3.160	111	2.080	5.130	2.445	629	4.440	13	151	24.289
Oats	8	43	14	72	3	4	33	46	46	440	-	33	742
Corn	7.044	26.547	1.374	18.840	600	12.029	24.212	11.684	1.350	11.500	46	594	115.820
Rice	-	-	-	-	-	1.751	1.038	11.130	-	69.869	-	-	83.788
	Total production (quintals)												
Wheat	211.210	339.250	25.590	574.200	13.440	130.080	1.064.960	212.700	48.192	618.764	80	14.602	3.253.068
Durum wheat	624	56.927	40	125.345	-	9.312	433.800	5.000	-	133.842	80	45	765.015
Barley	140.665	242.080	9.150	170.640	5.883	135.200	246.240	166.260	31.450	244.970	624	8.305	1.401.467
Oats	325	1.625	588	2.736	117	148	792	1.840	1.840	16.440	-	1.221	27.672
Corn	794.465	2.985.330	122.005	1.959.360	40.800	1.154.784	2.711.744	1.343.660	91.800	1.143.550	2.590	52.555	12.402.643
Rice	-	-	-	-	-	102.930	56.423	692.429	-	4.645.654	-	-	5.497.436

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Vegetables

	BG	BS	CO	CR	LC	LO	MN	MI	MB	PV	SO	VA	TOT
	<i>Cultivated area (hectares)</i>												
Potato	24	107	55	22	9	11	60	7	12	70	45	19	441
Cauliflower	5	10	-	1	5	5	10	1	-	7	1	1	46
Broccolo	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	42	-	1	-	-	47
Fresh eating tomato	750	-	-	10	50	400	2.000	1.100	50	300	-	30	4.690
Industrial tomato	-	701	-	2.280	-	695	4.054	100	-	920	-	-	8.750
Onion	8	10	1	10	1	-	34	4	2	262	-	1	333
Carrots	-	10	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	12
Asparagus	3	6	-	3	1	1	9	7	-	4	-	7	56
Radish	20	97	-	24	19	-	42	35	4	2	-	-	243
Eggplant	3	-	-	3	3	1	20	14	-	17	-	1	62
Peppers	1	--	-	4	-	-	54	2	1	13	-	1	76
Cucumber	-	1	-	-	-	-	3	7	-	-	-	-	11
Zucchini	55	319	5	121	9	68	1.105	300	14	284	8	6	2.294
Garlic	2	-	3	1	1	-	4	-	1	6	-	1	19

Vegetables

	BG	BS	CO	CR	LC	LO	MN	MI	MB	PV	SO	VA	TOT
	Total production (quintals)												
Potato	6.200	28.610	10.990	5.040	2.160	250	19.800	1.960	3.120	17.145	9.810	3.910	108.995
Cauliflower	1.525	3.000	-	290	1.450	1.450	3.500	250	-	1.750	100	100	13.415
Broccolo	500	-	-	300	-	-	-	10.500	-	100	-	-	11.400
Fresh eating tomato	4.500	-	-	60	250	2.800	11.000	8.800	350	1.800	-	150	29.710
Industrial tomato	-	427.610	-	1.418.160	-	430.900	2.115.660	54.400	-	494.000	-	-	4.940.730
Onion	2.440	2.980	300	3.000	300	-	11.100	1.200	500	85.225	-	200	107.245
Carrots	-	4.000	-	300	-	-	180	-	-	-	-	-	4.480
Asparagus	90	180	-	90	32	27	180	196	-	200	-	224	1.519
Radish	4.984	25.700	-	5.310	3.230	-	9.660	7.300	840	500	-	-	57.524
Eggplant	1.080	-	-	660	780	230	3.300	4.200	-	3.740	-	250	14.240
Peppers	300	-	-	840	-	-	6.480	600	200	3.380	-	200	12.000
Cucumber	-	250	-	-	-	-	522	2.100	-	-	-	-	2.872
Zucchini	17.090	95.700	750	26.620	1.350	18.360	144.755	90.000	2.870	82.076	960	1.080	481.611
Garlic	140	-	80	90	70	-	92	-	130	1.050	-	60	1.712

Legumes

	BG	BS	CO	CR	LC	LO	MN	MI	MB	PV	SO	VA	TOT
	Cultivated area (hectares)												
Peas	-	168	-	-	-	74	476	-	7	34	-	-	763
Beans	-	-	-	8	-	-	360	1	-	60	-	-	429
Lupins	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	77	-	-	-	2	79
Lentils	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	6	-	-	7
Chickpeas	-	-	-	-	-	22	-	-	-	525	-	-	547
Soy	1.776	4.899	330	7.980	260	4.195	16.900	3.485	1.109	11.475	2	91	52.502
	Total production (quintals)												
Peas	-	5.544	-	-	-	2.808	16.660	-	210	1.020	-	-	26.242
Beans	-	-	-	280	-	-	10.800	50	-	2.584	-	-	13.714
Lupins	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.540	-	-	-	30	1.570
Lentils	-	-	-	15	-	-	-	-	-	84	-	-	99
Chickpeas	-	-	-	-	-	550	-	-	-	14.070	-	-	14.620
Soy	53.486	183.234	9.900	263.340	7.280	142.630	540.800	108.035	26.616	312.785	50	3.350	1.651.506

Fruits

	BG	BS	CO	CR	LC	LO	MN	MI	MB	PV	SO	VA	TOT
	Cultivated area (hectares)												
Apples	28	84	12	12	10	2	225	9	10	130	800	7	1.329
Pears	9	5	3	26	3	1	408	6	23	24	22	2	532
Peaches	11	45	3	10	1	4	66	4	2	54	1	5	206
Apricots	9	12	-	4	-	2	17	3	1	24	-	-	72
Kiwi	30	77	-	56	1	25	443	7	2	12	16	1	670
Hazelnuts	9	11	2	3	2	27	36	5	4	45	2	2	148
Chestnuts	72	346	150	-	58	-	-	-	2	7	118	28	783
Walnuts	7	5	2	-	1	1	12	1	2	14	3	1	49
Wine grape	601	6.694	26	24	58	16	1.603	145	2	11.596	703	21	21.489
Melon	6	29	-	77	-	6	2.548	1	-	11	-	-	2.678
Watermelon	5	9	-	145	-	2	1.250	1	-	20	-	-	1.432
	Total production (quintals)												
Apples	3.460	18.610	2.760	2.640	1.900	270	68.575	1.050	1.000	20.404	312.000	1.540	434.209
Pears	1.820	920	600	3.510	450	130	81.600	810	2.070	3.575	4.400	300	100.185
Peaches	2.070	7.040	210	1.000	60	360	9.845	356	100	7.820	85	300	29.246
Apricots	1.162	780	-	360	-	140	918	299	70	2.605	-	-	6.334
Kiwi	3.464	9.163	-	11.455	70	1.750	44.300	525	120	1.740	1.680	82	74.349
Hazelnuts	72	165	16	18	8	54	180	45	28	450	10	16	1.062
Chestnuts	1.584	7.612	1.577	-	1.450	-	-	-	40	175	4.130	375	16.943
Walnuts	18	100	40	-	22	18	264	19	36	420	45	22	1.040
Wine grape	38.174	691.660	1.340	1.152	3.144	974	171.560	9.176	110	728.009	40.440	579	1.686.318
Melon	1.920	9.563	-	26.180	1.740	-	744.157	350	-	3.080	-	-	786.990
Watermelon	2.000	4.950		85.550	--	1.000	607.072	500	-	8.160	-	-	709.232

Annex 2 - Research involving supercritical fluid (SCF) extraction from tomato biomass

Tomato part	Pre-Treatment	Particle size	Cosolvent	Pressure (Bar)	Temperature (°C)	SCF	Targets	Best yield or recovery
Seeds	dried, milled, sieved	0.25–0.46 mm	No	245	40	50–392 kg/kgbio	oil	0.4 kg/kg oil free sample
Seeds	dried, milled	0.27 mm	No	108–245	40–70	295 kg/kgbio	oil	0.3 kg/kg sample
Pulp or skins of ripe tomatoes	dried, ground		No	172–275	40–80	6000 L/kgbio	lycopene and beta-carotene	64.41 (lyc) mg/100 g 34.88 (beta) mg/100 g
Paste	waste dried, ground, sieved	3 mm	5–15% EtOH	200–300	35–65	33–400 kg/kgbio	lycopene and beta-carotene	51% (lyc) 50% (beta)
Skins	dried, powdered		No	400	60–110	400 L/kgbio	lycopene	100%
Seeds and skins	none		No	138–483	32–86	16–100 L/kgbio	lycopene and tocopherols	7.19 ug/g, 61% (lyc), 0.15 ug/g, 86% (toc)
Skin and pulp	dried, ground		No	77–281	40	240 L/kgbio	all-translycopene	88% (% of total lyc)
Seeds and skins	dried, ground	80 and 345 microns	No	250–300	60–80	120 kg/kgbio	lycopene and beta-carotene	80% (lyc), 88% (beta)
Sun-dried tomato	dried, ground	1 mm	1–20% vegetable oil	335–450	45–70	15–53 kg/kgbio	lycopene	60%
Skins	dried		No	200–500	40–100	1.5–4.5 mL/min	lycopene	1.18 mg/g
Pomace	none	0.3–0.6	No	380–460	40–80	0.05 L/kgbio	carotenes and tocopherols	9.04 mg/g (carotenoids), 5.96 mg/g (tocopherols)

Skin and seeds	ground		5–15% EtOH	250–450	40–70	29,167 L/kgbio	lycopene	23.9 ug/g
Pulp and skins	dried, ground, mixed with hazelnuts	1 mm	No	400–450	60–70	21–53 kg/kgbio	lycopene	72.5%
Skins freeze-dried	ground	1 mm	5–15% EtOH	250–350	45–75	3.5 L/min	lycopene	73.3% (lyc) (49:3 trans:cis)
Skins and seeds	dried, ground	0.15–0.72 mm	No	200–300	40–80	0.01–0.07 kg/h	translycopene	93% (lyc)
Seeds	dried, ground, mixed with grape seeds		No	335–450	45–70	21–53 kg/kgbio	oleoresins	
Juice	removed serum		No	200–350	40–80	0.01–0.04 kg/kgbio	lycopene	76.9%
Ripe tomato puree	dried, processed to puree		No	450	65–70	41–46 kg/kgbio	lycopene	80% 9.31 mg/g
Pomace	freeze-dried powdered	0.2–0.45 mm	No	350–450	40–60		lycopene	32.5 g/100 g dw
Peel and seed	ground, sieved	1 mm	No	200–400	70–90	90–180 L/kgbio	lycopene and beta-carotene	56% (lyc), 68% (beta)
Skins and seeds	dried, ground	0.15–0.56 mm	No	120–300	40–80	19–131 kg/kgbio	lycopene	80%
Pomace	wet		No	100–300	30–50	- 5–15 kg/h	lycopene	1.58 mg/L
Pomace	dried, ground		No	69–275	40–80	9.6–28.8 L/kgbio	lycopene	82%
Ripe tomato puree	freeze-dried, puree, enzyme digestion	1 mm	No	500	86	10 L/kgbio	lycopene	27.6 mg/g dw
Pomace	freeze dried, milled, mixed with avocado oil			200–400	40–60	71 kg/kgbio	lycopene	80%

Pomace sun-dried	ground	300 microns	No	300–500	50–80	31–63 kg/kgbio	lycopene and beta-carotene	60.8% (lyc), 58.8% (beta)
Pomace freeze-dried	ground		No	200–550	40–80		cis lycopene	62% of total lyc (cis-lyc) 251.15 g/kg dw (oleoresin)
Puree	dried, sieved		No	350	60	.8 L/kgbio	lycopene and beta-carotene	2.92 g/kg (all-trans-lyc), 1.12 g/kg (beta)
Pulp	dried	0.25 mm	5% hazelnut oil	300–500	50–80	225 L/kgbio		22%
Peel and seed	dried, milled	0.1/1 mm	No	300–500	40–80	12 L/kgbio	lycopene	246 g/kg (oleoresin)
Peel and seed	dried, milled		No	400	60	20 L/kgbio	lycopene	1.32 mg/kg
Skin	dried	350 microns	No	350–550	60	2.2 L/kgbio	lycopene and beta-carotene	79% (oil) 0.86 (lyc), 1.5 (beta) mg/100 g
Pomace	wet		No	380	80	100 kg/kg bio	lycopene	619 mg/kg (lyc) 3.91 g/100 g dw (total), 64.9% (lyc), 34.9% (beta)
Powder	freeze-dried, ground		No	400	50	10.8–18 kg/kgbio		
Pomace	dried, milled or powdered	0.2–1.5 mm	No	380	80	35 kg/kgbio	lycopene	165.3 g/kg (total), 1.34 mg/g (lyc)
Peels	dried, ground		No	400	70–80	300 kg/kgbio	lycopene and beta-carotene	39.1 mg/g dw (lyc), 68.2 mg/g dw (beta)

Source: Aniceto J.P.S., Rodrigues V.H., Portugal I., Silva C.M. (2022) Valorization of Tomato Residues by Supercritical Fluid Extraction. Processes, 10, 28.

Annex 3 - Minutes of private stakeholders' involvement activities

Primary producers' organization involvement

Participants

- Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.
- Italian primary producers' organization (President of the Research group)

Date: 03 April 2023

Goal of the interview

- Understanding the status of the Italian and Lombardian agricultural and horticultural production.
- Understanding the main points of the agricultural supply chain related to the most waste production.
- Understanding if there are already alternative pathways for the residues generated by the supply chain.

Discussion

- According to internal estimations, in 2022, the agricultural sector in Italy counted €162 bn; Lombardy represents 25% of this turnover, with about 40.5 billion. Considering that Italy is made up of 20 regions, the agricultural sector in Lombardy is one of the main ones. In Lombardy, the agricultural sector is mainly linked to livestock production (particularly the dairy sector), while agricultural production (arable crops and fruit and vegetables) represents a minor share.
- Both vegetable and livestock industries produce residues at different points of the supply chain.

Arable land products:

Arable land products normally generate fewer residues than fruits and vegetables. The main waste production points are the harvest and post-harvest phases and the refining of the seeds. In the first case, the parts of the plants that remain in the field already have a known destiny, namely that of being sent to biogas plants, and then transformed into biomethane. If the conversion into biogas is not convenient, the vegetable parts left in the field are incorporated into the soil with the subsequent plowing, thus acting as organic matter. If the crop residues are not fermentable, and therefore cannot be converted into biogas, they are sent to the feed sector. This concept is also applied to the residues from the seed refinement phase.

Fruits and vegetables:

The fruit and vegetable supply chain is related to a higher generation of residues, which mainly refers to damaged products or products that do not conform to market standards, rotten products, or rotten parts. This is linked to the higher perishability of this type of product, which is in the range of hours, and the long journey these products make from when they are harvested to when they reach the marketplace. According to the latest estimations, on a national scale, only 28% of the fruits and vegetables produced are sold directly by the producers, while up to 72% reach the retailer system, passing through different stakeholders and several selection steps. From each of these selection steps, some products are discarded, so that only the best ones reach the consumers. The discarded products may have different fates according to their level of quality; the less damaged ones are given to non-profit organizations for the less well-off, while the fruits and vegetables that do not comply with food safety standards, are normally reported to producers, who use them to produce biogas or for the feed sector, or used for the production of side products such as juices and jams, where only a small percent of fruits and vegetables are of high quality and the rest is composed by products discarded from the retailers or the producers.

Considering all these already existing alternative ways to treat the discarded products and the residues from the production and commercialization of fruits and vegetables, and that this system is applied on a national basis, the real waste from this sector counts for about 1% of the entire production.

Livestock and animal products:

In Lombardy, the main part of the agricultural sector is represented by livestock production, with the dairy sector in the first place. It is estimated that the Lombard livestock sector generates around 9-10% of residues, which are mostly related to the processes of the transformation industry. Similarly to what happens in the fruit and vegetable sector, also here the residues deriving from the processing of meat and dairy products have a well-defined fate. Most of the discarded meat parts are sent to biogas production or used to produce lower-class products (processed meat, wurst, etc.).

The meat sector reuses all the residues deriving from the processing phases, even the bones are transformed into powder and used as feed for other animals (especially in the aquaculture sector).

Most of the products that are in the process of reaching the retailer system are discarded due to non-conformity to market standards or loss of food security and are transformed into something else, according to their level of edibility and their safety, they may be used for side productions, animal feed, or biogas. As an example, milk expired is used to produce processed cheeses until three days after its expiration date.

Scientific and technological representative of “green technology” providers involvement

Participants

- Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.
- Lombard institute for “*green technologies*” (First Researcher)
The main goal of the research team is to valorise agrifood by-products and waste by extracting added-value compounds or by producing biopolymers from the same sources

Date 13 June 2023

Goal of the interview

- To understand the sector and the prospects of secondary raw materials.
- To understand the latest trend in green chemistry and valorization of food-related by-products.
- To have information on the industrial feasibility of the biotechnological and chemical processes required for the extraction of valuable compounds from agrifood secondary raw materials.

Discussion

- Main future trends in this sector are: (i) production of biopolymer composites from vegetable oils and oil waste and (ii) study of complex natural polymers already carrying interesting functionalities; trying to extract and utilize them for our biorefinery goals.
- Main problems of this sector are related to the possibility of scaling up from the lab scale to the industrial one. In particular, the logistics and the economic feasibility of the biorefinery processes constitute the main issues.
The logistics needed for ensuring the right execution of all the phases from the waste collection to the purification and treatment of the compounds produced from it. Although several food matrixes have been proven to be a valuable source of oils or active compounds, even the logistics at the lab scale seem to be difficult. Whether the final goal is to produce biopolymers from vegetable oils or to extract valuable compounds or active ingredients from by-products of the food processing step, everything stands on maintaining the food waste of interest in the proper conditions to be used. This is a crucial point; the stability of the raw materials needs to be ensured. The problem is that being waste, this material is usually treated like that, therefore changing its natural properties. If the idea is to scale up these processes and deal with tons of material ready to be used in the biorefinery sector, a first stabilization and transformation of this material is needed, otherwise, the risk is to reduce the yield of productions with an already low cost-benefit analysis.
In addition, according to the cost-benefit analysis of the biorefinery processes evaluated by the Institute, most of these extraction, purification, and valorization processes are economically unfeasible on a large scale. This is mainly related to the

very low yield of valuable compounds finally purified from these food waste matrixes. As an example, the Instituite was active in the --- project, which evaluated the properties of a lipidic compound contained in the so-called “SilverSkin” a thin peel on the outer layer of coffee grains. The partnership found that the cosmetic properties of this compound are unique and never found in any other lipid, but its presence in the SilverSkin is about 3% in mass, therefore, although the technical properties are highly valuable, a real industrial scale would be possible with this very low yield.

An important point is also related to the fact that most of the compounds synthesized or extracted from these matrixes are not in the proper conditions to be used in the industry and need more purification or conjugation processes, therefore increasing the final costs.

- At the Lombardy level the most interesting sources are tomatoes, rice and coffee.

Tomatoes

The tomato supply chain is of course of real interest. This is not only related to the importance of tomato production in the region but also to the valuable compounds that can be extracted from the skin (the main by-product of the tomato processing sector), such as Lycopene, which although very unstable, is a powerful natural antioxidant, and the oils contained in the seeds.

Rice:

Residues of the rice grains treatments are rich in oil and proteins which can be extracted and used in different sectors.

Coffee:

Although coffee grains are produced in other continents, the consumption of coffee drinks is mostly in Europe, and Lombardy, like all Italy, is one of the main spots. Because of this, the process of coffee roasting is done by the same companies which produce coffee drinks in Europe. As previously reported, the main by-product associated with this production step is the SilverSkin, with its valuable properties. This is an example of a real Circular Economy.

Cosmetic industry involvement

Participants

- Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.
- Lombard Cosmetic industry (Raw Materials Project Development Specialist)
This company is directly involved in the sector of secondary raw materials for cosmetic products; many of the new R&D projects are related to this sustainable branch of the sector and the researchers are always open to the last trends and to evaluating and testing new sustainable raw materials

Date 14 June 2023

Goal of the interview

- To understand the limitations of this sector from the industry point of view.
- To understand the new trends in the sustainable production of raw materials for the cosmetic sector.

Discussion

- The potential of natural compounds in the cosmetic sector is high, and everything stands in their valorization. Moreover, from a marketing point of view, the possibility of selling cosmetic products made with natural ingredients from waste material is important too and raises the commitment of the company to be more sustainable.
- The main problems concerning the industrialization of most of the innovations done at the lab scale in this field are related to the cost/benefit balance and to logistics. Most of the time, the industrial scale of these processes wouldn't be possible considering the low yield of the compound synthesized or extracted from the specific agri-food waste matrix. The logistics of the whole process, from the waste collection to the final production of cosmetic products with natural compounds need to be enforced. According to the company, one of the main gaps is the absence of organizations involved in the first treatment of the waste material, including the collection and stabilization of it.
- One of the main needs of the cosmetic sector is the replicability concept. The products, as well as the molecules used, need to be always the same. This is not possible if the logistic of this process is not fixed, and, most importantly, if there are no players able to collect, stabilize, and treat the waste material following specific protocols. Within this supply chain, cosmetic companies will be involved just at the final point, when the natural products are added to the formulation. We can't think that they start new plants for the treatment of organic waste and extraction of compounds, covering the entire process.

Food industry involvement

A study in collaboration with the regional Chamber of Commerce allowed us to affirm that in Lombardy there is a very limited number of fruit juice industries: these are mainly small industries (almost artisanal) or large industries with a different core business (in general dairy product) and a collateral production line devoted to fruit juices: in both cases any Aseptic Bag-In-Bag solution is used.

A large industry with a specific production line dedicated to fruit juices and located in Emilia Romagna (in the Po Valley near Lombardy) was contacted, but this industry also does not use bag in bag solutions. So, we investigated different possible sectors of the food industry using (and wasting) Bag-in-Bag and we contacted a ready-made sauces industry.

Participants

- Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.
- Big company with a specific production line dedicated to fruit juices (R&D Fruit Juices and Beverages)

Date 15 November 2023

Goal of the interview

- o To investigate the use and waste destination of bag in bag solutions

Discussion

- o The company does not use bag in bag solutions but the receipt of raw materials to produce fruit juices (fruit concentrates) takes place via tankers

Participants

- Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.
- Big company with a production site in Agrate (province of Monza and Brianza), offering a wide range of products including ready-made sauces (Technical Category Leader - Sauces)

Date 3 December 2023

Goal of the interview

- To investigate the use and waste destination of bag in bag solutions

Discussion

- The company buy tomato pulp in aseptic Bag-In-Bag with a volume of 200 kg; approximately 16.000 Aseptic Bag-In-Bag are annually used and discarded with the waste code CER 020304 “*Waste unusable for consumption or transformation*”

*Involvement of a start-up active in the production of animal feed from catering waste***Participants**

- Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.
- Lombard start-up active in the production of animal feed from catering waste

Date 30 November 2022

Goal of the interview

- o To analyze the potential of collective catering waste

Discussion

- o The startup is already operative in the market with its own patented plant for turning different types of residues into pet feed. The business model is based on three main services: (i) selling the plant to the company, (ii) providing technical assistance and consultancy, (iii) providing possible clients.
- o As many tests have been already done using different inputs (mono- or poly-ingredients), there are several possible applications in the food industry, including food processing companies (vegetables, meat, fish), GDOs, schools' and companies' canteens. In particular regarding the GDO and canteens sectors, the main inputs may be residues from the preparation of food dishes, residues coming back from canteens (not consumed) and residues remaining on the dishes.

Scientific and technological representative of plasticulture users' involvement

Participants

- Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.
- Technical scientific expert and business consultant for the use of agricultural films

Date: 16 November 2023

Goal of the interview

- To understand market volume and use limitations of agricultural films
- To understand the waste system and end-of-life fate of agricultural films.

Discussion

- The end-of-life management of agricultural films is closely influenced by the specific region (in Italy an excellence is Sicily) but in general this represents a large cost in terms of taxes for farmers and the collection service is often unsuitable. The biggest challenge is linked to the presence of soil residues and/or chemical additives that make recovery expensive.
- At a national level approximately 30.000 kg of film are used for solarization, and 3000/4.000 kg of film are used for fumigation, but the use is almost completely concentrated in the regions of southern Italy (Sicily and Campania in particular).

Collective catering sector representative involvement

Participants

- Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.
- Association of Collective Catering (President)

Date: 21 March 2023

Goal of the interview

- To understand and define the structure of the collective restoration in Lombardy.
- To define the flow of operation from food preparation to consumption.
- To understand the production of waste and surplus from the supply chain.

Discussion

- According to Italian law, schools and companies' canteens must respect the specifications given for the specific environment in which they are located (schools, companies, public environments, etc.). These rules include the diet to be followed, the number of dishes per person, grams of food portion, the number of alternatives, and the availability of double portions for each person.

The canteens in the schools must follow a specific diet plan in serving food and guaranteeing the appropriate quantity of food to the children. Moreover, due to the continuous increase of "mono-diet children" and vegetarian and vegan diets, canteens must guarantee an adequate supply of food to all those children who, for religious, ethnic, or ethical reasons, do not eat specific foods.

The company canteen must provide each consumer with the same options considering all the possible preferences, ethical and religious diets, which means that, differently from what happens in the schools, the canteens in the companies don't produce servings according to the number of consumers but always provide two or three options to their consumers, generating a continuous overproduction. Again, the food left on the trays is safely stored and given to non-profit organizations for the less well-off.

In addition, according to Italian law, all the canteens must serve fresh food. This means that every dish is prepared by the restoration company starting from fresh food (not already prepared-processed). The same restoration company is responsible for the preparation of the ingredients (washing, cutting, cooking, etc.).

So, canteens usually produce a set number of servings per day. The quantity of food and meals produced is in fact correlated to the specifications, which refer to the number and type of consumers in that specific canteen. This system ensures that excluding unpredictable events (strikes, simultaneous absence of several consumers, etc.), the overproduction of food is reduced to a minimum.

- If the portions are more numerous than the consumers, the excess portions that remain on the trays are collected and prepared to be given to a non-profit organization for the less well-off (Caritas). For this step to take place, it is essential that food safety

is guaranteed, therefore the excess portions must respect the cold chain and be collected within a time limit, otherwise, they cannot be consumed and are eliminated.

- The organic waste produced by the canteen is collected by the local waste management authority daily.
- Canteens always try to reduce the waste produced and to find alternative solutions to the extra servings. In all the other cases, the schools and companies' canteens normally generate three types of waste, at three steps of the collective restoration system:

Processing waste: waste generated during the servings' preparation. Since the canteens only serve fresh food, they must process it. This phase includes washing, cutting, elimination of inedible parts, cooking, and other operations that naturally produce waste. This type of waste can't be prevented but represents a small percentage of the total food produced and consumed in a canteen.

Extra servings: as specified above, the extra portions which remain on the trays are promptly stored and maintained for poor people. This type of waste is generated in all cases when food security during this step is not ensured and these extra servings can't be eaten by other people (not ensured cold chain, contamination, logistic problems). In these cases, the portions are eliminated.

Food left on the dishes: this represents the real waste generated by the collective restoration system, especially in canteens in the schools, where children normally leave more food on the dish, even when the food provided has been selected following their specific needs and preferences. This type of waste is variable, even though there are specific food preparations that are less preferred by the children and generate more leftovers on the dishes. Moreover, some canteens give the children the possibility of having two portions of the "first serving", with the inevitable consequence that the "second serving" will be left at least in part on the dishes. This type of waste is inevitable; as it has been touched by consumers, its only destiny is the bin.

Annex 4 - Working group with key public stakeholders

Agenda of the event

“Circular Economy dimensions in a new validation model. From the Region of Murcia (Spain) to the Lombardy Region”

AGENDA

Thursday 26 September from 11.00 to 13.00

On line: <https://rb.gy/erpmro>

11.00 Welcome

11.05 Presentation of the table, of the Agro2Circular project and of the CE validation model

11.15 Dimension 1: ***Socio-economic dimension***

- round table discussion about a specific question previously shared with stakeholders
- vote on the current situation in Lombardy
- collaborative identification of barriers, facilitators and potential improvement actions

11.30 Dimension 2: ***Governance dimension***

- round table discussion about a specific question previously shared with stakeholders
- vote on the current situation in Lombardy
- collaborative identification of barriers, facilitators and potential improvement actions

11.45 Dimension 3: ***Policy & regulation dimension***

- round table discussion about a specific question previously shared with stakeholders
- vote on the current situation in Lombardy
- collaborative identification of barriers, facilitators and potential improvement actions

12.00 Dimension 4: ***Funding & financial dimension***

- round table discussion about a specific question previously shared with stakeholders
- vote on the current situation in Lombardy
- collaborative identification of barriers, facilitators and potential improvement actions

12.15 Dimension 5: ***Tecnologia, R&I, capacity building dimension***

- round table discussion about a specific question previously shared with stakeholders
- vote on the current situation in Lombardy
- collaborative identification of barriers, facilitators and potential improvement actions

12.30 Dimension 6: ***Environmental dimension***

- round table discussion about a specific question previously shared with stakeholders
- vote on the current situation in Lombardy
- collaborative identification of barriers, facilitators and potential improvement actions

12.45 Dimension 7: ***Standardization dimension***

- round table discussion about a specific question previously shared with stakeholders
- vote on the current situation in Lombardy
- collaborative identification of barriers, facilitators and potential improvement actions

13.00 Closing of works

Mentimeter voting report

Socio-economic dimension

Governance dimension

Policy and regulatory dimension

Funding & financial elements dimension

Tecnologia, R&I, Capacity building dimensions

Environmental dimension

Standardization dimension

Annex 5 - Public stakeholders' involvement activities

“Lombardy initiatives and best practices in the Circular and Sustainable Plastics Value Chain” Agenda

PLASTIX Open Seminar

“Lombardy initiatives and best practices in the Circular and Sustainable Plastics Value Chain”

20 November 2024

Belvedere Jannacci (31st floor) - Grattacielo Pirelli - Lombardy Region

Via Fabio Filzi 22, 20124 Milan (Italy)

08:30	<p>Registration</p> <p>Welcome coffee</p>
09:15	<p>Opening Remarks by Lombardy Region</p> <p>Guido Guidesi, <i>Regional Minister for Economic Development - Lombardy Region</i></p> <p>Lombardy Region Policy Initiatives for Sustainable Industrial Ecosystems</p> <p>Carlo Bianchessi, <i>Head of Unit for Corporate Competitiveness and Sustainability, Ecosystems and Value Chains - Lombardy Region</i></p> <p>PLASTIX Project</p> <p>Esa Kokkonen, <i>Baltic Institute of Finland</i></p> <p>The Lombardy Ecosystem for Advanced Manufacturing and AFIL Cluster</p> <p>Samuel Nazzareno Monaco, <i>AFIL (Lombardy Intelligent Factory Association)</i></p> <p>The Lombardy Sustainable and Smart Value Chain</p> <p>Alessandro Migliavacca, <i>Elettrotecnica Rold</i></p> <p>The Strategic Community on Advanced Polymers</p> <p>Gianmarco Griffini, <i>Polytechnic University of Milan</i></p> <p>Emilio Sardini, <i>University of Brescia</i></p> <p>Lombardy Stakeholders (part 1)</p> <p>Mariantonella Palermo, <i>Tecnoalimenti</i></p> <p>Maurizio Corti, <i>Cannon Group</i></p> <p>Giorgia Zanchin, <i>Centrocot</i></p>
11:00	<p>Coffee break and networking</p>

11:30	<p>Lombardy Stakeholders (part 2)</p> <p>Delia Di Monaco, <i>COREPLA (National Consortium for the Collection, Recycling and Recovery of Plastic Packaging)</i></p> <p>Stefano Turri, <i>INSTM (National Interuniversity Consortium of Materials Science and Technology)</i></p> <p>Francesco Notari, <i>Ogyre</i></p> <p>Nicolangelo Peduto, <i>Radici Group</i></p> <p>Regional Stakeholders</p> <p>Irene Punti, <i>Leitat Technology Center</i></p> <p>Angelica Jakobo, <i>Region Värmland</i></p> <p>Blanka Veligovšek, <i>PUP-Saubermacher d.o.o.</i></p> <p>Sanna Syyskallio, <i>Visual Recycling Oy</i></p> <p>Annika Boss, <i>RISE (Research Institutes of Sweden)</i></p>
13:00	Lunch

“Strategic Community “Secure and Sustainable Food Manufacturing” e Filiera agroalimentare sicura e sostenibile (FISICO)” Agenda

Strategic Community “Secure and Sustainable Food Manufacturing” e Filiera agroalimentare sicura e sostenibile (FISICO)

MARTEDI' 4 FEBBRAIO 2024

dalle 13:00 alle 16:00

Sala Eventi c/o Innovhub – Via Giuseppe Colombo 83, 20133 Milano

AGENDA

-
- 13:00 Registrazione e networking lunch
 - 14:00 Tour de table
 - 14:15 L'ecosistema dell'innovazione di AFIL, la Strategic Community “Secure and Sustainable Food Manufacturing” e la Filiera agroalimentare sicura e sostenibile (FISICO)
AFIL, Tecnoalimenti e Politecnico di Milano
 - 15:00 Opportunità regionali ed europee
AFIL
 - 15:45 I progetti GREENSMARTMED e Agro2Circular
AFIL e Tecnoalimenti
 - 16:00 Wrap-up e conclusioni

La partecipazione all'evento è gratuita, previa iscrizione al seguente [link](#).

Per informazioni, contattare Samuel Nazzareno Monaco (tel. 3407354766 - e-mail: samuel.monaco@afil.it)

GREENSMARTMED

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Annex 6 - Citizens attitudes and actions towards sustainable consumption, production, and waste management practices: waste management behaviours and awareness of recycled plastic materials

Tecnoalimenti analysed the **point of view of Lombardian consumers and citizens about plastic waste management and recycled plastic materials** through a survey including questions relating on the following aspects:

- awareness of recycled packaging material in the market
- availability to pay more or to change the shopping habits for a more sustainable food product
- waste management habits

The targets of the survey were the consumers of the Lombardy region, considering different age groups and social classes.

Consumers' sustainability awareness and attention to packaging recyclability

The first goal of the survey was to understand if the consumers are ready to the use of recycled plastic material in food packaging because it surely impacts the price and availability of food and beverage products and the management of these recycled materials after their use.

To analyse the influence of consumers' age on their behaviour when buying food, the two very distant age groups "18 – 25" and "46 – 65" years old have been compared.

Most of the interviewed consumers report paying **low attention to the recyclability and sustainability of the packaging when buying a food or beverage product**, while 33% pay high attention, and only 8% of the total interviewed don't pay attention at all.

Interestingly, the comparison of the answers from the two selected age groups doesn't show the big differences expected but the same pattern (Figure 1); even though the trend is very similar, however, the graphs show that the percentage of young consumers ("18 – 24 years old") which pay high attention to the sustainability of the packs (35%) is slightly higher compared to the pool of consumers from 46 to 65 years old (31%) and that, on the contrary, the amount of consumers reporting to pay low attention is a little lower (57% and 60% for "18 – 25" and "46 – 65" group ages, respectively).

Figure 1 - Consumers' attention in different age classes to recyclability and sustainability of food packaging when shopping.

These results are in contrast with what is normally thought of as young consumers and their greater responsibility and activism toward the sustainability of food production and the food system in general and show that, even though a slight trend seems in favour of what is mentioned above, the attention and awareness of older consumers to these topics is somehow the same of the younger ones. This suggests that in Lombardy, the importance of making food production and consumption more sustainable is at the same level for the young and middle-aged categories of consumers, even though the latter is normally less exposed to the digital and social media communication actions frequently used for disseminating these themes.

If the age of the consumers doesn't seem to influence their awareness and attention to the final recyclability of the containers they buy together with their food, Figure 2 shows a significant difference when comparing the behaviour of male and female consumers. Both age groups show more female consumers paying high attention as compared to male ones, with 15% and 7% of differences in the "18 – 25" and "46 – 65" years old-age groups, respectively. The trend is confirmed by the lower number of females reporting not paying attention to the sustainability of the packages at all, which is 13.5% for and 10.5% decreased when compared to the percentages of males, within the "18 – 25" and "46 – 65" years old-age groups, respectively.

These findings reveal that, at the expense of age, there is greater attention to packaging sustainability for females than for males, when buying food. This may suggest more awareness of the sustainability of what they are buying and the end of the packages.

Figure 2. Comparison of male and female consumers' attention to the recyclability of food packaging within the age group 18 – 25 (A) and 46 – 65 (B).

In contrast to what is described in Figure 1, the age of the Lombardian consumers seems to influence their preference for food products with recycled packaging and therefore, their buying habits. This doesn't directly connect with their awareness of the sustainability of the products they buy and, especially, the food packages' recyclability. More precisely, Figure 3 shows that 55% of young consumers prefer food products with recycled packaging, if available, while only 21% of older consumers report highly preferring the same products. In line with this, the survey reveals that there are fewer young consumers with a medium and low predilection for food products with recycled packaging when compared to the older ones. In other words, while most adult consumers (79%) report not giving preference to recycled packed-food products, the young aged-class of the population tends to prefer and therefore, buy more sustainable food products.

Figure 3. Preference for food products with a recycled packaging of consumers from different age groups

Willingness to pay more for sustainably packed food products

The consumer's willingness to pay an overprice for food products with packaging made of recycled or innovative material has been also analysed through the survey.

In this case, the idea was to evaluate how much the Lombardian consumers would directly support the transition to more sustainable food production and consumption with their own money. The interviewees had to choose between a surcharge of 5%-10%, 10%-20%, and of more than 20% from the initial cost of the food product, or the decision not to pay more for recycled packaging.

Figure 4 reveals that the vast majority of the consumers are ready to pay from 5% to 10% more for their food, more precisely, 70% of young consumers and 63,5% of the older ones would bear the surcharge, however, if the overpricing is higher than the 10%, the percentage of consumers willing to pay more decreases drastically to only the 10% and the 8.5%, respectively. Interestingly, the percentage of consumers not eager to pay more for a surcharge is in the range of 20%-26% of the total interviewed, meaning that even though the answer is clear and consumers in Lombardy seem to be ready for the higher expenses of this possible transition, there is a significant part of them who would pay less at expenses of the recyclability of the packages.

Figure. 4. Consumer's willingness to pay more for food products with a recycled packaging

Surprisingly, the attention of consumers to recyclable packages when buying food doesn't appear to be in line with their willingness to pay more for them. In particular, the survey reveals that 60% of the total consumers who reported giving low or not care at all are easier to pay a surcharge of 5%-10% from the normal cost of the products and that 8% would even pay an increment higher than the 10%. Only 32% of these low or not-interested consumers are also not ready for a price increase.

This analysis may suggest that, although maybe not interested or little aware of the current innovation of food packaging related to having more recyclable and in general more sustainable Food Contact Materials, most consumers are willing to pay a little bit more for their food if in presence of recycled packaging material.

Consumer-based waste management

The second part of the survey aimed to evaluate to what extent the consumers in the Lombardy region are aware of the waste management rules, how often they respect them, and how difficult they find them. In addition, the citizens interviewed were asked about their involvement in social initiatives related to public waste collection and management.

The results show that, in Lombardy, 71% of the consumers are aware of the waste management rules of their city and the destiny of the different materials, and that, within this group of citizens, the vast majority (81%) look the packages before to throw them away, searching for information on the material and the type of disposal required for it, while only the 8% seem to do not care about disposing properly their home-based waste.

Although the consumers who described difficulty finding the proper waste management indications on the packages are only 12% of all the interviewees, most of them (67%) are among the group which reported being aware and following the specific waste disposal rules. This may suggest that the information on the packs of food and beverage products is not always clear and that, because of this, even the consumers conscious of the proper rules, may dispose of their waste wrongly. This must be a point of improvement if the perspective is to increase the production and use of recycled material in the food and

beverage sector, otherwise, the risk seems to be clear: using more sustainable food packaging on one side and contributing to incorrect disposal of it on the other one.

The comparison of the two selected age groups described in Figure 5 highlights a slight difference between young and older consumers. In particular, the latter seem to be more conscious and look for more indications on the packages before throwing them away. As a confirmation of this, none of them reported not searching for disposal instructions and 86% said to always do it, which is higher compared to the younger consumers (75.5%).

Figure 5. Consumer's behaviour on waste management and disposal

With the city of Milan in its centre, Lombardy is considered the most innovative region of Italy, nevertheless, the results of the survey reveal that from the waste management point of view, it might not be so updated. Among the total number of interviewees, 82% describe a situation where even if there is the want to collect personal waste properly, the public bins are too few or always full and most of the time they don't provide a separate waste collection. Since only 18% of the interviewed population answered in a positive way regarding the public waste collection system, it is clear that this is another point of improvement. For sure, the will of citizens to keep the common spaces of the cities where they live in order and clean is quite significant, with 21% of the people interviewed reporting to have been involved in public initiatives related to the collection of garbage on the streets and in the parks, as well as event and training activities on recycling and separate waste collection.

Annex 7 – Exploitation activities

Italian leaflet

Roadmap per l'Economia Circolare

I nostri contatti

02 67077370

segreteria@tecnoalimenti.com

www.tecnoali.com

Verso la transizione circolare in Regione Lombardia

Questo progetto ha ricevuto finanziamenti dal programma di ricerca e innovazione Horizon 2020 dell'Unione Europea nell'ambito dell'accordo di sovvenzione n. 101036838

Territorial circular systemic solution for the upcycling of residues from the agrifood sector

40

partner

12

paesi coinvolti

14M€

budget

42

mesi di attività

2

filiere circolari analizzate

1

modello multi dimensionale

Agro2Circular in Lombardia

Stima e sistematizzazione dei dati relativi agli scarti prodotti dall'agricoltura

Casi studio: mele, pomodori, lattuga, uva

Due Business Models Circolari per l'uso nei settori cosmetico e nutraceutico di estratti bioattivi da scarti agricoli

Applicazione del modello multidimensionale come strumento di self-assessment

7 dimensioni valutate: ambientale, socio-economica, regolamentale, di standardizzazione, tecnologica, finanziaria, di governance

Il working group lombardo

✓ **Moderatori:**
Tecnoalimenti
Università commerciale Luigi Bocconi

✓ **Partecipanti:**
Regione Lombardia - Direzione Generale Università, Ricerca, Innovazione
Regione Lombardia - Direzione Ambiente e Clima
Cluster AFIL
Cluster LGCA
Cluster Cat.AI.
Conai

✓ **Obiettivi:**
Valutazione condivisa della attuale situazione regionale in termini di Economia Circolare
Cocreazione su potenziali azioni di intervento, priorità e obiettivi chiave

Booklet summarizing main activities and results in Lombardy

Agro2Circular

LOMBARDY REPLICATION CASE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838

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Economy Action Plan

THE PROJECT

Agro2Circular “Territorial circular systemic solution for the upcycling of residues from the agri-food sector” is a EU project proposing innovative valorisation routes for agri-food wastes upcycling and circular economy development through innovative routes of valorisation.

LOMBARDY REPLICATION STUDY

Replicability study aimed at identifying the potential applications in Lombardy of the systemic solutions developed within the Agro2Circular project; it adheres to the holistic and multidimensional approach that underpins the entire Agro2Circular project and is structured around two main lines of replicability

VALUE CHAINS REPLICABILITY

Contextual study was conducted on the **amounts and type of residues within Lombardy agrifood industry**.

This work of data systematization was highly relevant not only for the Agro2Circular replication but also at a strategic level for the Lombardy Region because to date there is no real awareness of waste generation from the primary sector and only an in-depth study on the sector's potential can enable the waste valorisation and the implementation of circular value chains (even beyond those hypothesized in the Agro2Circular).

Based on the potential economic and market value of horticultural wastes (in term of amount, seasonality, territoriality and presence of producer's aggregations) and in compliance with the "green" principles underlying the Agro2Circular project, the most relevant case studies for the Lombardy Region were identified, along with potential valorisation routes for the replicability of the Agro2Circular model.

A2C TECHNOLOGICAL VALORIZATION ROUTES

Horticultural biological waste are subjected to ultrasound-assisted extraction. The liquid phase is concentrated via nanofiltration and then purified with absorption/desorption on resins; after a stabilization phase with freeze-drying, **high-purity phenolic compounds** are obtained. In parallel, the solid phase obtained from the extraction is subjected to washes with oxidizing agents, sieve filtering and dehydration: the final product is the **fiber**.

Grapes and **apples** wastes value chains were selected for application of Agro2Circular technological model and replicability assessment: they are respectively the second and fourth types of waste in Lombardy in terms of abundance and they allow the application of technologies tested in the Agro2Circular demonstrators.

Selected value chain for final assessment

A2C value chains with slight modifications

Additional and collateral assessments

On the other hand, **tomato** and **lettuce** wastes are the first and the third most important flows in Lombardy and present strengths for circularization: application of the Agro2Circular model and technologies is possible with slight modification.

It is also worth to notice that the Lombardy region is not only important for agricultural and horticultural production but is also a very populous region with a strong vocation for collective catering. *It is that possible to estimate that the province of Milan only generates around 1.473 tons/year of food surplus (given to charitable organizations if safely stored), and 1.903 tons/year of real food waste.* For this reason, additional and collateral assessments related to collective catering waste will be performed in the application of Agro2Circular model.

Apples

Apples production in Lombardy is strongly related to the PGI mark and for this reason the quality standards (including aesthetics) are very rigorous. To estimate the waste from primary production due to non-compliant apples we can take into consideration an English report at least 25% of apples were discarded because they were "ugly

By transferring this data to Lombardy production, we can estimate waste from apple primary production as 13.000 tons/year

Wine grape

Grape cultivation and wine production are one of the most critical agro-industrial sectors worldwide, generating large amounts of waste with negative environmental impacts, but also with high economic value and several potential applications. Waste products are generated at each stage of the winemaking process. There are two different categories showing the origin of winery waste: collection of grapes (solid waste) and winemaking process (liquid waste). The first category broadly involves grape stalks (7.5% of total solid wastes generated by winery), grape pomace (45%), grape seeds (6%), stems, as well as wine yeasts. Pomace represents 20–25% of the initial weight of the grapes, being a solid residue resulting from the processes of fermentation and pressing of the grapes. In total, about 30% of the initial mass of grapes collected for winemaking is disposed.

Starting from a regional production of 1.790.510 quintals in 2023 we can estimate 98.600 tons/ year of grape waste in Lombardy

Industrial tomato

Tomato production generates significant amount of waste from unripe, imperfect, damaged and overripe fruits; specifically in the industrial tomato sector there are very close commercial agreements between producers and industries, so part of the production is discarded to ensure compliance with quality specifications. It is estimated that 15% of the industrial tomatoes produced are already discarded in the field.

Starting from a production of 6.577.520 quintals in 2023, we can estimate waste in the primary sector of 98.600 tons/year in Lombardy. But, an estimation based only on the Lombardy region can be limited and misleading for the replicability assessments of the A2C model: considering the territorial proximity and the structural organization of the production reality, it is much more useful to evaluate tomato production and the related waste production in the whole district of Northern Italy. According to data from OI Pomodoro da Industria Nord Italia, almost 2.800.000 tons of tomatoes were produced in 2023.

We can estimate industrial tomato agricultural waste for 420.000 tons/year in the district of Northern Italy

Lettuce

Lettuce cultivation (especially in greenhouses) takes place in a very protected environment so waste generation in the primary production step is negligible compared to the waste obtained from fresh-cut processing. In addition, tufts not suitable for harvesting are typically left in the field and used as soil enrichment so **we cannot really consider waste flows from lettuce primary production**. On the other hand survey conducted in a large Italian fresh-cut company revealed that at least 35% of lettuce head weight is wasted, mainly due to initial operations of external leaves and core removal. To approximately calculate the waste from the Lombardy industry of fresh cut salads, we can hypothesize that lettuce production (413.360 quintals in 2022 including open field and greenhouse production) is entirely destined for transformation.

Starting from literature data we **can estimate a generation of waste equal to 14.500 tons/year**

IDENTIFICATION OF INDUSTRIAL SYNERGIES AND CIRCULAR VALUE CHAIN DEFINITION

Lombardy region shows **great technological maturity** for the replication of Agro2Circular solutions for horticultural waste valorization both at polyphenols and fibre extraction step of at biomolecules application step.

Beyond the biomolecule extraction phase, the main applications of the extracts in Lombardy can be the **functional cosmetic industry** and the **nutraceutical industry**.

Often the same company can operate at both points of the supply chain; technological transfer can be supported by the presence of business associations.

**Environmental
assessment**

*In collaboration with VTT Technical
Research Centre of Finland*

**2 circular business
model definition**

*In collaboration with
Bocconi University*

CONDITIONS WITH POTENTIAL POSITIVE INFLUENCE ON THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF THE BUSINESS MODEL REPLICATION

Avoiding establishing water intensive production processes in particularly water scarce regions

Relying on electricity from renewable energy via company's own production or renewables certificates

Reducing transport distances by establishing industrial clusters at a sub-regional area

Considering the effect of modifications to the production model on specific local conditions

The first business model developed for Agro2Circular replicability in Lombardy is related to **cosmetic/nutraceutical companies able to use biological waste from horticulture to produce functional products**. This innovative transition is facilitated by a collaborative environment in the Lombardy with high concentration of companies in this sector, research centres, and a substantial local stream of waste that can support circular supply initiatives. Additionally, this favourable environment is further strengthened by the presence of industry associations and partnerships that foster connections across the supply chain, encourage collaboration toward a shared vision, and support the broader business community.

The second potential systemic solution replicable in Lombardy involves **companies able to implement directly their activities with a circular approach, without the need to modify an existing internal product or process**. With a strong emphasis on R&D, spin-off companies often rely on public or European funds dedicated to innovative projects. Their ability to secure funding is a key characteristic of the Lombardy region. Additionally, they benefit from a supportive research ecosystem and strong academic partnerships. From an environmental perspective, spin-off companies play a crucial role in advancing resource upcycling from agricultural waste. Due to the specificity of this research field, such innovations might not otherwise be developed within the industry.

STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT

- Relevant entities for the new value chain implementing Agro2Circular technologic solutions (for example primary producers' organization, scientific and technological representative of "green technology" providers, cosmetic industry) were contacted.
- Key public stakeholders were involved in a working group

LOMBARDY WORKING GROUP

Moderators

- ✓ Tecnoalimenti
Bocconi University

Participants

Lombardy Region, General Directorate for Universities, Research, and Innovation

Lombardy Region, General Directorate for

- ✓ Environment and Climate

Cluster AFIL

Cluster LE2C

Cluster LGCA

Cluster CAT.AL

National Consortium for Packaging CONAI

Goals

- ✓ Common assessment of the current regional situation in terms of Circular Economy
- ✓ Co-creation on potential intervention actions, priorities and key objectives

MULTIDIMENSIONAL REPLICABILITY

It includes the analysis of 8 dimensions and 33 elements applied to the specific territorial context of the Lombardy Region to stimulate in-depth reflection.

The analysis of each element was based on:

- feedback from the Lombardy working group
- targeted interviews with private stakeholders
- contextual study
- desk research targeted on specific elements of the multidimensional model
- previous experiences and knowledge within the TCA research team and its related industrial network

Average evaluation of Circular Economy elements in Lombardy was 3.7/5: the region shows a good level of progress towards the circular transition.

Best dimensions are socio-economic dimension and governance dimension (4.5 and 4.4, respectively). The factors of excellence in Lombardy are the **strength of the production system**, the **citizens participation** (in particular with reference to separate waste collection) and the **holistic and multidimensional approach to innovation** with the involvement of all decision makers.

On the other hand, the worst dimension is the standardization, but a very low score was also given to traceability (a technological element related to standardization). These are aspects which are still little known among stakeholders.

The main findings emerging from the application of the multidimensional model in terms of **Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities** and **Threats** are reported and outlined below.

Generally speaking, Lombardy region is ready for the circular transition thanks to the great technological maturity and the great sensitivity of the citizens (for example with very high rates of separate waste collection); on the other hand, the high demographic and industrial rate make the region very susceptible to environmental problems.

LOMBARDY CIRCULAR ECONOMY ACTION PLAN

**Regional key actors
identification**

**Drivers of the transition
to circularity**

**Providing of policy
recommendations**

**Roadmap to move
towards circular
systems**

According to the A2C multidimensional and holistic approach to the circular transition, the key actors for the implementation of an effective and efficient Circular Economy Action Plan are identified according to the **quintuple helix model**.

Starting from the application of the multidimensional model and from the feedback obtained from stakeholders, the following drivers towards the circular transition have been identified.

1. **Economic opportunities.** Reducing waste and use of resources allow for an immediate economic return; in addition, consumers are increasingly seeking sustainable and ethical products, incentivizing companies to adopt circular principles.
2. **Regulatory and policy push** Local, national and international legislation is increasingly stringent in terms of environmental requirements and policies mandate extended producer responsibility, recycling targets, and eco-design standards; on the other hand, grants, subsidies and tax benefits for circular initiatives motivate industries to transition.
3. **Environmental Pressures.** Lombardy is a leading region in Italy in waste sorting and treatment, but the high production of industrial and urban waste requires a more circular management. On the other hand, Lombardy region suffers from serious problems of air and water pollution pushing for a more sustainable management of natural resources.
4. **Supply chain pressure.** Companies are incentivized to secure their supply chains by using secondary materials and designing for reuse: the industrial density of the Lombardy region favours synergies between companies to develop industrial symbiosis projects.
5. **Consumer awareness.** Lombardy citizens are among the most sensitive in Italy to environmental issues, with a growing demand for sustainable products and sharing economy services.

From the discussion with stakeholders and from the application of the Agro2Circular Multidimensional Model emerged specific policy recommendations transversal to the individual dimensions and elements.

Most relevant policy recommendation can be summarized into two main aspects related to **holistic approach** and to **public financial support**.

1. Circular transition can be effective only if it involves, throughout the entire process from the decision-making step to implementation, all the actors and potential stakeholders (both politicians and economic operators along the supply chains and final consumers and citizens). So, the first policy recommendations group is related to the **active engagement of all stakeholders and key actors**.
2. The second policy recommendation group is linked to the public financial support for circular transition actions. Economic operators are increasingly aware of potential and advantages (including economic ones) deriving from Circular Economy but often they are not able to sustain investments, especially if long-term. So public financial support appropriately addressed can effectively boost circular transition: the most relevant public financial support can be directed towards prospective actions such as **Research & Development activities as well as Training & Education**.

Lombardy roadmap towards circular systems

It is a roadmap centred on **interdisciplinary cooperation** and **stakeholder engagement**: it would like to provide a reference able to stimulate the cooperation between public and private stakeholders with the aim to build strategic initiatives on Circular Economy as an opportunity to define a structured strategy to boost Circular Economy in the region starting from the needs and the priorities collaboratively pointed out by diverse regional stakeholders.

Objectives	Actions	Timing	Key actors
1.Reduce Waste	1.1 Strengthening separate waste collection for example improving the door-to-door waste collection capabilities	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civil society (in term of citizens awareness and participation) Public administration Industry (AMSA in particular) Environment
	1.2 Introducing incentives for companies that adopt waste reduction practices	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public administration Industry
	1.3 Promoting sustainable packaging using biodegradable or recyclable materials for packaging and reduce over-packaging.	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Industry Civil society Environment
	1.4 Developing new recycling and recovery technologies	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Industry Public administration (financial support to R&D)
2. Promote eco-design and resource efficiency	2.1 Introducing sustainability criteria in public procurement	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public administration Environment
	2.2 Introducing product design criteria for increase the percentage of secondary raw materials in new products	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public administration (financial support to R&D and eco – design directive) Research Industry

Objectives	Actions	Timing	Key actors
3. Encourage the use of secondary materials	3.1 Developing circular technologies, for example incorporate reusable materials and avoid harmful chemicals that hinder recycling	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support to R&D)
	3.2 Re-valorisation of secondary products and by-products through implementation of circular value chains	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support to R&D)
	3.3 Developing certifications and quality labels for circular products	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Environment
	3.4 Using technology to track materials and components in the supply chain allowing for efficient recovery and reuse.	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support to R&D and to industrial symbiosis)

Objectives	Actions	Timing	Key actors
4. Interdisciplinary collaboration	4.1 Strengthening stakeholder engagement	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society • Public administration • Industry • Environment • Research and education
	4.2 Creating opportunities for interaction and knowledge sharing	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administration • Industry • Environment • Research
	4.3 Promoting collaboration in R&D processes from the design phase to the industrialization phase	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support to R&D)
	4.4 Supporting industrial symbiosis	Medium term (3-5 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Industry • Public administration (financial support)
	4.5 Fostering collaboration with governments at territorial, national and international level to establish policies able to support circular practices	Long term (< 5y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administration
5. Spread Circular Economy Culture	5.1 Design of specific university/training courses closely connected with industrial environment and targeted to key topics able to provide students with the required skills and competencies.	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and education • Industry • Public administration
	5.2 Developing and implementing sustainable practices for example through awareness campaigns	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society • Environmental • Public administration
	5.3 Empowering consumers and public purchasers to make informed choices	Short term (1-2 y)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society • Environmental • Public administration (legislation about label)

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WHAT ABOUT THE FUTURE?

Lombardy Circular Economy Action Plan will be able to guide and support decision makers towards the **elaboration of official strategies** and action starting from needs and reflections already shared with stakeholders from different sectors.

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